
*Investigating Key Factors Influencing Effective Cybersecurity
Governance: A study of Pakistan's Private Commercial Banks.*

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DECLARATION

I, the undersigned, do hereby declare that, only the referenced work from previous studies – which I have listed using Harvard referencing list - is used for this thesis. Besides, the rest of the work of this thesis is carried out by me personally.

09/07/2022

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Abstract

In the contemporary digital landscape, the effective governance of e-banking information systems poses a global challenge. Similarly, despite the financial soundness of the banking industry in Pakistan, its vulnerability to cyber threats remains a significant concern. This study aims to identify key factors influencing cybersecurity governance in Private Commercial Banks of Pakistan (PCBP, Lahore), exploring internal and external challenges, and providing practical recommendations.

The theoretical framework of this thesis draws on the institutional logics perspective to highlight how stakeholders' actions reshape the social institutions governing cybersecurity in the banking sector. The study also incorporates the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and motivation concepts alongside the three lines of defence model. This comprehensive approach emphasizes institutional actions for robust cybersecurity governance in banks.

Empirically, findings based on 21 semi-structured interviews across 13 PCBP highlight an increasing threat of social engineering linked to customer awareness. In particular, digital literacy was proven more effective than formal degrees in combating cyberthreats. The study advocates immediate nationwide awareness programs by the government to instil a culture of cybersecurity, acting as a deterrent against cybercriminals. Moreover, hurdles such as insufficient legislation, the capabilities of law enforcement agents, and corrupt agents were found to impede effective cybercrime prevention.

The findings of the study indicate that the State Bank of Pakistan (SBP) faces challenges due to a lack of cybersecurity experts and experienced audit teams, enabling banks to manipulate performance superficially. Furthermore, inadequate cybersecurity training for directors contributes to governance issues, fostering cyberthreats like social engineering, ATM skimming, malware, and DDoS attacks. The study also highlights the potential threat of deepfake technology in the context of low cybersecurity awareness in Pakistan's banking sector.

In summary, this thesis advocates a holistic approach involving collaboration between PCBP, SBP, and the government to enhance cybersecurity governance. Leveraging institutional logics, the proposed framework holds potential applicability to developing countries grappling with similar cybersecurity challenges.

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Acronyms

APIs (Application Programming Interfaces)

Banking As A Service (BAAS)

Board of Directors (BoD)

Computer Emergency Response Team (CERT)

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)

Deterrence Theory (GDT)

Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS)

Gross Domestic Product (GDP)

Information Security Climate (ISC)

Multi Factor Authentication (MFA)

National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST)

Private Commercial Banks of Pakistan (PCBP)

Return on Asset (ROA)

Return on Equity (ROE)

State Bank of Pakistan (SBP)

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

United Bank Limited (UBL)

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DEDICATION

ABSTRACT

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CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1. Introduction

Cybercrime is an increasing trend throughout the world in all sectors, but the banking sector has been the major target of cybercriminals for more than a decade (Kitaw and Beaumont, 2017; Syed, Khaver & Yasin, 2019; Sadiq, 2019). In particular, electronic banking (e-banking) faces its own set of obstacles, necessitating the expansion of governance capabilities beyond traditional organizational boundaries (Chaimaa, Najib, and Rachid, 2021; Venkatesh, 2023). Various attempts have been made at governmental, professional, and academic level to suggest the best solution for cybersecurity governance in banks. Previous studies conclude that cybersecurity solutions need continuous updates with the development of dynamic and innovative cybercrimes to improve the cybersecurity governance. This stance have made management of cybersecurity risks a significant and multifaceted challenge for banks (Bernik (2014); Kopp, Kaffenberger and Wilson (2017), Eling and Lehmann (2018), Sadiq (2019), Syed et al. (2019), and Qadeer (2020); Wang, Nnaji, and Jung, 2020; and Mahmood, 2021). Beyond the evolving cyberthreat landscape, factors such as financial loss caused by cyberattacks, regulatory fines, and customer risk perception to adopt e-banking, emphasis on cybersecurity governance effectiveness. The potential repercussions on individual customers and the broader national economy underscore the urgency for financial institutions to promptly align their capabilities with an extensive array of internal and external factors. This alignment is crucial for effectively managing the heightened probability of loss resulting from an expanded attack surface (Syed et al., 2019; Khalil, 2020; Grewcock, 2021).

Following social factor concept, law and its enforcement (Al-Badran, 2021; Rakha, 2023), regulatory framework (Kopp, et al., 2017; Artemenko and Bychkova, 2020; Ogunwale, 2020), customer awareness (Alghazo, Kazmi, and Latif, 2017;. Hafiz Ali, Khan, Asghar, and Shuaib, 2019; and Bada, Von Solms, and Agrafiotis, 2019), and strategic planning (Goel, 2016; Alotaibi, Furnell, and Clarke, 2017; Malik and Islam, 2019; Wang, et al., 2020; Al-Alawi and Al-Bassam, 2021) have been proven effective factors to improve

cybersecurity governance of banks in different countries. Even though, with increasing rate of cybercrime in banking sector of Pakistan, the broader concept of study to find the factors except technological innovation which affect the cybersecurity governance, have not been given much attention in Pakistan (Sadiq, 2019; Syed et al., 2019; and Qadeer, 2020), especially the strategic planning. In light of the existing knowledge, it is essential to examine whether previous scholarly work has adequately addressed the unique factors of cybersecurity in banks. Hence, this research will adopt the institutional logics approach which incorporates broader perspective of society to find the factors of effective cybersecurity governance in private commercial banks of Pakistan, as they may encounter distinct determinants and inhibitors in achieving effective cybersecurity governance practices.

Thus, this study explores the essential factors for the successful implementation of cybersecurity governance in the context of private commercial banks of Pakistan. The chapter provides an introductory overview of the research scope and is organized into nine sections. Following this introduction, the second section explores the problem statement, encompassing both generic and industry-specific issues relating to cybersecurity governance. The third section addresses the significance of study, while the fourth section presents the research aim, objectives, and questions, all aligned to support the overarching research aim. The fifth section offers the contribution of study. The sixth section highlights the scope of study followed by, theoretical view, and methodology, in sections seven, and eight respectively. Finally, an outline of the proposed thesis structure is given in section nine.

1.2. Problem Statement

Cybersecurity governance of e-banking information system has been a topic of concern for more than a decade, both in developed and developing countries (Syed et al., 2019). Following Shad (2019) point of view, cybersecurity entails use of technology, processes, and practices to secure, detect, and recover from damages to confidentiality, integrity, and availability, of information in cyberspace. Governance is prescribed as a multidisciplinary perspective, containing strategic planning to protect against loss

(Schiliro, 2023). In contrast, cybersecurity governance consists of complying with industry standards and best practises while planning strategically to protect the confidentiality integrity and availability of information systems by mitigating risks (Savaş and Karataş, 2022). Concurrently, it is difficult to define e-banking as it can be viewed from multiple perspectives because it consists of multichannel distribution methods of financial services provided by banks. However, this thesis defines e-banking as ‘a practise of using banking services through technological devices connected with internet. For instance, online banking and shopping, mobile banking, use of ATM debit and credit cards etc. (Al-Badran, 2021).

The growth in internet usage has resulted in increasing rate of cybercrimes in banking sector (Jamshed, Rafique, Baig, and Ahmad, 2022). According to Banerjee (2022) cybercrime is any illegal activity conducted through a computer as a main source. Although, cybercrime in banks constitutes unauthorised access to information system, to imitate, modify or damage data and steal money, causing the confidentiality issue (Anwar, 2020). The confidentiality offences in banks has been a major topic of discussion among many countries’ governments, business executives, and IT professionals as well as cybersecurity experts and academics for more than a decade, who have been trying to introduce the modern cybersecurity measures to provide sustainability in information system of the banks (Awan & Memon, 2016). Yet, globally cybersecurity issue of banks is unresolved because of dynamic nature of cybercrimes which are hard to predict (Bruijn & Janssen, 2017; Shad, 2019; Halder, 2021). According to Bouveret (2018), confidentiality offences consist of cybercrimes which harm the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of the data. Also, the confidentiality offences lead to legal protection against them. The most common cyberthreats in the banking sector include social engineering, ATM skimming, malware, and Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS) attacks etc. (Syed et al. 2019) which are discussed in detail in the literature review Chapter 3. However, the Deepfake attack (machine learning to copy the voice and face of people to show as a genuine person) is a new version of cyberthreats which can be even more critical impersonating people using video (Mirsky & Lee, 2020).

These cybercrimes directed at banks not only cause banks to compensate affected customers for their financial loss, but banks also face hefty fines payable to its regulator for security breaches (Grewcock, 2021; Syed et al., 2019). On the other hand, a recent study by Afshan et al. (2018) shows that a bank which compromised its information security will lose its competitive advantage and the trust of its customers, which is a major concern. Customers' negative perception of e-banking cybersecurity becomes a hurdle to use e-banking services that may result in loss of profits and bankruptcy. Additionally, banks' very existence will become fragile as a single attack can cause bankruptcy because the cost of a single cyberattack for a financial institution is worth \$5.72 million on average, which is second highest among all sectors of an economy (IAM, 2021; Azmi, et al., 2018; Travelers, 2022). Hence, it can be concluded that the sustainability of the banking industry depends on the effectiveness of its information security governance (van de Weijer & Leukfeldt, 2017).

Previously the cybersecurity of banks' information systems has been considered an IT issue, therefore the concept of cybersecurity governance has been ignored (Kooper, Maes and Lindgreen, 2011; Williams, 2021). Following this perspective, the focus of practitioners and researchers has been only on the technological solutions for cybersecurity (Savaş and Karataş, 2022; Zafar, Asif, Ahmad, Ghazal, Faiz, Ahmad, and Khan, 2022). Overtime, attention has been diverted to social behavioural factors along with IT solutions for cybersecurity governance. The institutional logics which shape the cognitive behaviour of society justify that social behaviour includes actions of social actors (governments, regulatory institutions, and businesses) and these actors can play a crucial role to introducing or changing these behavioural actions (factors - Faik, Barrett, and Oborn, 2020). In this context, the literature shows that there are multiple social factors which affect the cybersecurity governance of the banking industry and can be categorised as internal and external. Moreover, dealing effectively with those factors can enhance the cybersecurity governance of banking industry otherwise these factors may turn into challenges (Naqvi, 2020; Syed et al., 2019). The internal factor mainly constitutes on the strategic planning of cybersecurity whereby the bank will consider technical, organisational, and legal aspects of cybersecurity. In detail, technical view emphasis

effective investment on technology and experts meeting the requirements of business's information security infrastructure (Al-Alawi and Al-Bassam, 2021). The organisational institutions focus on employees' and executives' cybersecurity awareness and training (Malik and Islam, 2019) while, the legal aspect requires banks to comply with regulatory requirements relating to technical and organisational aspects with ultimate purpose of cybersecurity governance (Alotaibi, Furnell and Clarke, 2017). The external factors require the regulatory bodies and government to play their role in cybersecurity governance by providing regulatory and legal conformity respectively. Although, these beforementioned internal and external factors might not be fully effective if the customers (human factor) remains illiterate and unaware about cybersecurity (Adholiya and Adholiya, 2019). This social behavioural concept of cybersecurity governance in banks has been widely studied mainly in developed countries while there is a research gap to be filled in this respect in developing countries, such as Pakistan.

Chang & Coppel (2020) and Jamshed et al. (2022) point out that the financial institutions in developing countries receive a high rate of cyberattacks because they have abundance of money with weak security systems, low levels of literacy, lack of investment in cybersecurity, weak infrastructure, and issues of human factors (e.g., unaware employees and customers). Such as, in Pakistan the literacy level is low and literature shows that literacy hinders people to be aware of cybersecurity (Balaraj and Shetty, 2019) while awareness is found to be a major factor for cybersecurity governance in banks (Hafiz Ali, Khan, Asghar, and Shuaib, 2019). Moreover, cybersecurity is a new perspective in banking industry of Pakistan since the whole technological infrastructure of banks is built without incorporating security systems (Mahmood, 2021). Thus, posing the weak cybersecurity features of a developing country, Pakistan is also confronting increasing trend of the cyberattacks in its banking industry along with other sectors (Syed et al., 2019). The private commercial banks of Pakistan are the major contributor of the GDP in country thus, the economy depends greatly on its banking industry. Hence, the failure of banking industry caused by cybercrimes may impact the whole economy (Anwar, 2020). Subsequently, considering the broader aspects of institutional logics there

is a need to conduct an empirical study to find the factors which result into cybercrimes the private commercial banks of Pakistan are facing, to fill this research gap.

1.3. Significance of Study

A commercial bank is an organisation that acts as an intermediary by accepting deposits from customers and lending money (Mayowa, 2020). Commercial banks have played crucial role towards the economic growth of countries as customers earn profits from their deposits, and loans used by businesses create employment opportunities; consequently, it increases the purchasing power of people (Zavadska, 2018; Rushchyshyn et al., 2021). Technological advancement has introduced innovative methods of banking which have made people's life easy therefore, e-banking is the need of the day and the banking sector is growing dynamically world widely, providing e-banking services (Hussain et al., 2017; van de Weijer & Leukfeldt, 2017).

On the other hand, banks have always been the target of criminals motivated to steal money. However, the method of crime is changed from physical robbery to cybercrime with technological advancements that enabled criminals to not only steal money from banks (by information security breach) but also, access the personal details of the bank's customers (Sadiq, 2019). Additionally, the stolen personal information of customers is further sold for misuse which raise confidentiality and integrity issue. Further, Kolade (2022) states that the developing countries must concentrate on the cybersecurity of their finance industry, being the most targeted industries for cyber criminals due to vulnerabilities caused by lack of sufficient cybersecurity and insecure infrastructure, which is the same case for Pakistan.

The recent attacks of 2018 to 2022 are examples of this. In 2018, the data of 19,864 cards belonging to 624 customers from 22 banks of Pakistan were hacked and sold on darknet by international hackers (Haroon, Niazi & Aneel, 2021). Due to which the affected banks lost \$25 million (Haq & Atta, 2019). A similar incident occurred in 2019 when around 57,000 card details from Meezan Bank Limited were compromised (Khali, 2020). In October 2021, the National Bank of Pakistan suffered disruptive attack (DDoS - Cimpanu,

2021). In 2022, several debit cards of United Bank Limited (UBL) customers were used by hackers for international transactions (Siddiqui, 2022). This shows the increasing rate of cybercrimes in banks of Pakistan (Jamshed et al., 2022). However, cybersecurity phenomenon is new in Pakistan therefore not many empirical studies have been conducted in this regard (Anwar, 2020).

The national cybersecurity infrastructure in Pakistan is poor (Khan & Ayub, 2020) and ultimately had effects on the banking sector regardless of security measures adopted by banks (Haroon, et al., 2021). On the other hand, due to corruption and poor political influences the focus on cybersecurity has been neglected until recently in Pakistan and only the military security on the country's borders has been focused on, in terms of national security (Anwar, 2020). The State Bank of Pakistan (SBP) started considering cybersecurity of the banking industry seriously and more intensely just after the cyberattacks in banking industry of Pakistan in 2018 (Qarar, 2018). This was the year when the requirement of cybersecurity of banks increased throughout the world due to increasing rate of serious cyberattacks.

Moreover, in general the government's negligence; the general lack of cybersecurity experts and technology in the country (Qadeer, 2020), the general lack of awareness of cybercrimes and the low literacy rate in Pakistan, are some of the reasons that the concerned topic has not been explored by researchers in depth (Malik & Islam, 2019). This indicates that the Government of Pakistan and SBP do not realize the need for information security in banks. The lack of a holistic regulatory framework for banks and lack of awareness of public about cybersecurity in Pakistan further proves this phenomenon (Haroon et al., 2021). SBP as a regulator of the banking industry in Pakistan introduced a cybersecurity regulatory framework in 2016, for Pakistan's banking industry but unfortunately, those regulations do not meet the contemporary needs of cybersecurity in banking industry. This makes Pakistan's banking industry more vulnerable to cyberattacks (Sadiq, 2019; Syed et al., 2019). Besides, the exemplary cybersecurity regulatory frameworks of NIST and ISO 27001 are available that is being used by countries all over the world as a best framework to make their banking cybersecurity rigorous because, these frameworks have proved to be effective and can be implemented

in all countries (Force, 2020). This implies that SBP do not acknowledge the necessity of information security in their banking industry (Shahbaz UI Haq, 2019) as, Świątkowska (2020) mentioned that many states, organisations, and people still underestimate the need for cybersecurity of information systems. However, the context of this study portrays to highlight the reason behind lack of holistic regulatory framework. Similarly, with such an increasing rate of cyberattacks in the banking sector of Pakistan (2018-2022) and non-responsive attitude of SBP and government of Pakistan towards rigorous actions to secure banks, there is a need to provide a comprehensive empirical study to indicate the major factors (justifying the institutions promoting those factors) for cybersecurity governance and necessary actions.

On the other hand, the whole banking industry in Pakistan is mapped without initial protocols of cybersecurity (Mahmood, 2021). However, if the SBP has required banks of Pakistan to secure their information security since the cybersecurity incidents of 2018 then it cannot be possible that with the recent realisation of implementing information security protocols, the whole banking chain (throughout the country) will be protected in couple of years (Kazmi, 2021). This is proven from the continued cyberattacks on banks in Pakistan whereby only from October 2018 to January 2019 around 260,000 bank cards' data was compromised and sold on the darknet and Joker's Stash (a website similar to darknet) worth \$25 million. These attacks continued in banks during 2021 and 2022 (Dissent, 2019), the reason being that Pakistan's banking industry's information security infrastructure is a decade behind of security protocols' implementation. However, to fully update and equip Pakistan's banking industry's information security infrastructure with robust cybersecurity features, a decade or more is required (Haroon et al., 2021; Mahmood, 2021). Therefore, the dependency on technology cannot be a solution for banks rather a holistic approach of various other factors (social factors) is required to improve the cybersecurity governance in banking industry of Pakistan (Haroon et al., 2021; Kazmi, 2021).

Considering this scenario, Świątkowska (2020) also mentions that while having these issues, the developing countries can better design their financial digital futures, immensely increasing their economic development growth as there are huge markets and

business opportunities available. For example, by upgrading technology systems (Khatri, 2017), hiring experts (Malik and Islam, 2019), multi-factor authentication (Ometov et al., 2018), awareness (Świątkowska, 2020) and improved regulations (Syed, Khaver & Yasin, 2019) etc. Therefore, the findings of this study can be useful to confirm previous literature application in context of Pakistan.

Moreover, the literature shows that besides the lack of law implementation and unsatisfactory regulatory framework for the banking industry (Kalyar, 2019); understaffed cybersecurity programs (lack of experts), cosmetic performance (just paperwork is done but no implementation) and 'security box centric' approach (stick to use old security measures) further affected the cybersecurity governance of banks under investigation in Pakistan (Anwar, 2020; Syed et al., 2019). Therefore, the results of this study can illustrate that if the private commercial banks of Pakistan are going through the same issue or alternatively they are capable of improving their cybersecurity governance even having lack of law enforcement and unsatisfactory regulatory framework. This will support to highlight the maturity level of cybersecurity governance in banks confirming their perception of importance of cybersecurity governance.

Furthermore, empirical studies in different countries have been conducted using multiple theoretical models to ascertain evidence regarding which factors results in cybercrime in their banking industry and what solutions can be found (Alzubaidi, 2021; Dupont, 2019; Cvitić et al., 2017). These studies help to explain the theoretical concepts and importance of the topic for academic researchers. And they also, provide model- based empirical recommendations to help practitioners. Concurrently, various studies have also been conducted on Pakistan's banking industry and cybercrime in the past (Ali & Hashim, 2015; Munir & Manarvi, 2010; Rasool, 2015; Awan & Memon, 2016; Jahankhani et al., 2014; Syed et al., 2019; Ullah et al., 2015; Sadiq, 2019; Jamshed et al., 2022). However, none of these studies have studied the cybersecurity of private commercial banks using the conceptual model similar to this study which includes various factors with institutional logics and empirical evidence (data collection). Rather, most of the studies are based on the self-interpretation of the authors who belong to the IT field.

Thus, this empirical study can highlight the factors of cybersecurity governance and need for their management in the private commercial banks of Pakistan with the help of institutional logics, previous empirical studies and first-hand information collected from practitioners in the field. This will help the government of Pakistan and SBP to understand the importance and necessity of information security in the banking industry of Pakistan and take immediate recommended actions to improve it. Hence, this study will contribute to that effort.

1.4. Research Aim, Objectives, and Questions

1.4.1. Research Aim

The aim of this study is to investigate the factors that underpin effective cybersecurity governance in private commercial banks operating in Pakistan.

1.4.2. Research Objectives

While the research aim represents the goal of this research and what aims to achieve, the research objectives below state how it sets to achieve it and what the steps are (Benste and Vincen, 2022). In order to satisfy the above research aim, the following objectives have been outlined as follows:

1. To investigate the significant internal and external factors (challenges) that affect cybersecurity governance in the private commercial banks of Pakistan.
2. To determine the maturity of cybersecurity governance in private commercial banks in Pakistan understanding the perception of banks about cybersecurity governance.
3. To understand the cybersecurity threats caused by identified factors in private commercial banks of Pakistan.
4. To recommend effective cybersecurity governance measures for the private commercial banks of Pakistan.

1.4.3. Research Questions

Considering the above aim and research objectives, this section presents the research questions which are closely aligned to ensure is central to the consistency and content of this thesis, acting as metrics in terms of the achievement of the research aim and research objectives. As indicated by scholars, the research questions drive the research direction ensuring that answers are identified and mapped (Wilson 2021; Benste and Vincen, 2022).

1. Which significant internal and external factors (challenges) are affecting the cybersecurity governance in the private commercial banks of Pakistan?
2. How the cybersecurity governance is perceived in private commercial banks of Pakistan which can ensure its maturity level?
3. Which cybersecurity threats are caused by identified factors in private commercial banks of Pakistan?
4. What can be the effective cybersecurity governance measures for the private commercial banks of Pakistan?

1.5. Contribution of Study

There is a vast gap in literature regarding cybersecurity governance of private commercial banks of Pakistan, towards which this study will make theoretical and practical contributions. First of all, investigating the internal and external factors this study provides deep insights on customer awareness by articulating how digital literacy; general public literacy and awareness; and effective awareness campaigns by government - customised based on category of people, can support customer awareness. This scrutiny has been neglected by previous studies mainly focusing on customer and public awareness and literacy and, government awareness programme in general (Ullah et al., 2015; Sadiq, 2019; Jamshed et al., 2022). Secondly, prior studies confirmed in general that there is a lack of law, its enforcement and regulatory framework in Pakistan. This research investigated that these factors highly contribute to provide effective cybersecurity governance, justifying why there is lack of law enforcement and regulatory framework. It is also explained that less number of auditors and their capabilities encourage

manipulation of actual performance with cosmetic performance by executives while, previous researches just informed that there is cosmetic performance (Syed et al., 2019; Anwar, 2020).

The strategic planning consisting of executive training and awareness; investment in technology and experts; and employee training and awareness has been rarely given attention by previous researchers investigating them for cybersecurity governance in private commercial banks of Pakistan or even in other banks of Pakistan. Hence, this study fills this gap by demonstrating the executive training and awareness as a major internal factor affecting compliance and implementation of strategic planning – influencing investment in technology, experts, employee training and awareness in private commercial banks of Pakistan. This also justifies why banks adopt box centric approach as neglected from prior studies (Syed et al., 2019). Moreover, these findings also shown the dependency of weak symbolic institution of executive decisions on structural institutions (regulatory framework). Finally, investigating collectively customer awareness, lack of law with its enforcement and regulatory framework this thesis analysed that how the law and its enforcement can be the most effective solution for cybersecurity governance in case of less awareness, poor regulatory framework and strategic planning affected by directors' decision.

Additionally, most of the previous studies considered some factors alone or with a combination of a few, to find their impact on cybersecurity governance on banking sector of Pakistan (Awan and Memon, 2016; Malik and Islam, 2019; Haroon et al., 2021). Rather this study has used the institutional logics concept to integrate the impact of all those factors collectively, and identify the most important factors, to study the social behaviour in context of cybersecurity governance of private commercial banks of Pakistan. This has also contributed to define the dependency of the factors of this study on each other which previous studies lack. Similarly, studying broader approach of institutional logics considering various factors, the findings of this study are useful to confirm previous global literature application in context of Pakistan and vice versa (Alotaibi, 2017; Bada, 2019; Ogunwale, 2020; Badran, 2021). Furthermore, this study has demonstrated the application of multiple theoretical concepts (TAM model, deterrence theory, motivation

cycle, stakeholder theory, CSR, three lines of defence model) considering the factors discussed in context of PCBP, by analysing the findings through literature, filling gap. Likewise, studying the concepts of internal cybersecurity governance (strategic planning; executives' and employees' awareness and training; and investment), this study depicted the maturity level of cybersecurity governance in banks confirming their perception of cybersecurity governance importance while, previous studies mainly discussed the SBP and government understanding of banks' cybersecurity governance (Shahbaz Ul Haq, 2019).

The results informed that lacking investment in appropriate technology, number of experts, employee training and awareness influenced by director's decisions have enabled cybercriminals to launch malware and DDoS attacks on banks whereas the previous studies mostly blamed the lack of technology in general. Thus, it is confirmed that these attacks will increase if directors' decision institutions not changed, facilitating cyber criminals with vulnerabilities in information system of banks. Further, social engineering is found a major threat for PCBP as well-educated people are becoming victim. However, the study proved why government need to make immediate actions which previous studies do not support with empirical results. Additionally, this study provides unique insights on enabling ATM skimming such as out-of-date ATM Windows, ignoring code analysis, admittance to admin controls of ATM Windows by supplier, accessibility of keys to open ATM machines and reboot facility at ATM to hide criminal acts, adding in old literature which just highlighted the ATM skimming issue.

Practically this study will help to enhance the understanding for importance of cybersecurity governance in banks by in depth discussion of threats, the effect of those threats on banks and customer confidence on e-banking, and factors which contribute to information security breaches. Multiple useful recommendation are provided to be implemented by banks, SBP and government, most of which previous literature lack with empirical evidence.

In addition, this study supports the findings of some previous studies conducted on banking sector of Pakistan considering some random factors of this research but lacking

empirical evidence, not referenced with up-to-date literature, neither portraying the theoretical concepts to develop the understanding of the topic. Rather, most of them are based on analyses conducted through secondary data such as government reports, newspaper articles, research papers and journal articles etc. or a general perception of the issue and personal knowledge of the authors. Furthermore, most of the previous studies were found to focus on law, legislation, and awareness factors only and their focus was not private commercial banks –even though they have been the most targeted banks from 2018-2022.

Also, considering the expected growth of the banking sector of Pakistan and the increasing trend of cybercrimes the empirically proven role of the factors of this study will attract future researchers to further explore them in depth considering other aspects such as culture, with purpose to add to the literature theoretically and practically. Moreover, considering employees the basic threat to the banks' information security this study proposes a performance motivation cycle which can also be tested by future researchers. This adds to the theories of motivation and literature on cybersecurity with their practical implications. To fill these research gaps the abovementioned research objectives and questions for this study were designed.

1.6. Scope of Study

The topic of cybersecurity is vast in nature as this includes technological innovations and creativity. This further includes social media, cloud computing, smartphone technology, critical infrastructure, software, business applications, cybersecurity experts, web security, secure internet connection, types of cybercriminals and cybercrimes, different methods of cybercrime, motivations of cybercriminals etc. (Jang-Jaccard & Nepal, 2014). Hence, instead of focusing on the technological aspect of the cybersecurity, this study will focus on the social behavioural aspects (factors) of cybersecurity following institutional logics concepts. The other concepts discussed include confidentiality offence of cybercrimes, and different methods of cybercrime (hacking; illegal data interception; illegal data acquisition; data interference and system interference), cyberthreats (social engineering; fake websites; ATM skimming; and power of attorney; DDoS; malware;

deepfake attacks), regulations (NIST, ISO 27001 and regulatory framework of cybersecurity issued by SBP), available solutions (Banking As A Service -BAAS; cloud storage; open APIs, open Banking, fend off deepfake attacks and multi factor authentication), and relevant theoretical models (The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM); Three lines of defence model; Cybersecurity a Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and Culture; Deterrence Theory (GDT) and Information Security Climate (ISC); and Theories of Motivation).

Similarly, this research is on banks of Pakistan but considering the resources of the author and the time limit only banks in Lahore were considered to collect the data. Specifically, as there are 15 private commercial banks in Pakistan therefore only one branch of each of those banks was chosen to conduct semi-structured interviews (21) from the relevant persons (electronically and in person). Nevertheless, the COVID-19 has proven to be a challenge with travel restrictions, but with extra efforts and expense the author managed to travel and collect the required set of data.

1.7. Theoretical Aspects

The social behavioural concept of cybersecurity governance has been grounded by different aspects of institutional isomorphism. However, this study relies on institutional logics approach as an advanced concept of institutions. Following institutional logics concepts, this thesis acknowledge that cybersecurity governance is dependent on internal and external factors collectively. The institutional actors (government, SBP, and private commercial banks of Pakistan) constitutes the logics/factors of cybersecurity governance which they can change when required. Along with institutional logics this study also considered TAM model; Three lines of defence model; CSR and Culture; Deterrence Theory and ISC; and Theories of Motivation to develop the understating of relative factors of this study.

1.8. Methodology adopted

This study is based on interpretivism philosophy to understand the factors causing threats presented in private commercial banks of Pakistan and find effective recommendations for their cybersecurity governance. Altogether 21 semi structured interviews (including 3 pilot studies; Two CISOs, and one cybersecurity risk analyst) were conducted (14 CISOs, and 7 different departments) within 13 private commercial banks of Pakistan (out of 15 intended) whereby the direct observations and recorded documents were produced repeatedly over the period of 2 years. The data was analysed using thematic analysis to interpret the detailed meaning of investigating factors and threats to find the recommendations (Moschkovich, 2019). The key findings of the study are presented in tables, and quotes in the results chapter six.

1.9. Structure of the Study

This research is based on eight chapters. Chapter 1 introduces the study. Chapter 2 defines the context of study followed by the Chapter 3 which is literature review to develop chapter 4 - conceptual framework. Chapter 5 highlights the methodology of study. Chapter 6 presents results to develop discussions in Chapter 7. Finally, chapter 8 concludes the study with contribution, future research, and limitations of this study.

Chapter One: In this chapter the researcher has introduced the topic (cybersecurity issue in private commercial banks of Pakistan) by discussing its background; research objectives and questions; significance, contribution, and scope of study; theoretical aspects; methodology; and structure of study.

Chapter Two: This chapter provides broader insights on the context of research. it explains the role of banks in the economy of Pakistan, cybersecurity landscape of Pakistan, cybersecurity law and the regulatory framework of Pakistan's banking sector with recent cyber incidents, and the increasing trend of cybercrimes in Pakistan. This builds the reason of choosing Pakistan for this study.

Chapter Three: It defines different terminologies used in the study. Further, this chapter explores the institutional logics following the detailed background of institutions and their development to develop the grounds on cybersecurity governance. Followed by it, factors; the cybersecurity methods, threats, and theoretical concepts relating to cybersecurity of banks; and cybersecurity frameworks, and solutions in order to develop a broader context of cybersecurity concept are discussed.

Chapter Four: This chapter presents the theoretical framework in order to develop research questions from the key concepts used in the literature review. Furthermore, it provides the graphical presentation of the conceptual framework identifying the link between key variables of the study.

Chapter Five: This chapter justifies the research methodology used for this study. Specifically, it depicts the reason of philosophical grounds to inform the choice of the research approach, strategy, and design for this study. The concepts of validity, reliability and ethics have also been discussed.

Chapter Six: This chapter provides the results of the data collected and analyse them to be used in discussion chapter. The analysis were made using themes to present the key findings.

Chapter Seven: This chapter discusses in detail how the research objectives are meet analysing qualitative data, relating it back to the literature and theory. It also provides the recommendations for PCBP, SBP and Government of Pakistan under research objective four.

Chapter Eight: It shows the conclusion revising the theoretical model. It also lists the contribution of study. Finally, it highlights the limitations of the study and future research prospects.

Following is the diagrammatical presentation of the structure of study.

Figure 1: Structure of Study

Source: Author Developed

In the following chapter, the literature is evaluated in a general context to set the theoretical foundation of this research.

CHAPTER TWO: PAKISTAN – THE EMPIRICAL FIELD OF INQUIRY

2.1. Introduction

This chapter demonstrates the context of the research area by justifying the rationale for considering Pakistan for this empirical research. This section of the study provides the historical development of banking sector of Pakistan with its contribution to economic development of country, resonating the importance of banking sector for Pakistan. the chapter discusses the weak cybersecurity landscape in Pakistan and contemporary laws and regulations for cybersecurity of banks. Finally, it sheds the light on the recent cyberattacks on banking sector of Pakistan whereby the main target were PCBP. Overall, this chapter highlights the need of effective cybersecurity governance in PCBP.

2.2. Define Bank and its functions

A bank is an institution transacting the business of accepting, for the purpose of lending of deposits of money from the public, repayable on demand otherwise, and withdrawable by cheque, draft order or otherwise and includes any post office savings bank (Abidi, Chandio, & Soomro, 2014, p. 46). Zavadska (2018) states that banks play the role of financial intermediaries, and the basic function of financial intermediaries is to increase their profits and wealth by selling/promoting their products.

2.3. Private Commercial Banks

The banks have always played a vital role in the prosperity of any economy (Rushchyshyn et al., 2021). The most important type of bank is a commercial bank because, they facilitate the public and businesses with financial services while ensuring economic and social stability as well as continuous growth of the economy. Subsequently, the banks are considered the backbone of an economy (Kalpana & Rao, 2017) and they are the basic focus of this study. The commercial banks are further divided into three categories: public banks, private banks, and foreign banks (SBP, 2019). Nevertheless, the private banks are the basic concern in this thesis.

2.4. Development of Pakistan and its Banking Sector

The banks of Pakistan have played a vital role in the growth and expansion of the economy of Pakistan. Initially, the lack of a sound banking system in Pakistan caused the country to struggle to manage its financial system, whereas now it is one of the most striking (profitable and stable) banking industries in the world (Hafiz-Ali et al., 2019). On the other hand, the development of a global and cohesive banking sector has had to confront different issues for example legislation, technological and structural changes (Angur, Natarajan & Jahera, 1999), the same as Pakistan, as discussed below.

2.4.1. Phases of Banking Sector in Pakistan

2.4.1.1. Establishment of Commercial Banking System for Pakistan (1947-1973)

Since the independence of Pakistan, its banking industry has faced three different phases: pre-nationalisation, nationalisation and post nationalisation as discussed below. During the pre- nationalisation phase (the era just after the partition of Pakistan and India: 14th August 1947), there were only two working banks, namely Australian Bank Limited and Habib Bank Limited (Zafar & Aziz, 2013). At that time, the Reserve Bank of India was playing the role of the central bank for both Pakistan and India. As the Reserve Bank of India was not performing very well in favour of Pakistan banking industry therefore it was realised that there was a need to establish a separate banking system for Pakistan (Khalabat, 2011).

Subsequently, in 1948 the government of Pakistan decided to establish the SBP, and the National Bank of Pakistan was founded in 1949. Originally, there was huge scarcity of resources and because of dominant political and socioeconomic circumstances the uncertainty made it difficult to run the banking systems smoothly (Ahmad, 2020). In addition, the absence of trained staff and professionals resulted in poor banking products and services. Hence, the State Bank of Pakistan Act was introduced by the government of Pakistan in 1956 and the banking companies' ordinance was introduced in 1962 for the betterment of the banking industry of Pakistan (Burki & Niazi, 2003).

2.4.1.2. Nationalisation of Banks in Pakistan (1974-1978)

It was 1974 when the second phase of nationalisation of Pakistan banking system started. From the 1950s to 1960s the private banks were leading the banking sector of Pakistan but, the partition of Pakistan and Bangladesh and poor economic circumstances forced the government to nationalise all the banks (Rammal, 2008). For this purpose, the government of Pakistan merged all banks into five banks all over Pakistan. The basic purpose of nationalisation of banks was to promote the welfare of society by providing credit facilities to all classes of society in Pakistan equally and to develop the economy by effectively utilising the capital which was being used by only a few bankers (Abidi, Chandio, & Soomro, 2014). A banking council was established to run nationalised banks smoothly.

2.4.1.3. Post Nationalisation Period

The nationalisation resulted in the growth of Pakistan's banking sector but largely it was beneficial only for politicians and government (Khalabat, 2011). During the 1980s to 1990s, the board of directors and chief operating officers of banks were being hired based on their political influence instead of on merit (Zafar & Aziz, 2013). The loans taken from the banks were not being used for the betterment of banking industry because the corruption was at its highest level during this period. On the other hand, interest free Islamic banking was introduced to promote the banking system (Shahid, Rehman, Niazi, & Raoof, 2010).

2.4.1.4. Privatisation of Banks

The third phase of Privatisation started in 1990s whereby the government of Pakistan decided to privatise all the banks and changed the National Act of 1974. Under this phase, the government made it easy to open private banks which subsequently resulted in the growth of private banking (Ahmad, Malik, & Hamayoun, 2010). The privatisation made it easy to manage the interest rates and helped to eliminate the credit ceilings. Subsequently, the government was able to set its borrowing rates as per the market rates and start the auction of its securities (Mujahid et al., 2014).

2.4.1.5. Post privatisation and Onwards

The changes made in Banking Companies Ordinance 1962 and the Bank of Pakistan Act 1956 for privatisation helped the regulatory system of Pakistan to become stronger (Usman, 2011). This helped to improve the internal controls of banks and made the supervision and corporate governance of banks effective. During this era, small and medium enterprise loans, and consumer as well as mortgage loans were promoted. The relaxed policies and regulations of the banking sector helped in the growth and development of Pakistan's financial sector (Khalabat, 2011).

Furthermore, by 1993 there were 33 total commercial banks working in Pakistan comprising 19 foreign and 14 local banks. Until 2001 there were 43 commercial banks which consisted of 19 foreign and 24 local banks (Akhtar, Ali & Sadaqat, 2010). Thereafter until 2010, there were a total of 9,348 branches of banks in Pakistan which included those of 25 local private banks, five public commercial banks, four specialised banks, and six foreign banks (Zafar & Aziz, 2013).

At present, there are 45 working banks in Pakistan which consist of 39 local and six foreign banks. Further, these 39 local banks include six public banks, 13 Islamic banks, 15 private commercial banks, four specialised banks and one public sector non-schedule bank (SBP, 2019). This shows that the banking industry in Pakistan is growing very quickly, but still it is not as developed and saturated as the banking industries of developed countries are. This means it has opportunity to grow (Hafiz-Ali et al., 2019).

2.4.2. Private Bank Choice for Thesis

The increasing uptake of internet banking is resulting in the success and development process of banking sectors all over the world. This is also the case of Pakistan since there is 'privatization phase' of banking sector with purpose to grow the banking sector, as discussed above. Furthermore, the significant role of banking sector in economic growth, where private commercial banks are the main players, is confirmed in the following sections. Therefore, the private commercial banks will be the focus of study. Another major reason of choosing private commercial banks is because the people have more

trust in private banks than in public banks, as private banks have to provide the best service possible as compared to public banks, to gain customers' trust (Waqar ul Haq & Muhammad, 2012). It is found that people with more trust, structural assurance and familiarity with banking feel more comfortable to use banking facilities (Afshan, Sharif, Waseem, & Frooghi, 2018). Although a bank which fails to secure its information system not only will lose its competitive advantage and customers, but its very existence is also brought into question (Saimimi, 2020). Eventually, it can be said that the sustainability of a bank can depend on its capability to control its information security system effectively (Zia UL Islam, Khan, & Zubair, 2019). Hence, it is not surprising that about 80% of executives in the financial services sector rank cybersecurity as a top concern (Travelers, 2022). While, the recent cyberattacks in Pakistan (2018, 2021, and 2022) were mainly on private commercial banks which caused a huge financial loss of \$2.6 million and loss of customers' trust. This creates a critical situation for Pakistan, as the country needs immediate measures to deal with current cyberattacks in order to run its economy smoothly.

2.4.3. Infrastructure of Banking Sector in Pakistan

All the banks in Pakistan are registered and work under the Banking Companies' Ordinance 1962. Working as a central bank, the SBP is responsible to control the whole banking system of Pakistan. Also, all the banks in Pakistan are legally required to abide by the rules, regulations and policies issued by the SBP (Habib, 2015). The National Bank of Pakistan (NBP) is a commercial bank which has its headquarters based in Karachi. It is owned by the Government of Pakistan, but it works as a commercial bank while, also acts as a trustee of public funds and represents the SBP where SBP is absence because, the SBP holds a major part of shares of NBP (Taqdees, 2018).

The banks of Pakistan are providing various services to their customers which include credit facility, bank overdraft, ATM facility, running finance, fixed rate interest on fixed deposits, current account, profit, and loss saving account, transferring funds, motor finances, housing finance, agricultural finance, and industrial expansion loan etc. (Afsheen, 2016).

2.4.4. Role of banks in Economy of Pakistan

2.4.4.1. Financial Position of Banking Sector

According to State Bank of Pakistan the total assets of the banking industry of Pakistan equals Rs. 28.790 trillion (Iqbal, 2021). Even with the economic slowdown, for 2019 the Pakistani banking industry earned Rs. 177 billion profit which was 20% higher than 2018 (Basir, 2020). While in 2020, the profit adequacy ratio increased to 18.7% from 17% in 2019, even in COVID-19 lockdown (Nizami, 2021). Finally, in 2021 there was a 15% (Rs. 268 billion) increase (Khan, 2022). The following section will show the development of the banking sector of Pakistan over time using different factors (return on assets, return on equity, gross domestic product, economic growth, and percentage of people with bank accounts).

2.4.4.2. The development in the banking sector of Pakistan and its impact on revenue generation/economic growth

Economic growth is one of the basic aims of any economic system (Puatwoe & Piabuo, 2017) and the banks play an important role in this because people trust banks and save their money with them. Banks lend their money to other people (retail credit), manufacturers and many other businesses (business credit) to use it and expand businesses which in return increases employment opportunities, supply, and purchasing power of consumers which results in increase in demand (Hafiz-Ali et al., 2019). Consequently, this increases Gross Domestic Product (GDP), economic growth and subsequently happiness in the country. Hence, banks are the backbone of businesses and the whole economy is dependent on them (Paun et al., 2019). The following Figure 2 shows the process of economic growth:

Figure 2: Process of Economic Growth

Paun et al. (2019)

Initially, in the early twenties Walter Bagehot and then Schumpeter (economists) pointed out the positive relationship between the finance system of an economy - which is mainly managed by banks, and economic growth. Later, from 1980s this relationship became the dominant topic of research (Miller & Chatterji, 2013). Proceeding further, in 1993 King and Levine conducted a study with the cross-country evidence using the data of 77 countries from 1960-1989. The results of this study revealed that the improvement in financial system (banks are the key players of financial system) can play a major role in economic growth (Gazdar & Cherif, 2015). Overtime, the research on banking sector growth and economic growth has been expanding. In time it was found that even the predetermined component of banking sector development immensely impacts the future rates of economic growth (Rushchyshyn et al., 2021).

Additionally, the high quality and effective functioning of the banking sector highly impacts the stability of the economy (Hafiz-Ali et al., 2019). This explains that the banks are the backbone of an economy (Mushtaq & Siddiqui, 2017) and in this regard the results of the studies conducted in different countries by Hshin-Yu Liang and Alan Reichert (2006), Saxena and Saxena (2014), Popov (2017), Puatwoe and Piabuo (2017), Guru and Yadav (2019), Paun et al. (2019), Berger, Molyneux, and Wilson (2020), and Chu (2020) show that there is a high positive relationship between changes in a country's banking sector development and economic growth. Nevertheless, supporting the above studies of economic growth which resulted from the banking/financial industry, the following available economic data (suggested by The Global Economy (2021) to analyse the

economic growth of a country) is used to produce further discussion about the role of the banking industry in the economic growth of Pakistan between the years 1960-2019.

i) Gross Domestic Product (GDP) Growth in Pakistan

The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) provides information about the size of an economy and its performance. The growth rate of real GDP indicates the general health of an economy. Furthermore, an increase in real GDP means that a specific economy is performing well (Callen, 2020).

Chart 1: GDP Increase in Pakistan (billions of U.S. dollars) 1960 - 2019

The Global Economy (2021)

The above Chart 1 shows the GDP growth in Pakistan from 1960 to 2019. It can be seen that since 1960 the GDP in Pakistan is continuously increasing from \$10 billion to \$320 in 2018 with gradual decrease during some years. It only had a huge decrease in 2019 to \$280 billion. The following Chart 1a shows that more than half of the GDP in Pakistan has come from the service sector, from 2009 to 2019 while the banking is one of the major service sectors of Pakistan which makes a large contribution towards GDP (Ahmed & Ahsan, 2011).

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Chart 1a: GDP Contribution of Agriculture, Industry, and Service Sectors

The Global Economy (2021)

Likewise, the following Chart 2 shows that between 2010 and 2019 the service sector contribution to GDP increased continuously while, in 2019 the overall gross domestic product in Pakistan decreased as shown in the above Chart 1.

Chart 2: GDP From Services in Pakistan Increased to 7,803,812 PKR Million in 2019 from 7,452,631 PKR Million in 2018

Trading economics (2021)

ii) Economic Growth Forecast 2020 - 2024

Chart 3: Economic Growth Forecast of Pakistan 2020 - 2024

The Global Economy (2021)

The above Chart 3 shows the -0.4% negative growth in 2020 due to Covid-19's impact on the economy of Pakistan while, according to the financial data available to IMF, it is expected that the economy of Pakistan will grow from 1.5% in 2021 to 5% in 2024.

iii) Banking Sectors' Return on Assets (ROA)

Chart 4: Pakistan Banking Sectors' ROA, in Percent (1996 – 2017)

The Global Economy (2021)

The above bar Chart 4 shows the banking sector' ROA in Pakistan from 1996 to 2017. It is clear that from 1996 (3.2%) until 2000 (1.3%) the return on banks assets in Pakistan has been decreasing. Then from 2001 (1.6%) until 2005 (2%) it started increasing. With a gradual decrease in 2006 it became negative from 2008 (-1.84%) until 2010 (1.7%) and then it started increasing from 2012 (with the highest return of 3.5%) with fluctuations. According to Lukosiunas (2021) ROA of more than 1% in the banking sector is considered good. Hence, apart from the recession period of 2008 to 2010 the banking sector of Pakistan had very good ROA since 1996 with highest ROA during 2012 (3.5%), lowest in 2008 (-1.84%) and at average 1.4% during those years.

iv) Bank Return on Equity (ROE)

Chart 5: Pakistan Banking Sector's ROE in Percent, (1996 – 2017)

Speights (2016)

The above Chart 5 shows that ROE in banking sector of Pakistan since 1996 (35%) till 2000 (20%) has been decreasing. Then it started increasing from 2001 (27%) until 2004 (29%). Later, decreasing from 2005 (28%) it became negative by 2008 (14%) until 2010 (18%), again, it started increasing from 2011 (0.5%) and was at highest in 2012 (40%) with a gradual decrease in the later years. According to Liargovas and Skandalis (2010) a double figure ROE is considered a good return on shareholders' investment and the above graph shows that from 1996 until 2017 the ROE has been over 15% except for the recession time of 2007 to 2011.

V) People with Bank Accounts

Chart 6: People in Pakistan with Bank Accounts, Percentage of The Population Over 14 Years of Age, 2011 - 2017

The Global Economy (2021)

As per the available data, the above bar Chart 6 reveals that only 16.5% of the population had bank accounts by 2017, and comparative to other countries globally Pakistan has population with around 70% unbanked adults (Mangi, 2021).

Chart 7: People with Bank Accounts, Percentage of the Population Over 14 Years of Age

The Global Economy (2021)

The above Chart 7 shows the percentage of the population who have bank accounts in Japan, USA, the United Kingdom, and China in comparison with Pakistan for the period

of 2011 to 2017. In all of the other countries except Pakistan, more than 60% of their population aged over 14 had bank accounts.

According to Haq (2015) the Economist magazine on the annual Economic Intelligence Unit (EIU) assessment and ranking of 55 countries about promoting financial inclusion, in 2015 Pakistan was ranked 5th. This indicates that the country has potential to growth. Also, Kazmi (2021) mentions that by 2021 the banking sector of Pakistan did not offer many other products that offer a more convenient lifestyle are being offered in developed countries, and the report shows that globally people are more adoptive to new technology which facilitates them. Subsequently, having vast market and product options the banks can play their role and further economic growth, but the cybersecurity must be inclusive of those products (Beck et al., 2022).

2.4.4.3. Summary of Development of Pakistan and its Banking Sector

The banking sector of Pakistan has been growing facing the different phases and the reforms introduced by SBP have played a vital role towards its performance. However, the purpose of this section is to see the worth, financial position and performance of banking sector of Pakistan over the years. The gross domestic product is chosen as a factor to see the performance (economic growth) of Pakistan so that it can show the overall economy of Pakistan from 1960 until 2019 (Mallett & Keen, 2012). It is found that the overall gross domestic product has been continuously increasing until 2018 with slight decreases. This means the economy of Pakistan has been growing over the years (Qamruzzaman & Jianguo, 2018). The notable thing is that this increase in GDP has highest proportion from services sector which is found to be increasing constantly from 2010 to 2019.

After the year of pandemic 2020, it is expected that the economy of Pakistan will grow faster from 2021 (1.5%) to 2024 (5%), (The Global Economy, 2021). On the other hand, comparing the change in the real GDP rate of Japan, US, United Kingdom, and China with Pakistan it is demonstrated that the change in the real GDP rate of Pakistan has mostly been higher than Japan, US, and United Kingdom since 2000 to 2017 which shows higher economic growth in Pakistan than other countries. Nevertheless, this growth is in percentage terms not in amount. As even with low percentage Japan, US and United Kingdom would have higher GDP as compared to Pakistan but, this growth at least shows the expected usual growth within the country (The Global Economy, 2021).

Furthermore, the ROA and ROE in banking sector of Pakistan has been over the required rate of return between 1996 and 2017 which shows that the banking sector has been playing a significant role in the economy of Pakistan (Qamruzzaman & Jianguo, 2018). Also, only 16.5% of the population over the age of 14 had accounts in banks in Pakistan by 2017 whereas Japan, USA, United Kingdom, and China had 75% of their population over the age of 14 with a bank account by 2017. This means there is still a huge market for the banking sector in Pakistan which will help to develop the economy fast. This economic performance in Pakistan resulted from banking sector performance which supports the studies with same context. Although, having such a significance role in the economy of Pakistan it is worth to highlight the security landscape of this industry as shown below.

2.4.5. Cybersecurity Landscape in Pakistan

It was in the early 1990's when Pakistan obtained internet availability as a developing country. Now Pakistan is known as one of the top five countries by number of internet users (World Population Review, 2022). According to Pakistan Telecommunication Authority (PTA) there were fewer than 2 million broadband subscribers in 2012 but, since the 3G service was introduced, the number has increased to 16 million in 2014 while it reached 100 million in 2021 (Ali, 2021). However, now the internet use has further widened in Pakistan to 116 million broadband subscribers with 52.60% penetration (PTA, 2022).

Having such a large population involved with information and communication technologies in Pakistan, its cyberspace has become a new domain which is facing challenges regarding the updated cybersecurity regulations. As per the global cybersecurity index report Pakistan is ranked 79th (NCSI, 2022). In 2020, Pakistan was listed in five locations where the highest malware attacks were encountered with having over 45% effects of them. Furthermore, Pakistan was also listed as one of five countries which had the highest number of cryptocurrency attacks in 2018 (Microsoft, 2020).

Along with this, in 2019, remarkable incidents happened during which hackers used a malware "Pegasus" to hack the mobile phones of senior Pakistani officials through WhatsApp. This incident became viral when it was found that the same malware was being used by international intelligence agencies to spy on Pakistani lawyers, politicians and so on (Abdul Qadeer, 2020). According to a report submitted to Islamabad High Court (IHC), the Federal Investigation Agency (FIA) has received 178,513 complaints of cybercrimes between 2019 and 2021. As per this report, the Cyber Crimes Wing (CCW) of FIA received largest number of complaints (94,227) in 2020. While in 2021, only from January to August 31st, CCW received 53,996 complaints throughout the country. And in 2019, 30,290 complaints were received (Asad, 2021). This shows the continuous increasing trend of cybercrime during pandemic.

However, the financial sector of Pakistan is not the exception of cyber challenges. ATM skimming, hacking and online payment frauds are one of the most well-known cyberthreats being faced in Pakistan. According to Malik (2019) out of 25 million bank account holders around 10,000 have become the victim of hackers throughout the industry. In short, the industry has lost a significant amount of money due to cyberattacks (Haroon et al., 2021).

On the other hand, cybersecurity laws have been introduced in Pakistan but, their implementation is a major challenge. The implementation of law is hindered by the weak institutional structure in Pakistan along with other major challenges for example hostile intelligence networks and anti-state elements (Syed et al., 2019). Pakistan is facing multiple challenges for example corruption, poverty, lack of technological expertise, and lack of a sound democratic system. However, cybersecurity is one of the most important challenges for Pakistan. There are several challenges the cybersecurity landscape of Pakistan is facing, as discussed below (Abdul Qadeer, 2020).

Owing to the lack of technological expertise to control surveillance, the national cybersecurity of the country is also weak. Further, the technology in Pakistan is vulnerable to malware for example Gamarue, Skeyya and Peals. This malware is used to install another malware in the system and steal the data. Another challenge to the technology of the country is Distributed Denial of Service (DDOS) attack, or data transfer from computer to the attack without acknowledgment and permission of user (Qarar, 2018). The best example for this attack is the most recent incident of 2018 in the banking sector of Pakistan whereby the data of customers was stolen. Of course, this causes trust deficit between customers and banks (Mohammad & Ahmed, 2018). In addition, in general, lack of awareness among people about cybersecurity is one of the reasons which makes cybersecurity of banks weaker (Anwar, 2020).

In addition, incorrect and incomplete explanation of cybersecurity on media is another challenge in Pakistan. And this challenge is affected by the weak institutional structure of the country. The country focuses on traditional security culture which includes border

security threat of nuclear attack terrorism etc. while putting cybersecurity on the back burner (Shahbaz UI Haq, 2019).

Besides, the recent cybersecurity law for the banking sector of Pakistan is challenged because of the weak democratic system of the country. The main reason of this dispute is that this law has granted high powers to authorities which are then misused (Khan, 2016). Besides, it does not provide proper protection for the information breach which is the current challenge for the country (Sridharan, 2016). Additionally, the law does not highlight the difference between cybercrime and cyber warfare or cyber terrorism therefore it becomes hard to decide which punishment relates to which crime (Kalyar, 2019).

Similarly, Pakistan has a low literacy rate, which is only 58% based on data available between 2006 and 2019 (Neil, 2019) and according to Balaraj and Shetty (2019) low literacy makes it hard for customers to understand the importance of information security. Therefore sometimes, they unintentionally share their personal information which results in cybercrimes against them (hacking, and ATM skimming etc.). Moreover, the use of E banking in Pakistan is at its initial stage with low number of e-banking users (Ahmad, Bhatti, and Hwang, 2020).

Nevertheless, in spite of all efforts made by the country to provide cybersecurity measures Pakistan is still at the initial stage of cybersecurity. In short, the cybersecurity landscape of the country including banking sector is weak. The security system of Pakistan is not proactive and comprehensive, instead it is reactive (Sadiq, 2019). Moreover, the provided measures lack cohesiveness along with understaffed programs relating to many measures not being implemented but simply being cosmetic. Most importantly, the methodology to solve the cybersecurity issues in the country is more “security box centric” whereby any out of box solution is overlooked (Syed et al., 2019). Another issue relating to cybersecurity is governance and documentation overkill whereby the majority of cybersecurity work is just done on papers with barely 5% to 10% (of approved policies relating to cybersecurity) implemented practically (Anwar, 2020). On the other hand, citizens in Pakistan innocently share personal information on social media with friends

without awareness of cyberthreat while cyber-criminals target these public platforms and steal data including that of locations (Awan & Memon, 2016). Kolade (2022) states that the financial industry of developing countries needs to prioritise their cybersecurity as they are the most targeted industries for cyber criminals because of lack of sufficient cybersecurity and unsecured infrastructure. According to Lewis (2018), roughly 1% of global GDP is lost every year due to cybercrimes which is counted as \$445 billion. Also, it is estimated that by 2030 around 20 billion devices will be connected globally. Hence, Pakistan needs to take serious actions to improve its cybersecurity in all sectors (Anwar, 2020).

Finally, making efforts, the national cybersecurity policy was most recently introduced by government of Pakistan in 2021, whereby it is stated that in Pakistan, the computer hardware are imported from foreign countries and then enter the country without appropriate check and balance. Later, those equipment are sent to the major organisations without critical scrutiny. This reliance on, insufficient national security standards and poor accreditation has resulted in vulnerable computer systems in Pakistan to cyberthreats through embedded malwares, backdoors, and chipsets (Khan & Ayub, 2020).

According to Marco (2012), businesses either regular or internet-based, are fundamentally required to be able to secure their customers from threats based on their businesses and the same is true for banks. However, the banks in Pakistan have continually failed in this during the few years, specifically, the private banks – having topical cyberattacks from 2018 to 2022, as discussed in the following sections (Anwar, 2020). A recent study by Hussain et al. (2017) on e-banking challenges in Pakistan reveals that transaction security, customers' accounts-threats and banking system security affects the use of banking services.

With increasing rate of internet users (World Population Review, 2022) Pakistan has encountered the increasing trend of banking users because, online banking makes the life of customers easier (Hussain et al., 2017). Most of the banking users in Pakistan are not aware of cybercrime techniques and use no security measures against cyberattacks

because of low literacy rate and little training from banks, which is one of the reasons for day by day increases in cyberattacks in Pakistan (Anwar, 2020). Furthermore, with the expected increase in advancement of internet in Pakistan, the number of internet users is also expected to increase which means if the banking sector is not secure from cybercrimes, then more people will be exposed to financial risk. Ultimately this can result in economic downturn hence, this is a serious matter (Syed, Khaver, & Yasin, 2019). Also, Awan and Malik (2018) found the empirical evidence from their study that cybercrimes negatively and significantly affect the efficiency of banks of Pakistan. Additionally, their results showed that Government policies can lessen this effect but not fully eradicate it. They recommend the proper focus on the institutions (factors) of the cybercrimes.

Likewise, a very recent study by Jamshed et al. (2022) on 'critical analysis of cybercrimes in Pakistan' suggests that using preventative measures such as full services network security, long passwords, updated software, and awareness can help to reduce cyberthreats in banks of Pakistan. Hence, it is found that throughout the country there is weak cybersecurity infrastructure including in banks. The following section will highlight the cybersecurity regulatory frameworks issued by SBP, to show what efforts SBP has made to secure banks and how effective these regulations are.

2.4.6. Cybersecurity Law and Regulatory Framework for the Banking Industry of Pakistan

2.4.6.1. Introduction

Making response strategies and solutions against the threat of cybercrime has been a significant challenge, mainly for developing nations (Bainbridge, 2017). A broad and well-designed strategy against cybercrime includes technological protection and legal instructions. Technological protection needs a significant amount of investment (Ward, 2016). This section will show what literature says about the cybersecurity regulations issued by SBP for the cybersecurity of banks. For this purpose, following are the most recent laws, departments and cybersecurity regulatory frameworks being used in Pakistan for its banking sector. According to these regulations, all banks are required to develop a cybersecurity control system. Also, the banks will be required to report any incident to SBP.

2.4.6.2. Laws and Department Established Relating to Cybersecurity

In their most recent study Syed, Khaver, and Yasin (2019) state that the increasing presence of Pakistan's economy in cyberspace has also increased the level of cybersecurity threat immensely. With this regard, over time different laws and regulations have been introduced in Pakistan to deal with cyberattacks but, those laws are not sufficient to fully protect from up to date cyberattacks. Therefore, it is necessary to continuously keep assessing cyberattacks and to introduce essential changes and corrections in cybersecurity laws and regulations (Sadiq, 2019). There are two response and security measures to handle privacy issues in Pakistan. One is the National Response Centre for Cybercrime (investigate crime) and the second is Pakistan's Senate Defence Committee (to pass laws), (Zahoor & Razi, 2020).

The following are the laws and departments established by SBP relating to cybersecurity.

2.4.6.3. Electronic Transactions Ordinance (2002)

The cyber regulations in Pakistan have been introduced over a period of time. The first document relating to cybercrime to be introduced was named as “electronic transactions ordinance, 2002” (Anwar, 2020). This document referred to only a few numbers of crimes as it was issued with purpose to identify and enable documents, records, information, communication, and transactions electronically as well as to offer the accreditation to certification service providers (Haq & Atta, 2019).

2.4.6.4. Electronic Crimes Act (2004)

Later in 2004, based on the above ordinance, the Ministry of Information and Technology and Government of Pakistan introduced “Electronic Crime Act” (Syed et al., 2019). This Act was introduced to deal with cyber stalking, electronic fraud, cyber war, data damage, spoofing, electronic forgery, cyber terrorism, and punishment for cybercrimes. Nevertheless, with the passage of time the emergence and enhanced electronic crime demanded serious legislation on cybercrime. Consequently, the following Act was passed (Haroon, Niazi, & Aneel, 2021).

2.4.6.5. FIA National Response Centre for Cybercrime 2007

Having the above Acts for electronic crimes, in 2007 the Federal Investigation Agency (FIA) introduced a national response centre for cybercrime. This is the one and only unit in the country which directly receives the complaints to assist other law enforcement agencies in case of cybercrime (Hafiz Ali et al., 2019). Basically, this is a law enforcement agency, but as it is the only organisation in Pakistan dealing with cybersecurity issues, Therefore, its performance can become compromised due to lack of staff (Sadiq, 2019).

2.4.6.6. Prevention of Electronic Crimes Act (2016)

As mentioned earlier, based on the need later the Prevention of Electronic Crimes Act was introduced in 2016 in Pakistan (Rasool, 2015). Before that there was no legislation for cybercrime in Pakistan (Zia UL Islam et al., 2019). Under this Act, any illegal access

to information system which includes unlawful copy of any kind of information, illegal access to any apparatus, electrical fraud, interfering communication, crimes against individual modesty or decency, scripting malevolent codes or their programming, cyber nuisance, hate speech or adoration of an offence, will result in both fines and jail for certain amounts and time respectively as a punishment (Khan, Tehrani, & Iftikhar, 2019). This Act still does not cover all aspects of cybersecurity. However, the cyber legislations are very ineffectual in Pakistan as much that they can be easily manipulated and dodged by anyone having a little computing knowledge (Khan & Anwar, 2020; Sadiq, 2019; Syed et al., 2019).

2.4.6.7. Computer Emergency Response Team (CERT)

The Electronic Crimes Act highlights that to strengthen the information security and critical infrastructure there is need to establish a specific institution which will formally work to control cyberattacks and reduce any loss, provide indication, offer quick and efficient retrieval, thwart such future events, and gain awareness of the threats against the organisation (Khan & Anwar, 2020). For this purpose, a Computer Emergency Response Team (CERT) has been established which consists of experts who can deal with cybersecurity of critical infrastructure or information data (Awan & Memon, 2016). Besides, the intelligence agencies' officers will also be working as part of this team. Additionally, this Act suggests that our information system needs the international support in order to prevent the cybersecurity threats (Syed et al., 2019).

2.4.6.8. Call Centre Facility

Most recently, SBP has instructed the commercial and microfinance banks of Pakistan to take a step against fake phone calls - relating to financial frauds, being experienced by their customers as such calls are increasing. For this purpose, the customers are now enabled to contact the call centre of their bank to block their credit cards and accounts to avoid any financial frauds (Siddiqui, 2021). Many customers have complained regarding money stolen from their accounts after they shared their confidential details for example online banking password or pin codes of credit and debit cards to scammers as a result

of either fraudulent emails or phone calls (Digital Adoption Banking, 2021). Normally, this kind of criminals present themselves as customers' banks and threaten customers by saying that their bank accounts and credit cards will be blocked if they do not provide the required information (Hafiz Ali et al., 2019). Another tactic which such criminals use is offering prize money or some other benefits to the customers to acquire financial information. This falls into the category of social engineering. Banks are required to ensure that the call centre agents are fully trained to effectively respond to such calls from customers, whereby they will identify the fraud (Khan et al., 2019). In addition, the recorded data will be reported to the Offsite Supervision and Enforcement Department (OSED) of the State Bank every month (Siddiqui, 2021).

2.4.6.9. Enterprise Technology Governance & Risk Management Framework for Financial Institutions

A framework plays the role of a system of standards, guidelines, and best practices to mitigate risks that are confronted in a digital world (Azmi, Tibben, & Win, 2018). Moreover, Ryerse (2020) says that 'a cybersecurity framework prioritizes the adaptable, repeatable, and cost-effective method to support the security and resilience of your business'.

According to C5-Annex (2018), this regulatory framework provides guidelines to manage risks associated with technology and shows the SBP's requirements for financial institutions in this regard. The instructions of this framework focus on improving the proactive and reactive environment of financial institutions regarding information security. Zia UL Islam et al. (2019) state that as per this framework the financial institutions will adopt an integrated risk management approach to control the risk relating to technology. However, implementing several guidelines of this framework the financial institutions will have to determine for themselves the applicable provisions of this framework which are relevant to technology risk. This framework supersedes the following regulations regarding technology security in Pakistan's financial sectors (C5-Annex, p6, 2018):

Guidelines on Information Technology Security issued vide BSD Circular No. 15 of 2004

Guidelines on Business Continuity Planning issued vide BSD Circular No. 13 of 2004

BCP Guidelines (Annexure – B) issued vide BSD Circular No. 03 of 2007

Information Systems: Guidelines on Audits and System Switchover Planning issued vide

BSD Circular No. 08 of 2005

Prevention against Cyber Attacks issued vide BPRD Circular No. 07 of 2016

Subsequently, this is the most recent framework issued by State Bank of Pakistan relating to cybersecurity of financial institutions which does not completely address the way with which the cybersecurity issue is to be dealt. Yet, all the banks of Pakistan are legally required to follow those regulations, to ensure the security of IT (Khan & Anwar, 2020; Sadiq, 2019; Syed, et al., 2019). Although, this framework includes 'Technology Governance Framework and Organisational Structure for Information Security Control System in Commercial Banks of Pakistan' which is given below.

2.4.6.10. Technology Governance Framework and Organisational Structure for Information Security Control System in Commercial Banks of Pakistan

Figure 3: Hierarchy of the governance system in Commercial Banks of Pakistan

Author Developed

The above organisational structure for information security control system in commercial banks of Pakistan shows the hierarchy of the governance system. This framework starts with the Board of Directors as a main authority in the bank (the highest authority) followed by Board IT Committee, IT Steering Committee, and finally IT Management Structure (C5-Annex, 2018). Furthermore, it can be seen that even though CISOs are the main

character to design policies for cybersecurity their position is at the lowest level in the governance systems of information system while, the Board of Directors is at the highest position to make decision regarding investment in cybersecurity.

The following section will show how the weak cybersecurity landscape as well as lack of law and unsatisfactory cybersecurity framework has, and can, impact the banking industry of Pakistan/private commercial banks.

2.4.7. Recent Cyberattacks on Private Commercial Banks of Pakistan

2.4.7.1. Topical Cyberattack on Pakistani Private Banks in 2018

i) Background:

At the end of October 2018, the customers of the banks of Pakistan who had subscribed to receive banking transaction notifications received alerts about money being transferred from their accounts (Mohammad & Ahmed, 2018). Bank Islami was the first bank which noticed abnormal transactions of \$2.6 million on the morning of 27th October 2018. Consequently, the bank shut down its international payment facility. Subsequently, many other banks issued security alerts and blocked their customers' debit and credit cards for online or international use as well as notified their customers by SMS. This reaction was not enough for the security of customers (Naik Bukht et al., 2020). Bank Islami lost Rs. 6m in 23 minutes (Haroon et al., 2021).

The most noticeable point is that even the FIA did not know when this breach of information security happened and cannot predict whether the same situation could happen again (Ahmed, 2018). This questions the security system in banks and the financial regulator – SBP because, the SBP has been unable to provide yet the contemporary security measures for banks and had not monitored the compliance of them until this incident happened (Rafiq, 2018). According to Shoaib (FIA Director retired Captain) 'Banks are the custodians of the money people have stored with them'. So, they are responsible if their security features are so weak that they result in pilferage (Qarar, 2018).

ii) The Attack:

Stored data from over 9,000 debit cards was posted on the darknet on 26th October 2018. The data was mainly from banks of Pakistan. However, the rumour was that only Bank Islami had suffered a data breach but the data on the darknet showed the real picture whereby thousands of debit cards' data from different banks of Pakistan was posted (Figure 4, Awan et al., 2018).

Figure 4: First Dump from the Darknet

Mohammad and Ahmed (2018)

The detailed data of 8864 debit cards which was found in the darknet relating to customers of nine banks of Pakistan is shown in Appendix F. It can be seen from the above Figure 2 that the Habib bank (largest bank of Pakistan) had the highest number of cards hacked. The Bank of Punjab, Standard Chartered Bank, Bank Islami, and JS banks follow consecutively (Mohammad & Ahmed, 2018). Again, on 31st October 2018, a second set of stored data of over 12,000 cards was posted on the darknet out of which 11,000 cards belonged to Pakistani banks (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Second Dump from the Darknet

Mohammad and Ahmed (2018)

The 11,000 debit cards of 21 Pakistani banks' customers were hacked as shown in Appendix F. Again, the Habib bank had the highest number of cards data hacked. UBL, Meezan, MCB and Bank Alfalah had lower numbers consecutively (Baloch & Firdous, 2018).

iii) What Exactly Happened?

The hacked data was available in two forms on the Darknet. One was available in the form of text which consists of personal details of customers for example name, address, contact number, debit card number, expiry date and CVV2 which facilitates an easy illegal online shopping action (Awan et al., 2018). The other data was in skimmed format. The skimmed card data is used to make duplicate cards which the hacker can physically use at an ATM or payment machine for illegal transactions. In total 19,864 cards' data of 624 customers was stolen from 22 banks of Pakistan. This does not include the small number of cards from other banks (Jamshed et al., 2022). However, this didn't stop here as explained below.

2.4.7.2. Meezan Bank Ltd Internal System Compromised in 2019

Another cyber incident of a similar nature to the above occurred in 2019 whereby around 57,000 cards' data were compromised from Meezan Bank Limited's internal system between January 24th and January 30th. Those cards were found on the darknet to be sold at a price of \$50 each (Khali, 2020).

2.4.7.3. Gemini Advisory

Gemini Advisory is the world's largest provider of intelligence for enterprise security. A few months after the above incidents and reporting, the research by one of the Gemini advisory members revealed that in reality 260,000 card payment breaches associated with Pakistan with a total value of around \$25 million were found on Joker's Stash between October 26th, (2018) and February 25th (2019). The first data was posted on this website on October 26, 2018, with more than 10,000 cards available for sale at \$100 each. The second and third data was posted on October 31st (2018) and November 13th

(2018) respectively with more than 190,000 cards available for sale at \$110 each. The detailed analysis of the incident showed that the point of data compromise was somewhere in Pakistan whereby the data of non-Pakistani cardholders who were travelling from different countries was also compromised. More likely the compromised data was of well-travelled tourist customers of Pakistan banks (Dissent, 2019). This shows the cyber criminals targeted the foreign customers of banks to access a higher value of money.

2.4.7.4. National Bank of Pakistan under Cyberattack in 2021

The National Bank of Pakistan which is owned by the government of Pakistan and is a subsidiary of State Bank of Pakistan, experienced a disruptive cyberattack on October 29th (2021). This attack affected many services provided by the bank including ATMs, internal network, and mobile apps (Cimpanu, 2021). The purpose of this attack was disruption. Immediate action was taken to isolate the incident and save other banks and customers. According to the bank no data was breached, and no funds were stolen (Carnegie, 2022). But the reality can be shown after investigation.

2.4.7.5. United Bank Limited (UBL) Customers under Attack 2022

According to Siddiqui (2022) overseas thieves stole money from United Bank Limited (UBL), one of the leading banks of Pakistan, by using compromised data of various debit cards to conduct fraudulent financial transactions in foreign currencies (\$). In response, the UBL stopped the service of international financial transactions through debit cards, for all its customers. However, the bank declared that they were not under cyberattack and no data breach or hacking had happened. Instead, it was suggested that the robbery was the result of personal information unintentionally shared by customers. But in reality, the data could have been compromised by ATM hijacking as in 2018 and 2019 (Hassan, 2022). It was announced that the lost money would be returned to the customers (because it was not customers' fault) as per the prevailing bank and insurance laws. As a solution, UBL declared that for all customers to use their debit cards for international

transactions they would have to switch on the service (international transaction) first and then they can use their cards for international transactions (Malik, 2022).

One of the customers complained to UBL: “My card was hacked on 19th of this month (2022), and I lost \$65. Immediately, I transferred the rest of my money to my friends’ account and blocked my account and reported to UBL. But I still receive messages of failed transactions which presents that someone is still trying to use my card” (Singh, 2022).

This suggests that these attacks are increasing with time, because most of the cybercriminals are financially motivated therefore, the banks are perpetually on the cybercrime criminals’ radar (IBM, 2020; Sadiq, 2019). In this regard, the following section will discuss the increasing trend of cybercrimes throughout the world, in developing countries and in Pakistan.

2.5. Summary of Chapter Two

The purpose of this chapter was to develop the understanding of how the banking sector in Pakistan has experienced substantial growth over the years since 1947 (independence) and has played a vital role in economic development of Pakistan. This led to understanding the importance of the banking sector specifically in Pakistan and its cybersecurity. It is found that during the last couple of years cybercrime in banks throughout the world have increased considerably and the private commercial banks in Pakistan also has been part of it referring to the recent cybersecurity incidents from 2018 to 2022. Most importantly, the literature shows that it is expected there will be an increase in cybersecurity incidents in financial institutions of developing countries because of weak information security infrastructure. In contrast, as a developing country, the cybersecurity landscape of Pakistan is very poor which not only includes the banking sector, but telecommunications, supply chains and government organisations such as National Database & Registration Authority (NADRA) etc. as well. Especially, the regulatory framework for banking industry of Pakistan is unsatisfactory. This implies that the banking sector of Pakistan is one of the most vulnerable sectors to cyberattacks. Moreover, the base of information security infrastructure of banking industry of Pakistan is developed without conjunction of security features. Therefore, the literature suggests that as a backbone of economy there is immediate need to find out which factors can help to improve the cybersecurity in context of PCBP which can be used to secure the banks in other developing countries as well like Pakistan.

CHAPTER THREE: LITERATURE REVIEW

3.1. Introduction

This section of the study will provide the detailed literature relevant to develop the understanding of research area and how it will lead towards making a conceptual framework with purpose to meet the research objectives of this study. The first part of this chapter will elaborate various terminologies used in the study. Summarising the application of institutional logics developed from the concept of institutional theory, worldwide increasing trend of cybercrime in banks, factors affecting e-banking, theoretical concepts relating them to cybersecurity of banks and threats to banks justifying attackers' motivation. Moreover, this chapter will shed light on international regulatory frameworks, third party solutions, and international standards for cybersecurity of banks in order to develop a widened concept of cybersecurity.

3.2. Key concepts and terminologies

This section of this chapter proposes to define key concepts and terminologies related to the cybersecurity governance to determine how prior literature has defined and perceived such concepts and if they are relevant to this research.

Figure 6: Key concepts of the Study

Source: Author Developed

3.2.1. Cyber

Conceptually, the term 'cyber' has been attempted to be defined by various authors. Yaokumah, Rajarajan, Abdulai, Wiafe, and Katsriku (2020) indicate that the word cyber originates in the ancient Greek word 'kybereo', which means 'to assist or guide' (Yan, Yan, and Lagerstrom-Fife, 2019). Etymologically the word was adopted in the early work of Wiener in 1948, who through its focus on cybernetics, has grounded the cyber terminology and its correlation with technology (Fields, 2018). Although it was adopted by many studies, the term became a usual terminology in the early 1980s with the start of the US ARPANET project, which started the early work of internet protocols (Lorents and Ottis, 2010; Fields, 2018; Donets and Krynytska, 2022).

In 1984 the term gained even more popularity through Gibson's *Neuromancer* publication (Kulshrestha, Gautam, and Singh, 2022; Donets and Krynytska, 2022). The literature indicates that Gibson is the parent contributor to the term (Donets and Krynytska, 2022). Later, other contributors, such as Clarke (1992), continued to re-validate the term (Gautam, Singh, and Kulshrestha, 2022) and by 2000 the term started to be associated with cybercrime (Loader and Thomas, 2013).

The typical pattern observed within the literature that is discussed in the context of electronic medium and virtual online environments (Zdzikot, 2022). Authors such as Fang (2018) and Shad (2019) explain that cyber consists of electronic communication, while the same view further extends to a virtual space where the exchange of information occurs between parties (Goutam, 2015). As such Lorents and Ottis (2010) outline that cyber is a time-dependent set of interconnected information systems and the humans that engage with them.

Although most often perceived as a prefix (Lopez, Setola, and Wolthusen, 2012), the term 'cyber' has also been correlated in past literature either with digitalisation, being associated with the internet expansion and adoption and its related online activities (Charlesworth, 2009). Later on, it has further been associated with cyberwar and cybersecurity (Gautam, et al., 2022; Snow, 2022). Comparatively, distinguishing terms

for physical versus online/cyber world activities is the difference between physical and technological infrastructure (systems, communication). Some authors even suggest that cyber can be defined as an imaginary world, though it has been reconceptualised as 'virtual', where the ideas of geographic boundaries are not applicable (Mitra and Schwartz, 2001). From another perspective, some other authors like Yaokumah et al. (2020) even suggest confusion, and at times, cyber and related terms are used interchangeably, although different in meanings.

To sum up, the term cyber has evolved over the years (Fields, 2018). With technology adoption, its semantics shifted to reflect better an eco-system where the perimeter is whole and maintained by technology and its interaction and dependency on internet capabilities. Whether a compound word or not, 'cyber' distinguishes itself and is an integrative terminology that clarifies the context of this research problem.

3.2.2. Cyberspace

Due to digital transformation in the past decade, cyberspace has become a contemporary term adopted in related studies, often understood as the place within the internet, where activities take place (Koepsell, 2003; Çomak, Şeker, Civelek, and Bozkuş, 2022; Feng and Li, 2023; Chen, Claramunt, Çöltekin, Liu, Peng, Robinson, Wang, Strobl, Wilson, Batty, and Kwan, 2023). Building on the idea that physical versus virtual interrelate, Posta and Tuncel (2023) suggest that the perception of space has changed due to digitalisation and new technologies. The same author indicates that the perception is progressing due to emerging technologies and cultural shifts.

However, joining the above traits of cyber, the cyberspace term have characteristics of two compound words: cyber and 'space'. Hence, it is a space or place which people use through virtual premise, to communicate or perform activities via computer devices, systems, and internet network (Yan, 2018; Fang, 2018; Radoniewicz, 2022).

To further understand implications, Choucri (2013) defines cyberspace as a borderless domain supported by the interconnection of millions of computers through a layered structure, where the physical tools facilitate the logical framework of interconnection,

which allows the processing, manipulation, exploitation, augmentation of information and collaboration of people as well as information (cited in Mbanaso and Dandaura, 2015, p.18; Yan, 2018). This idea had been extended within the literature, suggesting that cyberspace term and boundaries needs is yet to be reached an agreed definition.

The Table 1 below highlights the general agreement on cyberspace relating it to the interconnected computers and virtual space.

Table 1: Cyberspace Network Connectivity and virtual space

<p>Network and interconnectivity</p>	<p>'An electronic system that allows computer users around the world to communicate with each other or to access information for any purpose' (Cambridge Dictionary).</p> <p>'Cyberspace is a global networked, computer-sustained computer-accessed, and computer-generated, multidimensional, artificial, or 'virtual' reality' (Benedict, 1992, P.180, cited by Weber, 1995).</p> <p>'A global domain within the information environment, consisting of an interdependent network of information technology infrastructures and resident data, including the internet, telecommunications networks, computer systems, and embedded processors and controllers' (Medeiros and Goldoni, 2020, p.34).</p> <p>'Cyberspace is a vast, connected network of technologies' (Mohsin, 2023, p.2).</p>
<p>Virtual environment/space</p>	<p>'Cyberspace is an open, global, unregulated, and virtual area of decentralized human activities, social interactions, and application services in the information space transmitted by sensors and internet communication channels, supported by cyberinfrastructure' (Chen et al., 2023, p.2).</p>

Source: Author Developed

From the above, it is clear that cyberspace is a term that has its variations. The evidence identified has shown that the discipline has received considerable attention from academics, governments, and practitioners, given its impact and dependency on individuals and organisations, yet lacks an agreed definition (Çomak et al., 2022; Sloss, 2022; Dacorogna and Kratz, 2023). However, for this thesis cyberspace is a place which

people use for their communication and electronic activities using computer devices or electronic medium and internet (Fang, 2018).

3.2.3. Cyberthreat

According to Reich and Gelbstein (2012, p.228):

Cyberthreat is a possible action that may result in unauthorised access to, exfiltration of, manipulation of, or impairment to the integrity, confidentiality, or availability of an information system or information that is stored on, processed by, or transiting an information system.

These cyberthreats when become into action are called cybercrimes as discussed below.

3.2.3.1. Cybercrime

There is no universally accepted definition of cybercrime because different scholars have tried to look at its definition from their own point of view. However, to define cybercrime it must be noted that cybercrime is made up of two words “cyber” and “crime”. Therefore, the definition of cybercrime must include the characteristics of both words (Robert, 2021). The word “cyber” is jargon used for computers, information technology, internet, and virtual reality (as discussed above), while crime is an offence forbidden by law. Thus, cybercrime is the illegal act of organising attacks on both cyber-space and cybersecurity (Sadiq, 2019). Although, some of its detailed definitions are as follows:

The term cybercrime was invented by Suss man and Heuston in 1995. Cybercrime cannot be defined by a single definition because it is a combination of actions which are based on the material offence object and the methods which harm computer data or security systems (Sabillon et al., 2016). According to Phillip et al. (2022) cybercrime to an extent is a form of traditional crime that is ‘cyber-assisted’ by computers and performed on internet premises by certain parties. Phillips, Davidson, Farr, Burkhardt, Caneppele, and Aiken (2022) describe cybercrimes through three lenses:

- Type I technical in nature

- Type II cybercrimes that involve and exploit human through behaviour
- Type III cybercrimes that are leveraged with the support of emerging technology.

Finnie, Petee, and Jarvis (2010) state that in some circumstances, only hacking activities are considered as cybercrime. For example, the Council of Europe's cybercrime treaty only considers impairment of data or copyright and content infringements as a cybercrime. Gordon and Ford (2006) describe that a little broader definition of cybercrime will include any fraud or stalking using a computer. The U.S. Department of Justice enlarges this definition of cybercrime to comprise any illegal activity that makes use of a computer with purpose of storage of evidence (Banerjee, 2022). According to Banerjee (2022, p.1) cybercrime is a term used for 'all illegal activities that are conducted using a computer/technology as a basic source of commission'. Hence, this study will imply this definition of cybercrime. The other definitions simply explain one or a few of the features of cybercrime for example, harm to computer data or system, hacking, fraud, and stalking. Banerjee broadly includes all illegal activities using computer with purpose to access the information. Therefore, this definition will be considered for this study as it will include the access to banking customers' data by cybercriminals using social media, ATM, hacking, or any other source.

Furthermore, based on the type of cyber-attacker and motivation, cyberthreats can be divided into various types - cybercrime, cyberterrorism, cyberwar, and cyber espionage, of which cybercrime is the focus of this study (Shad, 2019). Determining the type of cybercrime, the cyberthreats can be divided into two forms: cyber-attack and cyber exploitation.

1) Cyber-attacks

Cyber-attack can be defined as a cyber-operation with a malicious purpose intended to access, change, disrupt, betray, damage, or devastate information computer systems or networks or the information and/or programmes installed in or passing through these systems or networks (Rusell, 2012). In addition, cyberattacks are direct attacks across cyberspace to an organisation using the internet in a way which results in operational

disruption, chaos, damage, deactivation, and malevolent control of the organisation's IT infrastructure (Naik Bukht, Raza, Awan, and Ahmad, 2020). Henceforth, the practical actions of cybercriminals to implement the cyberthreat turns into cyber-attacks.

2) Cyber vulnerabilities/exploitation

Cyber vulnerabilities are cyber exploitations finding weak information security systems and consist of confidential information secretly taken through cyberspace to support a cyberattack (Uddin, Hakim, and Hassan, 2020).

3.2.4. Cyber risk

Risk in context of organisations implies an event that can occur, has a frequency and a possible outcome (impact) that could harm the organisation, having an adverse effect . The cyber risk can occur as an event, threat or vulnerability and usually has consequence. In terms of occurrence, cyberthreat is a sub-term used for cyber-risk to indicate an emerging series of action could be performed by a cybercriminal (Strupczewski, 2021).

The literature shows that cyber risk is about the impact and damage to an individual, organisation or government (Biener, Eling, and Wirfs, 2015; Oltramari and Kott, 2018). According to Biener et al. (2015, p. 134),

Cyber risk may be defined as a function of 3 parameters: impact expresses the level of damage that a given risk may cause; threat expresses whether or not a given risk is probable; and vulnerability expresses whether or not existing information security measures are effective.

A study by Brewer (2000) defines cyber risk through lenses of vulnerability or weakness used by a third party to succeed materialisation of a monetary loss (also supported by Mukhopadhyay, Mukhopadhyay, Chatterjee, Saha, Mahanti, and Sadhukhan, 2013). Brewer presents a calculation for risk, indicating that the multiplication of a threat,

vulnerability and asset value could determine the risk value for an organisation. Likewise, Strupczewski (2021, p.6) extends this view with this definition:

Cyber risk is an operational risk associated with performance of activities in the cyberspace, threatening information assets, ICT resources and technological assets, which may cause material damage to tangible and intangible assets of an organisation, business interruption or reputational harm.

Biener et al. (2015) have reported an understanding of cyber risk in a similar matter, although the perspective of damage and impact shares a similar view. Böhme, Laube and Riek (2019) also defined the cyber risk, respectively, through lenses of probability of loss, including the magnitude of loss. In the context of the financial sector, cyber risk refers to operational risk and identifies the ability of an organisation to maintain confidentiality, integrity, and availability of data, managing vulnerabilities (Eling and Schnell, 2016; Bouveret, 2018; Böhme et al., 2018). Thach, Hanh, Huy, and Vu (2021) define cyber risk as a consequence of a cyberthreat taking place in cyberspace. Hence, it can be inferred for this thesis that cyber risk is the possibility of breaching confidentiality, integrity, and availability of information in cyberspace. Due to the increase in attack complexity, volume, and more targeted incidents (Kotsias, Ahmad, and Scheepers, 2023), cyber risks are acknowledged as a top emerging risk for organisations (Curti, Gerlach, Kazinnik, Lee, & Mihov, 2023). In particular, for banks, as emphasised by Pollmeier, Bongiovanni, and Slapničar (2023), cyber risk has become one of the top concerns (Amin, 2016; Strupczewski, 2021; Taherdoost, 2022).

3.2.5. Cyber resilience

In today's interconnected world, most systems which support the online activities of banks have become complex and interconnected to support daily operations for customers (Linkov and Kott, 2019; Assibi, 2023). However, such sophistication has triggered a rise in threat frequency and severity due to potential financial gain for threat actors (Dupont, 2019). Therefore, resilience has emerged as an approach to navigate the adversities from cyber-attacks, technical failures, technical legacies, or past financial crises. Drawing from

existing literature, resiliency explores the impact of disruptions and emphasis more adaptive capabilities for organisations (Assibi, 2023). Furthermore, cyber resiliency defines the ability of an organisation to continuously prepare, respond and recover from an adverse cyber event (Björck, et al., 2015; Filinovich and Hu, 2021). At its core, resilience is about an organisation's strength to protect its business, assets, processes, and people against cyber risks, defend against them, lower the effects of cyberattacks and still maintain effectively the intended outcome of the business (Dhillon, 2020; Choejey, 2018).

Multiple studies have described cyber resilience in various perspectives such; as a quantitative measure of operational performance (Smith, 2023); an organisation's capacity to cope with various risks and threats (Galinec and Steingartner, 2017); an ability to maintain a 'continuous existence' (Annarelli, Nonino and Palombi, 2020). Assibi (2023) indicates that organisations have developed business continuity programmes to address cyber risks not only to defend and recover but also to reduce business interruption, learn and strengthen the response to incidents and threats and also to fulfil compliance requirements given that banks are highly regulated. Such practices bring cyber resilience in the information security. Besides, Björck et al. (2015, p.312) defined cyber resilience as 'the ability to continuously deliver the intended outcome despite adverse cyber events'.

To sum up, it has been observed that previous studies had two views on resilience: 1) robustness to unpredictable and various attacks (Assibi, 2023); and 2) ability to cope, respond and minimise the effect of adverse events (Annarelli, Nonino and Palombi, 2020; Assibi, 2023).

3.2.6. Cybersecurity governance

1) Cybersecurity

Recent studies have shown that society and organisations' technological dependency implies risks and benefits. Studies of cybersecurity show the importance of addressing such risks and threats due to significant consequences on an organisation's capabilities (cyber resilience) to reach their objectives and goals (Adams, Brokx, Corte, Galič, Kala,

Koops, Leenes, Schellekens, Silva, and Skorvanek, 2015; Modi, Kuzminykh and Ghita, 2021; Shaikh and Siponen, 2023). In this regard, previous research has established that cyberspace is complex, and cybersecurity is gaining significant research interest from the last decade (Adams, et al., 2015; Modi, et al., 2021). Though, a variety of studies confirm that IT governance was on the lens of researching the problem (Shaikh and Siponen, 2023), although the focus of research over time has shifted to information security (cybersecurity) separating cybersecurity concept from IT (von Solms and von Solms, 2018).

A variety of definitions of the term 'cybersecurity' have been suggested. Generally, cybersecurity is described as a set of rules designed to secure information (Sadiq, 2019; Taherdoost, 2022) through 'the preservation of confidentiality, integrity and availability of information in the cyberspace' (Syed, Khaver and Yasin, 2019, p.2). Shad (2019, p.5) also indicated that:

Cybersecurity, also known as information technology security, refers to the technologies, processes, and practices to prevent, detect and recover from damage to confidentiality, integrity, and availability of information in cyberspace'.

Moreover, cybersecurity is often used interchangeably with word 'information security' since International Telecommunications Union justified that the idea of cybersecurity revolves around providing confidentiality, integrity, and availability of information in the right amount, place, and for the right person (Akintoye, Ogunode, Ajayi, and Joshua, 2022).

In addition to line with the previous literature findings, the term cybersecurity ranges in terms of definitions. Some decompose the term cyber and security (Ottis and Lorents, 2010) to differentiate the environment. Craigen et al. (2014) indicate that since 1998 up to 2014, cybersecurity and its related terminologies have been researched by significant literature and yet remained an unaddressed issue and thus defined cybersecurity as the organisation and collection of resources, processes, and structures used to protect

cyberspace and cyberspace-enabled systems from occurrences that misalign property rights' (Craig et al., 2014, 17).

Therefore, it can be inferred for this thesis that cybersecurity is a combination of rules developed to secure the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of information in the cyberspace. However, it remains equally important to define the cybersecurity governance to develop the effective discussion in the study.

2) Cybersecurity governance concept

Prior studies have examined governance through perspectives of strategic, tactical (technologies, processes and measures which are used to secure systems, networks, and information from cyberthreats) and operations (Ghelani, 2022; Odebade and Benkhelifa, 2023). Most research analysed the governance implications from the perspective of protecting an organisation from loss (AlGhamdi, Win, and Vlahu-Gjorgievska, 2020). While others suggest that is different depending on what industry, government, e.g., army or discipline; thus, its semantics is understood through a multidisciplinary perspective that has protection against loss in common (Schiliro, 2023).

The increasing trend of cybersecurity threats at national and international level requires effective cybersecurity strategy to avoid such threats. Previously cybersecurity has been considered an IT related problem therefore the management of businesses has been making efforts to resolve this issue (Kooper, et al., 2011; Williams, 2021). The consequences were the failures because cybersecurity is not an IT governance issue rather it is cybersecurity governance concern (Savaş and Karataş, 2022; Zafar, et al., 2022). For example, the IT governance definitions are studied over time, which relate it to managing technical controls perspectives and do not include the cyber environment. In this regard, Kooper, et al., (2011) illustrated that prior research considered it as IT governance yet represents a partial view that mainly covered the concept from a perspective of asset protection.

Comparatively, a cybersecurity governance includes meeting the industry standards and best practices to enable the financial organizations to mitigate cybersecurity risks and

defend their digital assets from cyber criminals while, IT governance includes IT related processes and leadership that confirms compliance with business's overall principles (Terlizzi, et al., 2017). This asserted the emergence of cyber governance and need for cybersecurity strategy (Qasaimeh and Jaradeh, 2022; Zafar, et al., 2022). Medcraft (2015) state that to reduce the impact and frequency of cyberattacks in financial systems the organisations must integrate an effective cybersecurity governance strategy with their IT governance system (also, supported by Zafar, et al., 2022). Furthermore, Williams (2021) asserts that the actions of organisations and their exposure to potential cyberthreats can be secured by directly linking cybersecurity with cybersecurity governance.

Several other attempts have been made to define cybersecurity governance. Tan et al. (2017) comparing enterprise governance and cybersecurity governance found that the first is about enterprise-wide decision-making. Though, the latter is middle-management (specific to cybersecurity relating it to overall system of business operations) decision-making, though within the same management context. Cybersecurity governance brings all important elements of cyber defence and effective risk management under one umbrella with purpose to identify vulnerabilities to avoid compromising assets security (Maleh, Sahid, and Belaisaoui, 2021). Moreover, cybersecurity governance facilitates with a strong and consistent association between an organisation's internal laws and related policies, procedures, and customs to administer and control the way a business is governed and decisions are made (Kooper, Maes and Lindgreen, 2011; Savaş and Karataş, 2022).

Kooper, et al. (2011) documented cybersecurity governance as a subset of corporate governance and an instrument to align business with technology through rules. Schinagl and Shahim (2020) suggest that cybersecurity governance is the third layer, being a subset of IT governance. In addition, cybersecurity governance has been defined as a practice of determining gaps (technology, human and process) within the internal practice and external threats and the capability to respond to them (Melaku, 2023). Whilst some prior research defines cybersecurity governance through the lenses of cyber risk management (CyberRM), emphasising that it is about cyber risk to IT-related assets, it

refers to an ability of an organisation to understand threats and vulnerabilities in order to assign adequate controls based on the value and criticality of assets, and thus reduce the highest impact (Böhme, Laube and Riek, 2019; Gatzert and Schuber, 2022; Nunes, 2023).

Vesić and Bjelajac (2023) indicate a definition through the lenses of safety and risk mitigation. Malatji, Marnewick and Von Solms (2022) suggested that cybersecurity governance is a capability which involves processes and procedures driven by a mixture of standards and frameworks. It has been noted that it implements an operational lens as well. The concept of cybersecurity governance comes from strategic control, which incorporates operational governance and coordinates activities of risk accountability, conformance, and performance to ensure that processes, practices, and activities are driven based on informed decisions (Savaş and Karataş, 2022). Furthermore, cybersecurity governance influences strategic decision-making whilst designating accountabilities and responsibilities (Tan et al., 2017; Williams, 2021). The common synthesis in the literature is that cybersecurity governance is a governing act and process to ensure confidentiality, integrity, or availability of systems and information (Adams et al., 2015; Savaş and Karataş, 2022).

Hence, this thesis concludes that cybersecurity governance is an act of fulfilling the industry standards and best practices and strategically planning to ensure the confidentiality, integrity, or availability of information by mitigating risks. Antoniou (2018) suggests that the management of an organisation should prioritise cybersecurity governance, because despite various failures of unsuccessful approaches still, many organisations lack strong controls which can be improved with cybersecurity governance depending on the level of management commitment (AlGhamdi, Win, and Vlahu-Gjorgievska, 2020). Although, there are some internal and external factors that affect the cybersecurity governance of banking industry (Munirul, et al., 2011; Barker, 2016; Kesharwani, Sarkar, and Oberoi, 2019; Dhillon, 2020; Maleh, Sahid and Belaisaoui, 2021; Utami and Damayanti, 2022). Considering the importance of cybersecurity governance, it is imperative to find out which factors are affecting cybersecurity governance in PCBP, given that it is the area of research which has not been given much

attention in the past. Therefore, this study will investigate those factors under the lens of institutional logics.

Overall, the cybersecurity governance focus varies across years and the Table 2 below summarises the key focus of prior research.

Table 2: Cybersecurity Governance

Key focus	Studies
Capability to reach goals and objectives	Adams et al., 2015; Modi, Kuzminykh and Ghita; 2021; Shaikh and Siponen, 2023.
Mitigation and protection against loss	AlGhamdi, Win, and Vlahu-Gjorgievska, 2020; Schiliro, 2023; Vesić and Bjelajac, 2023.
Resiliency as function	Melaku, 2023
Framework/set of rules to establish policies, processes, and procedures	Antoniou, 2018; Sadiq, 2019; Taherdoost, 2022; Malatji, Marnewick and Von Solms, 2022.
Rules for IT infrastructure configurations	Ghelani, 2022; Odebade and Benkhelifa, 2023; Nunes, 2023.
Internal rules for strategic decisions towards cyber risks	Kooper, Maes and Lindgreen, 2011; Tan et al., 2017; Savaş and Karataş, 2022.
Protection of IT and cyber-enabled assets	Craigien et al., 2014; Böhme, Laube and Riek, 2019; Gatzert and Schuber, 2022.
Governance as a priority for executives	AlGhamdi, Win, and Vlahu-Gjorgievska, 2020.
Alignment with corporate governance	Kooper, Maes and Lindgreen, 2011; Tan et al., 2017; Schinagl and Shahim, 2020.

Source: Author Developed

3.2.7. Cybersecurity Concepts and Relationships

To better understand the relationship between different terminologies discussed in this chapter with purpose to understand cybersecurity concepts easily, the following Figure 7 shows how these concepts can draw a clear picture of cybersecurity. Though, the security controls are the measures exercised by the organisation (stakeholder) to secure

the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of the system and its information and to mitigate information security threats (Force, 2020; Maleh, et al., 2021).

Figure 7: Security Concepts and Relationships (Introduced in ISO/IEC 27032)

Source: Choejey (2018)

3.3. Institutional Theory, Social Behaviour and Cybersecurity

During last few decades, researchers and IT professionals have been successful in introducing advanced security systems or at least divergently effective for cybersecurity (Awan & Memon, 2016). However, the factor of social behaviour hugely changes the circumstances with respect to cybersecurity, even with availability of efficient technology as a solution. Indeed, the social behaviour affects the cybersecurity saying that the level of IS security depends on the human actions (Joinson and Steen, 2018). Therefore, the academic researchers diverted their attention towards theories of social behaviour, especially institutional theory, aiming to clearly understand, explain, control, and predict cybersecurity issues in a business (Björck, 2004; Maalem-Lahcen, Caulkins, Mohapatra, and Kumar, 2020). In order to find the cybersecurity solutions, institutional theory can also be considered as an extension of open systems theory where the inputs, outputs, and transformations of organizations is judged emphasizing the importance of environment – as it influence organizational performance (Vuko, Slapničar, Čular, and Drašček, 2021). In short, institutional theory put emphasise on the reality that majority of the environment consists of social and cultural forces rather than production resources and work-related information (Singh and Alshammari, 2020). An example is building upon the success of scholars such as Kowalski (1994), Yngström (1996), and Magnusson (1999) in applying systemic approaches to IS security, there is a natural progression towards exploring the relevance of institutional theory in investigating cybersecurity issues.

By considering institutional theory as an extension of these approaches, it can potentially serve as a valuable tool for understanding and addressing the complexities surrounding cybersecurity. According to Corner and Hahn (2013) a rationale human behaviour is a result of certain criterion and logic used to make specific action. Therefore, the main focus of institutional concepts here is to manage social behaviour to provide cybersecurity solutions (Singh & Alshammari, 2020; and Vuko, et al., 2021). Institutional theory has been one of the dominant theories by the end of the 19th Century. However, it was surpassed by some other approaches by the first half of the 20th Century. In recent decades, institutional theory has received remarkable acceptance, moving in the 21st Century as a most conceptual and broad-based theory in the social sciences (Scott, 2005;

Hodgson, 2017; and Jeyaraj & Zadeh, 2020). In the following section the institutional concepts are discussed with the purpose to identify their implications in cybersecurity.

3.3.1. The Concept of Institutions and Actors

The most agreed definition of institutions was introduced by North (1990, pp. 3) as follows: “Institutions are the rules of the game of a society, or, more formally, are the humanly devised constraints that structure human interaction. In consequence they structure incentives in human exchange, whether political, social, or economic.” As per this definition the institutions consist of three basic elements. The first element is formal or written rules which can include political infrastructure, laws, crime control policies, product details, imposing taxation and tariffs, regulatory frameworks of banks and universities etc. These rules can be developed by governments as well as firms and responsible organisations. The second element is informal or unwritten rules which may consist of values, culture, norms, religions, and customs etc. These informal rules are constructed based on socially transmitted information implied on people by themselves with purpose to structure their relationships with one another. The third and important element is enforcement of those formal and informal institutions as they will be ineffective if they are not enforced. However, the institutions can function fully, partially, or not function at all in different circumstances. On the other hand, Yeager (1998) explains that institutions can be the main source of justifying differences in economic performance between organisations (Boliari and Topyan, 2007).

Besides, Hodgson (2017) mentions that institutions are social structures (family, religion, law, economy, and class etc.) that have been accepted in society to a high degree. They are comprised of cultural-cognitive, normative, and regulatory facts that along with related activities and resources result in stability as well as meaning to social life. Moreover, institutions are spread through various carriers such as symbolic systems, rational systems, daily routines, and facts etc. (Hodgson, 2017; Reay, Zilber, Langley, and Tsoukas, 2019; Hodgson, 2019). However, according to Scott (2004) institutions are functional at different levels of jurisdiction, for example from the level of the world system to the level of local interpersonal relationships. Additionally, institutions imply stability as

per their definition, but they result in changing processes, either incremental or irregular (Scott, 2004; Alvensson and Spicer, 2019; Glynn and D'Aunno, 2023).

Following the above perspectives of North (1990), Hodgson (2017) and Scott (2004), this thesis coincides that institutions are the formal and informal systems of developed and socially accepted rules which are functional at different levels of jurisdiction, spread through various carriers and can result in changing processes. However, those rules depend on a developed social culture which consists of patterns of behaviour and social conventions.

In addition, it has been emphasized repeatedly to understand the role of actors in institutional theory (Hwang, Colyvas, and Drori, 2019) because it helps to develop the understanding that how institutions are changed or maintained by intentional efforts of actors (Maier and Simsa, 2021). This concept provides a broader view of institutional logic by justifying that actors can be the entrepreneurs to create new institutions and maintain them or can act as a disruptor of institutions when they seek to change those institutions (Lawrence and Suddaby, 2006). According to North (1990), under institutional concepts organizations are the actors or players. They act as a group of individuals motivated to achieve a common goal whereby the institutions will play their role as rules of the game of a society (Hodgson, 2006). However, specifically these actors may consist of the political organizations (the Senate, council, or regulatory body); economic bodies (businesses, trade unions, family farms, or cooperatives); social firms (worship places, clubs, or athletic firms); and educational sector (schools, colleges, universities, and seasonal training centres etc.). Although, forming organizations requires scrutinizing institutions - governance structures, skills and learning from experiences, which will determine the success of organization over time. Hence, modelling organizations and their development is fundamentally influenced by the institutions of society which are changed, developed, or maintained by their actors (Boliari and Topyan, 2007). Bruton, Ahlstrom, and Li (2010) therefore assert that institutions may specify and lead the actors that what actions are appropriate or unacceptable.

3.3.2. Institutional Isomorphism

To highlight the effects of institutions, DiMaggio, and Powell (1983) introduced three techniques by which institutional '*isomorphic*' change exists. Isomorphism can be defined as restraining processes which force organizations to adopt the same code of conduct as of other organization working in same environment. This course of action suggests that the diverse actions of organizations are modified to become compatible with environment (Aksom and Tymchenko, 2020; Nawaz and Guribie, 2022). According to DiMaggio and Powell (1983) there are three types of institutional isomorphic changes: coercive, mimetic, and normative. The coercive isomorphism originates from formal and informal pressures from various organizations on specific organization which is tied to meet the cultural expectations of society (Seyfried, Ansmann, and Pohlenz, 2019). Mimetic isomorphism arises when response is required to an uncertain environment. In such a scenario, the goals become ambiguous, and organizations copy the actions of other organizations who become role models. Normative isomorphism stems when organizations collectively define the techniques and conditions of work as well as develop legitimization autonomy (Singh and Alshammari, 2020; Nawaz and Guribie, 2022).

These institutions with isomorphic concepts have been widely accepted and adopted in various domains within the Information Security (IS) profession with determination to manage organizational change behaviour (Jeyaraj and Zadeh, 2020). For example, Barton, Tejay, Lane, and Terrell, (2016) demonstrated that institutional pressures relating to information system security have impacted the senior management's beliefs and actions in IS initiatives. Discussing it further, it is found that considering the influence of institutions within the cybersecurity domain, businesses may become engaged in various actions against potential cyberthreats or cybersecurity breaches. These actions consists of prevention, detection, mitigation, and recovery plans (Lezzi, Lazoi, and Corallo, 2018; Somani, Gaur, Sanghi, Conti, and Buyya, 2017). Furthermore, the implementation of countermeasures against cybersecurity threats encompasses a wide range of both IT and non-IT elements. These countermeasures involve various aspects such as hardware infrastructure, data protection, networking protocols, physical security tools, well-trained employees, and regulatory frameworks, all working in tandem to deter and prevent

cyberthreats (Yeh and Chang, 2007). In addition, specific countermeasures, such as firewalls, encryption, antivirus software, and intrusion detection methods, hardware infrastructure, intrusion prevention, virtual private networking, and secure coding etc. have proven effective in addressing cybersecurity risks (Kumar, Park, and Subramaniam, 2008; Chen, Kataria, and Krishna, 2011; Jang-Jaccard and Nepal, 2014; Paté-Cornell, Kuypers, Smith, and Keller, 2018). Moreover, it is important to recognize that certain countermeasures extend beyond technical solutions. For instance, investments in cybersecurity, establishment of incident response teams, utilization of cyber-insurance products, the education and training of both employees and customers in cybersecurity practices, and comprehensive regulatory framework etc. all play crucial roles in fortifying an organization's information systems (Mukhopadhyay, Chatterjee, Saha, Mahanti, and Sadhukhan, 2013; Ahmad, Maynard, and Shanks, 2015; Gupta, Arachchilage, and Psannis, 2018; Paul and Wang, 2019).

3.3.2.1. Cybersecurity - Mimetic Isomorphism

In terms of mimetic institutional influence, organizations may learn from other organizations in different ways such as taking information from articles, magazines, trade publications, success stories, conferences, industry consortia, collaborations between identical hierarchical positions within business, and interlocking memberships of boards (Yeh and Chang, 2007; Seyfried, et al., 2019). Although, these learnings may not be fully effective since the other relevant avenues (institutions) of cybersecurity responses by other organizations might not be clear (Mukhopadhyay, et al., 2013; Jeyaraj and Zadeh, 2020). This may persist an organization to adopt such institutions. However, adoption of such acceptable institutions may prevent criticism from all stakeholders including customers (Kraatz, 1998; Lezzi, Lazoi, and Corallo, 2018). It can be deemed that Mimetic institutions are not assertive to solve the cybersecurity issue as they are adopted because of pressure despite they are not effective (Jeyaraj and Zadeh, 2020; Singh and Alshammari, 2020; Nawaz and Guribie, 2022).

3.3.2.2. Cybersecurity - Normative Isomorphism

Normative pressures on organizations relating to IS cybersecurity have placed huge importance on changes in education and training of professionals because cybersecurity requires unique expertise among professionals. These expertise needs to be polished over time considering the changes in the types, targets, and scope of cyberthreats (Sabherwal, and Jeyaraj, 2015; Singh and Alshammari, 2020). The Normative pressures for cybersecurity focus on vulnerabilities such as unauthorized access to data, secure networking, data recovery, DDos, insufficient authorization checks, weak credential-reset for cloud computing (Grobauer, Walloschek, and Stocker, 2010), virus, rogue employees, misuse of resources by employees, data infringement, social engineering (Rees, Deane, Rakes, and Baker, 2011), Trojans and hacking (Jeyaraj and Zadeh, 2020), data espionage, data or system interference (Paoli, Visschers, and Verstraete, 2018) etc.

Cybersecurity professionalisation concept in terms of Normative institutions include need to plan, organize, and implement cybersecurity measures against cyberthreats; use proactive approach of response; effectively and efficiently recover from cybersecurity breach; ensure compliance with cybersecurity standards and regulations and analyse as well as report potential or actual lapses or breaches (Barton, et al., 2016; Somani, et al., 2017; Singh and Alshammari, 2020). Various cybersecurity standards and regulatory frameworks (Aldasoro et al., 2020); NIST (Vigliarolo, 2021), and ISO 27001 are available as they are widely acceptable for cybersecurity (Culot et al., 2021). Following this perspective, cybersecurity training programs and job positions including CISO have become a norm within cybersecurity industry. Thus, organizations' actions of cybersecurity are defined by established professional norms within the industry. Hence, it can be said that organizations are pressured to follow the similar actions of cybersecurity informed by the way cybersecurity profession has evolved, ignoring the fact that those norms might not be proved to be effective for all organizations. This effects the professionals hired or trained by organizations, technology, or solution to be used, and overall strategies of businesses (Gupta, et al., 2018; Paul and Wang, 2019; Jeyaraj and Zadeh, 2020).

3.3.2.3. Cybersecurity - Coercive Isomorphism

Coercive pressures are result of formal or informal institutions established to influence the organizations to abide by law and regulations which can result in organizational legitimacy (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983; Seyfried, et al., 2019). Business partners, customers, suppliers, and Government agencies are the sources of asserting coercive pressures on organizations (Chwelos, Benbasat, and Dexter, 2001; Nawaz, and Guribie, 2022). Teo, Wei, and Benbasat (2003) and Jeyaraj and Zadeh (2020) state that external pressures play major role in adoption of security features by organizations. Lezzi, et al. (2018) asserts that coercive pressures from major suppliers and customers, influence businesses to follow law and regulations effectively. While, Zhu and Kraemer (2005) suggested that competitors' pressure is significant predictor of organizations' intention to follow e-business practices. However, in regard to cybersecurity, the laws and regulations imposed by the government could be the main source of pressure for organizations (Singh and Alshammari, 2020). Several regulations (such as NIST, and ISO 27001) are introduced by governments in different countries to provide guideline or facilitate other frameworks of IS, desiring to protect the IS systems. The availability of those regulations imply that in the absence of such regulations and laws, the organisations might not be engaged in applying the effective policies for cybersecurity (Didenko, 2020; Thach, et al., 2021). Therefore, the governments try to put pressure on businesses to follow the law and regulations. However, it is possible that those law and regulations might not be fully effective if they are not up-to date with latest cybersecurity requirements but still because of isomorphism businesses have to adopt them (Jeyaraj and Zadeh, 2020; Singh and Alshammari, 2020).

3.3.2.4. Criticism to Isomorphic Approach of Institutions

The work of DiMaggio and Powell (1983) has been accepted hugely however, there are some important insights about institutions which has been neglected and the roles played by contradictory institutional forms are also omitted by DiMaggio and Powell (Aksom and Tymchenko, 2020; Ansell, 2021). Moving forward to end of 20th Century, Meyer and Rowan (1991) and North (1990) endeavoured to discover some valuable facts about

institutions; however, Scott introduced a new concept of institutional influences categorizing them as regulatory, normative, and cognitive, during the first decade (2001 to 2008) of 21st Century (Dromi, 2020; Ansell, 2021). Firstly, the regulatory concept of institutions asserts restrictions and initiatives which leads and regulates individual and collective performance in society. Such regulatory institutions stem from the government legislations facilitating with the guidelines for individual and collective actions (Bruton, et al. 2010; Panfilo and Krasodomska, 2022). For example, the advancement of local cybersecurity laws and regulations adopting international regulations to provide comprehensive frameworks against cybercrime and their enforcement can make the organizations active user of those law and regulation (Filinovych and Hu, 2021). Secondly, the normative pillar is built based on social norms and indicates the obligatory patterns of individual and collective behaviour. In this regards, the normative systems consisting of values - which define what is appropriate, and norms result in development of a structure which leads people (Ansell, 2021; Panfilo and Krasodomska, 2022). For example, to secure the technology employed from cybercriminals, the businesses can set the norms to use only standardised technology as an obligatory pattern in society, so that security features are not compromised (Finnemore and Hollis, 2016). Lastly, the cultural-cognitive pillar consists of the widely accepted customs and beliefs within a society which lead to shared social behaviour. This pillar shows the actions of people based on their perceptions of culture which led them to limit appropriate actions (Panfilo and Krasodomska, 2022). For instance, in some countries use of personal mobile is part of culture which results in cybercrime by compromising with customers' data (Ameen, Tarhini, Shah, Madichie, Paul, and Choudrie, 2021).

This concludes that culture is an important factor which influence individuals' and organizations' actions based on their cognitive perceptions instead of norms (Omeihe, 2022). Thus, referring to the literature, this thesis supposes that institutions are the tools that facilitate with the efficient solutions for the predetermined issues such as hacking or become the factors (if they are weak) which support the cybercrimes (Kshetri, 2005). Thus, institutions are the factors for this thesis which could be used as a cybersecurity solution for PCBP. However, the main reason of multiple concepts on institutions is the

discontentment of theories which focus on the roles of norms, rules, and beliefs which may vary in different cultures and countries (Panfilo and Krasodomska, 2022). Similarly, the institutions (factors) which impact the cybersecurity of banks in developing and developed countries may differ (Hafiz-Ali, et al., 2019; Wang, Nnaji, and Jung, 2020), as discussed in detail in the following sections. For instance, the lack of investment in cybersecurity and low literacy can be the case in developing countries rather than developed countries (Kesharwani, Sarkar, and Oberoi, 2019; Naik Bukht, et al., 2020).

In short, institutional theory studies the processes and techniques which result in developing structures, schemas, rules, and routines as an influential guideline for social behaviour (Jeyaraj and Zadeh, 2020; Singh and Alshammari, 2020; Panfilo and Krasodomska, 2022). Institutional theory investigates how these systems are developed or diffused and what is their role in providing stability and meaning to social behaviour. Most importantly, institutional theory also analyses how these functional institutions deteriorate and collapse or shape successor structures (Scott, 2004b; Alvesson and Spicer, 2019; Aksom and Tymchenko, 2020). However, the focus of researchers is no longer on isomorphism of institutional theory rather it is moved to the effects of distinguishing institutional logics on individuals and organizations considering a larger variety of contexts, consisting of markets, industries, and stakeholders of businesses. Thus, institutional logics is an advanced form of institutional theory (Ocasio, Thornton, and Lounsbury, 2017; Gümüşay, Claus, and Amis, 2020). Therefore, the following section will discuss how institutional logics can be used to find the solution of cybersecurity in banks.

3.3.3. Institutional Logics

Institutional logic approach describes how cultural dimensions of institutions support and restrict social behaviour. It considers the role of culture as the main determinant of institutional analysis (Omeihe, 2022). According to Thornton, Ocasio, and Lounsbury (2013) the institutional logic perspective is developed based on the institutional theory. Institutional theory is a set of perceptions and theories of environmental effects on businesses and cultural homogeneity. Comparatively, institutional logics is a metatheory

of institutions which consists of organizations and does not only discuss the homogeneity rather it also focuses on heterogeneity which complement the limitations of institutional theory (Ocasio, et al., 2017; Gümüşay, et al., 2020). However, the main difference between these two concepts is that institutional logics theorises the dual concept of the material-practice-based concepts of institutions as well as their cultural-symbolic-based concepts (Friedland, 2018).

Institutional logics help researchers interested to find out how individuals and organisational actors act in various social locations in an interinstitutional system under different situations such as the institutional orders of family, religion, state, market, profession, and corporation (Pureza and Lee, 2020; Omeihe, 2022). Each institutional order of the interinstitutional system consists of specific organising principles, practices, and symbols that impact individuals and organisational behaviour. The principle, practices and symbols relating to any specific institutional order distinctively shape the reasoning to justify how rationality is understood or perceived by individuals and organisations (Thornton, 2012; Johansen and Waldorff, 2017).

Institutional logics shape rationale and mindful behaviour although, the individual and organizational actors can play their role in creating and changing institutional logics under this institutional context (Thornton, 2004; Faik, Barrett, and Oborn, 2020). Facilitating the connection between institutions and actions, the institutional logics approach works as a bridge between the macro-structural view and micro-process approaches (Thornton and Ocasio, 2008). According to Thornton and Ocasio (1999, p. 804) institutional logics are 'the socially constructed, historical patterns of material practices, assumptions, values, beliefs, and rules by which individuals produce and reproduce their material subsistence, organize time and space, and provide meaning to their social reality.' This concept of institutions considers structural, normative, and symbolic institutions significant and collective proportions instead of treating them separately structural (coercive), normative and symbolic institutions, as supposed by other approaches of institutions (Friedland, 2018; Frenken, Vaskelainen, Fünfschilling, and Piscicelli, 2020). Moreover, this also suggests that how institutions having their underpinning logics of actions influence the actions of individuals and organizations (Thornton and Ocasio, 2008; Pureza and Lee,

2020). Furthermore, it justifies that how actors, actions and contexts work interdependently under institutional logics (Johansen and Waldorff, 2017). Based on this view, it can be assumed that structural (coercive), normative and symbolic institutions lead the cybersecurity as the cybersecurity decisions and outcomes are products of interplay between multiple actors of society and their respective institutional structure, norms (material perspective) as well as perceptions (cultural perspective).

Various studies have been conducted to study Information Security (IS) using institutional theory (Teo et al., 2003; and Currie, 2009; AlKalbani, Deng, Kam, Zhang, 2017) but a very few number of studies have been conducted to apply the concept of institutional theory or institutional logics to analyse the issues of cybersecurity. According to Gümüşay, et al. (2020) institutional logics guide the behaviour of organizations. Such as the 'Structural Logics' which include the level of effectiveness and compliance of cybersecurity laws, regulations, policies, and procedures can facilitate or constrain the cybercrime. Similarly, the human social behaviour (norms, values, and belief) affects the cybersecurity (Björck, 2004; Forslund, 2020; Farid and Waldorff, 2022). For example, literacy and awareness of cybersecurity can help to lessen the cyberattacks (Alzubaidi, 2021). Lastly, symbolic (cultural) view of institutional logics was developed with purpose to justify the operation/actions of society from the 'bottom-up,' concentrating on micro-level processes that result from face-to face encounters to highlight the actions of society (Friedland, 2018). The main idea of symbolic approach is that the individuals use language and significant symbols during communication. Therefore, instead of focusing on how common social institutions justify and impact individuals, symbolic interactionists pay attention to individuals' interpretation of the subject which depends on their unique perception (Carter and Fuller, 2015; Farid and Waldorff, 2022). For instance, understanding of importance of cybersecurity by multiple actors of society such as governmental and regulatory officials or banking management depends on their individual perceptions based on the knowledge and information they have (Forslund, 2020).

Based on this perspective, the point to be noted here is that the collective utilization of institutional logics, encompassing the structural (coercive), normative, and symbolic elements that shape institutions, can offer valuable insights into the social behaviours of

different actors and their influence on organizational cybersecurity. An illustrative case is the European Union's cybersecurity policy, which employs institutional logics to ensure its comprehensiveness (Christou, 2014; Forslund, 2020). Considering the collective approach of material-cultural perspectives mentioned above regarding how institutional logics can enable or constrain the actions of diverse cybersecurity actors, it becomes essential to explore the institutions (factors) that affect the cybersecurity of private commercial banks in Pakistan. In line with this approach, the following institutional logics for effective cybersecurity governance are proposed:

Figure 8: Institutional logic and cybersecurity governance

Source: Author Developed

3.4. Global Trend of Cybercrime and Banking Sector

It was 1978 when the first spam email was sent on Arpanet (internet protocol - Bonazzo, 2016). Following advancements in technology, first-time in 1982 a virus was found on an Apple computer (Buch, Ganda, Borad & Kalola, 2017). Moving forward, with the passage of time, the technology has developed. Although, today industries, governments, businesses, and non-profit organisations are fully dependent on IT because the internet has made communication effective and has simplified day to day activities. However, this advancement in IT and telecommunications has also caused the information security threats like spamming, credit card and ATM frauds and identity theft (Zahoor & Razi, 2020). Therefore, it is necessary that all businesses including banks, attain the capability to be secure from cyberattacks and are also able to counterattack, to win in this new kind of war “internet cybercrime” otherwise, it can cause significant harm (Anwar, 2020). Though, this is easier said than done, because the internet facilitates the attacker to keep his/her identity hidden especially, in the case of state sponsored attacks and when the irregularity of attacks makes hackers anonymous (Syed et al., 2019). Hence, businesses must adopt effective measures or institutional logics for cybersecurity.

During the last 20 years, the number of cyberattacks has increased significantly in all countries (Sadiq, 2019). Both developed and developing countries are exposed to cyberthreats in all sectors, but a developing country, and nuclear power like Pakistan is more vulnerable to those attacks (Anwar, 2020). There is a notion that cyber-criminal activities are more profitable than drug trafficking (Capstone, 2019), and this trend is expected to grow both in developed and developing countries with increasing use of internet and technology (Weijer & Leukfeldt, 2017). Major cyberattacks target the critical infrastructure (the set-up of interdependent networks and systems, interconnected through multi layers of connection, that facilitates the flow of products or services) of an organisation. There are five broad sectors which can be classified as critical infrastructures: information and communication, banking and finance, energy, transportation networks and human services (Shad, 2019). Although, looking at the different sectors which are victim of cybercrimes, the financial sector is the main target of

cybercriminals. Specifically, for more than a decade, banks have been one of the favourite targets for cybercriminals (Sadiq, 2019).

For example, as compared to the first quarter of 2017 during its second quarter the number of cyberattacks grew by 24% globally, the manufacturing industry being the main target of hackers. The manufacturing industry (34%), finance industry (25%), and health care industry (13%) were the top three targeted industries for hackers during the period of 2016 to 2017. While, in 2018 the finance industry was ranked number one confronting 19% of all cyberattacks (Swivel, 2022). These attacks impose heavy costs on banks and other financial institutions who invest a significant amount of money to effectively combat such threats and fraud (Syed, Khaver, & Yasin, 2019). A recent study by Akinbowale, Klingelhöfer, and Zerihun (2020) confirms that the increasing number of cybercrimes have negatively affected the goodwill of banks and economic growth either indirectly causing loss of trust in digital infrastructure, or directly by the increase in number of frauds and extortion in both developed and developing countries. Lewis (2018) in his most recent report on “economic impact of cybercrime no slowing down” states that, compared to non-financial businesses, the banks spend three times more on cybersecurity. In addition, Kitaw and Beaumont (2017) in their study state that the banks and their customers are the basic target of cyber criminals as one of the UK banks has reported more than 1,000 attacks per day. They also mentioned that financial services companies confront cybersecurity incidents 300 times more frequently than any other industry.

Over several years, considering the dynamic increase in cyberthreats - thousands every day, in financial sectors, cybersecurity researchers have been providing security measures to secure computers, databases, systems, and networks from cyberattacks (Awan & Memon, 2016). Still, internationally cyber-security of banks has become a serious issue for governments and security policy makers because banks save confidential information on computers and use that on the internet professionally (Syed et al., 2019) while cybercriminals access that information illegally using different techniques, as discussed in the following section 2.8.2.

Moreover, modern economies are highly dependent on the banking industries. This fact can be seen by the financial crisis of 2008 when the crash of the banking industry impacted the global economy. This emphasises the importance of sustaining effective information security of banks (Kitaw & Beaumont, 2017). In this regard, Raytheon (2015) in his study concludes that a cyber crisis in one or more banks can have catastrophic financial impacts not only on one customer or a bank but to the whole economy of a country. Furthermore, information technology has changed the way we live our lives and use banking services (Chevers, 2019). The higher the usage of internet in a country means the higher the chances of cyberthreat, but at the same time the availability of a high level of technological advancement and literacy rate can help prevent cyberattacks (Syed et al., 2019). For example, the developed countries have a high level of internet usage and technological advancement (which comes from financial strength and with the availability of highly qualified people) and better literacy rates as compared to developing countries (IGI Global, 2020).

The recent issue of the COVID-19 pandemic resulted in an increase of online shopping and activities during the first half of 2021. Cyber criminals took advantage of this and started conducting cyberattacks throughout the world to maximise their own gains, as discussed below (Hummel, 2021). According to an FBI report, cybercrimes increased by 300% during the pandemic (Walter, 2020). Edward (2020) mentions that the American public lost more than \$97.39 million during COVID-19. In addition, Google blocked 18 million malware and phishing emails on a daily basis relating to Covid-19, in April 2020 (Kumaran, 2020). Additionally, the widespread uptake of remote working from home because of the pandemic increased the cybercrimes (using personal devices or internet and increased use of online websites) which resulted to increase the average cost of a data breach by \$137000 (IBM, 2021). Even cloud based cyberattacks increased by 630% between January and April in 2020 (Fintech, 2020). However, the banks, too could not escape from cybercriminals. Out of all attacks during the pandemic, 27% were towards banking organisations which encountered an increase of 238% in cyberattacks in 2020. Such attacks can be destructive for an economy, given its interdependence and daily transactions through banks (EIE, 2022). According to IBM, in general, 23% of the

cyberattacks are targeted towards financial institutions and the cost of a single attack (\$5.72 million on average) equals the second largest among all industries (IAM, 2021). Also, it is believed that 53% of cyberattacks in banks are conducted by financially motivated cyber criminals therefore, the banking industry is constantly on the cybercrime radar (IBM, 2020).

Banks in developing countries are facing cybercrime threats intensely because of weak security systems (Kshetri, 2010). Chang and Coppel (2020) state that in developing countries the low level of literacy, lack of resources to invest in cybersecurity, weak infrastructure, and human factors (for example lazy behaviour of employees towards using defensive technologies or unawareness) attract cybercriminals because under such scenarios they are less likely to be caught. However, the developing countries have a good level of growing financial markets (like Pakistan), with moderate use of internet as compared to developed countries but have a low level of technological security. This attracts, and makes them easy victims of cybercriminals (Anwar, 2020). Similarly, being a developing country Pakistan has exceptional growth of internet usage. It has reached to the heights of popularity for an ever-changing medium of information and communication in such a conservative society. Therefore, the internet penetration in Pakistan is increasing at a fast pace (Zahoor & Razi, 2020). Consequently, Pakistan is facing many cyberattacks in its education, telecom, military, and government sectors but mainly in its banking sector (Syed et al., 2019).

Based on a survey conducted on internet banking in Saudi Arabia, Pakistan, and India, considering the response of 1044 internet banking users and 92 internet banking websites, Alghazo, Kazmi and Latif (2017) state that there is a huge gap between the banks' expectations from users in the way they can securely use the internet banking as well as keeping their information safe, and the actual actions of the users. The reason is that the users' actions are based on their knowledge and understanding on the topic of cybersecurity (awareness). Also, Chang and Coppel (2020) in their most recent study to build cybersecurity awareness in developing countries conclude that in developing countries the low level of literacy and cybersecurity awareness builds a bridge for cyberattackers to target people in these countries. However, cybersecurity awareness

can strengthen the resilience of banking products such as mobile banking, e-payment systems etc. which can result in economic growth.

Similarly, even having poor cybersecurity infrastructure and other issues in their banking industry the developing countries can still improve the cybersecurity of their banks by upgrading their systems - if security is upgraded then cyber criminals will move on to attack the third parties with weak cybersecurity instead (Khatri, 2017), so incorporating cyber-risk of third party services providers into the enterprise-wide risk management (Crisanto & Prenio, 2017), multi-factor authentication (Ometov et al., 2018), awareness (Świątkowska, 2020) and improved regulations (Syed, Khaver, & Yasin, 2019). Therefore, there is a need to investigate that which factors (institutions) can play their role to enhance the cybersecurity in banks of Pakistan, entailing the features of a developing country. Hence, in the following section the factors which can help to improve cybersecurity of banks are discussed in detail.

3.5. E-banking and Factors affecting its Cybersecurity Governance

E-banking

The prevalence of technology in this century is leading banks to integrate new set of practices in their services. The banks which are identifying the need and adopting innovative technology into their services that go beyond traditional offerings are considered best banks. This brings the concept of Electronic-Banking (e-banking) (Marafon, Basso, Espartel, de Barcellos, and Rech, 2018; Anouze and Alamro, 2019; Ahmad, Bhatti, and Hwang, 2020). The purpose of e-banking adoption is to increase banking profits by increasing number of customers and their use of banking services (providing efficient services). Therefore, majority of banks have been and improving adoption of e-banking. The phenomena of e-banking is based on the development, design, and implementation of banking services available through internet. In other words, e-banking takes place when banking consumers use internet to access their bank account/details, or banking information to conduct a financial transaction (Yaseen and El Qirem, 2018).

Technically and intricately, it is difficult to define the term e-banking because it can be interpreted from various points of views as e-banking includes multi- channel distribution methods of financial services offered by banks. Multiple attempts have been made to provide all-inclusive definition of e-banking (Okolie and Eze, 2023). Furst, Lang, and Nolle (2000) defined e-banking as the automated provision of latest and traditional financial services provided to customers using electronic, interactive channels. Kricks (2009) says that e-banking is an automated delivery of new and traditional banking facilities directly to customers. This definition of e-banking is more empathetic because it emphasizes the transformation of conventional banking products and services in improved form, providing quality, real time access, lower operating costs, and efficiency in operations (Okolie and Eze, 2023; Nwakoby, Okoye, Ezejiofor, Anukwu, and Ihediwa, 2020). Pyun, Scruggs, and Nam (2002) refers e-banking, the convenience and satisfaction for user as customers can easily meet their banking need such as transactions through interactive channels called e-banking. However, some other authors suggest that e-banking is much broader than user convenience or satisfaction. Moreover, some authors define e-banking as a method which customers use to conduct banking transactions electronically with no physical appearance in the bank (Chaimaa, Najib, and Rachid, 2021). According to this definition e-banking is branchless or virtual banking considering that physical appearance in the banking industry has become less significant because banks are adopting e-banking. Although, e-banking definition provided by Basel Committee report on banking supervision is most famous and according to it (Okolie and Eze, 2023, p. 48), 'e-banking is the provision of retail and small value banking goods and services through electronic channels. Hence, for the purpose of this thesis, e-banking can be deemed as a practice of performing banking activities through intelligent devices coupled with the internet. For example, online banking, online shopping, mobile banking, automated teller machine (ATM), debit and credit cards etc. (Al-Badran, 2021).

E-banking is beneficial for both banks and customers. It facilitates banks to create improved efficiency in their services by enabling customers to open bank accounts, deposit or transfer funds through the accounts and make payments entirely online. Customer can perform the financial activities for example, purchasing and moving money

with fastest and convenient online services provided by a bank (Ahmad, et al., 2020; Nwakoby, et al., 2020). Specifically, e-banking services make the life of customers easy by performing all financial transactions and activities from home instead of visiting bank each time for every single activity as it used to be traditionally. Thus, providing multi-channel banking services has become a crucial part of competitive advantage for banks (Marafon, et al., 2018).

Offering multiple benefits to banks and their customers e-banking is not without certain challenges and threats in regard to information security (spamming, phishing, and credit card frauds etc.) and interest of the banking customer (Chaimaa, Najib, and Rachid, 2021). One factor that can restrict the adoption of e-banking is the customer risk perception of the e-banking services in general. Referring to the daily spread of news and experiences heard, the banking customers feel insecure in regard to cybersecurity threat of e-banking (Venkatesh, 2023). Risk has negative impact on customers behaviour or intention towards adopting e-banking services (Figure 9). Therefore, perceived risk or sense of loss can have huge effect on customers attention to use e-banking (Kaur and Sharma, 2022; Venkatesh, 2023). Several studies has been conducted from customer perspective to find the reasons of customers' behaviour or intention to adopt e-banking (Namahoot and Laohavichien, 2018; Marafon, et al., 2018; Anouze and Alamro, 2019; Ahmad, et al., 2020; Kaur and Sharma, 2022; Venkatesh, 2023; Almaiah, Al-Otaibi, Shishakly, Hassan, Lutfi, Alrawad, Qatawneh, and Alghanam, 2023). However, the context and purpose of this study is not the same. This study focuses on highlighting the factors which are resulting cybercrimes in banks that subsequently lessons the banking customers' trust and confidence on e-banking and negatively impact their adoption (behaviour/intention) of e-banking. Given that identifying those factors and proper governance of them Can reduce the number of cyberthreats and their impact. Hence, it is vital to find those factors and the following literature is conducted in this regard.

Figure 9: E-Banking Adoption

Source: Author Developed

3.6. Factors Affecting Cybersecurity of E-banking

According to literature there are multiple factors that can affect the cybersecurity governance of e-banking systems. Those factors can include IT related solutions and social behavioural factors. The focus of this study are the social behavioural factors only. However, these behavioural factors can be internal to the banks or external as well because society consists of organisations (government, regulatory bodies, and businesses) under the concept of institutional logics (Ocasio, Thornton, and Lounsbury, 2017; Gümüşay, Claus, and Amis, 2020). In this effort, extracting from the literature reviewed, in the following section the factors that affect the cybersecurity governance of e-banks and are result of social actors' behaviour will be discussed to develop a conceptual framework which could be studied in context of Pakistan banking sector.

3.6.1. Customer Awareness

The commendable growth in users of internet along with integral development of information and communication technological tools and practices are leading to multiple cyberthreats world widely in all fields such as economic, social, political, and financial (Wang et al., 2020). However, the banking users of internet are becoming major target of cyber criminals as they hold their confidential information which can be used to conduct

cybercrimes in banks, for instance withdrawing money or making unauthorised international transactions etc. (Innab et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2020; Alzubaidi, 2021). Information is a valuable asset for banking sector's growth and development in the era of technological innovation. The cyberthreats negatively impact the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of such information which results in lack of confidence and trust on e-banking. Consequently, it lessens the adoption and retention of e-banking by customers both in developed and developing countries (Jibril, Kwarteng, Chovancová, and Denanyoh, 2020; Akinbowale, Klingelhöfer, and Zerihun, 2020).

The advancement and innovation in digital technology has been considered an opportunity for growth in the banking sector but at the same time it is a significant threat for banks' sustainability and existence (Dermine, 2016). Using mobile banking, internet banking, credit card and debit cards for online transactions customers benefit from these services but simultaneously the threat and possibility of cyberattacks also become a major challenge for these services. Cyberattacks, ATM skimming, fraudulent activities, hacking, and phishing remains the major challenges in this regard. However, customer awareness proves to be a significant factor to avoid such cyberthreats (Hafiz Ali, Khan, Asghar, and Shuaib, 2019). In this regard, the results of some studies conducted by Orgill et al. (2004); Aloul (2012); Bele et al. (2014); Innab et al. (2018); Adholiya and Adholiya (2019); Wang et al. (2020); Alzubaidi (2021); and Gomes, Deshmukh, and Anute (2022) show that the customers who regularly remain engaged with services provided by banks are both the basic stakeholders as well as a threat to banks. Nevertheless, considering customers as a human factor, training, and awareness about most recent cyberthreats will help to prevent cybercrime.

Adholiya and Adholiya (2019, p.149) defined customer or user awareness as 'a thought about as containing information, self-view of abilities, real aptitudes and conduct, and mentalities, and the interrelationship among these components.' Zahiroh (2020, p.55) defines cybersecurity awareness as:

The level of understanding of internet users about the importance of information security; and the responsibilities and actions of internet users to implement

information security controls efficiently to protect the organization's as well as personal data and networks.

Therefore, cybersecurity awareness is the capability of people to highlight possible threats while using cyberspace, evaluate the risks, and avoid or solve the problem abruptly to secure personal data and property security (Wang, Qi, Zou, and Li, 2019). Moreover, Committee for National Security Systems (CNSS) articulates cybersecurity awareness as the competence to secure or defend internet use from cyberattacks (Teer, Kruck, and Gregory, 2007). Hence, following these concepts it can be inferred for this thesis that cybersecurity awareness is the level of awareness to people, about the risk of manipulation of information used in cyberspace and the control, to assure that the cybercrimes can be prevented.

Cybercriminals assess and take advantage of users' knowledge and cognitive biasness to conduct cybercrime while the user is using a specific service having less awareness and capacity to process the information system. Hence, developing good knowledge and understanding about possibilities of errors and mistakes in cyber activities and how to avoid such errors is important and can help to prevent cyberattack (Moustafa, Bello, and Maurushat, 2021).

Following the digital transformation concept, banks are now considering to digitise all banking services consisting of customers' confidential information, stored, and moving from one platform to another over a network. Various cyberattacks are targeted towards these activities because the customers have less awareness of such threats (Al-Alawi and Al-Bassam, 2021). ATM skimming is one of the most increasing threat, especially in developing countries; and active awareness about ATM skimming must be provided to banking customers so that they can prevent such frauds. ATM skimming is a widespread issue which needs targeted actions. ATM skimming takes place when skimming devices such as the rain cover or fake keypad is installed at ATM machines. The major risk of ATM skimming is card skimming, where the card data of customer is compromised and results in fraudulent activities for example, unauthorised online transactions or selling card details on Dark websites (Johri and Kumar, 2023). Such attacks take place because

the banking industry's defensive mechanism has various flaws therefore, there is a significant need of strategies to increase customer awareness of the actions that may be taken to combat cybercriminal activities in banking sector in a fastest way. Adopting such effective strategies can increase the banking users and high business performance may incur, as a result of high trust and confidence of customers on banks (Limna, Kraiwanit, and Siripipattanakul, 2022).

The banks in developing countries have integrated security features in their information systems still users' behaviour results in security vulnerabilities. For instance, having secure banking services yet the banking users in developing countries share their login credentials knowingly lacking the awareness of its impact or unintentionally. This may result in information compromising or security breaches (Alghazo, Kazmi, and Latif, 2017). Hafiz Ali, et al. (2019) and Bada, Von Solms, and Agrafiotis (2019) add in saying that the lack of awareness and customers' reluctance to change are one of the major factors in developing countries which cause cybercrime. Social engineering such as spamming or phishing is another prevailing approach used by cyber criminals nowadays and banking customers increasingly adopting online banking services are the prime targets for social engineers. Successful strategies to combat social engineering towards banking customers is compulsory for competitive advantage of banks (Chaimaa, Najib, and Rachid, 2021). Hijji and Alam (2021, p. 7152) define social engineering (SE) as 'a method frequently used by hackers and cybercriminals for building strategies to trick people into granting them access to a system by breaking security best practices and standards illegally or even without breaking the law.'

According to Ali, Ali, Surendran, and Thomas (2017) cybercrime and information security have always been simultaneous to each other. Since cyber criminals continuously keep looking to gain unauthorised access to the financial data of banking customers therefore it also creates fear to use e-banking services. To maintain customers' trust on e-banking it is important to aware the banking customers about how to avoid cyberthreats such as social engineering. Another study by Chang and Coppel (2020) confirms that cybersecurity awareness can highly strengthen the resilience of productivity-enhancing services for example e-banking and support the economic growth. Proven the importance

of customer awareness about secure use of banking services from the literature, it is evident to find out what factors can support the banking customer awareness about cybersecurity. The careful study of literature shows that customer literacy, (Balaraj and Shetty, 2019; Wang, et al., 2019) literacy level of general public as well as their awareness (Zwilling, et al., 2022; Aphane, 2023), and awareness program by Government (Wang et al. 2020; Gomes, et al., 2022), which are external to bank, can have positive impact on customer awareness as discussed below.

3.6.1.1. Customer Literacy - The topic of relationship between banking customers' literacy and their cybercrime awareness is of vital importance in this digital era. Based on the literature, customer literacy in context of cybersecurity can be divided into two main perspectives. One is based on the education of the customer and other is 'Cyber literacy'. Cyber literacy is also known as internet literacy, multimedia literacy, digital literacy, and online literacy etc. (Balaraj and Shetty, 2019). However, in relation to cybersecurity the cyber literacy refers to the banking customers' ability to effectively utilise latest banking services provided based on technological advancement and simultaneously comprehend the implications of using those services (Magomedov, Murzaev, and Zolkin, 2020). The educational literacy (also known as financial literacy) denotes banking customers' understanding of numerous financial concepts, products, and services provided by banks (ISA, Ibrahim, and Mohamed, 2021).

On the other hand, cybercrime awareness refers to understanding the cyber risks and cybersecurity measures linked with cyberthreats and online fraud, learned through cyber literacy - having (supported by) financial literacy (Wang, et al., 2019).

In this respective, during their studies Ismailova and Muhametjanova (2016), Kritzinger and von Solms (2010), Cone et al. (2007); and Adelola, Dawson and Batmaz (2015) found that customer literacy (education) rate plays a vital role in cybersecurity as literate people can learn awareness of cybersecurity quickly. In contrast, a study by Orgill et al. (2004) shows that literacy (education) has no direct impact on the awareness of cybersecurity. This can be supported by a study conducted by Rodrigues, Oliveira, Rodrigues, & Costa (2019) which illustrates that even academically literate people who use the latest technological features introduced by banks, if they are not information literate (cyber

literate) then they are vulnerable in cyber space. For example, they may open a link sent by hacker in an email, might share their personal information to a fake caller or on any social media platform, use a spam website, click on a link on a fake website to try to win a “prize” etc. (Alghazo, Kazmi, and Latif, 2017; Magomedov, et al., 2020).

This suggests that alone educational literacy cannot be considered as cyber literacy which leads to cybersecurity awareness, but educated people can learn fast cybersecurity awareness (Figure 10). Orji (2019) and Blazhevich, Burkaltseva, Shalneva, Smirnova, and Gadayeva (2019) further extend this node stating that lack of cyber literacy causes banking customers to respond to unsolicited communications professedly sent by banks but actually sent by criminals, targeting them to disclose their personal banking details. Therefore, this study will consider that customer literacy (both educational and cyber) has a positive impact on cybersecurity and will empirically find that either the results of this study support this literature or not.

Figure 10: Customer Literacy and Cybersecurity Awareness

Source: Author Developed

3.6.1.2. Literacy level of general public and awareness – The literacy level of general public and their awareness can also play an important role to aware the banking customers about cybersecurity and prevent or reduce the tendency of cyberthreats. The essence of public awareness about cybersecurity has been studied by multiple researchers from last decade (Nagyfejeo and Von Solms, 2020; Kovačević, Putnik, and

Tošković , 2020; Zwilling, et al., 2022; Aphane, 2023). It is found that counterintuitively the users of internet services who are least knowledgeable and are least aware of cybersecurity threats and prevention, are at high risk of cyberthreats (Marune and Hartanto, 2021). Overtime, it has become necessary for all citizens in every internet society, to be sufficiently educated about cybersecurity threats. However, in general there is a lack of adequate programs to address cybersecurity education (financial literacy) and awareness in all fields (Bruijn and Janssen, 2017; Khader, Karam, and Fares, 2021). Hence, there is a significant need of involvement and advancement of cybersecurity education at all levels, in all societies where the use of internet perquisites (Ahmad, Laplante, DeFranco, and Kassab, 2022).

The attempts have also been made to educate and aware people about cybersecurity risks, such as password security, social engineering, and fake websites etc., throughout the last decade world widely (Vacca, 2012; Peker, Ray, Da Silva, Gibson, and Lamberson, 2016). Zwilling, Klien, Lesjak, Wiechetek, Cetin, and Basim (2022) found that higher the education (financial) can result in higher level of cybersecurity awareness among people. For example, mobile broadband and smart phones are used by people with regional and social economic differences. Witnessing a sudden and substantial increase in the number of internet users during the last decade, the technological development in the mobile sector has also played its role to facilitate access to the internet from anywhere (Tulder, et al., 2019). The general public uses the internet to perform their daily tasks, conduct transactions, and interact with others. These activities all generate new personal data which can be accessed and analysed by third parties and if the third parties are not using secure connections, then that data can be compromised (stolen or hacked). Therefore, it is compulsory for the general public to know how to securely use their personal information when conducting those activities (Marune and Hartanto, 2021; Limna, et al. 2022).

Businesses and regulatory organizations have been giving attention to their information security by using more advanced technology and training their security professionals while, the cybersecurity awareness among the general public is neglected (Švábenský,

Čeleda, Vykopal, and Brišáková, 2021; Yaziz Bin Mohd, Wan and Zulkifflee, 2021). Consequently, the cybercriminals are making essential efforts to use the latest methods of hacking to steal money and information from the general public as a weak link (Aloul, 2012; Bada et al., 2019; Limna, et al. 2022). In their most recent study Yaziz Bin Mohd, et al. (2021) illustrate that public awareness of cybersecurity plays a major role in banks' effectiveness to combat cybersecurity threats. This is because along with banking customers, other members of the general public also use the cyberspace and awareness to the general public about cybersecurity will not only help to secure the cyberspace but will also help to spread this awareness to the banking customers, being part of the same society (Al-Alawi and Al-Bassam, 2021). As general public also consist of direct customers of bank which collectively presents the large number of audience for banks to spread awareness. Banks have limited resource (time and finance) to invest on cybersecurity awareness at such a large scale (Thach, Hanh, Huy, and Vu, 2021). However, the Government in collaboration of other organizations established to educate and aware people about cybersecurity can play its role in this regard (Nagyfejeo and Von Solms, 2020), as discussed below.

3.6.1.3. Awareness Program by Government – Another aspect to increase banking customers' cybersecurity awareness is Government initiative. In this digital advancement decade, many cyberspace users are unaware of how to protect themselves and their confidential information they use in the cyberspace. One of the major reason is that cyberspace users are unaware of cyber risks and threats they may come across (Bada, et al., 2018; Hafiz Ali, et al., 2019; Wang et al. 2020; Gomes, et al., 2022). Another reason is that people including general public and businesses might be aware of possible cyberthreats but they remain uneducated about the seriousness of the consequences of those threats. This can be supported by the results of the recent studies conducted by Kovačević, et al., (2020); and Zwilling, et al. (2022) which show that cyberspace users who even possessed sufficient cyberthreat awareness (even students who are digital natives) still apply minimal protective measures, mostly common and simple ones, because they are unable to comprehend the consequences of any cyberattack. Thus, continuous cybersecurity awareness campaigns with updated information are basic

element of enhancing cybersecurity awareness throughout the nation (Nagyfejeo and Von Solms, 2020; Kovačević, et al., 2020; Zwilling, et al., 2022).

Moreover, effective cybersecurity awareness campaigns must have coordination among various organisations working on it and adequate resources. Hence, a well-coordinated and coherent national cybersecurity programme is of vital importance to develop the basic level of awareness all over the nation (Li, He, Xu, Ash, Anwar, and Yuan, 2019; Nagyfejeo and Von Solms, 2020). According to Topping (2017) along with providing national cybersecurity regulations, it is government's responsibility to help organisations enable change (innovation in technology and its consequences) at a national level. Bada, et al., (2019) collecting various stakeholders' point of view resulted that lack of awareness is an institutional (government and businesses) problem instead of users' problem. Generally, people do not get involved in cybersecurity discussions regularly or are not equipped with sufficient knowledge about cybersecurity and how it can affect them (Bada, et al., 2019).

Bruijn and Janssen (2017) confirm it stressing that people working in the field related to cybersecurity are more aware than, people who do not belong to cybersecurity field.

This emphasises the need for awareness among general public about cybersecurity. Especially, if the people are not literate to the level that they can understand the implication and importance of cybersecurity then it becomes harder for organisations/banks to make everyone aware about cybersecurity because it requires time and money, which businesses may lack (Nagyfejeo and Von Solms, 2020). Comparatively, the government can play its role at the national level by using public tax money to raise general cybersecurity awareness (coordinating with other organizations) to the level that citizens can use measures to protect their personal information requested by cyber criminals (Bruijn and Janssen, 2017; Bada, et al., 2019). Bada, et al., (2019) further adds in that some temporary awareness programmes are provided by banks for example sending alert messages and emails or informing about password security etc. The study suggests that these initiatives have not been used nationally which includes every person of society. Hence, there is a need of more centralised awareness raising

government programme to fundamentally extend the understanding of cybersecurity throughout the nation.

Most countries have given priority to the importance of cybersecurity. Subsequently, some of them have provided specific guidelines for their private and public sectors. Ultimately this provoked to introduce cybersecurity training programmes to spread awareness relating to the effect of cyberthreats and how to avoid them (Alotaibi, 2019; Khader, et al., 2021). For instance, the U.S. government introduced the National Initiative for Cybersecurity Education to address awareness, formal education, specialised training, and work-related structure, intending to enhance the long-term cybersecurity behaviour of its citizens (Khader, et al., 2021). Another most recent and good example of this activity is the new national cybersecurity regulations issued by the UK government. Through this regulation the UK government declared that there is a need for sufficient cybersecurity skills and knowledge beyond the technical cybersecurity skills which professionals possess to secure the nation (Odebade and Benkhelifa, 2023).

To ensure the active consideration of cybersecurity it is necessary that people working in the Digital, Data and Technology profession in the government's commercial and legal functions should be able to receive training and awareness of cybercrime (Marsden & Goslin, 2022). Basically, this step by the UK government indicates the need of cybersecurity culture that empowers its people to learn, question, and challenge to improve learning. In this respect, it is necessary to start raising awareness throughout the nation. In addition, getting this right is a key to sustainable change (Shillair, Esteve-González, Dutton, Creese, Nagyfejeo, and von Solms, 2022). In 2017, Saudi Arabia also has established the National Cybersecurity Authority (NCA) to hold the nationwide control of cybersecurity. Subsequently, National Cybersecurity Centre (NCSC) was established to support the technical and operational aspects of NCA. Although, different countries have diverse cybersecurity legislative laws and awareness programmes however, it is worth to note that all countries have one universal fact that cybersecurity awareness is universally needed (Khader, et al., 2021).

Furthermore, the common consensus within cybersecurity community elaborates that people are the weakest link in security infrastructure (Li, et al., 2019). Several studies has been conducted on the relationship between human factor and cybersecurity, considering the role of human factors as a variable and found positive relationship suggesting that awareness is the solution (Orgill et al., 2004; Aloul, 2012; Joinson and Steen, 2018; Innab et al., 2018; Adholiya and Adholiya, 2019; Wang et al., 2020; Alzubaidi, 2021; Gomes, et al., 2022; Johri and Kumar, 2023). However, Alruwaili (2019); Chowdhury and Gkioulos (2021) and Chowdhury, Katsikas, and Gkioulos (2022) highlight that cybersecurity awareness general programmes may have limited results while, customization of awareness based on individuals' level of education and understanding can produce effective results. Bruijn and Janssen (2017) investigating why cybersecurity is not getting the attention it requires and how cybersecurity awareness can be spread effectively proposed six strategies as follows (Figure 11), designed in such a way that will generate more awareness:

Figure 11: Strategies To Increase Cybersecurity Awareness

Strategy	Strategy Description of an effective frame
1) Do not exacerbate Cybersecurity	Put the need in a realistic perspective. Exaggeration will only exacerbate the problem and work against the objective in the long term.
2) Make it clear who the villains are	Villains should be clearly recognizable as evil.
3) Give cybersecurity a face by putting the heroes in the spotlight.	Those who are guarding and protecting society should be placed in the forefront. Demonstrate their successes.
4) Show its importance for society	The benefits of taking action should be emphasized. Cybersecurity is key to economic growth and the prosperity of nations.
5) Personalize for easy recognition by the public	Connect cybersecurity to the daily life of people to ensure easy recognition. Groups are different.
6) Connect to undercurrent	Cybersecurity is closely interwoven with other issues that do receive political attention

Retrieved from: Bruijn and Janssen (2017, p. 5)

Jean-Pierre (2021) and Agbo-ola (2022) recommended that these strategies are useful implying that users of awareness programmes will not consider them inefficient or counterproductive in practice hence, they will be motivated to adopt them, considering the perceived usefulness. However, a recent study by Awan and Malik (2018) shows that government cybersecurity awareness policies/programmes can lessen the impact of cybercrime but not to great extent. Given that, the effectiveness of awareness programs by Government is linked with the organizational behaviour/strategic planning (Kemp, 2023). Therefore, banks need a comprehensive approach to deal with cybersecurity issues, such as strategic planning which is discussed in the following section. Supporting this view, Alghazo, Kazmi, and Latif (2017) mentioned that although with low customer awareness the banks still have high responsibility of ensuring secure banking experience for their customers. Furthermore, Joju, Shanmugam, and Joseph (2016) also suggested that banks need to focus on minimizing delivery gaps of cyber literacy and awareness, as well as integrate it in their strategic planning. Given that the customers prefer the product/service performance (security) rather than brand image in case of banks to gain the trust on e-banking. Hence, the rate of customer switching is subsequent to bank cybersecurity (Jibril, et al., 2020; Akinbowale, et al., 2020).

Though, it can be concluded that as a human factor customer awareness is an essential factor for effective cybersecurity in banks. However, this awareness can be supported by increasing overall literacy rate (customer and public), overall level of awareness (customer and general public) through Government awareness programs and can result in customer trust on e-banking as well as its adoption, as presented in the following Figure 12.

Figure 12: Customer Awareness and E-banking

Source: Author Developed

3.6.2. Strategic planning – Internal Governance

Strategic planning is an internal factor which can be used to strengthen the banking cybersecurity policies along with awareness to confront cyberthreats effectively (Al-Alawi and Al-Bassam, 2021). According to Ruiz-Vanoye et al. (2014) the information security strategic planning is a technique to formulate, execute and assess decisions of technological security that allows the financial organisation to achieve their information security objectives. Comparatively, cybersecurity management is the process of defining, developing, implementing, and imposing cybersecurity policies to prevent cyberthreats. Contrarily, cybersecurity governance is the long-term strategic planning. It ensures information security whereby management must provide direction and controls to protect the organisation resources and assets (Utami and Damayanti, 2022). Similarly, Sajko, Boone, and Buyl (2021) mentioned that cybersecurity governance is management of information security and its policies whereby the management will strategically plan for cybersecurity. Hence, cybersecurity strategic planning is organizational cybersecurity governance.

Previously, the executives of the businesses have been treating cybersecurity issue as a technological issue. Henceforth, the technological departments in the business have been dealing with them. But now the literature shows that the cybersecurity issue should be considered as a strategic issue rather than technological issue (Bainbridge, 2017; Hafiz-Ali, et al., 2019). This is because the managers of the businesses need to have a strategic plan to deal with cybersecurity threats as those threats are becoming complicated (Marotta and Pearlson, 2019).

Usable and integrated approaches, and strategic planning against cybercrime is compulsory (Henry, 2015; Cvitić et al., 2017; Malik and Islam, 2019; Wang, et al., 2020) because, the growing rate of occurrence, innovation, and seriousness of cybersecurity attacks is a serious matter for all businesses to warn them to ensure that their cybersecurity risk policy is receiving appropriate attention within their enterprise risk management (ERM) programs/strategic planning (Alotaibi, et al., 2017; Dhillon, 2020). By considering cybersecurity in strategic management the businesses can better highlight, analyse and manage the cybersecurity risks in the broader context of their overall business mission and goals (Stine et al., 2020; Naik Bukht, et al., 2020). Furthermore, information security strategic planning will also be useful to find and detoxify cybercrimes confronted by the data and information and it protects the security and confidentiality which is the ultimate objective of all organisations. Also, Cvitić et al. (2017) mention that the fast and vigorous growth of the information and communication environment requires constant improvement of the strategic, legislative, and executive planning.

According to Hafiz-Ali, et al. (2019), the essential element for a cybersecurity strategy in the banking sector includes protecting the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of confidential financial data and systems. Such an effective strategy can be developed through a combination of **technical** (Kesharwani, et al., 2019; Malik and Islam, 2019; Wang, et al., 2020; Al-Alawi and Al-Bassam, 2021), **organizational** (Alotaibi, et al., 2017; Malik and Islam, 2019; Naik Bukht, et al., 2020; Dhillon, 2020; Al-Alawi and Al-Bassam, 2021; Al-Badran, 2021), and **legal** (Lagazio, et al., 2014; Goel, 2016; Alotaibi, et al., 2017; Dhillon, 2020; Wang, et al., 2020; Al-Alawi and Al-Bassam, 2021) measures. The technical aspect of cybersecurity strategy includes planning to invest in required

technology and cybersecurity experts (Al-Alawi and Al-Bassam, 2021). The organizational view is based on employee development which includes all employees including executives (Al-Badran, 2021). The legal term consists of the banks' integration of regulations compliance in their technical and organizational policies. This develops security culture within the banks (Dhillon, 2020). Hence, the banks can focus on technical and organisational aspects integrating legal compliance to improve their information security.

Terlizzi, Meirelles and, Cunha, (2017) further asserts it as, it is found that to have successful strategic planning of information systems a bank needs to combine the cybersecurity regulatory framework with its strategic planning (legal compliance), introduce policies that direct the use of information technology (technical aspect), and develop a code of conduct for its employees (organizational view). This will establish a corporate security culture. Consequently, strategic planning for cybersecurity will be considered as a factor for this study. Hence, the results of this study will show that the private banks in Pakistan consider cybersecurity as a strategic issue and plan accordingly or not. Subsequently, it can be referred to be a reason of cyber-attacks. However, based on the above literature the following technical and organisational aspects of strategic planning are discussed in detail.

3.6.2.1. Technical Planning

Investment on Cybersecurity

Investment in cybersecurity is a crucial factor where executives must be convinced to understand the importance of cybersecurity beforehand making decision of sufficient budgeting to impose cybersecurity (Al-Alawi and Al-Bassam, 2021). Na-jibzadeh and Park (2021) mentioned that insufficient budget for cybersecurity means that the organisation cannot be armed with adequate resources which can ensure cybersecurity of its assets. It is required to ensure the stability and security of banking sector because it is a crucial part of society's critical infrastructure. The prevention of cyberthreats targeting the banking sector must be ensured to maintain customers' confidence in financial system of the country (Keränen, 2022). Different studies suggest that to

overcome the cybercrime issue in the banking sector there is a need for new, up to date as well as responsive technology and availability of high-level experts (Geyres & Orozco, 2016; Awan & Memon, 2016; Cvitić et al., 2017; KPMG, 2018; Dupont, 2019; Kesharwani, et al., 2019; Malik and Islam, 2019; PWC, 2019; Wang, et al., 2020; Al-Alawi and Al-Bassam, 2021). For example, considering emerging threats, banks also have to adopt/invest-in new measures to secure their customers' information. The banks can use information security technology that will support the secure banking experience. Such as, the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) could detect the trusted devices (laptop or mobile) used on daily basis by the user and if the user logged in using different device, the user will get a notification on the registered mobile number (Alghazo, Kazmi, and Latif, 2017).

However, these technological advancements and expertise are acquired by investing in cybersecurity (Geyres & Orozco, 2016; Wang, et al., 2020; Al-Alawi and Al-Bassam, 2021). Although, Varian (2004), Moore and Anderson (2012), Gordonet et al. (2015), Meulen (2015), Dupont (2019), Wang (2019), Malik and Islam, (2019) and Wang et al. (2020) state that lack of investment in cybersecurity is a major hurdle in improving banking sector cybersecurity. Uddin, Ali, and Hassan (2020) stated that to deal with dynamic cyberattacks the technology is required to be updated which carries a significant cost for the businesses therefore there are chances of higher marginal costs by investment in cyber technology which restricts businesses to invest in cybersecurity. However, even though financial institutions' investment decisions are made with paradox because the cybersecurity risks are unavoidable in the digital environment. Still, investment in cybersecurity is essential (Syed, Khaver & Yasin, 2019; Świątkowska, 2020; Na-jibzadeh and Park, 2021).

Supporting this, some other authors Bernik (2014); Kopp, Kaffenberger and Wilson (2017), BIS (2016), Eling and Lehmann (2018), Sadiq (2019), Syed et al. (2019), and Qadeer (2020) in their studies claimed that cybercrimes are unavoidable in spite of substantial increase in investments in the information security system of financial institutions which consists of technology and experts, because of the increasing number of new types of cyberattacks. Therefore, organizations continuously need to look for the latest cybersecurity solutions (Alghazo, et al., 2017; Cvitić, et al., 2017; Sadiq, 2019;

Wang et al., 2020; Mahmood, 2021; and Haroon et al., 2021). Comparatively, some studies found that the level of investment in banks' security depends on need to acquire the required technology or experts (Moore and Anderson, 2012; Awan and Memon, 2016; Malik and Islam, 2019; Al-Alawi and Al-Bassam, 2021). Though, it does not imply that the banks can work effectively with outdated technology in this dynamic cybersecurity environment (Khatri, 2017; Ometov et al., 2018; Haroon et al., 2021; Kazmi, 2021) as discussed above and below.

Use of Outdated technology by Banks

Uddin, Hakim, and Hassan (2020) pronounce that humans can have different motives to innovate the technology such as profit making or harming the business. Since it is impossible to control the motivational behaviour of humans developing technology however, the defensive technologies used by banks must be and aim for higher security. This situation brings technological dependency where adequate investment in technology innovation is made yet cyberthreats are there (Qadeer (2020). Following this concept, it is clear that we are living in the cybercriminals' era. Yet, some banks continue to use outdated legacy infrastructure which does not meet the latest security requirements based on evolving threats (Shahi and Sinha, 2020; Farnfield, 2020; Prakash, 2020; Manning, 2020). The recent example of this is the malware attacks on ATM machines which are increasing (Haroon et al., 2021). Most of these machines' operating system is based on Windows 7, even though Microsoft has stopped supporting windows 7 from January 2020 (Microsoft, 2021). Therefore, the banks which have not update their systems will make their machines vulnerable to attacks (Sadiq, 2019; Syed et al., 2019; Kazmi, 2021; Haroon et al., 2021).

Despite them being ineffective, replacing the present legacy systems of banking is extraordinarily expensive and complex. Additionally, huge potential operational risks come along with replacing core banking systems (Moşteanu, 2020; Banking Circle, 2020). In fact, fewer than 30% of 1st generation banking platform replacements could succeed (Heidmann, 2010). The most recent example of this is the TSB bank in the UK. In 2018, TSB tried to develop its own banking system but, mistakes and issues resulted in TSB

losing £176 million (Nish and Naumaan, 2019; Makortoff, 2019). The problems TSB faced because of this upgrade included, blocking 1.9 million customers' accounts showing incorrect balances and the access by customers' accounts to those of other TSB customers (Nish and Naumaan, 2019; Monaghan, 2018). According to Furr, Ozcan and Eisenhardt (2022), it is acknowledged the complex legacy IT environment is the greatest hurdle while adopting digital transformation. Furthermore, the cost is too high to modernise core banking systems which is another vital issue when it is being considered whether or not to adopt the new technology (Shahi and Sinha, 2020; Diener and Špaček, 2021).

Therefore, it is concluded for this thesis that investment in cybersecurity is an important factor to prevent cyberattacks in banking industry. Although, merely investing in the latest technology and experts of the field cannot mitigate cybersecurity risk. The proper set-up of cybersecurity experts and relevant staff training (discussed below) can be effective (Caron, 2015; Ahmad & Schreyer, 2016; Geyres & Orozco, 2016).

3.6.2.2. Organisational Planning

Employees Training and Awareness

Employees are considered one of the major human factors for any organisation's internal cybersecurity governance. The focus on staff behaviour is increasingly being considered as an important factor for organisations' information security vulnerability and breaches (Alotaibi, et al., 2017; Al-Badran, 2021). A study by Conway et al. (2017) shows that highly visible security systems with low observation of exposure to risk lead to weak security practices whereby the self-efficacy of employees is neglected. The vulnerabilities caused by employees' misconduct has been reason for sophisticated cyberattacks on the financial services industry. This reality requires consistent investment in employees training and awareness, as they are the first line of defence against most of the social engineering attacks (Servidio & Taylor, 2015; Dhillon, 2020). In their recent study Terlizzi, Meirelles and, Cunha, (2017) conducted on 500 employees of the top five banks of Brazil and 100 members of the general public, using Facebook. The results show that the bank

employees who are trained were found to avoid social engineering compared to employees with no training and members of the general public. Although, the need for further training was still realised because an anonymous Facebook user disrupted an online social network used by bank employees and had unauthorised access to sensitive information. Another recent study in Bahrain on 26 banks by Al-Bassam and Al-Alawi (2020) shows that out of 100 respondents, 26% agreed that banks face online identified theft, intentional damages to computer systems (23%) and hacking (11%) caused by employee's actions. However, the study concludes that enforcement of security policies, facilitating investment in cybersecurity, and mandating employee security awareness training are the most useful ways used by banks to mitigate cybersecurity risk and improve internal cybersecurity governance. Although, Wang, Nnaji, and Jung (2020) in their study on Nigeria to find the threats, practices and capabilities found that employee training is the crucial measure of cybersecurity in banks because employees may respond to a cyberthreat intentionally, unintentionally, or with purpose to harm the information system of the organisation. Similarly, Maalem Lahcen et al. (2020) justified employees' cybersecurity behaviour as a human error, which is the action of people breaking the control limits prescribed by the operating system. Subsequently, they categorised those errors in the following types, Figure 13:

Figure 13: Employee as a Threat

Source: Maalem Lahcen et al. (2020, p.7)

Thus, employees' cybersecurity behaviour can be categorised as unintentional, intentional, or malicious. However, regardless of the behavioural intention the consequences of human error in case of employees, can be huge for information cybersecurity of banks. Therefore, employees training and awareness of cybersecurity is compulsory. Supporting it, Naik Bukht, et al. (2020) state that cybercrimes negatively impact the organisations' performance however, the employees' knowledge and awareness of cybersecurity can weaken that impact. Some banks' employees continue using permanent passwords having weak combination of words and figures, have low information security literacy and low motivational behaviour to adopt latest technology. Given that, they are not aware about most serious cyberattacks such as, ransomware, social engineering, malware, DDoS, and phishing. Furthermore, they are not being trained about proactive cyberattack prevention techniques (Woldemichael, 2019). Despite of investing in latest technological solutions will not help unless the employees are not using it effectively and opens up the system for cyber criminals. The effective cybersecurity system of an organisation requires all employees to be trained about how to prevent cyberthreats (Al-Badran, 2021). In this view, Al-Alawi, and Al-Bassam (2021) found that lack of top management support, inadequate budget, lack of compliance and cybersecurity culture are the factors which can impact the employees training and awareness of cybersecurity as shown in figure 14:

Figure 14: Employee Training and Awareness

Source: Al-Alawi and Al-Bassam (2021, p.18)

A data breach in a bank not only causes the banks to bear the cost of the cyberattack and its loss but also to pay heavy fines to the banking regulator (Grewcock, 2021). Therefore, banks need a holistic approach considering various institutions (factors) including employees as one of the major components to secure the internal actors of banks who work on the frontline (employees), as hackers target them. Moreover, the banks should make security authentication on a 'zero trust model' whereby employees and contractors will only have access to limited resources of the bank for a specific period (IAM, 2021). Following this holistic approach even if the connection is compromised in an attack on banks' information security system, the harm could be limited.

The banks are facilitated with international and national regulatory frameworks which provide guidance about employees training and awareness (Kaffenberger and Kopp, 2019; Uddin, et al., 2020). It is leaders' and management responsibility to understand and align technological solutions and employee training standards with regulatory requirements and industry standards to enhance banks information security (Crisanto, and Prenio, 2017; Creado and Ramteke, 2020; Lie, Utomo, and Winarno, 2021). Hence, banking activities must fully comply with the standards and best practices for effective risk management and internal control (Rameli, et al., 2013; Diene and Špaček, 2021). However, the executive are not at exception when it comes to cybersecurity training and awareness, as discussed below.

Executives'/Directors' Training and Awareness

Al-Alawi and Al-Bassam (2021) state that executives' commitment and support to invest and improve the cybersecurity of a financial institution/bank is of high concern. A number of surveys and studies of cybercrime have revealed that even the highly advanced companies are facing cyberattacks or cyber failures and one of the major factors in this regard is disconnection between the technical employees dealing with cybersecurity and the ones who sit at the board (Alghamdi, 2021). The directors with up-to-date training and experience of technology or science are found to be a minority in boardrooms (Rothrock, Kaplan, and Van Der Oord, 2018; Robert & Ackerman, 2021). Only that minority directors reflect that their expertise in cybercrime is becoming the need of businesses in recent

years. The basic point is that whether the executives are unable to make and approve appropriate cybersecurity strategies (Bada, Von Solms, and Agrafiotis, 2018).

A well organised board of directors' team is consisted of people with complementary expertise and experiences who can address the current cybersecurity challenges mutually (Alghamdi, 2021). Most boards of directors nowadays have backgrounds either in finance, law, and business etc. but not in science or technology (Lehuedé, 2020). This presents a risk because with lack of compulsory minimum cyber expertise or skills, the board may make decisions simply as a passive consumer of metrics and information presented by management (Barker, 2016; Al-Alawi and Al-Bassam, 2021). Therefore, cybersecurity concern requires a shift from the information security professionals to the executives, given that appropriate attention is provided to cybersecurity. The traditional solutions of cybersecurity such as using firewalls are still necessary to use, but no longer sufficient (Shillair, Esteve-González, Dutton, Creese, Nagyfejeo, and von Solms, 2022). Rather a holistic approach to cybersecurity is required which includes across the institution - top to bottom, awareness of cybersecurity along with other strategic compliances. The major two benefits of providing directors cybersecurity training are that firstly, they will include a cybersecurity expert as a board of member and secondly, they will be able to analyse their organisation's cybersecurity maturity against regulatory standards such as NIST. This will improve their information security (Bada, et al., 2018).

Further, cybercrimes are becoming more advanced every day. Therefore, decision makers often have to deal with cybersecurity challenges about which they do not have comprehensive knowledge to make effective decision, still they need to critically address those challenges (Rothrock, Kaplan, & Van, 2018). Uncertainty is a crucial factor of a crisis and decision makers should take it as a consideration instead of treating it as an obstacle to respond to cyber incidents. Although, decision makers cannot predict cyber-incidents and their impact but if they have training, they can make better decisions to prevent them or effectively respond (Stern, 2014; Gale, Bongiovanni, and Slapnicar, 2022). Cybersecurity games have become a unique method to train decision makers to prepare effective strategies and respond to cyber incidents. These games enable capacity building of decision makers through controlled environments whereby mostly

hypothetical scenarios are presented that are developed to invoke discussion (Hill Jr, Fanuel, Yuan, Zhang, and Sajad, 2020). Meanwhile, decision making skills are put to the test and these games are known as an effective tool to train decision makers (Tioh, Mina & Jacobson, 2017). But many people believe it is more effective to use technical capabilities instead of games.

The major challenge of using games is to first identify the factors that influence cybersecurity decision-making. Therefore, some authors do not validate the effectiveness of games to train decision makers (Hussain, Kuhn & Shaikh, 2020). The training methods to improve decision-making skills can significantly benefit to the organisations. According to a Ponemon Institute survey in 2019 (on 507 organisations of 16 different countries and 17 industries), the average cost of each cyber incident was found around to be \$3.92 million. Therefore, businesses cannot afford to ignore investment in effective cybersecurity decision-making (Ponemon, 2019). Cybersecurity can be explained as 'a niche technical subject that requires a computer science degree to understand mysterious jargon of cybersecurity' (Haggman, 2019), which may explain why the technical skills and expertise of cybersecurity are found to be lacking amongst boards of directors (Rothrock, Kaplan, & Van Der Oord, 2018), policymakers (Hussain et al. 2018) and public (Bruijn & Janssen, 2017).

Since, the board of directors are not directly involved in cybersecurity planning, lacking the awareness/training, they mostly do not have direct counterargument about cybersecurity issue with CISOs. As per the ISACA state of cybersecurity report published in 2017, only 21% CISOs directly report to directors while 63% have to report through chief information officers. This gap in reporting structure presents cybersecurity as a technical issue rather than a strategic issue, reducing the scope of action and effectiveness of proposed cybersecurity proposals from CISOs (ISACA, 2017; Bada, et al., 2018). The results of a recent study conducted by Al-Bassam and Al-Alawi (2020) show that many banking and financial institutions remain conservative regarding the implementation and use of cybersecurity. Indeed, those financial institutions are unaware of the advantages of the use of cybersecurity. Furthermore, the incurring cost associated with the application of cybersecurity is one of the reasons of rejection to accept it.

However, Ogbanufe, Kim, and Jones (2021) found that institutional pressures have positive impact on executives' understanding of their responsibility to comply with regulatory requirements and emphasise on cybersecurity of the organisation. In addition, a recent study disclosed that a new regulation was proposed in EU whereby, the executives who will approve any incorrect certification for company's data security practices, will be jailed for 20 years and up to 4% of the company annual revenue will be penalty. The purpose of this regulation is to engage the executives actively in cybersecurity (Chatterjee, 2019). Bada, et al., (2019) in their most recent study to find internal and external factors affecting the cybersecurity governance found that executive training is one of the major factor affecting cybersecurity governance of banks, along with other factors discussed above (Figure 15) where ad-hoc initiatives are referred to government programmes for cybersecurity awareness.

Figure 15: Internal and External Factors suggested by Bada

Source: Bada, et al., (2019, p.113)

Thus, it can be summed up that executives' commitment and support is one of the most important factors for effective cybersecurity management activities in a financial institution (Alghamdi, 2021). Henceforth, based on the literature on strategic planning, the internal cybersecurity governance concept is developed as follows:

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Figure 16: Internal Cybersecurity Governance

Source: Author Developed

3.6.3. Cybersecurity Law

The term cybercrime is basically a social concept underlined by the intention of actors in regard to norms defined by law. Thus, cybercrime law and policies address the intention and behaviour of people in relation to social and economic consequences (Lagazio, Sherif, and Cushman, 2014). Kosseff (2018, p.1010) provides a broad and flexible definition of cybersecurity law that identifies the general aspects of it and defined cybersecurity law as:

Cybersecurity law promotes the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of public and private information, systems, and networks, through the use of forward-looking regulations and incentives, with the goal of protecting individual rights and privacy, economic interests, and national security.

The technological innovation brings new opportunities for cyber criminals to use it as an effective tool to break or go against the law. Cyber laws are introduced to deal with cyber criminals. However, the simple nature of cybersecurity laws in different countries have facilitated cyber criminals to conduct illegal activities while, create complexities for

governments to track those criminals (Manwaring and Hanrahan, 2019). Therefore, a comprehensive cybersecurity law must be developed to facilitate the governments and their agencies to adopt a proactive approach to deal with cyberthreats (Lippert and Cloutier, 2021; Mishra, Alzoubi, Anwar, and Gill, 2022).

The banks in different countries have been confronting almost similar kind of issues such as fraud or less security of e-services provided by bank resulting in lower customer trust. However, the government laws which sometimes do not provide the required level of security for e-banking environment risks, is a crucial factor in banking industry cybersecurity (Hafiz-Ali, Khan, Asghar, and Shuaib, 2019; Kesharwani, Sarkar, and Oberoi, 2019). However, to win against cyber criminals there is need of extensive and safer approach. Given that technological solutions or social behaviours alone cannot prevent the cyber criminals but the law enforcement agencies should be able to assess and charge cyber criminals effectively (Deora and Chudasama, 2021). For this purpose, the law needs to be updated along with the innovation in technology so that the possible cyberthreat is identified and appropriate law is introduced to prevent any threat to use of that technology (Gomes, Deshmukh, and Anute, 2022). A recent study conducted by Etomilade-Oduola (2020) found that cyber laws in Nigeria have failed to effectively protect banking consumers from cybercriminals' attempts and secure their interests. Given that the Nigerian cyber laws are not composed of strict punishments and clear actions which can be taken against cyber criminals. The cyber criminals take advantage of jurisdictional arbitrage opportunities and conduct cybercrimes from countries where cyber laws are not implemented. Inconsistent cyber laws motivate cyber criminals to do illegal activities knowing that they will not be caught and penalized (Kesharwani, et al., 2019).

Libicki (2021) supports this view as, nations cannot develop unless respective governments grantee secure and dependable digital connectivity. Consequently over 100 nations have taken steps to device their national cybersecurity laws to address innovative cybersecurity threats. For instance, Europe is more developed as compared to other countries in terms of cybersecurity innovation. EU introduced a cybersecurity law as well as a network and information security (NIS) proposal in 2013. The Cyber Crime centre (EC3) in EU supports the European citizens and businesses by raising awareness of

dynamic cyberthreat trends (van de Weijer, Leukfeldt, and Bernasco, 2019). Although, it cannot be implied that solely it is government's responsibility to prevent cyberthreats by developing cybersecurity law, instead each organisation and individual in society has to be responsible for their own actions actively to reduce cybercrimes (Mishra, et al., 2022). For example, El-Muhammady (2021) mentioned that even Malaysian government introduced new cybersecurity law to deal with cybercrimes still it is difficult to prevent cybercrimes in Malaysia because there is lack of cybersecurity experts and the technology. Hence, cybersecurity law along with other supporting factors can be effective to prevent cybercrimes, rather than standing alone (Hafiz-Ali, et al., 2019; Kesharwani, et al., 2019).

In short developing different cyber laws, every country have the shared goal of reducing cybercrime. The next step followed by developing critical cyber law is its implementation (Mishra, et al., 2022), as discussed below.

3.6.3.1. Law enforcement

In 2014, Williams proposed that cybercrime is not a new issue rather it is the future of law enforcement. Globally, investment in IT security increased to \$124 billion in 2019 from \$71.1 billion in 2017. The cybersecurity incidents which happened in 2017 and 2018 named 'big ticket cases of data breaches' were the main impetus to increase the investment in cybersecurity with the purpose to reduce and detain data protection breaches (Ofori et al., 2020). Wang et al. (2021) state that the increasing rate of cybercrimes has presented new forms of global challenges to law enforcement agencies that conventionally have been operating under specified geographical jurisdictions and patrol regions. The local law enforcement agencies have noticed that by using cyberspace the cybercriminals have benefitted from globally connected internet which they use to conduct cybercrimes in other countries (Al-Badran, 2021). Governments in different countries, previously have not been allocating sufficient budgets for law enforcement agencies, underestimating its requirement (Ibrahim, Karabatak, and Abdullahi, 2020). Consequently, the law enforcement agencies are not equipped with high tech professionals. Unspecified enforcement of law turns in to unsolved cybercrime

cases. Aiming to demotivate cybercriminals, such cases should be solved through the fast-track mobile courts to respond to the complaints and build people's confidence (Kethineni, 2020). However, lack of sufficient number of qualified employees who can enforce law cause difficulty to make the decisions of criminal proceedings quick and prompt (Vitvitskiy, Kurakin, Pokataev, Skriabin, and Sanakoiev, 2021). Additionally, James and Warren (2010), and Kao et al. (2020) endorsed it saying that for quick response against cybercrime and to achieve justice there is a need of effective law enforcement investigation which requires efficient IT skills and an in depth understanding of cybercrimes activities. Furthermore, the law enforcement has to be very rigid and up to date with crimes. For this purpose, an act has to be enforced that can help track such activities among public. Likewise, punishments and penalties have to be enacted consistently to lessen such crimes (ISA, Ibrahim, and Mohamed, 2021).

Law enforcement through cybersecurity team - equipped with skills and authority required, can support the society by hugely reducing chances of cybercrimes. However, the delay in identifying the new threats to the available technology is one of the obstacle to modify the national cybercrime law (Al-Bardan, 2021). Improved cybersecurity and securing information is significant for each nation's safety and economic well-being (Muhammady, 2021). Anti cybercrime activities are the speciality of law enforcement agencies due to the innovative nature of these criminal threats. The investigation process of these cybercrimes is complex because detecting and recording traces of such crimes in virtual space is challenging. The facility to remotely remove the traces of crime enables cyber criminals to reduce the evidence against them (Le, Nguyen, Tran, Pham, Ngo, and Vu, 2020). Although this requires law enforcement officers to again specialised knowledge to combat such criminals. Since cybercrime has become an international offence therefore the law enforcement officers need to acquire international level expertise to secure the banking sector (Al-Badran, 2021). Another aspect is that, financial institutions hide most of the cyberthreats confronted, from law enforcement agencies, considering their reputation among customers. This restricts the law enforcement to be effective (Vitvitskiy, et al., 2021).

Kao et al., (2020) and Wang et al. (2021) asserted that the collaboration between law enforcement agencies plays a major role in fighting against international criminals. Provided that fighting against borderless cybercrimes includes the unnatural limitations of internet (invisibility, ambiguity, and provided guardianship; Jaishankar, 2008; Al-Badran, 2021; Rakha, 2023), as well as the challenge of managing alliances throughout jurisdictions and gathering appropriate support from different impacted authorities (Britz, 2013; Mishra, et al., 2022; Rakha, 2023). This results in the low rate of clearance of cybercrime cases as compared to traditional crimes (Vitvitskiy, et al., 2021).

In their most recent study in Nigeria to highlight cybersecurity breaches, practices, and capability Wang, Nnaji, and Jung (2020) established that the lack of satisfactory levels of law enforcement are listed as one of the key factors that result in lower cybersecurity capabilities of banks. Supporting this study, another study by Yaziz Bin Mohd et al. (2021) describes that law enforcement in a country can improve cybersecurity landscape. However, government needs to play its role to make the law enforcement system efficient by collaborating with the involved authorities (also supported by Kao et al., (2020); Wang et al., 2021; Vitvitskiy, et al., 2021; Al-Badran, 2021; Mishra, et al., 2022; and Rakha, 2023). Therefore, it is equally important that having comprehensive law, its' enforcement remains important as shown in Figure 17.

Based on this literature review, it can be concluded that law and its enforcement must work together to demotivate cyber criminals and ultimately cybercrime in banking sector can be reduced. However, law and law enforcement (as a factor) itself only cannot guarantee to prevent cyberattacks. There is need of consolidation of other factors' governance simultaneously, to effectively prevent cyberthreats in banking industry (Khan, Malik, Nazir, and Khan, 2023), as discussed in this study.

Figure 17: Cybersecurity Law, Law Enforcement and Cybercrime

Source: Author Developed

3.6.4. Lack of Satisfactory Regulatory Framework of Cybersecurity

Increasing trend of adopting information systems and technologies in daily practices specifically, in banking sector critically made banks dependent on these systems and technologies. Therefore, it is compulsory to secure those systems, calculating risks that can threaten them, through regulatory frameworks (Bouveret, 2018; Artemenko and Bychkova, 2020). Shen (2014), following NIST cybersecurity framework defines cybersecurity framework as a set of industry standards and best practices to assist businesses control cybersecurity risks as well as secure their digital assets from cyberattackers whereby the IT governance of business would consist of IT processes and leadership that will ensure the compliance of regulations.

Previously, cybersecurity has been considered simply an IT issue which is completely incorrect. Over time, it has been realised that cybersecurity needs regulatory guidance to attain sustainability (Bainbridge, 2017; Hafiz-Ali, et al., 2019). During the last decade, the

cybersecurity regulatory framework has gone through extraordinary changes - including the concepts of general risk management and business continuity rules in different countries such as Europe, Hong Kong, Russia, USA, and Singapore (Goel, 2016; Kosseff, 2018). Though, cybersecurity has become a focus of discussion for international rules and regulations implemented by various international organisations such as BCBS, CPMI, FSB, G7, IAIS, IMF, IOSCO, OECD, and the World Bank Group whereby, the financial sector is at the core of new regulatory initiatives. These regulations may vary country to country if a standard international framework (NIST/ISO27001) is not adopted (Didenko, 2020; Thach, Hanh, Huy, and Vu, 2021). There are several reasons to improve banking sector regulatory framework. For instance, the dynamic cyberthreats demand a totally different attitude considering that some attacks will not be prevented therefore financial institutions need to focus on identifying and responding to threats instead of attempting to build impenetrable cyber-fortresses (Calliess and Baumgarten, 2020). Furthermore, adoption of digitalized banking services; increasing dependence of banks on interdependent operational networks such as financial markets infrastructure or various service providers; high cost of cyberattacks in banking sector; and regardless of security measures still banks become victim, are some other reasons (Bouveret, 2018; Kesharwani, Sarkar, and Oberoi, 2019). According to Novák and Doucek (2017) it is essential to ensure that the cybersecurity regulatory framework in place can address the best ways to manage the contemporary cyber risks. A framework which does not meet this condition needs to be revised so that it can fulfil the purpose of this regulation. Moreover, Kopp, Kaffenberger, & Wilson (2017) state that the cybersecurity regulations should be up to date to the level that it is ex-ante (which can enable the banks to use measures or standards that can help to anticipate the level of threat and control them proactively).

Ogunwale (2020) suggested that appropriate and consistent implementation of all relevant regulatory guidelines about cybersecurity will assist introduction of cybercrimes as well as fostering customers' trust in banking system. This can be supported by the findings of a study conducted by Ezu, Nwobia, Adigwe, and Okoye (2020) that there is

need of improved synergy between banks and the regulator implementing comprehensive regulations, to prevent the cybercrime.

Digitalization brings financial benefits to banking sector, simultaneously it imposes major challenges as well which regulatory body of the country (state bank) has to consider to maintain the balance between securing financial stability, protecting customers, and fostering innovation (Artemenko and Bychkova, 2020). Regardless of the robust policies developed by the banks if the regulatory framework for the banking industry is unsatisfactory, those policies will not be effective. The most recent example of this is when, in 2020, the Indian government took 10 initiatives to improve the cybersecurity throughout the whole country, but those initiatives failed because of ambiguity in the legal framework for surveillance and monitoring cybersecurity (Securium, 2020). Although, cyber criminals have been targeting financial sector world widely but more efforts and resources has been invested to address cybersecurity risk in developed countries while developing nations received far less attention. The developing countries have modest cybersecurity efficiencies and limited ability to respond to cyberattacks, still they have to deal with these attacks to secure their critical financial infrastructure (Lagazio, Sherif, and Cushman, 2014; Catota, Morgan, and Sicker, 2018; Kesharwani, et al., 2019). However, NIST regulatory framework (discussed in section) introduced by U.S. government can serve as an example of improving service quality regulatory framework in developing countries (Thach, et al., 2021). Teoh, Mahmood, and Dzazali (2017) further supports it saying that NIST is technology neutral framework - including industry best practices and standards, which can even be used for critical national infrastructure development.

Thus, it can be concluded that regulatory framework is another factor which can contribute to prevent cyberthreats in banking industry.

Next section

Several other related social theories have been of vital importance to build the better understanding of the research problems and their solution. Hence, the above factors will now be discussed in the light of multiple theoretical logics, with aim to highlight how these

theories create logics for the factors (challenges) and actors of this study to make their actions for effective cybersecurity governance.

3.7. Theoretical Logics

The concept of employee's awareness about cybersecurity is related to the TAM model and is also confirmed by deterrence theory. However, expanding this view this section specifically discussed TAM model in reference to awareness of cybersecurity to customers, public, employees, and executives. The TAM model suggests the awareness while the deterrence model suggest the strict law and its implication, and comprehensive regulatory framework with effective check and balance, as a tool for cybersecurity governance. The 'three lines of defence model' pursue the use of up to-date cybersecurity training for directors thus confirms executives' training as a challenge for cybersecurity governance. Furthermore, CSR theory highlights that based on stakeholders' expectations it is banks' responsibility to ensure cybersecurity of its information system by planning strategically. This will develop cybersecurity culture and will support cybersecurity governance of banks. Finally, the motivation theories are discussed which resulted in the development of a 'performance motivation cycle' for employee motivation and training.

3.7.1. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The technology acceptance model is based on the concept of the Theory of Reasoned Action about beliefs, attitude, intention, and behaviour to highlight the chances of user acceptance of an information system. The Theory of Reasoned Action is a social psychological model which explains the key factors towards the intentional behaviour of people (Seuwou, Banissi, & Ubakanma, 2016). According to this model, peoples' behaviour towards specific performance is determined by their behavioural intention to conduct the behaviour. That behavioural intention is specified by different factors which include their attitude and subjective norms (Kang, Choi & Kim, 2021).

The human factor (customers and employees) is known to be weakest link for information security. If users will not accept or use the security measures and systems, the organisation cannot make effective use of that technology (Wang, 2010). An employee

may be found to be the perpetrator of the cybercrime instead of an external hacker. However, whether the customer or employee, if either does not use the technology measures appropriately then cybersecurity is impossible (Lai, 2017).

Following this perspective, the technology acceptance model identifies that greater the accepting users of a new technology will be, the greater will be willing to implement proposed change in their practise and, they will make efforts to ensure the new changes are successful (Boot, 2016). Also, this model suggests the employees as a basic threat to cybersecurity of business. Implementing this model for an information security system, it is necessary for banks to introduce a technology which is easy to use by all users whether employees or customers. Also, the banks should clearly convey (aware) the importance of using that technology measure for cybersecurity. This is called ease of use and usefulness awareness (Josefsson, 2017).

This is also proved from an empirical study conducted by Lai (2017) to study 'consumers intention to use a single platform E-payment' using a TAM model. The results of this study show that awareness in terms of - security of the technology, perceived usefulness, and ease of use, significantly affect the customers' behaviour to use the suggested technology. Also, another recent study by Afshan et al. (2018) on 'internet banking' used TAM with the integration of several risk dimensions and initial trust model to predict behavioural intention of banking users and employees. The results of their study show that people with more trust, structural assurance, and good knowledge of banking (awareness) are comfortable to use banking.

Following this perspective, it is deemed that the awareness of usefulness, ease of use and management support can be effective to develop the understanding about importance of cybersecurity and its governance. Subsequently, this concept of awareness and training can be implied to customers, public, employees, and executives as well (Figure 18). Henceforth, based on this view it can be proposed that the awareness to customers, public, employees, and executives can play important role in cybersecurity governance (Bruijn and Janssen, 2017; Afshan, et al., 2018; Khader, et al., 2021).

Figure 18: TAM Model and Cybersecurity Governance

Source: Author Developed

3.7.2. Three lines of defence model

This model involves the various parts of a business that need to own certain activities of risk management and be responsible for them, using first, second, and third lines of defence (Lehuedé, 2020). According to BDO (2021) businesses can achieve risk management effectiveness if the control and assurance functions of the three lines of defence model are carried out consistently. The model is based on the following three layers to manage cybersecurity risk as shown in Figure 19 (Luburić, 2017):

First line of defence — Operational management

These people work at operational level whereby each business unit implementing risk and control policies, as well as states the cyber risk they confront; and adopts risk controls and self-assessment for risk, fraud, crisis management and recovery (Lehuedé, 2020).

Second line of defence — Risk management function

The second line establishes a distinct independent function by considering cybersecurity control frameworks, defining major risk indicators as well as metrics, generates

assessments, and evaluates performance by checking the first line's effectiveness in alleviating cyber risks (Alijoyo, 2022). These people are senior management from different departments to give the first line credible challenge and convey their assessment to the board about cumulative risks at enterprise level, to be used in a risk management setting (Ho, 2018).

Third line of defence — Internal audit

This line is comprised of an internal auditor and can also include external auditors and regulators. They are all responsible to perform an independent objective assessment of organisation processes and controls throughout the above two lines of defence where the focus is on operational effectiveness and efficiency (BDO, 2021). This assessment verifies that the company's internal control framework is appropriate and facilitates checks about the competence of the controls implemented. This line normally reports directly to the board of directors or the audit committee (Am, Cahyaningtyas, & Sasanti, 2021).

Figure 19: Three lines of defence model

Source: Luburić (2017, p. 35)

The hierarchy in this model has some unclear and ambiguous functions (Bantleon et al., 2020). However, to overcome the challenges of this model a new three lines model was introduced by Institute of Internal Auditors (IIA) as shown below in Figure 20 (Eulerich, 2021):

Figure 20: The IIA's Three lines model

Eulerich (2021, p. 8)

The new model is suitable for all types and sizes of businesses. It starts with the principle of governance with the aim to create a purposeful management and monitoring structure as a base to effectively secure the company in the long term (Cro Forum, 2021). In this structure, the management and supervisory board of directors or audit committees must include high degree of integrity, appropriate governance as well as comprehensive transparency, and be recognised by stakeholders as reliable partners holding a high level of accountability (IIA, 2020; Holland & Floam, 2020). Clinton (2020) states that the governance is run by a board of directors and who can have a high degree of integrity and transparency in cybersecurity when they are fully involved and have up to date and appropriate knowledge. Therefore, based on the type of organisation, using this model

each business will have to define its governance structure whereby the board of directors are involved as the basic stakeholders of the business who are accountable for its performance. Hence, this model confirms the importance of executives'/directors' training for cybersecurity (Brasseur, 2020).

3.7.3. Cybersecurity a Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and Culture

Culture is considered an important part of any organisation however there is no unified definition of culture. Shein (2010) defines organisational culture as 'a pattern of shared basic assumptions followed by a group with purpose to solve its problems through external adaption and internal integration, which has proved successful to be adopted confidently and, therefore, to be taught to new members as the right method of to understanding , thinking, and feeling in relation to those problems' (Lehman, 2017). A recent study by Wileya, McCormac, and Calic (2019) in Australia using 508 survey questionnaire reveals that organisational culture and security culture are related with Information Security Awareness (ISA). However, security culture plays a vital role to mediate correlation between organisational culture and ISA. This indicates that organisations should place emphasise on security culture rather than organisational culture to improve information security awareness. On the other hand, Lee, Park, and Lee (2013) portray that CSR plays a major role in businesses to influence their employees' attitude towards their companies and behaviour, through strategic planning of cybersecurity. Furthermore, employees' understanding of CSR activities results in establishing their attachment with the organisation they work for. CSR creates a sense of pride for employees - when they feel that by complying with CSR they are contributing towards society positively (Slack et al., 2015). The results of a study by Kim and Han (2019), to find out whether the employees of a corporately socially responsible company better comply with Information Security Policies (ISO), reveal that strategically planned corporate social responsibility culture of the business affects employees' attention positively to comply with ISO. Employees tend to comply with ISO considering it a corporate social responsibility of their company, once they realise the benefits of compliance (comes from startegic planning- explained in section 2.6.2) and the cost of noncompliance. Hence, investing in cybersecurity is the corporate social responsibility of businesses to secure their customers' personal information by startegic palnning (Anand, Duley, & Gai, 2022). In this context, the following three theories are studied to further understand the responsibility of business towards their stakeholders (customers, employees and society).

3.7.3.1. Classical Theory of Milton Friedman (1970)

According to Lothian (2015) the renowned classical theory of Milton Friedman (1970) suggests that the basic responsibility of all businesses is to earn profit and make their owners wealthy. The perception of this theory is that the use of profit for social

(stakeholders') welfare is an illegal tax on business and is useless because involving in CSR activities will deviate business' attention from main objective of profitability and will result in lower efficiency (Kolstad, 2007).

3.7.3.2. Carroll's CSR Pyramid

According to Jariko et al. (2016) Carroll developed a new approach to CSR. His pyramid depicts that profitability is the main CSR for any business because without profits firms will be unable to invest in CSR activities. Therefore, legal, and ethical aspects of business come after profitability while an optional philanthropic requirement comes at the end. The theory became popular in management as it differentiates the philanthropy and ethical activities (Carroll, 2016).

This above two concepts of theory were once mostly accepted but now the world has changed, and people have become aware of their rights and businesses' responsibilities. This has also resulted to change the perception of business managers. Consequently, the following concept of CSR is more appreciated in our societies (Faryal, 2018).

3.7.3.3. Stakeholder theory of R. Edward Freeman (1984)

The stakeholder theory of R. Edward Freeman (1984) is a paramountly emerged theory in CSR (Phillips et al., 2019). Harrison and Wicks (2013) define stakeholders as the individuals who can or are affected by the actions of business for example owners, customers, suppliers, and employees etc. The concept of this theory is that the management must pay attention to the interests of all stakeholders equally. The reason is that caring for interest of different stakeholders causes the enhanced reputation of the business and ultimately the financial state of the business improves. This is supported by a study conducted by Waheed (2015) whereby a survey of Price Waterhouse Cooper shows that most of the CEOs throughout the world are engaged in to implement CSR to improve their business performance. And 47% of them agreed that the secret of their companys' success is implementation of CSR. This is also supported by Carufel (2017), Kim and Kim (2020). A most recent study by Jamshed et al. (2022) on 'critical analysis of cybercrimes also referred CSR theory highlighting that it is banks' and government

organisations' corporate social responsibility to provide information security to banking customers. Hence, the following Figure 21 shows that being influenced from stakeholders the businesses adopt CSR concept whereby they strategically plan (considering all factors discussed in section 2.6.2 – about strategic planning) for cybersecurity which results in developing cybersecurity culture and ultimately a successful cybersecurity governance.

Figure 21: CSR and Cybersecurity Governance

Source: Author Developed

3.7.4. Deterrence Theory (GDT) and Information Security Climate (ISC)

Understanding the importance of information security and securing it from external threats, organisations have found employees to be a primary issue (Hayward & Glendinning, 2010; Eling & Wirfs, 2019). This is because, even with the existence of technical, organisational, or any other factors if the employees' behaviour is not supported or they are not motivated to work then any cybersecurity system will not be effective (Wang, 2010). Consequently, firms have introduced compliance policies for their employees whereby they have applied deterrence theory to stop criminal activities of employees (Park et al., 2012). The idea behind deterrence theory is to discourage employees from performing unwanted actions. This theory provides the concept that criminal punishment is justified because it results to reduce or deter crimes (Lee, 2017). D'Arcy and Herath (2011) mention that it is the most widely used theory in information

systems (IS) security studies, especially regarding behavioural IS security research. Considering the rational point of view of human behaviours, this theory proposes that criminal behaviour can be controlled with the fear of sanctions that are certain, severe, and swift. Another study by Trang and Brendel (2019) on ‘meta-analysis of deterrence theory in information security policy compliance’ shows that managers use sanction mechanisms to deter employees from their deviant behaviour and to create an information security climate. This view is also supported by Ofori et al. (2020), and D’Arcy and Herath (2011). However, it is found that a deterrence approach is not always best, and the research has mixed evidence (Trang & Brendel, 2019; Lee, 2017; D’Arcy & Herath, 2011). Therefore, to deal with this issue a concept is explained in the following section about motivation theories.

However, the same concept of deterrence can be applied by government and regulatory authorities to prevent cybercriminals. Referring back to studies (Wang et al., 2021; Vitvitskiy, et al., 2021; Al-Badran, 2021; Mishra, et al., 2022; Rakha, 2023; Khan, et al., 2023) the strict law and its enforcement can demotivate cybercriminals to conduct illegal activities. Similarly, comprehensive and clear regulatory frameworks; and cohesive implementation of them can improve banks’ cybersecurity governance (Lagazio, Sherif, and Cushman, 2014; Catota, Morgan, and Sicker, 2018; Kesharwani, et al., 2019; Thach, et al., 2021), as mapped in the following Figure 22:

Figure 22: Deterrence Theory and Cybersecurity Governance

Source: Author Developed

3.7.5. Theories of Motivation

Since employees are found to be the most basic threat to business information security therefore it is necessary to emphasise how they can be motivated to work in best the interest of the business (Eling & Wirfs, 2019). There are various motivation theories of behaviour in the literature. However, most of them are categorised as either content or process theories. Content theories highlight “what”, while process theories consider “how” human behaviour can be changed or motivated. Content theories are considered to be the earliest theories of motivation. In the real-world environment, the content theories have played an important role in management practice and policy whereas academically they are less well accepted. The other name for content theories is “needs theories”. The following Figure 23 lists the most famous content and process theories.

Figure 23: Content and process theories

EPM (2018)

With the help of content theories, the theoretical model of behavioural/motivation factors is developed to find out the basic factors which can play a role in performance motivation based on these content theories. The “Cycle of Performance Motivation” has been

developed to help managers to motivate their employees effectively without any leaving room for mistakes.

3.7.5.1. Content Theories

Maslow's Hierarchy of Need

Performance in the workplace is a matter of motivation. Additionally, as per different studies employees are motivated by different factors (Tezcan et al., 2017). Those factors play a role in employee satisfaction which develops into motivation. Furthermore, this concept of motivation can be best described by Maslow's theory of motivation (1943, 1954) 'hierarchy of needs' (Figure 24). According to this theory employees are motivated towards their hierarchical needs (McLeod, 2016). This is proved through the findings of a research conducted by Graham and Balloun (1973) on the members of 37 different companies. Therefore, motivation has a psychological relationship with humans through which they can be convinced to do things in required ways (Faryal, 2018).

Figure 24: Maslow's theory of motivation

McLeod (2016)

The concept of Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory is that human satisfaction starts from basic needs— 'physiological needs' (food, water, warmth, and rest) and safety needs (security and safety)' towards self-actualization needs (Freitas et al., 2011). This means that only when one level of needs is met then the employees will be motivated to satisfy the next level of their needs. This represents that the needs continually change overtime. Therefore, it is important for managers to determine the level of needs for employees and then offer the relevant reward which will actually encourage them to perform to the required standard (Tezcan et al., 2017).

Herzberg's Two Factor Theory

Frederick Herzberg presented the concept that the two factors – 'motivators and hygiene' are compulsory for motivation of employees as discussed below (Alshmemri et al., 2017):

Motivators:

These factors include promotion, higher level of job offer, advancement and growth. If these factors exist, they will help to motivate employees to work hard.

Hygiene Factors:

These factors include better working environment and reward system etc. They do not motivate employees to work hard rather they will demotivate employees if do not exist.

Hence, Herzberg recommends that to motivate employees (Thant et al. 2021):

- Remove the factors at the workplace which result in poor job satisfaction and, promote salary and supervision which can decrease dissatisfaction.
- Boost employees' job satisfaction by making their job role interesting, facilitating them with challenging tasks and by making their job satisfactory through involving various functions.
- Empower employees giving them increased responsibility

McClelland's Three Needs Theory

This theory explains that all humans have three needs to a greater or lesser extent as listed below (Rybnicek et al., 2019):

- Need for achievements - People are motivated by making breaking records or there being available opportunities to be promoted.
- Need for affiliation - people are motivated by collaboration with others or feeling proud being part of a group.
- Need for power - people are motivated being in power and having high status.

McGregor's Theory X and Theory Y

Theory X - under this theory it is perceived that the employees are intrinsically lazy and unmotivated and are unwilling to work hard in case of an opportunity. Therefore, the management have to work hard and, continuously control and supervise employees (Prottas & Nummelin, 2018).

Theory Y - this theory assumes that the employees are ambitious towards their work. Therefore, the managers consider to facilitate employees with the right conditions so that they can perform to the standard set. Using this theory, the employers might (Keerthana et al., 2018):

- Consider job enlargement as a job satisfaction factor
- Use collaborative management style to make employees feel that they are important in decision making
- Set high targets for employees which can encourage

Alderfer's ERG Theory

This theory is similar to Maslow's hierarchy theory. It focuses on three needs (Acquah et al., 2021):

- Existence needs - for example food water and feeling safe.

- Relatedness need - positive collaboration with people.
- Growth need - An attractive job opportunity with many small growth opportunities and the prospect to learn new things day by day

The only difference between this theory and Maslow's theory is that according to this theory different needs can be met at the same time. Also, if a higher-level need is not met but the employee can still focus on continually meeting the lower-level needs.

Mayo's Motivation Theory

This theory is based on the view that job content (the tasks which make up the actual job) and social relations (the ease of interacting with peers) motivate employees more than pay and environmental factors. Mayo determined how well the group can perform under two factors (Muldoon et al., 2019):

1. Norms - the group focuses on positive or negative behaviour
2. Group cohesiveness - how good collaboration did members of group have

3.7.5.2. Process Theories

Adam's Equity Theory

This theory highlights that the employees are motivated if they believe that they are treated fairly relative to others at the workplace. According to this theory the employees can assess themselves in the following situations (Grayot, 2020):

- Comparing their experience within the current organisation
- Comparing their experience with their previous organisation
- Comparing them with others within the organisation
- Comparing themselves with others outside the organisation

Vroom's Expectancy Theory

According to this theory the behaviour is chosen to maximise one's pleasure and minimise one's pain. To motivate an employee the following factors must exist (Lloyd & Mertens, 2018):

- Expectancy - the surety that if employees make effort there is possibility to meet the targets
- Instrumentality - the opportunity of reward in exchange of meeting the target
- Valence - the interest of employee to value and get the reward

Taylor's Motivation Theory – Scientific Management

This is one of the first motivation theories. It can be broken down into two sections:

4. It explains how employees behave
5. It recommends how to maximise performance

Taylor believed that employees can only be motivated by money therefore they do not enjoy the work (Mustafa et al., 2020). Subsequently the employers must monitor employees all the time. However, he suggests the following principles to meet the goal (Dahlgaard-Park et al., 2018):

- Breakdown the job in manageable parts
- Describe each part efficiently
- Provide training to perform as expected
- Allocate piece rate pay to encourage employees to be productive

Bandura's self-efficacy theory of motivation

According to this theory the self-confidence of a person to perform a specific task motivates him. People with low self-confidence are unlikely to perform to the full potential. The following factors can help to determine self-efficacy for a target (Ugwuanyi et al., 2020):

Experience: experience in similar work will give confidence to do well

Vicarious experience: gain confidence by watching others performing the work

Social persuasion: encouragement from others gives confidence and vice versa

Physiological feedback: after performing a task the physiological action of your body will determine your self-confidence. The easier the reaction the higher the self-confidence you have.

Skinner's reinforcement theory of motivation

According to this theory there are four factors which motivate good and bad behaviour (Qi, 2019):

1. Positive reinforcement - giving reward and employees perform desired behaviour
2. Negative enforcement - rewarded employ to remove negative factors from work
3. Punishment - to stop the desired behaviour which can cause negative consequences
4. Extension - stopping learned behaviour

Locke's goal setting theory

According to Locke, if one's goals are set right, it will motivate and increase the productivity. The following factors make the goals right (Jeong et al., 2021):

- Clarity - a goal must be clear
- Challenge - a goal should be challenging but not too hard
- Commitment- the employees must be committed to achieve the goal
- Feedback - continuous feedback on performance is must otherwise the motivation will be lost over time
- Task complexity - a goal should not be too complicated

3.7.5.3. Theoretical Concept of behavioural/motivation factors for content theories

Table 3: Accumulated Factors of Content Theories

Source: Author Developed

The above concepts of motivation factors (Table 3) is created with the help of content theories discussed in the above section. This Table 3 shows the accumulated factors of motivation discussed in all those above theories of motivation. Furthermore, Table 3 demonstrates that all of the authors of those theories have pointed to the same factors for employee motivation. Based on this view, Table 3 is divided into seven basic categories. Each category has a combination of more than one factor where possible taken from discussed theories, as they fall in the same category. The first four categories represent the combination of similar motivators for employees, which are taken from above content theories. However, the author of the each of those theories has used a slightly different way of suggesting those same factors of motivation. Factor number 5 is slightly different as it highlights the de-motivators at a workplace which need to be removed. Factors number 6 and 7 point out something else to be considered at work while analysing performance and motivation, namely lazy and ambitious employees although it is usual that the management will be employing either theory X or Y at one time. However, this study recommends that the management must find out who are the

lazy and ambitious employees within the organisation and treat them accordingly instead of generalising either of the theories. Again, once the ambitious employees are found theory Y looks for motivators to motivate them. In short, it can be concluded that all of these theories are working around three basic factors “provide hygiene factors, categorise employees (lazy or ambitious), and apply the right motivator” to attain the required performance in organisations.

Hence, this process is a cycle of performance analysis (Figure 25) whereby the managers motivate their employees to obtain the target. It is the managers’ job to figure out the right motivator for the relevant employee.

Figure 25: Performance Motivation Cycle

Source: Author Developed

After the above detailed discussion on institutions/factors of cybercrime all over the world the following section will highlight the emerging cyberthreats specific to the banking industry.

3.8. Evolution of Computer Crime and Cybercrime alongside of Development of Computer Technology

In the 1960s, the usage of technology increased when an advanced transistor-based computer system was introduced. At that time, there were only physical damages to computers and stored information (Whiteside, 1978). Later in 1970s, the reduction in prices of computers allowed businesses and members of the general public to increase their use of computers (Kabay, 2008). Although the traditional computer damage crimes continued, a new form of illegal use of computers, data manipulation and manual to computer-based transactions - which resulted in multimillion-dollar computer related frauds – began to occur (Geneva, 2012). Thereafter in the 1980s, use of personal computers increased significantly which also increased the number of computer systems and prospective targets for criminals. The use of unauthorised copies of software and patents theft crime were found to be increasing during this period (Glynn, 1984). Also, the ability to spread a software within networks facilitated criminals to distribute malicious virus software.

Moving onwards to the 1990s, by this time there were a vast number of internet users and the discovery of the “WWW” interface brought new challenges. This discovery legally enabled the information accessible in one country to be obtainable globally - also in countries which had a high crime rate. Also, the speed of exchanging information increased (Granville, 2003). Hence, initially the computer crimes were based locally, while the internet enabled electronic crimes to convert into international crime (Geneva, 2012). During the first decade of the 21st century, the most critical ways of committing crimes were “phishing” and botnet attacks. Furthermore, the rapid growth of technology such as “voice-over-IP (VOIP)” communication and cloud computing, made it harder for law enforcement agencies to deal with and investigate the crime (Marco, 2012). This new technology enabled the criminals to automate attacks which increased the number of crimes (Jang-Jaccard & Nepal, 2014). Following are the types of cybercrimes.

3.8.1. Types of Cybercrime

To understand the literature on cybersecurity, it is important to understand different types of cybercrimes which are currently being used and are relevant to this study. According to Gordon and Ford (2006), the term cybercrime includes many kinds of criminal activities. Therefore, it is hard to categorise each type. Although, based on cybercrime conventions, the European Commission classified cybercrime into the following four categories (Phillips et al., 2022):

1. Confidentiality offences (includes integrity and accessing data as well as computer system)
2. Computer-related offences
3. Content-related offences
4. Copyright-related offences

Confidentiality, content-related, and copyright related offences are concerned with legal protection whereas the computer-related offences are concerned only with the method used to commit the crime.

3.8.2. Focus of this study: Confidentiality Offences - Integrity and Availability

The focus of this study is confidentiality offences as they deal with having unauthorised access to the personal data and stealing money. Implying legal protection, confidentiality offence also includes integrity and availability risk of data (Anwar, 2020). A confidentiality offence means the unauthorised access to data in a business, by third person, which is data breach. The integrity is concerned with the misuse of systems and data to conduct fraud. An availability offence is concerned with unavailability of private data of customers within a business on time when required, which causes disruptions (Gřivna & Drápal, 2018). These three offences have different impacts on targets. The confidentiality issue requires time to materialise, by damage to the reputation of the business and litigation

expenses. Such frauds cause financial losses and disruption hinders effective operation of business (Bouveret, 2018).

3.8.2.1. Types of Confidentiality Offences

According to Phillips et al. (2022) there are five types of confidentiality offence which are explained below. Using these pathways through the internet the cybercriminals try to access the confidential data for different purposes which become challenges as explained in the following section (2.4.).

3.8.2.1.1. Hackers and Hacking (Illegal access)

The main cybercriminals are hackers. However, the meaning of the term “hacker” has been modified over decades. The major activities of hackers are mostly seen as dark, evil, hidden and especially with intent to cause harm to society’s information systems (Sabillon et al., 2016). According to Geneva (2012), hacking is an unauthorised access to information through computers. Jain and Shrivastava (2014, p.77) define hacker as a term commonly applied to a "computer user who intends to gain unauthorised access to a computer system." The frequency of instances of this offence has increased with the increase in internet use. The most famous examples of hacking are against US National Aeronautics and NASA, US Air Force, Pentagon, Yahoo, Google, eBay, and the German Government (Australian Institute of Criminology, 2005).

In terms of frauds in banks, the hackers might try to gain unauthorised access to the customers’ confidential data either directly by hacking the personal devices of customers or by hacking a whole bank’s accounts or the entire banking system of an economy. The most recent example of hacking a whole banking system was in October 2018 when hackers accessed the data of almost all banks of Pakistan, staying outside Pakistan, and stole \$2.6 million (section 4.3.7).

3.8.2.1.1.1. Hacking Process/Methods

To hack a computer, the offender will breach the password of secure websites and remove password security on a computer (Kumar & Agarwal, 2018). While, the other activities relating to hacking include consciously facilitating with faulty hardware or software to gain unauthorised access to a computer, making fake websites by exaggerating their features to insist users to reveal their information, and installing hardware and software key loggers which copy the password of any device (Geneva, 2012).

3.8.2.1.1.2. Reason of Increase in Hacking

According to previous studies, the following three basic reasons of increase in hacking attacks are recognised in developing countries (Jamshed et al., 2022; Marco, 2012):

1. Insufficient and incomplete security system
2. Growth of software which help automate attacks
3. Increased number of personal computers as a target for hackers.

3.8.2.1.2. Illegal Data Acquisition (Espionage)

The importance of sensitive data and its accessibility via hacking promotes data espionage. This is similar to hacking, but the purpose of espionage is to access sensitive data especially at national level for example, foreign policy, defence, financial, technological, industrial, and commercial interests and sell it (Khali, 2020). Furthermore, this is a confidentiality offence. For this purpose, criminals use different techniques including virus protection software, social engineering (one way is phishing) and avoid protection software (Ablon, 2018).

The most famous example of data espionage is a case in the 1980s, where German hackers accessed US government secret data and sold it to other countries' agents (Geneva, 2012). In the case of banks, espionage can be used against both banks and their customers. Also, as it seems to be very high data breach technology as it can be

used at national level. A recent example of this is the cyberattack in 2018 in banks of Pakistan when the cyber criminals sold the credit and debit cards of customers on the darknet. This indicates that the customers and banks in Pakistan need to have advanced solutions to be secured (Zia UL Islam et al., 2019).

3.8.2.1.3. Illegal Data Interception

By unauthorised access, hackers can intercept communication between two users of the internet when weak internet service providers such as wireless provided by hotels, restaurants, bars etc. are used (Bande, 2018). This is a data confidentiality offence and data integrity issue whereby, if either the bank or the customer is sharing personal information using an unsecured internet connection then the hackers can easily intercept the communication and then read, alter, or delete it (Abdul Qadeer, 2020).

3.8.2.1.4. Data Interference

The data over internet is important for private users, businesses, and administrations. Lack of access to such information can cause devastating financial loss. The offenders can infringe the reliability of data and interfere the data by deleting, suppressing, or changing data (Jamshed et al., 2022). Data interference is another way of stealing or destroying data. This is a data availability issue. For this purpose, the hackers use malware software which is designed to gain unauthorised access to information and then either steal it or destroy it (Hafiz Ali et al., 2019). Further, malware is a very famous type of malicious software used by hackers and its types are explained in the following section (Namanya et al., 2018).

3.8.2.1.5. System Interference

Similar to data interference the computer system can also be interfered. Most businesses are connecting internet services with their production units to reap the benefit of access from anywhere. If attackers have access to such computers, this can cause financial loss to the business (Bande, 2018).

However, following the above-mentioned pathways the cyber criminals use one or more of the following techniques - based on their objective, to conduct confidentiality, integrity, and availability crimes, in relation to banks (Phillips et al., 2022).

3.9. Cybersecurity Threats

A recent study by Wang, Nnaji, and Jung (2020) conducted in Nigeria (a developing country) to find cybersecurity breaches, practices and capabilities reveals that viruses, worms, Trojan infections, spam mails, and hacking are found to be the most common threats used for sophisticated cybercrimes. Several studies (Brander, 2021; IBM, 2018; Liwong, 2018; Kavanagh 2021; Ozarlan 2022; Stanikzai & Shah, 2021; Wang et al., 2021) also mentioned other threats the banks are currently facing given below, along with the above-mentioned threats (Figure 26), followed by attackers' motivation.

Figure 26: Common Cyberthreats in Banks

Source: Author Developed

3.9.1. Social engineering

Social engineering is one of the major threats to information security. It refers to the activity of exploiting humans to obtain illegal access to sensitive information by social interface and digital device for example a computer (Dhillon, 2020; Ghauri, 2021). It is known as a practice of bad faith, whereby the scammers try to misuse peoples' greed, vanity, and positive beliefs (Terlizzi et al., 2017). Subsequently, social engineering is a practice to exploit the weakest link in the security chain of an organisation. This shows that the basic threat to a business are its employees, not the hackers (Orgill, et al., 2004; Allen, 2007; Terlizzi, et al., 2017). The 2018 Intelligent Index by IBM indicated that more than two thirds of compromised data cases were caused by phishing attacks due to employees. Further, it was found that social engineering is used to access the huge amount of personal data information held by the banks (IBM, 2018). According to Swaine (2022) in the UK during the first half of 2021, using social engineering cyber criminals stole £753.9 million, which was 30% more compared to the first half 2020. This shows an increasing trend of social engineering even in developed countries. However, following are the types of social engineering:

Vishing (Telephone fraud) - Telephone fraud is one of the most widespread methods of social engineering. It is a voice-based phishing attack using VIP (voice over IP) to gain financial details of banking customers through a fake call centre (Innab et al., 2018; Hijji and Alam, 2021; Woldemichael, 2019). Initially, the scammer asks the banking customer to verify his bank information through the link sent on email (Yaziz Bin et al., 2021). The successful social engineers use surveillance and lack of banking customers' knowledge to gain financial information from them (Hafiz Ali, Khan, Asghar, and Shuaib, 2019).

Smishing (Text message fraud) – For smishing the fraudster sends a text message to try and trap someone to share his/her personal information to steal money from bank (Swaine, 2022).

Phishing (Email fraud) - Phishing is an electronic tactic whereby people are contacted by someone using email (Ali, et al., 2017; Chaimaa, et al., 2021) portraying themselves

as a legitimate organisation, to trap the person to share his/her sensitive financial information, for example bank account details, credit card details and passwords (Munirul, et al., 2011; Ghauri, 2021).

3.9.2. Fake websites and online shopping

The use of a fake website is very common to steal personal information of users (hacking) if the user opens a fake website himself unintentionally or alternatively by clicking on a link either by email (phishing) or during online shopping or browsing, the users are directed towards a fake website where they are asked to enter their passwords (Salahdine & Kaabouch, 2019). During 2020, 745,000 fake websites were created globally with around 18,000 websites launched every day on average and hackers mostly used emails to get traffic on their websites (Parakash, 2020).

3.9.3. ATM skimming

ATM skimming is one of the major concerns relating to cyberattacks which requires a sustainable solution. There are two ways of ATM skimming. The first is to connect rain cover (a chip) with the card reader slot of ATM machine to steal the debit card or credit card details. The second method is to install a fake keypad to capture the pin codes entered by the user (Hattali, Hussain & Frank, 2020). According to Vasiliev (2021) during 2020 ATM skimming increased 35% globally.

3.9.4. Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS)

DDoS are cyberthreats which exhaust the resources to make them unavailable for the legitimate users thereby violating one of these security components availability. These attacks to the networks are increasing and are devastating (Namanya et al. 2018). During the Covid-19 pandemic in 2021 cybercriminals launched a staggering 5.4 million DDoS attacks from January to June 2021. It shows the increasing trend of DDoS attacks. It is also reported that the finance industry was which received the largest number of DDoS attacks (Hummel, 2021).

3.9.5. Deepfake Attacks

The deepfake is an upcoming crucial cyberthreat for banks. As discussed earlier, with the day-by-day technological advancement, the cybercriminals are also adopting the latest technologies to make cyberattacks more sophisticated and difficult to defend against. For example, the new malicious technology to defraud has been introduced by cyber devils (cybercriminals) called “deepfake” (Kumire, 2020). The word deepfake consists of two separate words “deep” means deep learning and “fake” refers to machine learning and artificial intelligence to manipulate voice or video content with the purpose to deceive people (Mirsky & Lee, 2020).

According to Stone (2019), Symantec (cybersecurity leader in industry for last the 10 years) already reported three successful audio “deepfake” attacks on private firms. These attacks imitated a voice call from the CEO to the CFO directing an immediate transfer of a large amount of money. Artificial intelligence attacks could also enable the hackers to hack the banks’ core systems more quickly and disguise their target more credibly, so that eventually the banks will be unaware of the reality that they have been compromised (Kumire, 2020). Hence, it is understood that we are in the era where hackers can access their target anywhere in the world when they want. This makes businesses (especially those which own a large amount of money and personal information of customers), to focus on making cybersecurity stronger as well as airtight, and the banks are one of such businesses.

3.9.6. Malware

Namanya et al. (2018) define malware as “any code added, changed or removed from a software system in order to intentionally cause harm or subvert the intended function of the system”. The malware can harm information and money (Chaimaa, et al., 2021). A report of data collected from observed network traffic of more than 200 million devices globally shows that malware attacks are increasing, and the new banking Trojans are trying to steal messages containing one-time passwords (Sadiq, 2019). Moreover, those Trojans can capture keystrokes whereby the overlying bank login screen will be changed

to the cybercriminal's login screen, taking screen snapshots, and getting Google Authenticator codes (Alenezi, Alabdulrazzaq, Alshaher, and Alkharang, 2020; HNS, 2021). The most repeated types of malwares in banking sector are discussed below.

Virus

A virus is designed to copy itself and spread from one file to another file by sitting in one of the basic executable files. Once the user opens and uses this file the virus will start spreading and will damage the whole system (Gupta, 2013).

Worm

This is a standalone malicious software which damages other computers but without the need of any user activity meaning it doesn't spread through files rather it spreads from one computer to another computer (Guo et al., 2016; Alenezi, et al., 2020).

Trojan horse

This is a malware program which looks like genuine software to persuade the user to download it. Once the user downloads it the hackers can use this software to spy, steal or damage the data (Gupta, 2013; Alenezi, et al., 2020).

Spyware

Spyware is a programme that secretly monitors infected systems and gathers data relating to a person or an organisation without their consent and awareness (Namanya et al., 2018; Lysenko, Bobrovnikova, Popov, Kharchenko, and Medzaty, 2020).

Ransomware

This is a malware which is used to take hostage of users' system, files, or data to encrypt them and leave a message that a certain ransom has to be paid to gain the decryption key (Namanya et al., 2018). A recent survey of 5,600 IT professionals in mid-sized organisations of 31 countries, conducted by Sophos commissioned research agency

shows that in 2020 ransomware attacks were 37% of total cyberattacks in those companies which increased to 66% by 2021 (Sophos, 2022). While, Henriquez (2021) highlights that the banking industry all over the world was disproportionately affected by experiencing a 1,318% increase in ransomware attacks by the first half of 2021. This shows that the cyber criminals have become considerably more capable of conducting more significant attacks at larger scale (Alenezi, et al., 2020; Sophos, 2022).

Crypto ransomware

This is a type of ransomware which is used to encrypt the users' files and then threaten them with deletion of those files if they do not pay the ransom (Shah & Farik, 2017).

Doxware

Doxware is a type of crypto ransomware which cyber criminals use to threaten the data user that the criminal will make his or her data public if the ransom is not paid (Zucker-Scharff, 2019).

3.10. Attacker Motivation

There is a huge amount of literature available discussing the presence of cyberattacks on financial institutions but there is also a need to discuss what motivates attackers to commit cybercrime (Hafiz Ali et al., 2019). It is a fact that discussing the attackers' motivation here will not affect the results of this study, but it can help to understand the reasons why the financial institutions are the target of hackers as financial institutions can be careful about it if they know the reason why they could be attacked (Zia UL Islam et al., 2019). Therefore, this section will discuss those possible motivations as per the available literature.

Money

According to IBM (2020) money is the basic motivation for hackers to attack financial institutions. The cybercriminals who are expert in using and innovating the technology use their expertise to become rich overnight. This kind of attack targets any financial

institution most probably those which have more money and the ones which have weak cybersecurity.

Revenge

Technology experts can use their expertise to take revenge which may be another reason for cyber criminals to commit cybercrime against a financial institution. A hacker can use his expertise to destroy a business by stealing its money, but this is not usually the case. This kind of attack targets only specific institutions (Chng et al., 2022).

Use of expertise

There is no doubt that hacking or inventing the latest technology, which can hack systems and can cause the financial loss to businesses, requires a mastermind behind it (IBM, 2020). Some technologically expert individuals feel proud that they can hack or cause financial loss to a business by their hacking. This kind of attack targets any institution, but most probably the one with the availability of a high amount of money and with good cybersecurity. The reason for this is that higher the loss and breach of high-level cybersecurity, the higher the satisfaction and pride for the hacker. Such attacks are rare but usually cause considerable losses (Owen & Head, 2022).

However, having these motivations, cybercriminals cannot succeed alone, unless some factors/institutions assist them as discussed in section 2.6. The following section will elaborate the most famous international cybersecurity frameworks for banks.

3.11. Cybersecurity Frameworks

The two most famous cybersecurity frameworks are NIST and ISO/IEC 27001 - information security management system, as discussed below. Using these two frameworks, businesses can assess the majority of their cybersecurity practices. Consequently, an action plan can be developed to remove weaknesses in information security system (Imprivata, 2021).

3.11.1. NIST cybersecurity frameworks

Force (2020, p. 2) defines cybersecurity frameworks as,

A catalogue of security and privacy controls for information systems and organisations to protect organisational operations and assets, individuals, other organisations, and the nation from a diverse set of threats and risks, including hostile attacks, human errors, natural disasters, structural failures, foreign intelligence entities, and privacy risks.

NIST stands for the 'National Institute of Standards and Technology' at U.S. the Department of Commerce. Working to secure national companies from cyberattacks it has introduced a cybersecurity framework in 2013 which was mainly designed for the companies that are part of U.S. critical infrastructure (Goldstein, 2019). This is a voluntary framework but because of its acceptability and applicability for all size and type of organisations this framework is now being used by private and public organisations in many countries (Hughes, 2022). Furthermore, this framework assists all type of businesses to clearly understand, manage, and reduce their cybersecurity risk, with purpose to protect their networks and data (Vigliarolo, 2021). To fulfil this objective, NIST has introduced a thorough and adaptable catalogue of security and privacy controls which can meet the present and future security needs of business considering dynamic threats, vulnerabilities, requirements, and technologies (Imprivata, 2021).

Force (2020, p. 2) defines security controls and privacy controls as,

“Security controls are the safeguards or countermeasures employed within a system or an organisation to protect the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of the system and its information and to manage information security risk.”

“Privacy controls are the administrative, technical, and physical safeguards employed within a system or an organisation to manage privacy risks and to ensure compliance with applicable privacy requirements.”

Figure 27 shows the list of security and privacy control types which are divided by NIST into 20 “families” for ease of use:

Figure 27: Security and Privacy Control Families

Force (2020, p. 8)

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3.11.2. ISO/IEC 27001 – Information Security Management System

It is an international standard which was introduced in 2005 by joint work of International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO) and International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) and then revised in 2013. This standard introduced best practices for an information security management system. The ISO standards will improve organisations' IT security management for example financial information, intellectual property, employees' personal data, or third parties' data (ISO, 2019). The ISO organisation is based in Switzerland. The latest version of ISO 27001 was introduced in September 2013. The most important role of ISO 27001 is that it explains the way an organisation can build its information security management system (Clay & Hogan, 2021). However, by its implementation the organisations will be required to standardise their information security rules, responsibilities, and controls to enable organisations to effectively manage their complicated systems and any security threat that arises from them. It is the most popular standard for information security and the third most widespread ISO certification (Ganji et al., 2019). Moreover, this standard is applicable to all type of organisations regardless of their size and nature. Many organisations which considered cybersecurity seriously have required their business partners to be ISO/IEC 27001 certified. For example, many famous technological providers including apple internet services, Amazon Web Services, GE digital, various Microsoft business units, as well as Facebook's workplace have been providing ISO certification to Netflix for post-production and widespread publicity (Culot et al., 2021).

Additionally, based on guideline provided in ISO/IEC 27035-2:2016 named as 'Information technology - Security techniques - Information security incident management - part 2: Guidelines to plan and prepare for incident response' many medium sized and large businesses are using information security governance and control framework which is discussed below.

3.11.2.1. Information Security Governance and Control System

The information security system has become the number one priority of Chief Information Officers' (CIO's) of all businesses, because of the breaches and vulnerabilities as discussed in earlier sections (Whitman & Mattord, 2021). The CEO, board of directors and mainly the CIOs of every business must evaluate and critique annually their information safety strategies as well as incident repossession competences and be up to date with the best practices (Hafiz-Ali et al., 2019).

For this purpose, many government agencies and private industries have developed the cybersecurity frameworks. The names of some most famous frameworks are listed in the following Table 4 (Azmi Tibben, & Win, 2018):

Table 4: Famous cybersecurity frameworks

Azmi et al. (2018)

However, according to McLaughlin and Gogan (2018) based on ISO/IEC 27035:2011 information security governance and control consist of a cycle of five interrelated activities as shown in Figure 28 below. Following is the explanation of how this cycle works and which challenges it can encounter.

Figure 28: Cycle of Five Interrelated Information Security Tasks and Controls

McLaughlin and Gogan (2018, p240).

i) Prepare

The first step in this cycle is preparation. The businesses prepare themselves for information security attacks by learning about the inspirations and behaviours of attackers, measuring risks, developing strategies and procedures, creating effective response teams, conducting periodic test exercises, arranging post-incident conferences, and assembling important modifications into information security policies and procedures (Mahn, 2018).

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ii) Prevent

After preparing for information security attacks, the second step for each business will be attempting to prevent such attacks. Organisations try to avoid information security attacks by using different tools, designing policies for suitable use, and arranging education trainings to encourage employees as well as various other users to follow safer behaviours instance, setting up strong passwords and always complying with set policies and procedures (ISO, 2016).

iii) Detect

If any incident happens, even after prevention, the organisations must be able to notice rapidly and accurately, and investigate the potential information security attack, before it causes any damage to the business. Computerised interruption detection systems as well as manual reporting processes, support to notice irregularities in the information security system (McLaughlin & Gogan, 2018).

iv) Response

After detecting, the organisation's response to a feasible information security attack, must be activated by the exposure of indications that point to a breach. To minimise the impairment to business operations, employees, customers, and business partners, from the instant aftermath of an attack, the trained respondents, managers, and other employees should be well-aware of what actions they should take and what they should not do (Tøndel et al., 2014).

V) Learn

Once the incident is resolved, the business response team and other significant stakeholders should take part in post-incident interrogation exercises. This is to learn by sharing their lessons, deliberating on how to develop more secure systems and procedures and, also considering how they can respond more effectively in case of the next incident (Mahn, 2018).

3.12. Cybersecurity Solutions in Banks - Provided by Third Parties

To deal with the increasing trend of cybercrime some intelligence-driven methods have been introduced by private information security providers for example BAAS and cloud storage, open APIs, open banking (Iyer, Karthikeyan, Khan, & Binu, 2020). However, the experts have also introduced techniques to fend off deepfake attacks and Multi Factor Authentication (MFA) is an international method to prevent cybercrime as discussed below.

3.12.1. BAAS and Cloud Storage

BAAS is an end-to-end process, ensuring the overall secure completion of the financial transaction. The BAAS service enables banks to pay attention onto optimising the front-end customer experience, without replacing the pipes that deliver core banking services (Moneythor, 2020). This significantly minimises the risk of disruption of the bank's operations, lessens the cost of digitising the whole present infrastructure and enables banks to provide a better service and customer experience in a very shorter duration than upgrading or designing, building, and implementing a new platform (BAAS, 2020).

Apparently, BAAS seems similar to open banking. This is because both technologies facilitate the users to access a financial institution's platform (Moneythor, 2020). The basic difference between BAAS and open banking is that open banking facilitates third parties to access the information of existing bank customers while, BAAS allows third parties to access the bank's functionality which enables non-banking companies to connect their customers to their own banking facilities without the use of existing banks footprints (Ochoa et al., 2020). For example, open banking enables service providers such as "Mint" to get access to their customers' banking data and analyse it to provide the best services while, the BAAS enables a provider such as technology company "Simple", to develop its own distinctive services for its customers using its own brand, supported by the banks existing infrastructure and expertise (Anderson, 2019).

On the other hand, the following trend in some non-financial firms such as tech giants, banks are also considering adopting cloud strategies especially for the purpose of data

storage. This is because, the cloud has been considered to be more secure than firms' own legacy systems. While, to address the cloud storage threat, many firms are trying to incorporate security as a service into their systems which could enable flexibility and scalability (Kumire, 2020).

3.12.2. Open APIs (Application Programming Interfaces)

As its name implies, the function of APIs is exchange of information between systems although, open APIs are publicly available interfaces which enable businesses to access the data being shared or other functionalities. In open banking, using open 'APIs the third parties can have authorised (by customer) access to the data of a financial institution's customer, or to that institution's service offerings and their functionality (Premchand & Choudhry, 2018). Hence the use of open APIs enables customers to gain better control over their personal data and allow third parties to provide value added services for the customers (IBM, 2020). For example, a company called "Mint" whose basic work is to manage personal finance, is mainly dependent on access to bank data using open APIs, to create new and valuable services for customers by which the company can visualise and understand the customers' financial information. This kind of business is not possible without open banking and open APIs (Anderson, 2019). But, again the providers of an API service have to use a high level of security.

3.12.3. Open Banking

Open banking is a system that facilitates a user with a network of financial institutions information through APIs. With the help of open APIs' sharings, third parties can have easy access to financial information. This enables them to develop innovative applications and services for their customers (Open Banking, 2021). For example, the open banking standard rules in the UK enables customers to have secure access to their financial data easily, with the functionality that they can manage their wealth and use banking services more simply than before (Voas et al., 2022). Moreover, the UK's open banking standards also allow developers the flexibility so that they can create new services and applications for banking customers to manage their finances. In the European Union, this open

banking regulatory system is known as PSD2. In the US, there is no regulatory initiative for open banking standards (Premchand & Choudhry, 2018).

However, as all these solutions are provided by third parties if their system is not secure it will make banks vulnerable (Pratt, 2021).

3.12.4. Fend Off Deepfake Attacks

Deepfake audio attacks need to be supported via emails or texts. However, as such technologies keep updating with advancement and become harder to detect, it will be compulsory to develop anti-deepfake protocols, which may consist of various checks and verifications (Stone, 2019). Another way of dealing with such attacks is to train employees for similar attacks, to not proceed with audio or email instructions only. It is essential for firms to increase their security by making sure that their employees learn the code words (language cybercriminals use) and comprehend cutting-edge social engineering methods although, awareness is not the only solution (Okwero, 2020).

Additional to deepfake protocols, Multi Factor Authentication (MFA) can be used throughout the whole firm environment. This is because deepfake attacks are often joint with other social engineering techniques that can be prevented or mitigated using solid identity and access management (IAM) methods (Banyal, Jain, & Jain, 2013).

3.12.5. Multi Factor Authentication (MFA)

As digitalisation decisively penetrates everywhere in society, the authentication through this digitalisation process is one of the key sources of securing it. This digitalisation process includes various areas of the hyper-connected world which consists of online payments, communications, and access to the information of the higher management etc. Specifically, multi factor authentication is supposed to be used by human for every interaction, enabling fast, user-friendly, and reliable authentication using a service (Ometov et al., 2018).

1. Originally, single factor authentication was used mostly because it was simple to use and user friendly. For example, the use of a password or pin to gain access to the user ID is called single factor authentication (Kim & Hong, 2011). However, this proved to be the weakest level of authentication as by sharing the password, the security of an account can be compromised immediately. Furthermore, by using social engineering (Heartfield & Loukas, 2016) methods an unauthorised user can easily gain access to sensitive information. Usually, the users who consider single factor authentication method user friendly as well as easy and still want to use it, they need to consider the minimum password complexity requirement to make this method reliable (Ometov et al., 2018). It is now realised that single factor authentication is not a reliable and adequate source of protection for highly sensitive data, the loss of which could be devastating. Therefore, the two-factor authentication was introduced (Gunson, Marshall, Morton, & Jack, 2011). Using this method, the representative data like username or password is combined with the personal ownership factor which can be smart card or a phone (Bruun, Jensen, & Kristensen, 2014). Since the two-factor authentication has also not been proven very secure, multi factor authentication was introduced. Using multi factor authentication three types of factor groups are used to connect the right individual with the required information. The following are groups of factors (Harini & Padmanabhan, 2013):

2. Knowledge factor - password or a secret answers to a question
3. Ownership factor – cards, smart phones, or other possessions, and one time password etc.
4. Biometric factor - biometric data or behaviour pattern

Using multi factor authentication a higher level of safety and continuous protection to the devices and other critical services can be provided against unauthorised access using any of the two group factors. The most important part of multi factor authentication is based on biometrics factor, whereby an individual is recognised based on their behavioural and biological features. This step further has improved the security because, the users have to provide evidence of their identity which is confirmed using two or more different factors (Banyal, Jain, & Jain, 2013). The following Figure 29 shows the discussed authentication methods:

Figure 29: From SFA to MFA methods' revolution

Ometov et al. (2018)

Nowadays, multi factor authorization is expected to be used in situations where safety requirements are higher than normal for example, a daily ATM cash withdrawals where the users of the ATM machine have to provide the card and enter the right pin code to withdraw the money.

3.13. Summary of Chapter Three

This chapter has developed an outline of theoretical understanding of the factors/institutions/challenges which affect the cybersecurity governance of banks by facilitating the cybersecurity threats. The chapter builds the grounds of institutions and their actors in society to change or create certain actions. Espousing the deep insights of e-banking and its adoption based on customers' risk perception, this chapter concludes that internally the *strategic planning* is of major concern as it encourages to comply with regulatory requirements of investing in cybersecurity governance (Hafiz-Ali, et al., 2019; Al-Alawi and Al-Bassam, 2021). However, employees are proposed to be the major factors as a human factor (Wang, et al., 2020; Maalem Lahcen et al., 2020). Therefore, a theoretical performance motivation cycle is developed to tackle the effects of this factor. On the other hand, the literature suggests that externally *cybersecurity law and its enforcement, regulatory framework and customer awareness* can be the main factors of cybersecurity governance (Alzubaidi, 2021; Etomilade-Oduola, 2020; Vitvitskiy, et al., 2021; Ezu, et al., 2020). Moreover, the empirical studies illustrate that social engineering is most common cyberthreat in banking sector resulting from unawareness (Ghauri, 2021). Likewise, ATM skimming is also increasing due to unawareness. Nevertheless, the MFA can be useful to prevent this cyberthreat (Ometov et al., 2018). Comparatively, the Malware and DDoS attacks are also common in developing countries' banks while the Deepfake is a new threat which is even easier to cheat people using fake video imitation (Mirsky & Lee, 2020). Furthermore, besides the institutional logics, the empirical studies illustrated the supportive measures for cybersecurity improvement such as adoption of international regulatory frameworks, theoretical solutions, and third-party solutions. Thus, this chapter indulges to explore that which cybersecurity threats the targeted banks (private commercial banks) in Pakistan are facing and which factors/institutions are supporting those threats to occur. Reviewing it, the results can be compared with available literature as well as theoretical solutions and the suitable recommendations can be provided. Following this perspective, the researcher carries out this study. For this purpose, the following conceptual framework is developed based on the above literature.

CHAPTER FOUR: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

4.1. Introduction

According to Van der Waldt (2020, p. 1) conceptual frameworks is ‘the key part of a research project as well as a key success factor in the approval of research manuscripts.’ Various academic scholars such as Miles and Huberman (1994), Jacard and Jacoby (2010) and Ravitch and Riggan (2017) defined conceptual framework as a visual presentation of key theoretical concepts and factors of the study. Such a framework forms a shape of graphical or schematic diagram illustrating the core concepts and their relationships. Maree (2012) argued that conceptual framework is not only graphical presentation of ideas rather it is also presented in narrative forms. In this regard, Ravitch and Riggan (2017, p.10) defined conceptual framework as:

The identification of presumed relationships among key factors or constructs to be studied, and the justification for these presumptions may come from multiple sources such as one’s own prior research or ‘tentative theories’ as well as established theoretical or empirical work found in the literature.

Thus, conceptual framework is a best tool to justify the natural progression of the phenomenon under research (Camp, 2001). It creates links of concepts used in advancing and systematising the knowledge empirically generated by the previous researchers (Peshkin, 1993). Therefore, it helps researchers to explain how the research problem will be answered. It is an integrated method of studying a research problem (Maxwell, 2013) that informs the whole research design (Liehr and Smith, 2009). Luse, Mennecke, and Townsend (2012) state that conceptual framework facilitates the researcher to specify and define key factors of study under the context of the research problem. Therefore, for this thesis a conceptual framework is mapping the key concepts that relate with each other, underpinning the study (Dixon, Gulliver, Gibbon, and Hall, 2001).

Simultaneously, the conceptual framework also influences ontological, epistemological, and methodological concepts of the research. The ontological view is generated based

on previous research which indicates what is the nature of reality. The epistemological assumption highlights how reality about things has been assumed in previous studies. Finally, the methodological assumption depicts that how the conceptual framework will be tested (Jabareen, 2009). Moreover, critically examining the literature reviewed, the conceptual framework helps to design the essential research questions to represent the research problem. Therefore, it is deemed that the practical (methodology and data collection) part of the research depends on the conceptual framework (Luse, et al., 2012). In this effort, the following section will formulate the research questions of this study.

4.2. Research questions development

The main research question of this study is '*What are the key factors influencing effective cybersecurity governance in private commercial banks of Pakistan?*'. Followed by it, the literature reviewed supported the development of the following sub-questions of this study.

Social behaviour institutional logics and cybersecurity

The social behaviour concept illustrates that the usefulness of information technology for cybersecurity in businesses remains a challenge due to the social behaviour of society (Joinson and Steen, 2018). According to () under the context of social behaviour and institutional theory the society consists of the government, regulatory authorities, and businesses. Consequently, the researchers diverted their attention from technological solutions to social behaviour and institutional theory to determine, justify, control, and predict cybersecurity issues (Björck, 2004; Maalem-Lahcen, et al., 2020). The institutional theory can provide useful insights, into cybersecurity solutions under the context of social behaviour, as an extension of open systems theory whereby the actions and their consequences can be predicted emphasising the importance of environment - affecting organisational performance (Singh and Alshammari, 2020; Vuko, et al., 2021). Several attempts have proved the systematic application of institutional theory to information systems security confirming its natural progression towards its application to investigate cybersecurity research problems (Kowalski, 1994; Yngström, 1996; Magnusson, 1999;

Teo et al., 2003; Currie, 2009; AlKalbani, et al., 2017). A cognitive social behaviour is caused by specific criteria and logic. Therefore, the basic concept of institutional theory is to manage social behaviour to provide cybersecurity solutions. However, the most accepted definition of institutions is given by North (1990, p. 3) as, 'Institutions are the rules of the game of a society, or, more formally, are the humanly devised constraints that structure human interaction. In consequence they structure incentives in human exchange, whether political, social, or economic'. Hodgson (2017) defined institutions as social structures highly appreciated in a society and consist of cultural-cognitive, normative, and regulatory aspects. According to Hodgson (2019) institutions spread through different carriers for example symbolic systems rational systems social routines and actions etc. On the other hand, Scott (2004) defined institutions as functions of different jurisdictional level such as worldwide organisational systems to interpersonal relationships. Scott (2004) emphasised that institutions bring stability simultaneously, they can influence to change the practices (Alvesson and Spicer, 2019; Glynn and D'Aunno, 2023). Subsequently, for this thesis the institutions are the formal and informal systems of established and socially accepted norms, functional at various levels of jurisdiction, adopted through multiple carriers and can influence the actions and processes. Precisely, institutions can be considered as tools, supporting to solve the predetermined problem; or as a challenge (in case they are weak) facilitating the issues (cybercriminals, Kshetri, 2005). Therefore, this study will consider institutions as factors-challenges of this thesis which can facilitate the effective cybersecurity governance in PCBP.

Concurrently, the literature has asserted to understand the role of actors in institutional concepts to understand how these institutions are managed by intentional behaviour of these actors (Hwang, Colyvas, and Drori, 2019; Maier and Simsa, 2021). According to North (1990) organisations (political organizations, economic bodies, social firms, and educational sector) are the actors who develop, maintain, and change the institutions to achieve a certain goal. A number of studies have viewed information security systems in lens of; one of the isomorphic change out of memetic, normative, and coercive – based on DiMaggio and Powell (1983) institutional isomorphism (Barton, et al., 2016; Jeyaraj

and Zadeh, 2020); and in lens of regulatory, normative, and cognitive isomorphism - following the perspectives of Meyer and Rowan (1991) and North (1990). Though, the researchers have shifted their attention to study social behaviour under the context of institutional logics as an advanced form of institutional theory (Ocasio, et al., 2017; Gümüşay, et al., 2020).

The institutional logics is a metatheory of institutions that not only considers the homogeneity within the actions of different actors in a society rather it also emphasises on heterogeneity of those actions, that was not focus of institutional theory (Thornton, et al., 2013; Friedland, 2018). Therefore, it focuses on the collective aspects of structural, normative, and symbolic institutions, instead of treating them separate carriers of institutions - as suggested by institutional theory. This approach of institutional logics suggests that the collective utilisation of these institutional logics can provide useful insights into the social behaviours of different actors and their impact on organisational cybersecurity (Christou, 2014; Forslund, 2020). Implying this theory, it becomes imperative to investigate which institutions (challenges) affected the cybersecurity of private commercial banks in Pakistan. In this respect the following research questions can be developed from the literature reviewed.

E-banking and Cybersecurity Governance

E-banking is the need of century and to be successful the banks have to provide innovative and efficient banking services to their customers to attain the competitive advantage (Marafon, et al., 2018; Anouze and Alamro, 2019; Ahmad, et al., 2020). Based on the multiple definitions studied in this thesis (Pyun, et al., 2002; Kricks, 2009; Chaimaa, et al., 2021; Okolie and Eze, 2023), the broader understanding of e-banking incorporates utilisation of banking services with non-physical appearance, using intelligent devices connected with the internet. Such as, online banking, online shopping, mobile banking, ATM, debit, and credit cards etc. (Al-Badran, 2021). E-banking facilitates customers with ease of life and increases banking efficiency and profitability. However, it also brings the challenges and threats relating to information security (Chaimaa, et al., 2021). This promotes customer risk perception and creates negative behaviour towards adoption of

e-banking services (Marafon, et al., 2018; Anouze and Alamro, 2019; Ahmad, et al., 2020; Kaur and Sharma, 2022; Venkatesh, 2023). The literature suggests that there are multiple factors (challenges) promoting cyberthreats as well as cybercrime in banks and affecting their cybersecurity governance (Naik Bukht, et al., 2020; Dhillon, 2020). Conceptualising various definitions of cybersecurity governance under this thesis, the cybersecurity governance can be defined as an ability of the organisation to meet its goals and objectives, mitigating risks providing protection to ensure resilience by establishing policies, procedures ,and processes to make strategic decisions aligned with corporate governance (Kooper, et al., 2011; Tan et al., 2017; Taherdoost, 2022; Malatji, et al., 2022; Shaikh and Siponen, 2023; Vesić and Bjelajac, 2023; Melaku, 2023). This constitutes that cybersecurity governance is an integral and important part of banking information system. Therefore, it is imperative to investigate the factors (challenges) fostering the cybercrime in banks.

Institutional Logics and Factors Affecting Cybersecurity Governance

The institutional logics purpose that the social behaviour of organisations can be studied using three collective concepts; structural normative and cultural cognitive (Christou, 2014; Forslund, 2020). Following this perception, the literature builds that there are internal to banks and external challenges (factors) impacting the cybersecurity governance of banks, as discussed below.

Internal factors (challenges):

The main internal challenge for banks is strategic planning which incorporates sub-factors creating sub-themes of this study.

1. Strategic planning

It is a method of formulating, executing, and assessing the decisions about technological security enabling the financial organisations to fulfil their information security goals (Ruiz-Vanoye et al., 2014). Perceiving strategic planning from cybersecurity governance lens it can be defined as management of information security through long term strategic

planning for cybersecurity. Therefore, in relation to cybersecurity the strategic planning is internal cybersecurity governance (Sajko, et al., 2021). According to Hafiz-Ali, et al. (2019) effective cybersecurity strategic planning, aiming to secure the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of financial information and systems, can be based on *technical* (investment in technology and experts), *organisational* (training and awareness of executives and employees), and *legal* (compliance with regulations and standards to make strategic planning) aspects altogether (Lagazio, et al., 2014; Goel, 2016; Malik and Islam, 2019; Wang, et al., 2020; Naik Bukht, et al., 2020; Dhillon, 2020).

The technical aspect requires banks to provide sufficient budgets for investment in innovative technical solutions as well as cybersecurity experts to ensure the effective cybersecurity governance (Na-jibzadeh and Park, 2021; Al-Alawi and Al-Bassam, 2021). The literature shows that lack of investment in innovative, up-to-date, responsive technology, and high level of experts to deal with dynamic cyberattacks is one of the major hurdle in cybersecurity governance (Varian, 2004; Moore and Anderson, 2012; Gordonet et al., 2015; Malik and Islam, 2019). Therefore, some organizations prefer to adopt cost efficient and not fully secure solutions such as (BAAS and cloud storage, open APIs, open banking). The relevant cost of such investment, and fact that avoidance of such attacks is not ensured because of their innovative nature, restricts executives to make a decision about investing in cybersecurity governance (Bernik, 2014; Kopp, et al., 2017; Uddin, et al., 2020; Qadeer, 2020). Nevertheless, the investment in cybersecurity governance yet is essential (Syed, et al., 2019; Świątkowska, 2020; Na-jibzadeh and Park, 2021). Al-Alawi and Al-Bassam (2021) suggest that it is vital to convince the executives, making them understand the importance of cybersecurity governance, to invest in it. Hence this shows the investment dependency on executives' perception of cybersecurity governance.

The organisational perspective includes cybersecurity training and awareness of employees and executives. The employees are one of the basic challenge for organisational cybersecurity, as a human factor (Alotaibi, et al., 2017; Al-Badran, 2021). The cyber risk to the information security system of organisation from employees can be intentional or unintentional. However, the training and development has been proved as

an effective tool to reduce such a risk, because employees are the first line of defence against cyberattacks (Servidio & Taylor, 2015; Woldemichael, 2019). Therefore, it is leaders' and management's responsibility to adopt (comply) employee training standards required along with technological solutions to ensure the effective cybersecurity governance (Creado and Ramteke, 2020; Lie, et al., 2021). Simultaneously, executives are the ones who approve the strategy planning proposed by management (CISO). Hence, executives' commitment and support in cybersecurity governance investment related decisions is of vital importance (Al-Alawi and Al-Bassam, 2021). Alghamdi (2021) found that the lack of executives' understanding about cybersecurity importance is one of the major reasons that even highly advanced companies are failing to secure their information systems, since directors in boardrooms armed with cybersecurity training or degrees are minority (Rothrock, et al., 2018; Robert & Ackerman, 2021).

The logic is that the ever-changing cybercrimes are increasing in banks. Subsequently, executives need to make decisions to deal with these criminal activities about which the league comprehensive understanding which can make the decision ineffective (Rothrock, et al., 2018). It is supposed that executives are not there to predict cyberattacks and their impact but having training and knowledge will enable them to make effective decisions about cybersecurity governance (Stern, 2014; Gale, et al., 2022). Thus, strategically planning (legal aspect) about developing policies for investment (technical aspect) and establishing code of conduct for employees (organisational aspect) can enhance cybersecurity governance in banks (Terlizzi, et al., 2017).

External factors (challenges)

1. Customer Awareness

Customer awareness for this thesis is deemed as the ability of banking customers to identify possible cyberthreats using cyberspace, assess the risk, and prevent or solve the problem instantly to secure your personal information (Wang, et al., 2019). Appreciating the use of internet there is a commendable growth in internet and e-banking users which is opening doors for cybercriminals to steal money from banks, targeting banking

customers (Wang et al., 2020). Considering customers as a weak human factor, cyber criminals assess their knowledge and awareness of cybersecurity and accordingly plan cyberattacks to access personal information of banking customers (Moustafa, et al., 2021). Different studies confirmed this resulting that banking customers are targeted by cybercriminals because they have no or less awareness of such threats (Alzubaidi, 2021; Al-Alawi and Al-Bassam, 2021; Gomes, et al., 2022). Alghazo, et al. (2017) state that customer awareness is important because once the banks have invested heavy amount of money on technical and expert solutions of cybersecurity yet customers share their confidential banking information because of lack of awareness, which is mostly the case in developing countries. Nevertheless, customer awareness can be proved as an efficient and effective technique to prevent cybercrimes in banks and support cybersecurity governance (Aloul, 2012; Bele et al., 2014; Innab et al., 2018; Hafiz Ali, et al., 2019). However, customer awareness may depend on multiple factors suggest customer literacy, general public literacy and awareness, and government awareness programmes.

Magomedov, et al. (2020) mentioned that customer literacy can be categorised as financial literacy (education) and cyber literacy (ability to use e-banking services acknowledging their implications). However, it is proved that educated people can become cybersecurity aware easily because they can develop the understanding of importance of cybersecurity (Rodrigues, et al., 2019). Contrary, it is confirmed that even educated people become victim of social engineering by clicking on links or responding to criminal attempts to share their confidential information. This proves that even being educated is not sufficient right to use cyberspace securely (Alghazo, et al., 2017; Magomedov, et al., 2020). Thus, cybersecurity awareness is crucial to support the cybersecurity governance in banks.

Comparatively, the focus is businesses and regulatory authorities has been on technology and experts while the awareness among public is not given attention (Švábenský, et al., 2021; Yaziz Bin Mohd, et al., 2021). Cyber criminals are keep looking for weak links in cyberspace such as lack of awareness of general public as a human factor, to gain financial information from them (Aloul, 2012; Limna, et al. 2022). The general public makes the use of internet on daily basis to perform their regular activities such as bill

payment or online shopping from family member's card etc. These actions generate new data that can be accessed and used by third parties subsequently by cyber criminals having read cybersecurity of third parties (Marune and Hartanto, 2021; Limna, et al. 2022). Therefore, it has become necessary for all members of our society to be aware about cybersecurity. In reality people are less aware of cybersecurity issues as it is an emerging phenomenon and there's a lack of sufficient efforts to aware them (Bruijn and Janssen, 2017; Khader, et al., 2021). Al-Alawi and Al-Bassam (2021) state that public awareness will support spread off awareness through banking customer being part of the society. Hence, it is required to take adequate actions to spread cybersecurity education and awareness at all levels (Ahmad, et al., 2022).

Lastly, role of governments to spread cybersecurity awareness is of vital importance because banks have limited resources which cannot be sufficient to aware each customer and member of society (Bada, et al., 2019). Kovačević, et al., (2020) and Zwilling, et al. (2022) found that even being aware of cybersecurity measures people do not use them as they are not aware of consequences of cyberattacks. Therefore, continues cybersecurity awareness effective campaigns informing people about dynamic cybercrimes is a need of nations (Nagyfejeo et al., 2020). Considering it as a government responsibility to aware their people about cybersecurity, many developed nations have already started effective programmes of cybersecurity awareness (Alotaibi, 2019; Khader, et al., 2021). The purpose of these programmes is to empower people to get knowledge, question, and challenge to enhance their learning. This will create the cybersecurity culture throughout the nation (Shillair, et al., 2022). Thus, government programmes can have effective and fast awareness over the nation. Overall, it can be summed up that cybersecurity awareness is of wider importance for cybersecurity governance in banks which can be tested in private commercial banks of Pakistan.

2. *Cybersecurity Law and its enforcement*

For this thesis, cybersecurity law ensures the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of information used in cyberspace, by providing policies and regulations in interest of national security (Kosseff, 2018). Deora and Chudasama (2021) suggest that

technological solutions or awareness is not sufficient to prevent cyberattacks unless law proposes harsh punishments to demotivate cyber criminals. Libicki (2021) supported it as, the development of nations depends on government's commitment to secure the digital system of country. The banks in all countries have been confronting almost similar kind of cyberthreats. However, the countries with weak cybersecurity laws (that does not clearly define the crimes and their relevant punishments) have been the target of cyber criminals (Hafiz-Ali, et al., 2019; Kesharwani, et al., 2019). Taking advantage of jurisdictional arbitrage opportunities Cyber criminals target the countries fear the law is not comprehensive which can restrict them (Kesharwani, et al., 2019). Hence, the cybersecurity law addressing the dynamics cybercrimes and empowering authorities to implement strict punishments, is the need of era (Gomes, et al., 2022).

On the other hand, the local law enforcement agencies have recognised that world widely cybercriminals are benefiting from globally connected internet to conduct cybercriminal activities in different countries (Al-Badran, 2021). The governments in multiple countries have not been allocating appropriate budgets for law enforcement agencies underestimating the necessity of cybersecurity, resulting insufficient number of qualified law enforcement professionals (Ibrahim, et al., 2020). This has caused to slow down the solutions of cybercriminal cases which motivates cybercriminals (Vitvitskiy, et al., 2021) while fast track mobile courts to enforce law against cyber criminals will prevent cybercriminals (Kethineni, 2020). Kao et al. (2020) suggest that for fast and effective resolution of cybercrime cases the law enforcement agencies need to be equipped with efficient IT skills and in depth understanding of cybercrimes. Internet facilitates cyber criminals to remove the traces of their evidence (Le, et al., 2020) hence, to implement law, the law enforcement officers need to be specialised in cybersecurity capabilities (Al-Badran, 2021). Another aspect is that collaboration between multiple law enforcement agencies within country and internationally can be useful to faster the response against international criminals (Vitvitskiy, et al., 2021). Yaziz Bin Mohd et al. (2021) is there is that law enforcement results in improving cybersecurity landscape in a country. Consequently, the government needs to make immediate initiatives to provide a comprehensive law and

facilitate its enforcement to support the cybersecurity governance in banks (Wang, et al., 2020).

3. *Lack of Satisfactory Regulatory Framework of Cybersecurity*

A cybersecurity regulatory framework is a catalogue of security and privacy controls to secure information systems of an organisation from different threats and risks such as hostile attacks, structural failures, foreign intelligence entities, and privacy risks etc (Force, 2020). The banks and regulatory bodies have been considering cybersecurity as IT issue therefore have not been allocating sufficient budgets for cybersecurity (Bainbridge, 2017; Hafiz-Ali, et al., 2019). Contrary, the last decade has been revolutionary for regulatory framework of banks, considering cybersecurity issue (Goel, 2016; Kosseff, 2018). Cybersecurity in banks have become point of discussion in different international organisations who have introduced rigorous cybersecurity regulatory frameworks (NIST/ISO 27001) which can be used by any bank in the world regardless of its size etc. (Didenko, 2020; Thach, et al., 2021). Novák and Doucek (2017) asserts that the regulatory framework of a banking industry must address the contemporary cyberthreats and their solutions otherwise, it needs to be revised (Kopp, et al., 2017). The regulatory body of the country is responsible to provide a comprehensive regulatory framework for its banking sector considering the dynamic cyberthreats, determined to maintain the balance between ensuring financial stability, information security, and fostering innovation. Moreover, to implement this regulatory framework the synergy between banks and the regulator is important (Artemenko and Bychkova, 2020). Given that regardless of comprehensive strategic planning of banks if the regulatory framework does not facilitate the best measures for cybersecurity, the purpose remains ineffective. Thus, a regulatory framework plays an important role in cybersecurity governance of banks.

The following table 5 shows that since 2006 until 2021 customer awareness, law and law enforcement, regulatory framework and strategic planning are common concern for researchers. This attracts author's attention to explore these factors in the context of this study.

Table 5: Literature to Retrieve Factors

No.	Author	Topic	Factors	Methodology
1	Ezeoha (2006)	Regulating Internet Banking In Nigeria : Some Success Prescriptions– Part 2	Law, regulation, and customer awareness	Secondary (Theoretical based)
2	Hafiz-Ali, Khan, Asghar, and Shuaib (2019)	Issues of E-Banking in Pakistan: Managers' Perceptions about E-Banking Issues	Security, regulatory framework , reversal of wrong transaction, literacy, and customer awareness .	Exploratory Interviews
3	Naik Bukht, Raza, Awan, and Ahmad (2020)	Analysing cyber-attacks targeted on the Banks of Pakistan and their Solutions	Strategy (Employee Awareness)	Secondary (Theoretical based)
4	Malik and Islam (2019)	Cybercrime: an emerging threat to the banking sector of Pakistan	Strategy (Employee Awareness)	Survey (Quantitative)
5	Goel (2016)	Cyber-crime: a growing threat to indian banking sector	Customer awareness, traditional law enforcement policies, standards, and methods (strategy)	Secondary (Theoretical based)
6	Lagazio, Sherif, and Cushman (2014)	A multi-level approach to understanding the impact of cybercrime on the financial sector	Strategy, regulatory framework, and law	Secondary (Theoretical based)
7	Alotaibi, Furnell and Clarke (2017)	Information Security Policies: A review of Challenges and Influencing Factors	Strategy and Employee Awareness	Secondary (Theoretical based)
8	Dhillon (2020)	WHAT TO DO BEFORE AND AFTER A CYBERSECURITY BREACH?	Human behaviour, Employee awareness and strategy	Secondary (Theoretical based)
9	Wang, Nnaji, and Jung (2020)	Internet banking in Nigeria: Cybersecurity breaches, practices, and capability	Lack of investment, and strategy-compliance	Survey (Quantitative)
10	Al-Alawi and Al-Bassam (2021)	Assessing The Factors of Cybersecurity Awareness in the Banking Sector	Strategy (training, investment budget, compliance, and culture).	Survey (Quantitative)
11	Alghazo, Kazmi, and Latif (2017)	Cybersecurity analysis of internet banking in emerging countries: User and bank perspectives	Customer Awareness	Survey (Quantitative)
12	ISA, Ibrahim, and Mohamed (2021)	The Relationship Between Financial Literacy and Public Awareness on Combating the Threat of Cybercrime in Malaysia	Public Awareness Law Enforcement	Survey (Quantitative)
13	Diene and Špaček (2021)	Digital transformation in banking: A managerial perspective on barriers to changes	Strategy, technology, regulation, customers, and employees	Contextual Interview

Source: Author Developed

Furthermore, these factors have also been commonly highlighted in the following (table 6) most widely used information security governance frameworks:

Table 6: List of Regulatory Framework Suggesting Factors

ISG components	ISO 27002	COBIT	CGT F	CISW G	FFIEC	PCI
Law	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X
Regulatory Framework	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X
Awareness	✓	✓	✓	X	X	✓
Strategy	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X

Retrieved from: [Munirul, Ismail, and Mohamed Sidek \(2011\)](#)

These factors has been studied in developed countries by multiple researchers however there are very few number of studies conducted in this regard in developing countries. Therefore, this study will attempt to investigate these factors in context of private commercial banks of Pakistan. However, from this section the following two research questions are developed:

1. *What are the significant internal and external factors (challenges) that affect cybersecurity governance in the private commercial banks of Pakistan.*
2. *How the cybersecurity governance is perceived in private commercial banks of Pakistan which can ensure its maturity level?*

The first research question is developed directly from the literature which suggests that there are internal and external factors which affect the cybersecurity in banks. However, the second research question is developed based on the understanding that the internal factors are related to strategic planning which is consistent with executives' and management's perception of cybersecurity governance. Therefore, along with studying the internal factors affecting the cybersecurity governance of banks it is also important to investigate what is the perception of banks in relation to cybersecurity governance. It will allow the researcher to analyse the internal factors intrinsically relating them to banks perception of cybersecurity governance.

Cybersecurity threats

Focusing on the confidentiality offence which consists of integrity, and availability, as well of information security, the literature suggests that over time the cyber criminals has been using dynamic and complex cyberthreats to breach the cybersecurity of the organisation and access confidential information of banking customers to steal money. For this thesis, confidentiality offence is when unauthorised access is made to information. The integrity consists of misuse of systems and information for fraudulent activities. The availability offence arises where the data of banking customers is not available when required and results in disruptions (Gřivna and Drápal, 2018). The reason to choose social engineering, fake websites, and online shopping (IBM, 2018); ATM skimming (Wang et al., 2021); DDoS (Stanikzai & Shah, 2021); and malware (Liwong, 2018) for this study is that as per the literature these all challenges are confronted in banks in different countries. While, none of the studies have considered them empirically in private commercial banks of Pakistan. On the other hand, deepfake is a new trend therefore this study will be one of those early studies which analysed this challenge in banking sector of Pakistan. However, these threats are defined as follow in context of this thesis:

Social engineering

It is one of the major and trending threat in banking sector. It is an act of exploiting humans by providing them inaccurate information, using social interface and electronic devices, to obtain their personal information which can be used to steal money from banks (Dhillon, 2020; Ghauri, 2021). It is conduct of cybercriminals who try to mislead people through their greed vanity and positive beliefs (Terlizzi et al., 2017). Hence, for this thesis it is believed that social engineering is an activity to exploit the weakest link within the information security chain of the business (Orgill, et al., 2004; Allen, 2007). Social engineers can use phone calls (vishing), text message (smashing) or emails (phishing) to trap people, portraying themselves as banks or other business, trying to get bank account details, credit or debit card details and passwords of banking customers (Hafiz Ali, et al., 2019; Ghauri, 2021; Swaine, 2022).

Fake websites and online shopping

It is referred to a threat which incurs when a person uses a fake website intentionally or unintentionally or have been diverted to fake website by clicking on a link sent through social engineering where he or she will be asked to share their personal details to win a prize (Salahdine and Kaabouch, 2019).

ATM skimming

ATM skimming can be done through two techniques. The one is when a rain cover (chip) is attached to the card reader slot of the ATM to imitate the card details. The other technique is to Install a sleeping bag to record the pins relating to cards (Hattali, et al., 2020).

DDoS

DDoS attack is used for availability threat to the information. It incurs when the information of the legitimate customers is not available and unreachable within the system of bank (Namanya et al. 2018).

Deep fake attacks

It is a new method of cybercrime. Deep fake is conducted when and artificial intelligence is used to manipulate voice or video content of a person to present it as original (Mirsky & Lee, 2020).

Malware

Malware is a malicious code added, modified, or removed from a software, with purpose to harm or subvert the specific function. It is used to devastate the data or steal the money (Chaimaa, et al., 2021). To conduct these activities the cyber criminals, use various types of malware such as:

Virus-it is a malicious code which can copy itself and can spread from one file to another remaining in the basic file. It is activated when the user starts using the file (Gupta, 2013).

Worm-it is a standalone malicious software which spreads through one system to another without opening any file (Guo et al., 2016; Alenezi, et al., 2020).

Trojan horse-it is a software which is used to spy, steal, or damage the information. The user downloads it considering a genuine software rather it downloads the malicious codes (Gupta, 2013; Alenezi, et al., 2020).

Spyware-this software is used to spy infected systems and collect personal data of people and businesses having unauthorised access (Namanya et al., 2018; Lysenko, et al., 2020).

Ransomware-it is used to hostage the users' system, files, or information to encrypt them and decryption key is only provided once the demanded money is paid to cybercriminal (Namanya et al., 2018).

Crypto ransomware-it is similar to ransomware but is used to threaten people that the files will be deleted if they do not make the payments (Shah & Farik, 2017).

Doxware-it is a crypto ransomware used to threaten people that the information will be leaked publicly if the ransom will not be paid (Zucker-Scharff, 2019).

This literature means to investigate the research question three of this study:

3. Which cybersecurity threats are caused by identified factors in private commercial banks of Pakistan?

This research question will allow the author to investigate what kind of cyberthreats the private commercial banks of Pakistan are confronting. This will indicate the level of seriousness of cybercrime in private commercial banks of Pakistan so that relevant recommendations can be made.

Mitigating cyberthreats

The detailed literature allows to understand that the cybersecurity threats in banks are increasing because of the factors discussed in this study. However, if those factors are managed effectively the cybersecurity governance of banks can be improved. For example, cybersecurity awareness will enable banking customers to take educated actions and avoid cyberthreats (Alzubaidi, 2021; Gomes, et al., 2022). The effective strategic planning which includes investment in technology and experts as well as executives and employees training, can boost the cybersecurity governance of the banks and will develop the cybersecurity culture (Hafiz-Ali, et al., 2019). Finally, law and its enforcement (Deora and Chudasama, 2021) and comprehensive regulatory framework can play the role of safeguards for banking cybersecurity (Deora and Chudasama, 2021).

Thus, answering the research question 1, 2, and 3 which will explain which factors are affecting cybersecurity governance in private commercial banks of Pakistan and which threats those banks are confronting it will be efficient to answer what can be the best recommendations based on the literature and data collected to resolve those factors or challenges. Hence following is the 4th research question of the study:

4. What are the recommended effective cybersecurity governance measures to improve the cybersecurity governance in private commercial banks of Pakistan?

The theoretical framework and formulations of research questions in this chapter enabled the development of conceptual framework of this study presented in figure 30. The conceptual framework illustrates the connection between different concepts of this study, discussed in this chapter.

Figure 30: Conceptual Framework for Cybersecurity Governance of PCBP

Diagrammatic Presentation:

- Arrow up and down: show the link
- Arrow right and left: directs extension
- Square box: is used for categorising factors
- Three-D box: is used to represent problem
- Oval shape: shows the ultimate target
- Curved arrows: show the similar concept of factors

4.3. Summary of Conceptual Framework

This chapter was designed to justify the choice of research questions and the conceptual framework. The graphical representation of conceptual framework starts with emphasising on importance of cybersecurity governance which impacts customers risk perception and restricts adoption of E banking (Marafon, et al., 2018; Anouze and Alamro, 2019; Ahmad, et al., 2020; Kaur and Sharma, 2022; Venkatesh, 2023). Further, it is based mainly on institutional logics which suggests that the behaviour of society (consist of government, regulatory authorities, and organisations) must be studied collectively considering structural, normative, and symbolic logics (Christou, 2014; Forslund, 2020).

Gümüşay, et al. (2020) asserts that institutional logics map the behaviour of society. Thus, following this assertion, this conceptual framework will attempt to find how different factors/institutional logics have affected the behaviour of various actors towards cybersecurity governance of e-banking. Following this perspective, various factors (internal and external) which as per the literature are affecting the cybersecurity governance of banks have been included to investigate them in context of private commercial banks of Pakistan. The structural logics indicate towards the level of effectiveness and compliance with cybersecurity laws and regulations facilitated by government and regulatory bodies to prevent cybercrimes in banks. This suggested to consider law, its enforcement and regulatory framework as structural logics for this study. Similarly, human social behaviour which consists of norms, values and beliefs are normative logics that highlight the literacy and awareness of banking customers and public in context of this study (Björck, 2004; Forslund, 2020; Alzubaidi, 2021; Farid and Waldorff, 2022). Finally, the symbolic-cultural institutional logics pinpoints the strategical actions of organisations to manage their operations affectively (Friedland, 2018). Thus, strategic planning of banks may fall in the category of symbolic-cultural institutional logics. Moreover, the employees and customers are considered as a

human factor and the weakest links in information security of banks (Gomes, et al., 2022).

Concurrently, Thornton (2004), and Faik, Barrett, and Oborn (2020) refer that institutional logics shape rationale and mindful behaviour therefore the actors can influence to create and change the institutional logics. Referring back to North (1990), Hodgson (2006) and Giddens (1984) definitions of institutions, organisations for instance, states (government), regulatory bodies and firms are systems of rules, thus are also institutions (Hodgson, 2019). However, Mishra, Alzoubi, Anwar, and Gill (2022) state that being institutions (systems of rules), concurrently organizations and governments are the primary actors in cybersecurity. Hence, elaborating the role and impact of listed internal and external factors from the literature it can be inferred that Banks, regulator and Government are main actors for this thesis, as deemed by Kaffenberger and Kopp (2019). Accordingly, this study will attempt to find out and recommend the effective creation or changes in observed institutional logics by the concerned actors. Hence, it is believed that the effective management of factors of this study can propose efficient recommendations for cybersecurity governance of private commercial banks of Pakistan.

The above theoretical and conceptual framework decides which research methodology is best for this study hence the next chapter will unlight the research philosophy, research design and concerns relating to validity reliability and ethics of this study.

CHAPTER FIVE: METHODOLOGY

5.1. Introduction

This chapter five of this study will show the research paradigm that will be used for this study. A research paradigm is a research design which entails different techniques to conduct a certain study (Willis, 2007). It is a logical and consistent exploration of new knowledge and meaningful information about a specific topic (Collis & Hussey, 2014). Hence, this chapter will describe the chosen research design and various stages of research as well as methods based on research onion of this study. The use of research tools and methods will be justified followed by the research philosophy, research approach, research design, research strategies, and data analysis techniques and procedures. Finally, the ethical considerations along with validity and reliability of data will be discussed.

5.2. Difference between Research Methods and Research Methodology

To understand the research significance comprehensively, it is important to understand the difference between research methods and methodology. The research methodology has wider scope than research methods because, research methods are part of research methodology (Raithatha, 2017). In short, the research methods for this study will include the data collection techniques which can be deployed to conduct this study while, the research methodology underpins all the steps and factors which can influence the effectiveness of research methods used (Kothari, 2011).

5.3. Saunders Research Onion

According to Melnikovas (2018) Saunders research onion facilitates with the systematic approach to simplify the methodology chapter of the research. According to this approach, a research is similar to an onion which has different layers that can be peeled off one after another whereby the outer layer guides the way to the inner layer. This cycle continues until the researcher reaches to the end of an onion (figures out the best methods of study which will help to complete the research objectives of the study). The idea of the research onion was introduced by Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2016) for business studies and is extensively used in social sciences with purpose to

construct the theoretical framework of research. According to Muranganwa (2016) the idea of research onion provides a firm basis for construction of consistent and justifiable research design. Also, a suitable research methodology can be developed following the steps given in the research onion (Raithatha, 2017). Hence it is usable as the basic academic research model. However, the research onion has been proved as an efficient model commonly used in social sciences (Raithatha, 2017; Melnikovas, 2018) as well as exact sciences (Muranganwa, 2016). Therefore, this study will also take the help of research onion to develop the appropriate methodology to conduct this study so that the results of this study can be reliable and justifiable (Muranganwa, 2016). Following is the research onion (Figure 31) which illustrates the step by step methodology for this study.

Figure 31: Saunders Research Onion

Saunders et al. (2012)

5.3.1. Philosophies of Research

The meaning of the word philosophy is “love of wisdom”. The word philosophy is taken from two Greek words which are ‘phileo’ means love and ‘sophia’ means wisdom (Roark, 1982). However, philosophy is the study of general and fundamental issues which are relating to the existence, knowledge, standards, cause, mind and language (Jung, 2118). There are basic four branches of philosophy which further have sub-branches as follows (Ornstein & Leine, 2008):

Figure 32: Types of Philosophy

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Ornstein and Levine (2008)

However, three basic grounds of education through philosophy are ontology (looking for reality), epistemology (searching for knowledge) and axiology (relating to values). Therefore, only these three will be discussed in this study. Nevertheless, epistemology is the most basic one. Because only knowledge can reveal reality and enables values’ realisation (Jung, 2118). Although, to be educated about or gain knowledge of what

can be the set of recommendations regarding cybersecurity measures to improve the cybersecurity in private banks of Pakistan, the author must have to use the suitable philosophy to successfully obtain the research objectives, as discussed below.

5.3.1.1. Metaphysics

Metaphysics is the most important branch of philosophy which studies the existence of reality or essence. It answers two basic questions, what is there and what is it like? This is an ancient area of study which is continuously arousing curiosity (Abdul Masih, 2016). Metaphysics is known as the queen of all sciences and philosophy of mind, philosophy of religion, universal, ontology and causality are sub branches of metaphysics (Tantray & Dar, 2016). Besides, ontology is relevant for this study as it deals with to find out the reality about the social topic under discussion as discussed below.

5.3.1.1.1. Ontology

What is existing is known through ontology (Willis, 2007). According to Adams St. Pierre (2011) the ontological philosophy is used for qualitative research which is conducted to discover new knowledge (i.e., is the object existing in reality or is it based on assumptions). The basic research question in a qualitative research design following an ontological view is to decide the nature or characteristics of the reality/object based on ontological beliefs (Al-Ababneh, 2020). However, there are three ontological beliefs which are as follows (Levers, 2013):

1. There is a single reality.
2. There are multiple realities.
3. The reality is constantly negotiated, debated, or interpreted.

Although, this study is based on the ontological believe that there are multiple realities. The reason is that this study is qualitative (exploratory) in nature for which data is collected using interviews, observation, or open-ended survey questionnaires (to get in-depth knowledge) as discussed below (Boru, 2018). This detailed data will answer the questions about which the literature does not have other studies available (this

encourages to conduct this study), (Pratt, 2016). Following is the epistemology of this study based on this ontology.

5.3.1.2. Epistemology

The word epistemology is taken from two Greek words 'episteme' and 'logos' which means knowledge and science or study respectively (Grayling, 2019). And, this study of knowledge is called philosophy. This kind of study is critical. In addition, the first basic issue which a researcher has to face is to know about the nature of knowledge as well as its limitations. However, epistemology plays its role in this regard through its branches of knowledge which is why it is the most basic branch of philosophy (Zalta et al., 2020). There are two branches of epistemology scepticism and dogmatism. Scepticism follows the perspective that there is relativity of human knowledge (following the ontological concept that there are multiple realities). While, dogmatism believes that the knowledge does not have relativity and it is absolute based on the ontology that there is one reality (McGrath, 2013). Nevertheless, based on the above ontology for this study the epistemology for this study will also be scepticism which will be based on qualitative data, as discussed below.

Additionally, epistemology is a philosophy of knowledge which explains all specific steps about how to gain knowledge about reality (Hesse-Biber & Leavy, 2006); how we know what we do; what is justification of trusting in what we do; and what standards of proof a researcher should meet in looking for truth relating to world and human experience (Tantray & Dar, 2016). For the purpose of this study the cybersecurity is an existing thing or reality. And epistemological theory will guide to choose the methodology which can help to find out factors affecting cybersecurity governance in private commercial banks of Pakistan, in a valid and reliable way to meet the ultimate aim of the study.

In addition, Dudovskiy (2022) states that epistemology offers philosophical grounds relating to the level of possibility up to which the knowledge is possible. As mentioned earlier, it also facilitates to confirm that the gained knowledge is satisfactory and authentic because it is based on and relates to journal articles (various knowledge provider resources) nature (the logic of rationale of generating hypothesis from previous research), sources (the existing empirical research) and limitations of

knowledge (having scepticism that the study is not perfect as it is based on constructivism). Hence, following the above mentioned epistemological concepts the results of this study will be authentic. Moreover, after deciding the epistemological method for specific study rest of research design will be based on it (Hesse-Biber & Leavy, 2006) as discussed below.

5.3.1.3. Axiology

Axiology describes values. It is further divided into three parts, namely politics, ethics and aesthetics. Ethics prescribe moral values and the principles of ethical behaviour. While, aesthetics examine values in beauty and art, and politics deal with values in political environment (Ornstein & Levine, 2008). However, this study does not evaluate ethics.

5.3.1.4. Review on Philosophies

The multiple branches and sub-branches of philosophy as discussed above, the most relevant philosophes for an academic researcher are ontology and epistemology. Because, firstly an academic researcher will choose the nature of reality to be considered and secondly, how this reality can be known. However, adopting the concept of selected ontology (multiple realities) and epistemology (relativity of human perception), the following section justifies the purpose of this study.

5.3.1.5. Research Purpose

Based on the research objectives of the study, a research can be classified as follows:

1. Descriptive
2. Correlational
3. Explanatory
4. Exploratory

This study will be classified as exploratory because, according to Goundar (2012) exploratory research is conducted to explore an area of study about which little is known or to investigate the chances of conducting a specific research study (visibility/pilot study). However, based on the objectives of this study, description of

cybersecurity situation in selected banks (descriptive study - Boru, 2018), finding relationship between cybersecurity, factors, challenges as well as solutions (correlational research - Phyllis, 2014) or, clarifying why and how this relationship exists (explanatory research - Sharma, 2019) is not the ultimate purpose of this study. Rather, this study intends to explore (exploratory research - Saunders et al. 2012) the factors affecting cybersecurity governance of private commercial banks of Pakistan. The exploratory research is qualitative by nature and based on the theoretical or the hypothetical concepts. It ends up producing new knowledge about the problem (Kivunja & Kuyin, 2017). It is also known as interpretive research because of its flexible and open-ended nature. Additionally, the exploratory research design generates new concepts and theories based on literature review and data collection. Similarly, exploratory research is mostly done through qualitative methods (observation and the other techniques like interviews or open-ended survey questionnaires) which enable the researcher to collect preliminary data to go in depth (Boru, 2018). For example, in the case of this study, the literature is available about social factors affecting cybersecurity governance in banks, based on the data collected from different countries (a little is known). While, there is less or no research available which has been conducted using the conceptual model which this study is considering to find the factors affecting the cybersecurity governance in private commercial banks of Pakistan. Hence, the semi-structured interviews will help to acquire the in-depth knowledge of the topic. The detailed discussion is constructed throughout this chapter to choose these methodological approaches for this study. The following section initiates from rationalizing the epistemology (methodology) of this study, to gain knowledge.

5.3.1.6. Nature of science of study

According to Chalmers (2013), to choose a paradigm for a research it is important to identify the nature of science of study. Although, to obtain the knowledge or explore a problem area there are two methods; natural and social sciences (Blaike, 2000).

Natural sciences

This research method is used to conduct studies on nature therefore it is called a scientific method of research (Grayling, 2019).

Social sciences

This research method is used to conduct studies on social or human behaviour. It has the following basic sub-branches:

1. Positivism
2. Interpretivism
3. Pragmatism

Hence, there are three basic approaches/paradigms of research using social sciences. However, each paradigm consists of a different view about research philosophies (ontology and epistemology) and methodology (Creswell, 2013). As given positivism follows a scientific way of following hypothesis, deductive and quantitative family, so the result of study is same. Interpretivism follows the inductive, qualitative family and generates a hypothesis, so the result of study will change. Pragmatism follows the mix of positivism and interpretivism (Morgan, 2014; Schoonenboom & Johnson, 2017). In the following section these three concepts are discussed in relation to this study.

5.3.1.6.1. Positivism

The concept of positivism is taken from the philosophical theories of August Comte (a philosopher from France), who emphasised that the observation and reasoning are the basic ways of interpreting human behaviour. He drew attention to the reality that real knowledge is based on personal experiences and the method of obtaining this knowledge is observation and investigation (Mack, 2010). Therefore, today's positivist researchers adopt this scientific concept of August Comte's in their studies and implement quantitative methods which include reports, structured questionnaires, and surveys etc (Williams, 2020). However, based on the nature of this study quantitative approach is not concern here. Therefore, positivism concept will not be applied for this study (Pham, 2018).

5.3.1.6.2. Interpretivism/Constructivism

The interpretivism paradigm is based on the view that the methods which are used to study the human and social sciences cannot be the same as those which are used in natural sciences. This is because humans have individual perception and interprets

their world and subsequently act accordingly, while the natural world does not (Hammersley, 2013). Therefore, interpretivist researchers (exploratory study) follow relativist ontology whereby one research factor can have various interpretations instead of having a truth which is determined following a process of measurement. Hence, interpretivism is used in qualitative study. Hence, this study will follow the interpretivism philosophy because with purpose to gain a thorough understanding of cybersecurity issue in private commercial banks of Pakistan in context of the unique conceptual framework of this study rather than of generalising the basic understandings of the phenomena for the whole population (Creswell, 2007). The interpretivism paradigm can also be known as anti-positivism as it is originated as a reaction of positivism and it opposite to quantitative method. It can also be called constructivism as it follows the viewpoint that the individuals can construct meaning (Moschkovich, 2019).

This paradigm is mainly based on hermeneutics and phenomenology theoretical concepts. Hermeneutics is the study of meaning and interpretation of historical texts. And the interpretivist paradigm is based on this meaning making cyclical process (Ernest, 1994) whereby the research will interpret the meaning of qualitative data collected for this study. Another basic theory which has influenced the interpretivist paradigm is philosophical movement of phenomenological theory. The philosophy of phenomenologists put emphasis to consider human beings' subjective interpretations and their own thinking of the world as a basic point of understanding social phenomena (Horrigan-Kelly, Millar, & Dowling, 2016). Hence, ontological assumptions of interpretivism paradigm insist that various people in society perceive social reality in multiple ways. Consequently, this study will gather in-depth qualitative data through collecting various views of people (having different perspectives than each other) in Pakistan about each component of conceptual framework of this study regarding cybersecurity in private commercial banks of Pakistan (Cohen, Manion, & Morrison, 2018). The basic belief of interpretivist researchers is that it is not possible to conduct a research based on objective observations from outside, instead an objective must be observed from inside with the help of direct experience of the people. They also believe that a uniform cause and effect relationship which is developed using natural science cannot be established in an academic environment where lecturers and students construct meaning (Williams, 2020). Henceforth, the role of the researcher following the interpretivism approach will be to understand, clarify and interpret social

reality about cybersecurity in private commercial banks of Pakistan with the help of different participants (Cohen, Manion, & Morrison, 2007).

5.3.1.6.3. Pragmatism

Pragmatism approach is based on the view that researchers should adopt the philosophical and/or methodological approach that suits best for a specific research problem (Creswell et al., 2011; Morgan, 2014). However, pragmatism philosophy is rejected to be used for this study because it only supports concepts that are related to actions. Also, following pragmatism approach a study cannot be completed using a single way of generating knowledge because single method of research would enable the researcher to obtain limited knowledge of topic and provides a narrow picture (Saunders et al., 2012).

5.3.2. Research Approach

There are two approaches of research; inductive and deductive. Soiferman (2010) defines the inductive approach as a study started from bottom up, using the interpretations of participants to develop broader themes and produce a theory interconnecting the themes". Cho and Lee (2014) state that the inductive approach is used under qualitative (exploratory) research. Comparing it with the nature of this study - which is exploratory, the inductive approach fits best (Thomas, 2003). Thus, the research approach for this study will be inductive (bottom-up) whereby the researcher will conduct the literature review, develop a conceptual framework, collect the data, and then generate the results (Kiger & Varpio, 2020). In contrast, according to Woiceshyn and Daellenbach (2018) through deductive approach hypothesis are developed based on existing theory and literature, which are tested by developing a research strategy. Consequently, the results of deductive study then are specified to a specific sample. Thus, deductive approach is a top-down approach which will not help to meet the research aim of this study.

5.3.3. Research Design

5.3.3.1. Qualitative data

Qualitative research is a method of naturalistic investigation which looks in-depth knowledge of social phenomena within their natural setting. Qualitative research focuses on “why” instead of the “what” within social phenomena and is based on the direct experiences of humans considering them the meaning making agents in their regular lives (Ahmad et al., 2019). Instead of using logical and statistical methods, the qualitative researchers employ multiple methods of research to study the human phenomena like interviews, observations, focused group, and case study (Almeida, Faria & Queirós, 2017). Hence, based on the nature of this study the data of interviews will be qualitative which will help to acquire in-depth knowledge of the topic.

The nature of qualitative data is non-numerical, descriptive, or nominal usually. Such type of data is in the form of words and sentences and, most of the times the qualitative data captures feelings, emotions, or subjective perceptions of the object under study (Syed Muhammad Sajjad, 2018). These characteristics of interview data will help to produce a good quality data for study. Additionally, qualitative data cannot be quantified and is also known as “categorical statistics”. The basic purpose of using qualitative methodology in this study is to generate comprehensive information with the purpose to understand the different aspects of the topic of research (Almeida, Faria & Queirós, 2017).

5.3.3.2. Quantitative Data

This is data which is based on numbers to explain the results of the study. The researcher has to have a good knowledge of calculations and explanations of the statistics used to convert the quantitative data into information (Techo, 2016). According to Rutberg and Bouikidis (2018) the basic purpose of quantitative methods is to clarify, forecast, or examine relationships, define the current conditions, confirm the previous results, or analyse the possible effects on specific results. However, quantitative data does not fit for the nature of this study (exploratory), (Schoonenboom & Johnson, 2017).

5.3.3.3. Sampling

A sample for a study can be defined as, a group of people who will actually participate in the study (Berndt, 2020). Mweshi and Sakyi (2020) state that during the research on a group of people usually it is impossible to gather data from every single person of that group. However, to achieve valid results of the study the researcher has to carefully select the sample that will represent the whole group. There are two methods of sampling. One is probability sampling – which means each member of the population has an equal chance of being selected. It is based on randomly selecting a sample which allows the researcher to generate strong statistical inferences generalising to the whole group (Bellagambi et al., 2020). The second method of sampling is non-probability, which means not every person of the population has a chance of being selected. It consists of non-random selection of sample facilitating the researcher with the convenience of approaching participants at his/her ease which results in easy data collection (Gill, 2020).

5.3.3.3.1. Sample Size

There are different types of banks in Pakistan. The most emerging ones are listed below in Figure 33 (SBP, 2019):

Figure 33: Types of banks in Pakistan

SBP (2019)

For the purpose of this study, out of the above types of banks, only the private commercial banks will be considered as the basic population. The reason is that the

recent cyberattacks have mainly been on private commercial banks from 2018 to 2022 as discussed in the literature. That is why this study is pursued.

In total, there are 15 private commercial banks in Pakistan but only branches in Lahore were considered for this study to represent the whole population, owing to limited access to respondents and time constraint. This leads to non-probability sampling (Mweshi & Sakyi, 2020) as it is used for qualitative data collection. The author belongs to Lahore, so location and people are known, consequently data collection was convenient and less costly using non-probability sampling. Although, the probability sampling is used for quantitative data (Gill, 2020).

For qualitative (interview) data using non-probability sampling method one branch of each of 15 private commercial banks was chosen from Lahore (based on personal reference with interviewees) because of lack of time (Saunders et al., 2009). Dworkin (2012) states that the sample size of a qualitative study is dependent on the resources and time available, and objectives of research. Similarly, as there are 15 private commercial banks so one branch will justify all of the branches for that bank. Likewise, the interviews were conducted from CISOs (14) and a mix of managerial level, or experienced members of banks (7). A similar study by Ojeka, Ben-Caleb, & Ekpe (2017) on 'Cybersecurity in the Nigerian Banking Sector', used only 13 listed banks out of 21 for their study while, Awan and Malik (2018) conducted a study on the impact of cybercrimes on the efficiency of banking sector of Pakistan has used ten banks of Pakistan as the sample for data collection. This confirms that the interview sample size (21) is appropriate for this study.

5.3.3.4. Research Objective Development

The research objectives for this study are based on literature review (as justified in conceptual framework chapter four) and a most recent study conducted by Sadiq (2019) on 'assessment and enhancement of cybersecurity risks in Pakistan'. The study of Sadiq (2019) is of similar nature to the current study. However, the research conducted by Sadiq (2019) does not discuss the previous empirical studies, has not mentioned NIST or ISO 27001, has not collected empirical data and neither has it used theoretical concepts to support the understanding of problem and solutions.

5.3.3.5. Interview Questions' Selection

According to Mashuri et al. (2022) a semi-structured interview consists of a number of open-ended questions related to the areas of research. The use of open-ended questions enables the researcher to define the topic under investigation. Furthermore, Ahmad et al. (2019) state that using open ended questions provides opportunities to both the interviewer and interviewee to explore some topics in more detail to reach valuable recommendations. Following this perspective, the interview questions (Appendix G) are open ended as well as based on the research objectives of this study and literature review. Although, the highlighted questions in Appendix G shows the new questions raised during pilot studies to go into details. For research question 1 initially 4 questions were designed. However, after pilot studies 2 additional questions (Q1b and Q1d) were raised spontaneously following the interesting discussion from interviewees.

5.3.3.6. Data collected

21 interviews were conducted from 13 different private commercial banks out of 15 intended banks (Figure 34). The respondents of 13 banks (Figure 34) were happy to participate while data was not collected from Summit and Samba bank only (2 out of 15) as respondents had high confidentiality issues and management was not cooperative. Thus, 21 interviews were conducted. The interviewees were contacted from LinkedIn and some with references. Further, the snowballing technique of non-probability sampling was used whereby the participants referred potential participants who took part in the interviews.

The collection of data has been quite challenging. First of all, the confidential issue was raised by many of the respondents. They were not comfortable to share confidential information about banks as their jobs and career could be at risk. To overcome this barrier, the researcher referred them to the ethical consideration aspect of university and ensured them that the confidentiality of banks and the participants would be guaranteed. Still, many of the respondents refused to participate in the research. However, snowballing technique proved to be useful as new participants felt confident considering the reference, while some participants only agreed to give non recorded interviews in person. Although, the participants were contacted through

Linked in, WhatsApp, and email. Zoom was used to conduct and record interviews, where allowed by interviewees. Though, the time difference between UK and Pakistan was a constraint to arrange good time for interview. However, the pilot studies (3 cases) enabled the researcher to plan accordingly to overcome any such barriers such as requesting further reference of interview (using snow bowling technique) after every interview.

Figure 34: Participated Private commercial banks of Pakistan

SBP (2019)

5.3.4. Research Strategies

A research strategy is a plan of action (data collection) to answer the research questions (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2016). According to Kabir (2016) data collection is a process of collecting and analysing information about variables of interest, using a developed systematic methodology which enables a researcher to answer generated research questions, test hypotheses and evaluate results. The following sections will discuss the different methods of data collection and justify why semi-structured interviews are used for this study.

5.3.4.1. The concept and importance of data collection

The basic purpose of any data collection is to capture reliable evidence which can be analysed and result in answering the research questions (Goundar, 2012). Also, the choice of suitable data collection methods and visibly defined instructions to use those methods correctly can help to reduce the possibility of occurrence of errors (August & Tuten, 2008). Henceforth, the author will make effort to choose the right methods of study for this research, based on the discipline of study (pragmatic approach) and previous studies conducted in similar context.

However, the process of data collection begins with determining which kind of data needs to be collected. Then a sample from a particular population is selected. Subsequently, different data collection methods are used to collect the data from that sample (Kabir, 2016). Although, the collected data falls into two categories, primary and secondary data which are further explained below (Ajayi, 2017).

5.3.4.2. Types of Data

5.3.4.2.1. Primary Data

The primary data is an original and unique data collected from the first-hand experience of researcher (Hox & Boeije, 2005). It is possible to conduct a research without secondary data but the research merely based on secondary data is not fully reliable and might be based on biasness as the secondary data is already manipulated by human beings. The most famous sources of collecting primary data include survey, questionnaire, interview, and observation as explained below (Ajayi, 2017).

5.3.4.2.1.1. Survey

Survey is the method of data collection in which the data is collected from a targeted group of people which obtains information about their opinions, behaviour, or knowledge relating to a specific topic. The common types of survey include written questionnaires or electronic (e-mail, Google form, or website), face to face or electronic interviews, and focus groups surveys (Ponto, 2015). For the purpose of this study, the interviews will be used as the same method has been used by Hafiz-Ali et al. (2019) conducting a research on 'Issues of E-Banking in Pakistan: Managers' Perceptions about E-Banking Issues.

a) Interview

This is a face-to-face conversation with the respondents. It is the most effective method of collecting in depth data unless the respondent intentionally hides the information (Walliman, 2006). There are three types of interviews named as unstructured, semi-structured, and structured. Semi structured interview is considered suitable for exploratory research where the qualitative aspect of study is concerned to get in depth knowledge of the research area. The semi structured interviews allow the researcher to combine a predetermined set of open questions to explore the knowledge on defined areas of research (Adams, 2015). According to Mashuri et al. (2022) the semi structured interview is more effective than other types of interviews because it will enable the researcher to get the required knowledge. Therefore, during this study the semi-structured interviews were used. However, the interviews were divided into two rounds. The first round was based on pilot studies to authenticate the research process, as explained in the following section. The second round incorporates interviews from CISOs (14) of banks. However, during second the interviews from other employees of banks (7) were also taken randomly.

The semi structured schedule used for pilot studies allowed the addition of questions during interview and to go in depth (Schoonenboom & Johnson, 2017). However, the interview questions are developed through literature review and research objectives of this study, conceptualised in the conceptual framework. The purpose of this is to relate the answers of interview questions to the research questions 1, 2, 3, and 4 to make the analysis easy and complete the research objectives 1, 2, 3, and 4 which will help to meet the ultimate aim of this study to find the key factors affecting the

cybersecurity governance of private commercial banks of Pakistan. However, the responses of interviewees were spontaneous rather than biased (Emans, 1986).

The interviews were taken via Zoom, as this allowed the respondents to feel comfortable knowing that with whom they are having conversation. Consequently, the response rate was higher, and the author was confident to ask more questions and take enough time (Collis & Hussey, 2014). Also, the interviewer recorded the interviews as well as observed the body language, expressions, and reactions relating to different questions. This helped the interviewer to interpret the results easily and accurately (Bowling & Ebrahim, 2005). Nevertheless, during recorded interviews, it was easy to take notes (Opdenakker, 2006).

Pilot Study

According to Arain, Campbell, Cooper, and Lancaster (2010) a pilot study is a small feasibility study conducted to test multiple aspects relating to matters planned for a large scale, in depth or confirmatory analysis. However, pilot study is not designed to answer specific research questions rather it facilitates the researcher to get estimated idea about the methods to be proposed before starting a large-scale study. Thus, it saves time and money preventing fatal flaws in the study (Vogel, and Draper-Rodi, 2017). For this purpose, during the month of May and June in 2023 three pilot studies were conducted.

The pilot studies involved three different people having relevant designations in the bank who could inform about important information to be used for analysis of this research. Those three respondents included two CISOs, and one cybersecurity risk analyst. Each interview for pilot studies ended up roughly after an hour. The questions used in pilot studies (Appendix G) aimed from respondents their understanding of the themes used in the study, estimated time for interviews distributing and emphasising on different topics discussed, behavioural aspects of interviewees including overall experience and identify any omissions. Although, the pilot studies confirmed that the themes of this study are comprehensive and understandable for interviews. This also provided an understanding of the level of information where the respondents felt confidential issues. Additionally, conducting pilot studies assisted the researcher test and refine research questions (Appendix G) and the process of relevant questions one

after another to relate themes in the analysis (Adams, 2015). The respondents of pilot study were experts of the field therefore answering the questions from research guide the respondents provided relevant answers which were easily connectable to the literature. This helped the interviewer to prompt relevant questions during this semi-structured interviews to go into deep insights of the topic. Moreover, pilot studies built the researcher confidence to establish affinity with the interviewees to gain their confidence and reduce observational bias (Mashuri et al., 2022). Hence, pilot study is used to evaluate the consistency of planned methods and processes of research strategy of the specific study (Lowe, 2019).

The critical incident technique was also found effective and adopted through the pilot studies which allowed interviewer to understand the reaction of actors under investigation towards required situation (Hughes, Williamson, and Lloyd, 2007). For example, to answer first research question (Which significant internal and external factors (challenges) are affecting the cybersecurity governance in the private commercial banks of Pakistan?) two additional sub-questions were added to the script which are:

Q1b. If customer awareness is important then what role does your bank play to create that awareness?

Q1d. If literacy is important then is a degree holder customer considered literate to support cybersecurity governance of your bank and what is literacy rate of your banking customers?

The question 1b was asked realising the interviewee emphasising on customer awareness as; *'Our customers need detailed awareness about how to use banking securely rather than making them aware generally. We need to think above than traditional concepts of training our customers (Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst)'*. This question then was asked from all other respondents and the responses have added valuable insights highlighting the capacity, role and cybersecurity understanding of banks. Similarly, question 1d. was inquired once the respondent critically mentioned that *'One of the major impacts of low financial and cyber literacy is poor understanding of cybersecurity and its importance. Consequently, they share their confidential data and become victim which result in financial loss to them and*

reputational loss to bank (Bank H: CISO)'. Likewise, to 1b question collecting responses from all respondents 1d question also added useful information specifying that what level of literacy is required for banking customers. These two questions are highlighted in interview schedule (Appendix G). This technique enabled the interviewer to get deeper knowledge of the reasons of actions of banks and their perception (Butterfield, Borgen, Amundson, and Maglio, 2005). Altogether, 2 new sub-questions were added in the script with the help of pilot study. These questions has been useful to investigate and answer the research questions appropriately.

Participants of Study

The main informants of this study are CISOs and IT risk managers.

CISO - A CISO is a chief information security officer (CISO). It is the highest designation in the Department of Cybersecurity. CISO is the head of cybersecurity in a bank. It is CISO's responsibility to implement comprehensive cybersecurity Myers to secure confidentiality, integrity, and availability of customers data. They must develop robust security protocols, encryption standards, and access security to protect customer data (Karanja, 2017). Thus, CISO is the mean dealer of cybersecurity governance within the bank. Therefore, CISOs are considered main informant of study.

Other Informants

The other informants apart of CISOs were cybersecurity risk analyst, customer relationship and marketing manager, operations head, senior credit control manager, cash controller, operations head, and senior retail and corporate banker. Besides cybersecurity risk analyst, remaining respondents do not work directly with CISOs yet they are part of bank and have knowledge of working environment of cybersecurity. Since, this study is not reliant on information about technological solutions which can be obtained from a technical person as CISO. Hence, every member of the bank can be considered as a respondent.

Interviewees' Bank Details and Profiling

The interview data was collected from 21 people who work in 13 different private commercial banks of Pakistan out of 15 selected banks. Each interview is assigned with the bank ID allocated by letters from A to M. Therefore, in the following data analysis and discussion (chapter 6 and 7) those banks will be presented as Bank A to M with 21 respondents along with their designations. However, each interviewee has distinctive position which has added valuable findings and case profiles of interviewees are shown in the following tables (7, 8, and 9).

The data is collected from at least one CISO within one branch of each from 13 banks. However, Bank D facilitated data from 2 branches for CISOs. This accumulate 14 interviews. Moreover, 7 remaining interviews were conducted randomly from within 13 different banks, representing other informants as discussed above. The information of banks is provided in Appendix – B.

Interviewees' Profiling Assessment

This section shows the professional profiles of 21 interviewees of private commercial banks of Pakistan who participated in this study. That is why it is called interviewees' profiling. The purpose of this section is to examine the qualifications, experience, and knowledge of the interviewees because the trustworthiness of qualitative data is dependent on the personal profiling of the interviewees which includes their qualifications, experience, and knowledge of the field. The stronger level of qualifications, experience, and knowledge of the field the interviewees have, the more likely the data will be valid (Hafiz Ali et al. 2019). Subsequently, this will help the author to be confident about the collected data that the data is collected from relevant people and make the results of this study reliable. The following tables (8 and 9) presents the interview number, interviewees' designations, qualifications, their experiences in the field and interview length (time). Table 7 presents the total number of interviews from each bank.

CISOs are the main respondents of this study and the Table 8 shows that apart of one CISO (Bank A) all of the CISOs hold the specialised Master's degrees in cybersecurity plus up to date diplomas, licences, certificates, and trainings to deal with dynamic

cybersecurity issues. Likewise, remaining 7 interviewees (except Bank E) have at least Master's degrees in their field which ensures that they qualify for their roles. Only one of the interviewees' holds bachelor's degree in commerce but alongside of that he also holds ACCA qualification to be eligible for his role. Furthermore, each CISO and other respondents must possess minimum of 5-year experience. This confirms that the interviewees have right experience of working and degrees to collect the required data for this study. Also, the purpose to use the mix of people (7) from banks having different designations was to get the detailed information about the study and match it (Nobles, 2021). Therefore, the responses of other participants were matched with CISOs' responses to validate results (Chapter Six – Tables of Quotes show the responses supported by other participants). The detailed analysis of interviewees' profiles will be presented in chapter six.

Once, the trustworthiness of collected data is ensured, now the data can be analysed confidently. However, the interview data will be analysed using themes so that it will ultimately answer the research questions and objectives. Also, the codebook used to generate themes is given in Appendix E.

Table 7: Bank Cases

Case No.	Bank Name	Respondents		Total Respondents from Each Bank
1	Bank A- Bank Al Habib	CISO	Cybersecurity Risk Analyst	2
2	Bank B- UBL	CISO	Customer relationship and marketing manager; Operations head	3
3	Bank C- Soneri Bank	CISO		1
4	Bank D- MCB	CISO		2
	Bank D1- MCB	CISO		
5	Bank E- Bank Alfalah	CISO	Senior credit control manager	2
6	Bank F- BOP	CISO	Cash controller; Operations head	3
7	Bank G- Habib Metropolitan	CISO	Senior retail and corporate banker	2
8	Bank H- Faisal Bank	CISO		1
9	Bank I- Allied Bank	CISO		1
10	Bank J- Habib Bank Limited	CISO		1
11	Bank K- JS Bank	CISO		1
12	Bank L- Standard Chartered	CISO		1
13	Bank M- Silk bank	CISO		1
Total		14	7	21

Author Developed

Table 8: CISOs' Profiling

Serial No.	Bank Name	Designation	Experience	Qualification	Time
1	Bank A	CISO	12-years	Bachelor's degree in IT, with multiple diplomas	1 Hour
2	Bank B	Senior information security member (CISO)	Over 10-years' experience in banking industry	Masters in Information Security Management	1 Hour
3	Bank C	Banking and Compliance officer (CISO)	8 years	Masters in science, Licenses and certificates	1 Hour
4	Bank D	CISO	8 years working as an auditor and various positions	Masters in cyber-Operations and warfare, USA. And BCS. License and certificates	1 Hour
5	Bank D1	Leading Information Security Consultant (CISO)	12 years-experience in networks, Information Technology, and Information Security	BS Electrical Engineering (Masters) and different licenses and certificates	1 Hour
6	Bank E	CISO	10-years	Masters in computer science IT and related certifications	1 Hour
7	Bank F	CISO	6-years	MIS and Database administration certification	1 Hour
8	Bank G	CISO	7-years	BS (Masters) in IT and diplomas	1 Hour
9	Bank H	CISO	7-years	MIS and certificate	1 Hour
10	Bank I	CISO	10-years	Master in IT and diploma (U.S)	1 Hour
11	Bank J	CISO	15-years	MIS and training in cybersecurity	1 Hour
12	Bank K	CISO	6-years	Master in IT and diploma	1 Hour
13	Bank L	CISO	8-years	MSc IT and certificate	1 Hour
14	Bank M	CISO	8-year	BS (Masters) in IT and certificate	1 Hour

Author Developed

Table 9: Other Respondents' Profiling

Serial No.	Bank Name	Designation	Experience	Qualification	Time
1	Bank A	Cybersecurity Risk Analyst	More than 5-years, expert in Financial Risk, Credit Risk, Market Risk, Banking and Compliance	Graduate in IT/ Masters	1 Hour
2	Bank B	Customer relationship and marketing manager	Over 10-years' experience in banking industry	MBA	1 Hour
3	Bank B	Operations head	Over 10-year experience in banking industry	MBA	1 Hour
4	Bank E	Senior credit control manager	20 years	B.Com, ACCA and certificates	1 Hour
5	Bank F	Cash controller	More than 5 years	MBA	1 Hour
6	Bank F	Operations head	Almost 5 years	Masters in banking	1 Hour
7	Bank G	Senior retail and corporate banker	More than 10-year experience	B.Com (Hons)/ Master's in Commerce	1 Hour

Author Developed

b) Questionnaire

Questionnaire is the most commonly used method of survey in quantitative research. It is a list of questions which can be either open ended or close ended about which the respondents give their opinion. It can be conducted using telephone, mail, face to face in a public area or an organisation, email etc. (Bryman & Bell, 2018). However, this study cannot be completed using quantitative data as it is of exploratory nature while quantitative questionnaire is more suitable for explanatory study (Dudovskiy, 2022; Collis & Hussey, 2014).

c) Critics of Interview for this Study

The data was planned to be collected from Pakistan, this could take a lot of time (Joinson, 2001) as the author had to arrange online meetings to take interviews. Although, the transcription of interviews also required a lot of time (Emans, 1986;

Creswell, 2014). Moreover, because of time difference in UK and Pakistan it was hard to manage the interview time which could best suit the author and the interviewee (Creswell et al., 2018).

5.3.4.2.1.2. Observations

This is a process of observing people while they are behaving or reacting towards a specific object (Barker, 1980). Observation can be carried out by informing or without informing the people who are being observed. Also, it can be conducted in natural settings and in artificially created environments as well (Busetto, Wick, & Gumbinger, 2020). However, this method is not possible for this study as it will require long time and access to such settings to make observations (Creswell, 2013).

5.3.4.2.1.3. Advantages of primary data

The basic advantage of primary data is that the collected data is specific to the research problem under study. Also, the primary data has not been published previously and is more reliable, authentic as well as objective. Because it is not changed or modified by individuals hence it has greater validity than secondary data (Creswell et al., 2018). The quality of data collected is assured as the author collects data herself so is confident about its quality. Besides, if required the further data can also be collected during study (Ajayi, 2017).

However, the primary data collection also has some disadvantages. The basic disadvantage of primary data is that the researcher needs a lot of time, money, and research to decide why, what, how, and when to collect the data (personally or virtually). The primary data collection also requires the consent of the respondent which hinders the data collection (Collis & Hussey, 2014).

5.3.4.2.2. Documentary Analysis

This is a data collected from a source which has already been published in any form. The literature review of the study is based on documentary data (Walliman, 2006). This data has been collected by someone else for a specific purpose, but it is used by the author for a different purpose (Collis & Hussey, 2014). The other sources of documentary data for this study include books, records, government reports,

newspapers, published statistical data, data achieves, published articles, journals, and databases etc. as it has been used in a similar study by Syed et al. (2019).

5.3.4.2.3. Advantages and disadvantages of documentary data

There is less effort required to collect documentary data as it is available on hand. Therefore, it is less expensive too as it can be accessed using free means or cheaper sources as mentioned above (Berndt, 2020). Finally, the user of documentary data is not responsible for the quality of data as it is not collected by himself or herself (Almeida et al., 2017).

On the other hand, the documentary data might not be reliable and accurate as the primary collector of this data might not be reliable, so the data can be misleading or biased. Therefore, for this study the only documentary data which is available from an authentic source will be collected (Ajayi, 2017). Besides, the documentary data becomes obsolete and older with time so might not be suitable for the current research. Hence, to meet the research objectives of this study only the recent data will be used and extra care will be carried out to use the documentary data for this study (Berman, 2017).

5.3.5. Techniques and Procedures

5.3.5.1. Participants' Profile Analysis

First of all, the detailed analysis of Participants' profiles (section 6.2.) were made using the total number of participants as a base. This ensured the appropriateness of participants to take part in the research.

5.3.5.2. Thematic Analysis

Thematic analysis is one of the most widely used types of analysis for qualitative data. It consists of identifying, analysing, and interpreting meanings of qualitative data (Braun and Clarke, 2006). In thematic analysis codes and themes are used to analyse the qualitative data. A code is a topic relating to literature or constructed inductively by in-depth reading of qualitative data. Furthermore, a theme is a conceptual topic that is more abstract than code, which can be developed in the following two ways (Nowell et al., 2017).

5.3.5.3. Codebook Approach of Themes

The qualitative study with semi structured interviews benefits from the flexibility to probe on specific issues using more open and follow up questions and provides a framework to make prior themes (Cohen et al., 2011). Thus, there are two approaches to develop the themes from qualitative data. One approach is inductive whereby the codes are generated through deep data review. The other approach is deductive whereby the codes are based on initially considered literature or conceptual framework (Nowell et al., 2017). Basically, a study based on conceptual framework or theoretical framework can be based on exclusively deductive codes. Also, if conceptual framework or theoretical framework of a study provides the strong stance regarding what kind of themes the study should expect then the themes can be generated from that framework (Gale et al., 2013). However, according to Fereday and Muir-Cochrane (2006) it is best to use a hybrid approach to develop themes in exploratory when deductive themes are used. In this approach deductive code manuals (codebook) are used initially to code the qualitative data followed by the inductive codes generated - which provide new information from participants, through in-depth reading of qualitative data. A code manual is a data management tool which helps to organise segments of similar or related data to assist in interpretation and facilitating with that clear picture of evidence for credibility of research (Crabtree & Miller, 1999). Before starting the in-depth analysis, the researcher defines the codebook with examples (Fereday & Muir-Cochrane, 2006). The codebook for this study is provided in Appendix E.

5.3.5.4. Themes development

In the codebook, the nodes were developed using conceptual framework contents to cover every aspect of the research. Braun and Clarke (2006) mentioned that 'a node let the researcher collect the relevant data in one place so that it can show the emerging patterns and ideas to generate themes.' These deductive parent nodes were considered sub-themes that helped to develop the themes which matched with the interview questions and components of conceptual framework. Also, the inductive themes of additional research components were discovered (Appendix E). The same methodology was used by Nowell et al. (2017) in their exploratory study based on 117 interviews.

5.3.5.5. Coding Process

Swain (2020) states that using manual coding is best if fewer than 30 interviews are used. It will furnish the researcher with in-depth knowledge of the study by writing step by step findings by hand instead of just inserting information in software like NVivo which will generate the results. This study has used the following method of generating themes as introduced by Swain (2020), with a little difference where Swain (2020) generated post priori nodes throughout the reading for deductive nodes.

Step One - Transcribing Interviews

The first step in thematic analysis was to transcribe all the interviews into English language as some of the interviews have been conducted in Urdu. Also, the 4 written (out of 21) interviews were transformed on word and then transcribed.

Step Two - Familiarising with interviews' data

The second step was to read the full transcripts of each interview to identify which part of data matched with which node.

Step Three - Division of interview transcript data

In the third step, the researcher copied and pasted the data that was relevant to each node.

Step Four - Generating codes

In the next step, with detailed reading of data under each node the codes were generated using the code book guide. Each code was assigned with the number to show how many times it was repeated throughout all transcriptions.

Step Five - Identifying sub-themes

The generated nodes in the above step highlighted the sub-themes which could be used under a main theme.

Step Six - Generating themes

Finally, the sub-themes were best fit in the components of conceptual framework which were named as main themes. This helped to conduct a detailed analysis of the aspects of data of core interest (Braun & Clarke, 2006). This also saved time by preventing having to create too many codes which would result in attaining the clarity in organising and interpreting data by eliminating counterproductive codes (King, 2004).

Step Seven - Inductive themes

Completing the deductive themes, the separated data irrelevant to codebook nodes was read in detail to generate inductive codes. Then those codes were listed under new nodes. These nodes were then aligned with the literature to find the relevant themes (Appendix E).

5.3.5.6. NVivo Software

After aligning the qualitative data in codebook this data was transformed to NVivo software to generate the final results as using codebook data will help to provide the most required data (Nowell et al. 2017). Following the themes generated through coding and thematic analysis, the key findings of the study along with quotes to develop the understanding of results was presented. The next step was to analyse interview data comparing the final results with the literature review and revise conceptual framework. Finally, the factors of interest were found and recommendations were provided.

5.4. Ethical Consideration

Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2012) state that the researcher should follow the ethical codes which highlight the rights of participants of research who can be affected by research. The research ethics are based on two perspectives: teleology and deontology. Teleology is the concept that if the benefit of collected data is higher than the negative impact on the participants then the required data should be collected anyway ignoring the rights of participants (Ismail & Benlahcene, 2018). In the reverse case, deontological perspective recommends that working beyond the rules is never

justifiable and in case the rules are disputed then they must be reappraised or changed when required (Brown, 1987). This study has followed the deontological perspective. All the participants were required to give prior consent to participate in this study. A consent letter and participation information sheet was sent to participants for qualitative data. These documents clearly mention the research objectives, participants' right to withdraw their consent and ensured the confidentiality of identity of participants (Baumane-Vitolina, Cals, & Sumilo, 2016).

5.5. Validity and Reliability of Interview Data

According to Haq (2014) the qualitative data is concerned with trustworthiness while the quantitative data is concerned with rigorosity (validity and reliability). However, the trustworthiness in qualitative research is the same as reliability and validity in quantitative research. Validity refers to the integrity and implementation of research methods used by researcher and the precision to present the accurate findings interpreting the data. Thus, to make the research results valid there should be consistency between theories, models, and their justification of theoretical study (Whittemore, Chase, and Mandle, 2001). Comparatively, reliability justifies dependability of analytical methods used To confirm the replication of results by the researchers (Noble, and Smith, 2015). Stahl and King (2020) state that Lincoln and Guba (1985) presented the approach for trustworthiness (validity and reliability) by credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability.

Credibility - it is a measure to figure out if that research findings are correct and accurate. To confirm the credibility of research data the researcher has used the persistent observation. The responses relating to each component of research from each interviewee were compared after conducting each interview with other conducted interviews (Nowell et al., 2017).

Transferability - Once the credibility of research is confirmed then the researcher can use thick descriptions to indicate that the research findings are applicable in other circumstances, which is called transferability. In case of this study, thick description refers to the rich details of the data collection process, the original interviews' data and their transcription, the method of approaching participants is available. This makes the findings of this study transferable to relevant context. Furthermore, the purposeful

sampling (CISO and IT risk managers) and data saturation by applying the pilot study and extensive interviews confirms the repetition of results which could be applied to other banks (Shenton, 2004).

Confirmability - The confirmability of research shows that the researcher has been unbiased throughout the research and the findings are based on participants' responses. The data collected through recording using simple and understandable questions, the analysis made using thematic coding, and results withdrawn from them shows the consistency of data and unbiasedness. Moreover, the interview data was reviewed by supervisor (Stahl & King, 2020).

Dependability - Finally, dependability confirms that the findings of this study can be repeated under same cohort of participants, coders, and context. The dependability of this study can be confirmed through the full record of interviews, transcripts, data analysis, and step by step work, which is available with researcher (Lietz et al., 2006).

CHAPTER SIX: QUALITATIVE FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

6.1. Introduction

This chapter provides insights on the qualitative data collected using open-ended questions in semi structured interviews. The results and analysis of data represents the responses of 21 interviewees which consists of 14 CISOs, and 7 other respondents from 13 different banks. The purpose of data analysis is to highlight the key results to demonstrate the factors and threats of cybersecurity governance faced by PCBP. It will also help to explain the logical understanding and perception of PCBP about cybersecurity governance using the interpretivism technique, providing recommendations for effective cybersecurity governance.

The first section of the analysis presents the profiles of participants of study for example, designation, experience, qualification, gender, and age. Followed by it, this chapter will provide insights of useful key analysis and findings of factors and threats of cybersecurity governance in PCBP. This will emphasise the importance of research findings.

6.2. Participants' Profile Analysis

Demographic analysis which are consisted of designation, experience, qualification, gender, and age of respondents will be presented in this section using overall participants' composition and participants' size. This data will indicate the nature and characteristics (appropriateness of participants to participate in the study) of the main respondents of this study - CISOs (who are responsible for ensuring cybersecurity governance within banks), and others (part of working environment of bank where cybersecurity governance is implemented through CISOs).

Designation Analysis

The following Table 10 of designation analysis shows that majority of respondents (14 out of 21) were CISOs. The designation of CISO is the highest position in a bank to control the cybersecurity governance system. Therefore, the CISO are the best candidates who can provide rigorous information to complete this study. One third of the respondents (7 out of 21) were from the other departments of banks. Although they

are not directly working with cybersecurity governance but are important part of bank implementing the guidelines, processes, and controls provided by CISOs to improve cybersecurity governance. Hence, the data collected from them will be useful to complement the information provided from CISOs to ensure how their subordinates appreciate their efforts. However, responses of other participants were supported by CISOs.

Table 10: Designation Analysis

Designation	Participants' Size	Overall Participants' Composition
CISO	14	14/21
Other	7	7/21
Total	21	21

Author Developed

Gender Analysis

The gender analysis depict that majority of respondents (20 out of 21) were male besides the bank F who was a female (1 out of 21) cash controller. However, it is assumed that gender difference will not affect the results of this study as both male and female work in the similar environment of cybersecurity governance in banks, experiencing multiple procedures, protocols, and controls to ensure information security.

Table 11: Gender Analysis

Gender	Participants' Size	Overall Participants' Composition
Male (CISOs and others)	20	20/21
Female (Cash controller)	1	1/21
Total	21	21

Author Developed

CISOs' – Qualification, Experience, and Age Analysis

The designation of CISOs confirms their suitability to collect the data. Furthermore, their qualification is another aspect to analyse. The criteria to appoint a CISO is to

have advance bachelor's degree at minimum in Computer Systems, Computer Engineering, Management Information System or equivalent from an institute recognised by Higher Education body of Pakistan or international reputable university, with extensive professional experience of information technology management. Candidates with certifications of for example, CCISO, CISSP, CISM, CISA, CEH or OSCP are preferred (SBP, 2016).

The Table 12a below shows that 13 out of 14 CISOs had master’s degrees in one of the above-mentioned disciplines. Only one responding (1 out of 14) had bachelor's degree but along with that he also had cybersecurity certificate to be eligible for his role. In spite, majority of CISOs (8 out of 14) also acquired cybersecurity certification while 3 also had cybersecurity management licence. The licences enable CISOs to be a legitimate individual to provide cybersecurity services. In addition, 4 out of 14 CISOs further completed cybersecurity diplomas to update their knowledge of the field. Finally, 1 out of 14 CISOs received specific training to get updated skills along with its qualification.

The age of CISOs confirms their level of involvement in industry and maturity of experience. The Table 12d shows that 10 out of 14 CISOs are of age category between 26-35 years while 4 out of 14 were between 36-45. This illustrates that all of the respondents fall in the category of young but mature people of industry having work experience of their field between 5 to 15 years (table 12c). Hence, it can be concluded that the profiles of CISOs participated in the study meet the criteria to be eligible for their roles therefore, the information collected from them is valid and reliable.

Table 12a: CISOs’ Qualification

Qualification:	Participants’ Size	Overall Participants’ Composition
Bachelors	1	1/14
Masters	13	13/14
PhD	0	0/14
Other	0	0/14
Total	14	14

Author Developed

Table 12b: Relevant qualifications and trainings

<i>Relevant qualifications and trainings</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Licence	3
Certification	8
Diploma	4
Other training	1

Author Developed**Table 12c: CISOs' Experience**

Experience:	Participants' Size	Overall Participants' Composition
Less than 2 years	0	0/14
Between 2 and 5 years	0	0/14
Between 5 and 10 years	10	10/14
Between 10 and 15 years	4	4/14
Between 15 and 20 years	0	0/14
More than 20 years	0	0/14
Total	14	14

Author Developed**Table 12d: CISOs' Age**

Age:	Participants' Size	Overall Participants' Composition
26-35	10	10/14
36-45	4	4/14
46-55	0	0/14
56-65	0	0/14
Above 65	0	0/14
Total	14	14

Author Developed

Other Respondents' – Qualification, Experience, and Age Analysis

The other respondents consist of Cybersecurity risk analyst, Customer relationship and marketing manager, Operations head, Senior credit control manager, Cash controller, Operations head, and Senior retail and corporate banker. Besides cybersecurity risk analysts, the designations of six other respondents are not directly related to cybersecurity decisions. Although, they are part of cybersecurity governance controls implementation within banks. Table 13a depicts that 6 out of 7 of them hold master's degree in relevant fields of their expertise and only 1 out of 7 respondents held bachelor's degree (holding ACCA and certificates with 20 years' experience in banking representing seniority of age category of 46-55 year). Similarly, Table 13b illustrates that 2 out of 7 respondents had 5 to 10 years while 3 out of 7 participants had 10 to 15 years' experience of the field in banks. Only 1 out of 7 respondents had almost five years' experience (Cash controller) falling in age category of 26 to 35 year. Hence, majority of respondents (6 out of 7) were between the age of 26 to 45 years (Table 13c) that again categorised as young and mature people of banking industry with the work experience ranging from 5 to 15 years mostly.

Therefore, it can be confirmed that these respondents must have necessary experience to elaborate the cybersecurity work environment and its issues faced on daily basis within bank. Consequently, data collected from them is relevant and valid.

Table 13a: Other Respondents' Qualification

Qualification:	Frequency	Percentage
Bachelors	1	1/7
Masters	6	6/7
PhD	0	0/7
Other	0	0/7
Total	7	7

Author Developed

Table 13b: Other Respondents' Experience

Experience:	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 2 years	0	0/7
Between 2 and 5 years	1	1/7
Between 5 and 10 years	2	2/7
Between 10 and 15 years	3	3/7
Between 15 and 20 years	1	1/7
More than 20 years	0	0/7
Total	7	7

Author Developed

Table 13c: Other Respondents' Age

Age:	Frequency	Percentage
26-35	3	3/7
36-45	3	3/7
46-55	1	1/7
56-65	0	0/7
Above 65	0	0/7
Total	7	7

Author Developed

6.2.1. Summary of Participants' Profile Analysis

In short, the Participants' Profile analysis show that the designations of main respondents (CISOs) of this study are appropriate while the designations of other respondents are also helpful to get the insightful information about the cybersecurity governance. Moreover, all of the respondents (21) held the required qualifications (Master's, licence, certificates, diplomas or other qualifications where applicable), and experience of the field necessary to collect the data. The age of majority of the respondents (CISOs – 14 out of 14 and other respondents - 6 out of 7) fall between 26 to 45 years that prescribes the level of competitiveness and maturity relating it to their experiences. The gender differences are not considered to differentiate the level of expertise and learning. The following section provides the key results of data collected for this study and their analysis.

6.3. Analysing Cybersecurity Governance in PCBP

This section shows the findings of all interview questions, analysing each question using key themes, keywords, and quotes from the respondents for each research question. There were 4 research questions however, each research question had multiple sub-questions to clearly understand the perception of respondents about the research questions under investigation. According to Braun and Clarke (2006) the critical implication of thematic analysis enables to produce astute analysis to address the research questions. In context of this view, the theme were generated (section 5.3.5.4.) by forming analytical codes from descriptive codes – resonating them to research questions (Section 1.4.3). The analytical codes guided to map the findings of research questions and build the following themes (supported by sub-themes) from the literature review/conceptual framework. Investigating research question 1, 2, 3, and 4 sub-questions Q1a to Q6; Q7 to Q10; Q11 to Q12; and Q13 to Q16 are inquired respectively, as presented in quotation tables throughout the chapter. Although, to discuss the results of this study the banks are allocated with the case numbers. Even though, it is not a case study technique but aligning banks with case numbers will support effective data presentation as 6 of the banks (Bank A, B, D, E, F, G) have more than 1 respondents (Table 7). The following are the responses research questions one to four.

Research Question One: Which significant internal and external factors (challenges) are affecting the cybersecurity governance in the private commercial banks of Pakistan?

6.3.1. Theme 1: External Factors affecting cybersecurity governance in private commercial banks of Pakistan

6.3.1.1. Sub-theme: Customer Awareness and Cybersecurity Governance

The following Tables 14a to 14f show the key codes of interviewees about ‘customer awareness’ relating it to customer training, customer literacy, literacy level of general public and awareness, literacy measurement, literacy rate, and awareness program by government. To investigate the role of customer awareness of cybersecurity questions (Q1a to Q1f) were raised, as mentioned in Table 14g.

When asked does awareness of your customers has any impact on cybersecurity governance of your bank, if yes then how, and what percentage of your customers are aware?, They responded as follows:

In view of all participants' experiences and perceptions (21 out of 21) of customer awareness, in Pakistan customer awareness is one of the most critical factor to improve the cybersecurity governance of their banks (Table 14a). The banks have not given attention to customer awareness neglecting it as a human factor and have been focusing on technological solutions (Bank K: CISO). While, Bank A and L (CISOs) mentioned that customer unawareness make them victims as they reveal their confidential information which they should not disclose. Indicating their customer awareness rates from countrywide-annual surveys conducted by banks (accumulating the results of all branches) the CISOs of 2, 5, and 3 banks reported 30%, 40%, and 50% customer awareness respectively. This depicts that most of the banks (5 out of 13) have 40% customer awareness rate while 2 banks also had 30% customer awareness, which is lowest. However, majority of the banks (10 out of 13) fall in the category of maximum 50% awareness rate while only two banks had 60% and one bank had 70% customer awareness rate.

The CISO of bank B pointed out that having best performance reward internationally in 2020 their customer awareness rate was 70% because most of their customers are educated businessmen or job holders. He also mentioned that their bank is very strict when opening an account and they use critical verification system to avoid cybercrime. A customer who does not meet the minimum criteria of awareness cannot open account with their bank. Yet, 70% of cybersecurity issues are result of customers' mistakes, even being aware (*also confirmed from Bank B: Operations head*). Bank B (CISO) also stated that not all banks are using such verification systems as they are expensive (*also mentioned by Bank B: Operations head and Bank A CISO*).

Comparatively, Bank G (senior retail and corporate banker) mentioned that according to annual survey in 2021 their customer awareness rate increased to 41% still the cybercrime report as well showed the increased rate for that specific year. Similarly, Bank I (CISO) highlighted that having 50% customer awareness rate our information security assets remain 50% unsecure from unaware customers, hence, customer unawareness makes management to struggle in cybersecurity governance even

having latest technology (Bank H CISO). Further highlighting customer awareness issue Bank K (CISO) mentioned that identifying data leaked through social engineering, customers can call bank and block the card but the issue remains unawareness to perform this activity. The concern to worry is that:

“If the financial loss is resulted from customers’ side unintentionally by sharing their details (through social engineering or online websites) still the bank tries to recover as much as possible to build customers’ confidence. Customers have attitude of imposing all responsibility on bank (Bank J: CISO).”

Thus, the responses of all interviewees about customer awareness suggested that this is one of the critical factor which banks must consider to improve their cybersecurity governance. Backing up this stance, the following question was asked from the interviewees.

Table 14a: Customer Awareness

Customer Awareness	CISOs	Other Respondents
One of the most critical factor human factor (21)	All	All
Neglecting human factor (1)	Bank K	
Awareness rate 30% (2), 40% (5), 50% (3), 60% (2), 70% (1)	13 Banks	13 Banks
50% customer awareness means 50% asset security (1)	Bank I	
Our bank struggles with 40% awareness (1)	Bank H	
Awarded for best performance internationally in 2020 (2)	Bank B	Bank B: Operations head
Our customers are mostly job holders or businessmen, so they are literate and aware about cybersecurity (2)	Bank B	Bank B: Operations head
Although we use critical verification system because of low literacy (2)	Bank B	Bank B: Operations head
41% of their customers are aware but cybercrime increased (1)		Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker
Well-educated people become victim		Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst
Customers can block the card by calling but unaware (1)	Bank K	
Bank tries to recover as much as possible to build customers’ confidence (1)	Bank J	
Customers have attitude of imposing all responsibility on bank (1)	Bank J	
Unawareness results in fraud (2)	Bank K and L	
Not all banks using expensive system available (3)	Bank A and B	Bank B: Operations head
People reveal confidential information to unauthorised people (1)	Bank A	
Customers need to understand which information they can disclose (1)	Bank L	

Source: Interview Data

Customer Training

To answer the fact that what role your banks play to aware their customers the following claims were found:

All of the participants (21 out of 21) ascertained that there is no specific training required by State Bank to be given to customers (Table14b). Banks aware their customers about cybersecurity but using limited resources such as guiding them in person, by messages, e-mail, notice boards, website, brochures, posters, and handouts etc. Bank E further added that:

The training is a great help to the customers but again you need infrastructure, finances, room, and everything. There are millions of customers. We can only train top 200 or 300 customers of each branch and that will greatly help for the security for the banks and the customers. However, government has this potential (Bank E: Senior credit control manager; supported by Bank A CISO).

The similar thought was shared by all Bank A and M (CISOs) and Bank F: Cash controller suggesting that awareness is not given attention because its time consuming and costly. On the other hand, customers do not bother to learn how they can make secure use of e-banking (*all CISOs-except Bank B, and Bank F: Cash controller*). This could be supported by the statement of *Bank E: Senior credit control manager* that our ATM cards are supported by third party services who provide clear written guidance about not sharing confidential information. Still, customers are caught up by social engineers, ignoring the guidance provided. In this regard, Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst insisted that:

Our customers need detailed awareness about how to use banking securely rather than making them aware generally. We need to think above than traditional concepts of training our customers (also mentioned by CISOs - Bank D, I, and J).

Supporting this point of view, the concern was brought into attention that government of Pakistan need to use multiple channels of awareness at national level (*CISOs - Bank A, D and M; Bank E: Senior credit control manager*) such as using TV and radio

as this will help customers to be aware of cybersecurity of e-banking regardless of their education (Bank M: CISO).

Hence, these findings assert that customer awareness can play a major role in cybersecurity governance of banks but the resources to invest in such awareness is a hurdle. Moving forward the next relevant question was as follows.

Table 14b: Impact of Customer Training on Awareness

<i>Impact of Customer Training on Awareness</i>	CISO	Other Respondents
No specific training is given (generally required by SBP) (21)	All	All
Banks aware the customers about cybersecurity (21)	All	All
Limited channels of awareness (21)	All	All
Guide customers in person, by SMS, email, notices displayed and website, brochures, posters, handouts, (21)	All	All
No training because of lack of time, infrastructure, finances, room etc. (2)	Bank A	Bank E: Senior credit control manager
Time consuming and costly (4)	Bank A and M	Bank E: Senior credit control manager Bank F: Cash controller
People don't bother to know about cybersecurity (14)	All except Bank B	Bank F: Cash controller
ATM cards and credit cards of our bank are backed by big there (1)		Bank E: Senior credit control manager
Government of Pakistan need to use multiple channels of awareness at national level (4)	Bank A, D and M	Bank E: Senior credit control manager
Our customers need detailed awareness (4)	Bank D, I, and J	Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst
Regardless of education customers will have awareness through TV and Radio	Bank M	

Source: Interview Data

Customer Literacy

When inquired, can the level of literacy of your customers be useful for their cybersecurity awareness? If yes then how The following responses were received:

Table 14c depicts that all CISOs and other respondents (21 out of 21) emphasised that customer literacy is the most relevant to customer awareness. When bank make efforts to aware their customers, their literacy level hinders it. Bank K proposed that 70% people in Pakistan are the easy victims of cybercriminals with low literacy and awareness. Pursuing it, 3 out of 13 banks presented the following viewpoint:

A person who is literate (financially literacy) will have awareness while an illiterate person will not have or have less awareness comparatively (Bank F: Cash controller; supported by Bank J and M CISOs).

Concurrently, asserting the importance of customer literacy Bank H (CISO) told that:

One of the major impacts of low financial and cyber literacy is poor understanding of cybersecurity and its importance. Consequently, they share their confidential data and become victim which result in financial loss to them and reputational loss to bank (Bank H: CISO).

Simultaneously, 2 out of 21 (L-CISO and Bank G-Senior retail and corporate banker) banks highlighted that to deal with literacy issue customers are provided instructions based on their qualifications to ensure their understanding of secure use of e-banking, at the time of account opening. Still, if a customer is negligent then he is responsible for its literacy.

However, Bank L-CISO and Bank G-Senior retail and corporate banker (2 out of 13 banks) mentioned that a banking customer must be at least graduated to be aware of cybersecurity issues. Alternatively, another 2 out of 13 banks (*Bank M -CISO; Bank E: Senior credit control manager*) showed that our customers need some level of financial literacy instead of very good level of literacy to securely use e-banking services provided. A similar view was provided by 4 out of 13 banks:

Regardless of degree if a person is aware about cybersecurity is considered a literate customer but we have very few numbers of such intellectual people (Bank E: Senior credit control manager; supported by Bank A, L, and E CISOs).

Hence, being financially literate will support the learning in general (2 out of 13 banks - *Bank J and M CISOs*). This confirms the answer for above question that customer literacy is very relevant to aware them about secure use of e-banking services as a financially literate person can learn quickly. However, the level of literacy do not have to be very high. To clarify this concept the following question was asked.

Table 14c: Impact of Customer Literacy on Awareness

<i>Impact of Customer Literacy on Awareness</i>	CISO	Other Respondents
One of the most critical factor (21)	All	All
Customer literacy is an issue (21)	All	All
Literacy level relates to awareness (3)	Bank J and M	Bank F: Cash controller
70% people are vulnerable to cyberspace	Bank K	
Bank with illiterate customers is more vulnerable to cyberattacks (1)	Bank H	
Customers should be graduated (2)	Bank L	Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker
Instructions base on qualification (2)	Bank L	Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker
At the time of account opening customer is informed (1)		Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker
If a customer is negligent then he is responsible (2)	Bank L	Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker
Users need some level of literacy rather than a good level of literacy (2)	Bank M	Bank E: Senior credit control manager
Degree does not matter (4)	Bank A, L, and E	Bank E: Senior credit control manager

Source: Interview Data

Literacy Measurement and Literacy Rate

To investigate If a degree holder customer is considered literate to support cybersecurity governance of your bank and what is literacy rate of your banking customers? The responses were as follows:

The findings in Table 14d show that for banking cybersecurity, a literate person can be the one who is aware to operate a system securely (21 out of 21 respondents). As mentioned above (4 out of 13 banks), the degree is not a concern (CISOs - Bank A, L, and E; Bank E: Senior credit control manager). Bank B further elaborated mentioning that we use enhanced due diligence and transaction monitoring system to determine the level of customer digital literacy rather than financial literacy. Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker discussed KYC (know your customer) system to identify the level of their customer literacy. In addition, the CISO of bank G clearly spotted that:

“For a Financial Institution, any customer who takes care of his personal/banking data is literate, irrespective of his formal education level (Bank G).”

Henceforth, all above views of the respondents (21 out of 21) confirmed that degree is not important however, the secure use of e-banking will be considered as customer literacy for the financial institution. Though, the digital literacy is supported by financial literacy.

However, the results also showed that only 4 out of 13 banks (Bank A, B, D, and L) had 70% literacy rate which is highest out of all the responded banks (13). Only one bank (K) had 60% literacy rate while, Bank C (1), Bank J and E (2), Bank F, I, and M (3), Bank G and H (2) had 5%, 30%, 40% and 50% literacy rate respectively. Thus, majority of banks (8 out of 13) fall in category of 50% literacy rate. Moreover, considering the importance of awareness and literacy in general from the above discussion, the following question was inquired.

Table 14d: Literacy measurement and literacy rate

<i>Literacy measurement and literacy rate</i>	CISO	Other Respondents
A literate customer is defined as who knows how to operate a system securely (21)	All	All
Enhance due diligence, Transaction monitoring System (1)	Bank B	
Regardless of degree is aware how to deal with cybersecurity (4)	Bank A, L, and E	Bank E: Senior credit control manager
Using KYC system (1)		Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker
Customer taking care of his personal/banking data is literate (1)	Bank G	
5% literacy (1 – Bank C), 30% literacy (2 – Bank J and E), 40% literacy (3 – Bank F and I, M), 50% literacy (2 – Bank G and H), 60% literacy (1 - Bank K), 70% literacy (4 – Bank A, B, D, and L)	13 Banks	13 Banks

Source: Interview Data

Literacy Level of General Public And Awareness

The following findings show the relation of public literacy and awareness to cybersecurity governance of investigated banks:

The Table 14e illustrates that all respondents (21 out of 21) confirmed that the literacy and awareness level of general public highly contributes to effective cybersecurity governance of banks. All CISOs; Bank E: Senior credit control manager and Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker (16 out of 21 respondents) told that the literacy level is low in Pakistan, around 60%. *Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst* shed light on the reality that:

“The increasing trend of use of internet have emerged the trend of online payments especially for shopping. And majority of people who use internet is based on teenagers (less literate and have very less or no awareness of cybersecurity). However, use of online services involves third party services for example websites or online payment methods whereby the mentioned majority uses bank cards mostly of their guardians or family members. In this way if they are not aware about cybersecurity, they will share the bank details of our customers which will result in data breach (Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst).”

Bank G (CISO) added as I have experienced that very educated and technology savvy people fall prey to simple social engineering just because of lack of awareness. Furthermore, Bank J and M (CISOs) highlighted that higher the rate of literacy and awareness of cybersecurity among general public will result in mitigating the cybercrimes, by developing the culture of cybersecurity. 5 out of 13 banks recommended that there is need of awareness at large scale (Bank A, C and M – CISOs; Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst; and Bank E: Senior credit control manager).

Therefore, referring to all these points it is concluded that general public literacy and awareness can help to improve bank cybersecurity. However, following the perspective of low level of literacy and banks with lack of funds to spread the awareness at the large level, the next question was as below.

Table 14e: Literacy level of general public and awareness

Literacy level of general public and awareness	CISO	Other Respondents
Literacy level of general public and their awareness about cybersecurity plays an effective role (21)	All	All
Literacy level of general public is low, around 60% (16)	All (14)	Bank E: Senior credit control manager Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker
Majority of people who use internet is based on teenagers (1)		Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst
Use bank cards mostly of their guardians or family member (1)		Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst
Higher the literacy and awareness of cybersecurity (culture), lower the chances of becoming victim (2)	Bank J and M	
Awareness at large platforms by government (5)	Bank A, C and M	Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst; Bank E: Senior credit control manager
Educated and technology savvy people falling prey to simple social engineering	Bank G	

Source: Interview Data

Lack of Awareness Program by Government

Specifically explaining that how the awareness is possible where literacy rate is also low, the interviewees provided following stances:

All respondents (21 out of 21) responded that there is an urgent need of awareness programme by government of Pakistan to spread cybersecurity awareness in whole country (table 14f). *Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst mentioned that:*

The increasing trend of using internet in Pakistan is resulting to increase the presence of people of Pakistan in cyberspace simultaneously. This indicates the usage of technology is appreciated by people. However, the drawback of technology cannot be ignored that technology is a source of data confidentiality breach.

Bank A, C, D, M – CISOs; Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst; Bank E: Senior credit control manager (5 out of 13 banks) mentioned that the government of Pakistan has already conducted some conventions to aware general public about cybersecurity however those conventions are not sufficient. There is a need of awareness at large platforms. Additionally, Bank I (CISO) mentioned that it is government's responsibility to aware its nation to secure their information assets. Bank M (CISO) supported it as

'it is matter of whole nation instead of the banking customers. Therefore, 7 out of 13 banks suggested that government should consider the literacy level of people and accordingly provide the well-designed awareness programmes (Bank A, B, G, H, I, J, and K – CISOs). While, Bank A, C, D, and M (CISOs); Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst; Bank E: Senior credit control manager (6 out of 13 banks) recommended that the use of television, radio and similar extended channels can be useful to spread awareness in whole country. Bank A asserted that it is government's and organisations' Corporate Social Responsibility to spread the awareness and banks have done a lot in this regard. This statement puts responsibility on government of Pakistan. However, Bank A, B, L, and M (4 out of 14 CISOs) said that government of Pakistan cannot afford all awareness programmes running across the board though they can focus on certain awareness programmes based on the literacy and awareness level of people.

Table 14f: Lack of awareness program by government

Lack of awareness program by government	CISO	Other Respondents
Urgent need of awareness program by Government (21)	All	All
Increase in presence of people of Pakistan in cyberspace (1)		Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst
Technology is a source of data confidentiality breach (1)		Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst)
It is government's responsibility to aware the people (1)	Bank I	
Well-designed awareness program by government based on the category of people (7)	Bank A, B, G, H, I, J, and K	
This is the matter of whole nation rather than only banking customers	Bank M	
Conventions every three or six months will not be effective (6)	Bank A, C, D, and M	Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst; Bank E: Senior credit control manager
The use of television radio and extended channels is useful (6)	Bank A, C, D, and M	Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst; Bank E: Senior credit control manager
It is CSR and banks have done a lot (1)	Bank A	
Pakistan government cannot afford to have all the awareness programme running across the board (4)	Bank A, B, L, and M	

Source: Interview Data

Summary for Customer Awareness Findings

All (21 out of 21) of the respondents agreed that customer awareness is one of the critical factor with no specific training provided by banks, as it is beyond the capacity of banks (table 14a). Moreover, it is emphasised that customer literacy, and awareness and literacy of public along with government awareness programmes can play a major role towards customer awareness. The government have to take initiatives to introduce well designed and relevant awareness programmes based on the level of understanding of people in the country. In general, low literacy rate (under 60%) is indicated from 16 out of 21 respondents. Whereas, customer literacy is measured in banks if a customer is able to use e-banking services without compromising information security regardless of degree (21-all respondents). Table 14g provides the key quotes of interviews to support these findings.

Table 14g: Customer Awareness Quotes – Q1A to Q1f

<i>Q1a. Does awareness of your customers have any impact on cybersecurity governance of your bank, if yes then how?</i>	Customer Awareness - customer training, customer literacy, literacy level of general public and awareness, literacy measurement, literacy rate, and awareness program by government	Supported by CISOs	Supported by Other Respondents
	"Management has been considering only technological solutions as a best measure to deal with cybersecurity issue neglecting human factor. In reality, with increasing cybercrime rates the technological solutions should be considered side by side of human factors to make effective use of them (Bank K: CISO)."		
	"50% customer awareness means 100% of your information security assets will be utilised but there are chances that these assets only could help those customers who are aware of cybersecurity (Bank I: CISO)."		
	"The result of our last survey of cybersecurity awareness showed that only 41% of their customers are aware about cybersecurity. Comparing these results with last two years there is a minor change (increase) in number of customers who are aware. Contrary, a substantial increase in number of cybercrimes has been reported as compared to last two years (Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker)."		
	"The worst case is that even many of our well-educated people are not aware of cybersecurity tactics and become victim (Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst)."		
	"Our bank is awarded for best performance internationally in 2020 and 70% of our customers are literate as most of them are job holders or businessmen, so they are aware about cybersecurity. Also, we use critical verification system before any transaction. Hence, there is no chance a hacker can access the data. Hence, in Pakistan there is system which can better deal with cybersecurity but not all banks have it. It is expensive. The only chance of data loss is on customer end (Bank B: Operations head)."	Bank B	
	"If the financial loss is resulted from customers' side unintentionally by sharing their details (through social engineering or online websites) still the bank tries to recover as much as possible to build customers' confidence. Customers have attitude of imposing all responsibility on bank (Bank J: CISO)."		
	"People do have the tendency to reveal their confidential information to unauthorised people such as date of birth (Bank A: CISO)."		
	"It is very important to educate the customers about which information should be shared and which not (Bank L: CISO)."		
	"The customers can block their cards in case of fraud, but the problem is that people are even unawareness of this regulation (Bank K: CISO)."		
<i>What percentage of your customers are aware?</i>	Awareness rate 30% (2 – Bank A and C), 40% (5 – Bank D, E, F, H, and J), 50% (3 - Bank G, I, and K), 60% (1 – Bank M), 70% (2 – Bank B and L)	13 Banks	13 Banks
<i>Q1b. If customer awareness is important then what role does your bank play to create that awareness?</i>	"No specific training is required by SBP. Therefore, limited channels are used by banks to aware their customers for example, banks' websites, brochures, posters, handouts, in person, email and SMS etc. (Bank D: CISO)"	All	All
	"If customers asks us then we tell them about secure use of banking but normally people do not bother to know about cybersecurity. They take bank as an institution where they can deposit their money and withdraw it when needed (Bank F: Cash controller)."	All CISOs- except Bank B	
	"Our customers need detailed awareness about how to use banking securely rather than making them aware generally. We need to think above than traditional concepts of training our customers (Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst)."		
	"The training is a great help to the customers but again you need infrastructure, finances, room and everything. There are millions of customers. We can only train top 200 or 300 customers of each branch and that will greatly help for the security for the banks and the customers. However, government has this potential (Bank E: Senior credit control manager)."		
	"I was in one of the meeting with the State Bank and I told them if a company can put their ads on TV and everywhere about the secrets about the smoking why you cannot put such advises on the TV, on the radio relating to cybersecurity. Most of the people are not literate and people use radio quite often during the travelling as well so even if they do not want to listen they will. Hence, regardless of education they will have this kind of training and awareness at least (Bank M: CISO)."		

Q1c. Can literacy be useful for your customer cybersecurity awareness?	"One of the most critical factor (Bank A: CISO)."	All	All
	"A person who is literate will have awareness while an illiterate person will not have or have less awareness comparatively (Bank F: Cash controller)."	Bank J and M	
	"There are three types of customers our banks have. The first type is well educated (bachelor or master's degree holders) people who account for only 20% to 30% of our total customers. The second type is people with low level literacy (high class in school or intermediate level) and they are around 40% of total of our customers. The third type is people with no literacy at all and they are counted as almost 30% of our customers. However, the second and third type are more vulnerable to cyberattacks (Bank K: CISO)."		
	"Banking customers should at least have graduation. Our 40% customers are graduated. A customer is instructed as per his qualification. At the time of account opening the customer will read the security features in Urdu (national language in Pakistan) and English if he can or the employee will explain. Nowadays, the bank has printed form for cybersecurity terms and conditions with account opening documents. Still if a customer is negligent then he/she is responsible (Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker)."	Bank L	
	"One of the major impacts of low literacy is poor understanding of cybersecurity and its importance. Consequently, they share their confidential data and become victim which result in financial loss to them and reputational loss to bank."	Bank H	
Q1d. If literacy is important then is a degree holder customer considered literate to support cybersecurity governance of your bank?	"A literate customer is defined as who knows how to operate a system securely (Bank B: CISO)."	All	All
	"Regardless of degree if a person is aware about cybersecurity is considered a literate customer but we have very few numbers of such intellectual people (Bank E: Senior credit control manager)."	Bank A, L, and E	
	"For a Financial Institution, any customer who takes care of his personal/banking data is literate, irrespective of his formal education level (Bank G:CISO)."		
What percentage of your customers are literate?	5% literacy (1 – Bank C), 30% literacy (2 – Bank J and E), 40% literacy (3 – Bank F and I, M), 50% literacy (2 – Bank G and H), 60% literacy (1 - Bank K), 70% literacy (4 – Bank A, B, D, and L)	13 Banks	13 Banks
Q1e. How would you explain the relation of public literacy and awareness to cybersecurity governance of your bank?	"Literacy level of general public and their awareness about cybersecurity plays an effective role (Bank D1)".	All	All
	"The increasing trend of use of internet have emerged the trend of online payments especially for shopping. And majority of people who use internet is based on teenagers (less literate and have very less or no awareness of cybersecurity). However, use of online services involves third party services for example websites or online payment methods whereby the mentioned majority uses bank cards mostly of their guardians or family members. In this way if they are not aware about cybersecurity, they will share the bank details of our customers which will result in data breach (Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst)."		
	"Higher the rate of literacy and awareness of cybersecurity among general public of a nation the lower the chances that the cybercriminals will attempt to make them victim (Bank J: CISO)."	Bank M	
	"The general public literacy rate in our country is quite low - roughly around 60% (Bank H)."	All	Bank E and G
	"This is very relative. We have observed some very educated and technology savvy people falling prey to simple social engineering techniques (Bank G: CISO)."		

Q1f. How the awareness is possible where literacy rate is also low?	"Urgent need of awareness program by Government (Bank B: CISO)".	All	All
	"The increasing trend of using internet in Pakistan is resulting to increase the presence of people of Pakistan in cyberspace simultaneously. This indicates the usage of technology is appreciated by people. However, the drawback of technology cannot be ignored that technology is a source of data confidentiality breach (Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst)."		
	"There is need of well-designed awareness program by government based on the category of people (level of education). The basic efforts by conducting conventions every three or six months will not be effective with this fast-growing rate of cybercrime. However, awareness programs throughout the schools, universities, Islamic organizations, public sector, including street-based approach can play a major role towards making people aware in fast way (Bank H: CISO)."	Bank A, B, G, I, J, and K	
	"The government of Pakistan should acknowledge its responsibility to aware the people of its country who have low literacy rate and awareness about cybersecurity. You can notice that the governments of developed are making initiatives to aware their public about information security (Bank I: CISO)."		
	"As this is the matter of whole nation rather than only banking customers. Therefore, the government of Pakistan should focus on introducing awareness programmes which can help people to get educated regardless of their level of literacy so that they will not become victim of cyberattacks such as social engineering (Bank M: CISO)."		
	"It is considered as a CSR and banks have done a lot by creating electronic media, print media, and advertisements, email, and message to their customers for securing data but still a number of customers failed to secure the data or share the data then it's not going to help. This might align for smaller investment on cybersecurity. hence, government need to help (Bank A: CISO)."		
	"Pakistan government cannot afford to have all the awareness programme running across the board but there should be a topic on which previous banks are successful (Bank A: CISO)."		

Source: Interview Data

6.3.1.2. Sub-theme: Lack of satisfactory regulatory framework of cybersecurity

When inquired that having NIST or ISO 27001 guidelines why regulatory framework issue is not resolved and how your bank provides effective cybersecurity governance then? The following responses were received:

All CISOs (14) and other respondents (7) agreed that regulatory framework of cybersecurity for banking industry is one of the most critical factor and there is lack of satisfactory regulatory framework of cybersecurity in Pakistan (Table 14h). Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst pointed that:

“Law provides the protection while regulatory framework provides the guidelines to run the organisation in a way that it meets its objectives effectively and securely. Therefore, a business without protection and guideline will be on a direction which is not secure and does not know how to meet its objectives effectively and securely (Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst).”

Nonetheless, some of the respondents commented that following recent regulatory framework issued by SBP their banks use T18 version (banking software) and fully secure network (Bank C: CISO), must provide protection to information system of bank at any cost (all CISOs -14), professionally plan for information security (Bank D: CISO), use quick and thorough information security system (Bank B and D: CISOs) – which are adhesive to state bank requirements (6 out of 13 banks; Bank CISOs - C, D, E, H, I, and J). Bank C, D (CISOs); and Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker (3 out of 21) further added that these information security systems detect any suspicious activity and straightaway stop. Additionally, Bank C, D, I and J (4 CISOs out of 14) informed that banks must use information security control system as per the regulations. Bank F: Operations head confirmed that those systems are in operations 24/7 while Bank A, B, D, E, and H (CISOs); and Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker (altogether 6 out of 13 banks) revealed that for most of the banks these information security systems are tested 24/7 to prevent cybercrime. Nevertheless, Bank B – CISO uncovered that every 3 months their information controls are tested and an SOP is introduced to update it based on new cyberthreats. In addition, all respondents (21) exposed that executives are immediately informed about any cyber

incident using hierarchy to make abrupt decisions. Besides, they also reported that on monthly basis executives are provided detailed reports on overall cybersecurity matters to keep them updated. Furthermore, Bank A and E (CISOs) mentioned that if the banks do not ensure their information security then the regulator can impose fine to the bank. Finally, 5 out of 13 banks (CISOs - Bank C, D, L and M; Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker) said that many people are aware about the ATM scamming, which is the result of the efforts of banks to aware people. All of these responses confirmed that the banks are and they have to implement the information security standard required by the regulator. However, some of the respondents also raised the issues regarding these standards and flaws in their implementation as follows.

Bank A, I, D, and M (4 out of 14 CISOs) referred that 20 years back there was no concept of cybersecurity in banking industry of Pakistan, when the whole banking industry was integrating information technology to adopt e-banking services. Explicitly, Bank I (CISO) explained this phenomenon as:

“20 years back there was no concept of cybersecurity in banking industry of Pakistan, when the banks were developing their IT infrastructure. Therefore, our banking industry even lacks fundamentals of cybersecurity. However, using antivirus, firewall, or just updating software is just show off. These protocols can only be a bandage for our information security system, but it cannot secure it. Base is necessity to win the race (Bank I: CISO; also supported by more 3 out of 14 CISOs – Bank D, D1, and M).”

Bank J (CISO) further inserted in that since there lack of fundamentals of information system security therefore, it is four times harder now to include information security in IT infrastructure of our banks. Therewithal, 6 out of 14 CISOs reported that as cybersecurity concept is new in Pakistan banking industry therefore there is majority of IT employees (such as 20 IT staff) in banks and, only 4 information security experts - which is a very low ratio (Bank A, D, E, F, K, and M). In addition, 3 out of 14 CISOs mentioned that our banks just increased a little budget for the CISOs in response to cybersecurity incidents of 2018 (Bank B, D, and D1), which is a show off to SBP. Moreover, responding to those incidents the regulations are strengthen over time but their implementation is subjective to banks which leave the excuses for banks to not adopt cohesive cybersecurity solutions (Bank A: CISO).

Some other respondents also highlighted issues from SBP perspective. 8 out of 14 (CISOs - Bank A, E, G, D, D1, K L, and M) referred that:

“The IT staff is most responsible but the whole environment is to blame. Same as our IT infrastructure is equipped without security protocols similarly the policymakers in SBP are working for years and years without having background of information security. Therefore, they only have been focusing on making policies while practical implementation has been neglected. Their only concern is to secure their jobs by manipulation of reality (Bank K: CISO).”

Supporting above statements, 4 out of 13 banks also informed that SBP only focuses on governance approach (Bank D, D1, E, H, and M - CISOs). Additionally, Bank D (CISO) said that audit takes time because of limited audit team which allows manipulation by banks. Also, Bank M (CISO) added that the auditors are fresh graduates they do not have industry experience to spot on flaws in banking information security system. Bank B, H, and M – CISOs (3 out of 13 banks) raised the point that:

“Developed countries use proper information security system, allocate sufficient budget for cybersecurity, and have strong law as well as regulations for cybersecurity, still they are hacked, or their security is compromised. While, in Pakistan the regulator (SBP) mostly focuses on governance approach and no attention is given to implementation (Bank H: CISO).”

Therefore, we need a comprehensive regulatory framework with efficient protocols of security as introduced by NIST or ISO 27001 which will require strict implementation of controls (Bank D, D1, H and M: CISOs – 3 out of 13 banks). Bank E (CISO) support it as regulations and practices which comes into strategy are the major factors to improve cybersecurity governance but unfortunately, Pakistan banking industry is generally regulatory driven with less implementation. Hence, banks try to achieve regulatory compliance minimum with no extra efforts to secure their information systems reducing costs. Bank G (CISO) mentioned that banks should not expect the regulations to be too much explicit instead they should be willing to find out the best solutions and implement.

Table 14h: Lack of satisfactory regulatory framework of cybersecurity

Lack of satisfactory regulatory framework of cybersecurity	CISOs	Other Respondents
One of the most critical factor (21)	All	All
Lack of satisfactory regulatory framework of cybersecurity (21)	All	All
Law provides protection while regulatory framework provides the guidelines (1)		Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst
Use T18 version and fully secure network (1)	Bank C	
Provide protection at any cost (14)	All	
It is planned by professionals (1)	Bank D	
Quick and thorough	Bank B and D	
Adhesive to state bank requirements (6)	Bank C, D, E, H, I, and J	
Detects any suspicious activity and straightaway stops (3)	Bank C and D	Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker
Information security system is tested 24/7 (6)	Bank A, B, D, E, and H	Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker
Every 3 months is tested and an SOP is introduced (2)	Bank B	
Information security control system (4)	Bank C, D, I and J	
Information security control system 24/7 (1)		Bank F: Operations head
Many people are aware about the ATM skimming (5)	Bank C, D, L and M	Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker
Executives are immediately informed about any cyber incident using hierarchy (21)	All	All
Reported on monthly basis to executives (21)	All	All
Developed countries are hacked or their security is compromised (3)	Bank B, H, and M	
SBP only focuses on governance approach (5)	Bank D, D1, E, H, and M	
20 years back no concept of cybersecurity in banking industry of Pakistan (4)	Bank A, I, D, and M	
Our banking industry even lacks fundamentals of cybersecurity (3)	Bank D, D1, and I	
Using antivirus, firewall, or just updating software will bandage not secure (1)	Bank I	
Four times harder now to include information security in IT infrastructure of our banks (3)	Bank D, D1 and J	
Policymakers in SBP are working without having background of information security (8)	Bank A, E, G, D, D1, K, L, M	
20 IT staff and only 4 information security experts (60 OT)	Bank A, K, E, F, and M	
Just increased a little budget for CISOs after incident happened in 2018 (3)	Bank B, D, D1	
Audit takes time (1)	Bank D	
Limited audit team (1)	Bank D	
Need of a comprehensive regulatory framework with efficient protocols of security as introduced by NIST or ISO 27001 (4)	Bank D, D1, H and M	
Auditors are fresh graduates	Bank M	
Regulations are strengthened over time but their implementation is subjective	Bank A	
Regulator can impose fine to the bank	Bank A and E	
Pakistan market is generally regulatory driven	Bank E	
Regulations and practices which comes into strategy are the major factors.	Bank E	
Banks try to achieve regulatory compliance minimum.	Bank E, M	
Should not expect the regulations to be too much explicit	Bank G	

Source: Interview Data

Summary of Regulatory Framework of Cybersecurity Findings

Lacking the comprehensive regulatory framework, the issues reported were less number of cybersecurity experts, lack of training to staff, lack of adoption of vulnerability scanners as not strictly required by regulator, subjective implementation of regulations, lack of budget allocated by executives, lack of check and balance, governance approach rather than implementation, and lack of experienced auditors etc. These all issues resist proper cybersecurity governance of banks. Following (Table 14I) are some other key quotes apart of the above stated, to support these findings.

Table 14I: Regulatory Framework Quotes

Question 2.	Regulatory Framework Quotes	Supported by CISOs	Supported by Other Respondents
Q2. Having NIST or ISO 27001 guidelines why regulatory framework issue is not resolved and how your bank provides effective cybersecurity governance then?	“The SBP requires banks to pre-plan for cyberattacks and use at least T18 software with secure network or the latest version T 24. Most importantly the banks need to provide protection at any cost. But no guideline (rigid protocols) is provided. Also, the banks in Pakistan are following the information security control cycle same as introduced by McLaughlin, to be prepared for information security attacks is confirmed as being used (Bank C: CISO).”	All CISOs	
	“Law provides the protection while regulatory framework provides the guidelines to run the organisation in a way that it meets its objectives effectively and securely. Therefore, a business without protection and guideline will be on a direction which is not secure and does not know how to meet its objectives effectively and securely (Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst).”		
	“As per the SBP’s requirement our system immediately detects any suspicious activity and straightaway that activity is stopped by cybersecurity department. All the commercial banks are bound by the central bank to have their software and banking platform updated regularly (Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker).”	Bank C and D	
	“As per the regulatory requirement the executives are immediately informed about any cyber incident using hierarchy. Otherwise in normal circumstances they are reported on monthly basis (Bank E: Senior credit control manager).”	All	All
	“First of all, our bank is following the regulatory framework issued by SBP as a requirement. Secondly, that regulatory framework is not effective as it does not provide the banks with the proper guideline for information security controls as are provided in detail in other cybersecurity regulatory frameworks for example NIST (Bank B: Customer’s relationship and marketing manager).”		
	“Lacking efficient staff, SBP has not been making efforts for long to improve the cybersecurity regulatory framework for banks. This highlights that the importance of information security of banks has been neglected over the years. And the major reason of this neglect is poor check and balance from government of Pakistan and political influences (Bank E: Senior credit control manager).”		
	“Human body works as blood circulates. Similarly, information security of banks is sustainable with updated regulations (Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker).”		
	“Cybersecurity regulations are security gates which if applied in information security of banks, any stranger tending to harm the confidentiality, availability or integrity can be detected and stopped (Bank B: CISO).”		
	“For example, if the directors are required to be trained, the banks are required to maintain certain number of cybersecurity experts based on their size etc. the management will have a road map to follow and focus on securing its information system rather than on saving money (Bank J: CISO).”		
	“Developed countries use proper information security system, allocate sufficient budget for cybersecurity, and have strong law as well as regulations for cybersecurity, still they are hacked, or their security is compromised. While, in Pakistan the regulator (SBP) mostly focuses on governance approach and no attention is given to implementation (Bank H: CISO).”	Bank B and M	
	“The IT staff is most responsible but the whole environment is to blame. Same as our IT infrastructure is equipped without security protocols similarly the policymakers in SBP are working for years and years without having background of information security. Therefore, they only have been focusing on making policies while practical implementation has been neglected. Their only concern is to secure their jobs by manipulation of reality (Bank K: CISO).”	Bank A, E, G, D, D1, L, and M	

<p>"20 years back there was no concept of cybersecurity in banking industry of Pakistan, when the banks were developing their IT infrastructure. Therefore, our banking industry even lacks fundamentals of cybersecurity. However, using antivirus, firewall, or just updating software is just show off. These protocols can only be a bandage for our information security system, but it cannot secure it. Base is necessity to win the race (Bank I: CISO)."</p>	Bank A, D, and M	
<p>"This is too late and four times harder now to include information security in IT infrastructure of our banks. Although it is not impossible, but it will take a decade (Bank J: CISO)."</p>	Bank D and D1	
<p>"A bank with 12,000 computers has 20 IT staff and only 4 information security experts. While, in this case the board will prefer to take services of software companies who are just sitting to sell their products (Bank D1: CISO)."</p>	Bank A, E, F, K, and M	
<p>"There is limited number of audit team. It takes roughly 3 months to do audit of a bank. It means every bank will have another audit after minimum two to three years. During that time if the bank is not following the right protocols of information security there is no check and balance on it (Bank D: CISO)."</p>		
<p>"Regulations have been strengthened over time but implementation of the regulation into the banking system is again subjective because some banks have the financial strength to manage that and some do not. While, implementing the controls the primary consideration is whether the system is capable enough to absorb that change to the new changes which the regulator has advised and if the systems does not have then the controls take more time for implementation on the end of business (Bank A: CISO)."</p>		
<p>"Cybersecurity is a regulatory driven as well as best practise driven as well but in Pakistan market is generally regulatory driven. So according to me regulations and practises which comes into strategy are the major factors (Bank E: CISO)."</p>		
<p>"Cybersecurity regulations are just fine. We should not expect the regulations to be too much explicit. Implementation of controls in compliance to the regulations varies with respect to every organization's environment.(Bank G: CISO)."</p>		
<p>"The issue is who is the auditor because they do not have the industry or practical experience and enough knowledge of cybersecurity (Bank M: CISO)."</p>		

Source: Interview Data

6.3.1.3. Sub-theme: Improving Cybersecurity Governance through Law and Law Enforcement

To articulate in absence of law and its implementation how your bank manages with cyberthreats, the following reasons were given:

The following Table 14J highlights that all informants (21) agreed that law and law enforcement is also one of the most relevant factors and our country (Pakistan) has lack of law and its enforcement (21). In this regard, Bank K (CISO) and Bank F: Cash controller (2 out of 13 banks) pointed out that our law does not provide protection against innovative cyber threats. Bank A (CISO) exemplified it as:

“Bringing the criminals to justice it is not a preventive control because law for cybersecurity is not effective in Pakistan (Bank A: CISO).”

Bank L (CISO) and Bank E: Senior credit control manager suggested that law and its enforcement can lessen the frequency of cybercrime. Whereas, Pakistan is an example of such a place where anyone can enter to harm the information system (Bank K: CISO). Bank E: Senior credit control manager argues that:

“The cybercriminals are successful to find the ways of data breach. Hence, I think that in this case if the information security control system of banks is backed up with law enforcement it can lessen the frequency of cybercrime. Furthermore, as the banks are responsible to implement information security strategically simultaneously the government have to play its role by enforcing law to strengthen the information system of banks (supported by all CISOs 14 out of 21 respondents).”

Bank J (CISO) mentioned that the need of cybersecurity law enforcement is driven from the dynamic trends of cybersecurity breaches. However, Bank I, L and M (CISOs) and Bank B2: Operations head (4 out of 13 banks) recommended that harsh punishments can prevent cybercriminals. Besides, Bank B2: Operations head related law and its enforcement issue to the weak IT infrastructure of Pakistan as:

“Our banking infrastructure is mapped out with no security, but we are working on to improve it. However, the effective law enforcement can immensely help by

demotivating cybercriminals frightened of punishments (Bank B2: Operations head; supported by Bank D - CISO)."

2 of the 13 banks said that law provides back up to information security system of a country along with technological solutions. If there is no law or its implementation which illustrates no security backup. Ultimately the increasing cybercrime will result in losing customers' confidence hence no more banking (Bank A – CISO and Bank B: Operations head). Similarly, another 2 out of 13 banks (Bank F and I - CISOs) highlighted that strict law and its enforcement could be door to stop cyber-criminals by imposing strict punishments.

On the other hand, all CISOs (14) pronounced that it is very hard to manage with weak law and its enforcement as awareness is the major factor. They also added that:

"Even the adoption of robust technology cannot stop cybercriminals because they can use customer as a weak link through social engineering. However, the strict punishment can stop them (Bank M: CISO)."

Bank A, B, E, G, L and M (CISOs) suggested that we have to strategically mitigate cybersecurity risk and that strategy must include law enforcement (6 out of 13 banks). Bank C, D, D1, and M (3 out of 13 banks) further strengthen it as, if no law enforcement then heavy investment is required to remove the vulnerabilities from information system which does not seems feasible.

Bank G (CISO) brought into attention that law enforcement apparatus operates within the available laws. If there is no strict law the enforcement agencies cannot help. Furthermore, the law enforcement agencies acutely need to be equipped with up-to-date cybersecurity training and technology which is not possible without governments support by allocating appropriate budget for cybersecurity of nation's information system (Bank F). 4 out of 13 banks (Bank E, F, L, and M-CISOs) shed light on another perspective that the call centre agents who are supporting cybersecurity law enforcement in Pakistan, they are fresh graduates who legitimately can be fraud, as they take people banking data and sell it once they leave the job completing their experience.

Table 14J: Cybersecurity governance: law and law enforcement

Cybersecurity governance: law and law enforcement	CISOs	Other Respondents
Law enforcement is one of the most critical factors (21)	All	All
Our law does not provide protection against innovative cyber threats (2)	Bank K	Bank F: Cash controller
Our law for cybersecurity is not effective because it does not do justice (1)	Bank A	
Law can lessen the frequency of cybercrime (1)	Bank L	Bank E: Senior credit control manager
Lack of Law and its enforcement (21)	All	All
Pakistan is a place where anyone can enter (1)	Bank K	
Government have to play its role by enforcing law (15)	All	Bank E: Senior credit control manager
Harsh punishments can demotivate the cybercriminals (4)	Bank I, L and M	Bank B2: Operations head
The need of law enforcement is driven from the emerging trend of cybersecurity breaches (1)	Bank J	
Our banking infrastructure is mapped out with no security (2)	Bank D	Bank B: Operations head
No security backup means no banking (2)	Bank A	Bank B: Operations head
It is very hard to manage as awareness is the major factor (14) statement	All	
We have to strategically mitigate risk (6) statement	Bank A, B, E, G, L and M	
If no law enforcement then heavy investment is required (4) statement	Bank C, D, D1, and M	
Even robust technology will not help	All	
Strict law and its enforcement could be door to stop cyber-criminals (2)	Bank F and I	
Law Enforcement apparatus operates within the available Laws	Bank G	
Law enforcement agencies need capacity building by providing training and technology	All	
Call centre agents legitimately can be fraud	Bank M	
Banking call centres they hired fresh graduates	Bank F, E, L, and M	

Source: Interview Data

Summary of Law and Law Enforcement Findings

The results show that with low rate of awareness along with corrupt law enforcement agents and inappropriate training and technology for law enforcement agents, private commercial banks find hard to manage their cybersecurity governance in absence of law and its implementation in Pakistan. Table 14K shows the key quotes to elaborate these findings.

Table 14K: Law and Law Enforcement Quotes

Question 3.	Law and Law Enforcement Quotes	Supported by CISOs	Supported by Other Respondents
Q3. In absence of law and its implementation how your bank manages with cyberthreats?	“The need of law enforcement is driven from the emerging trend of cybersecurity breaches in different sectors all over the world and financial industry remains the top target of cybercriminals whose motivation is money. And we are part of this (Bank J: CISO).”		
	“The cybercriminals are successful to find the ways of data breach. Hence, I think that in this case if the information security control system of banks if backed up with law enforcement it can lessen the frequency of cybercrime. Furthermore, as the banks are responsible to implement information security strategically simultaneously the government have to play its role by enforcing law to strengthen the information system of banks (Bank E: Senior credit control manager).”	All CISOs	
	“Bringing the criminals to justice it is not a preventive control because law enforcement for cybersecurity is not effective in Pakistan (Bank A: CISO).”		
	“If there is no law how it can be enforced. No doubt there is a document named with law for cybersecurity in Pakistan, but that law does not provide protection against innovative cyberthreats (Bank F: Cash controller).”	Bank B, D, H, I, J, and K	
	“There are no hard and fast law available in Pakistan for cybersecurity. CERT is making efforts to help in cybersecurity of banks, but it needs a lot of improvement (Bank D1: CISO).”		
	“Law enforcement apparatus operates within the available Laws (Bank G: CISO).”		
	“The example of such a country is like a place where anyone can enter and do the harm but there is no jurisdiction which will held the criminal responsible, lacking the well-defined deterring policies which can be used against that criminal (Bank K: CISO).”		
	“The harsh punishments by enforcing law can deter and demotivate the cybercriminals. However, learning from other countries - where the harsh punishments are described in law against cybercrimes and their implementation takes place for a purpose, the government of Pakistan should take the initiative and introduce as well as enforce such laws in urgency to secure the heavy amount of deposits of nation (Bank I: CISO).”	Bank L and M	Bank B2: Operations head
	“Our banking infrastructure is mapped out with no security, but we are working on to improve it. However, the effective law enforcement can immensely help by demotivating cybercriminals frightened of punishments. Otherwise, cybercrimes will increase and ultimately will result in loss of customers’ trust. Consequently, the banks will lose profits and bankrupt (Bank B2: Operations head).”	Bank D	
	“Even the adoption of robust technology cannot stop cybercriminals because they can use customer as a weak link through social engineering. However, the strict punishment can stop them (Bank M: CISO).”	All	
	“The law enforcement agencies should focus on capacity building by providing training and technology to combat cybercrimes (Bank F: CISO).”	All	
“If you call on the call centre they will ask you what <u>is your mother’s name</u> , father name, your birth location, date of birth; is it the correct number and is the registered number etc. That legitimately can be fraud. The reason behind that is, in a banking call centres they hire fresh graduates. They come there ,they join, they work for like not more than ten months and then they leave. There are multiple incidents in Pakistan like these fresh graduates, they just note down the credentials and then they sell it outside who is accepting responsibility, no one. (Bank M).”	Bank E, F, and L		

Source: Interview Data

6.3.2. Theme 2: Internal Factors affecting cybersecurity governance in private commercial banks of Pakistan

6.3.2.1. Sub-Theme: Directors' Training and Awareness

The investment and employees training and awareness will be discussed under the theme of 'Directors' training and awareness', following the sense of responses. Moreover, the 'Strategic Planning' is also part of directors' perception but it will be discussed to answer research question 2.

When asked should executives really acquire the knowledge of trending cybersecurity threats and their possible impacts on banks' cybersecurity governance if yes, then why, the following responses were received:

The Table 14L shows that all CISO (14) commented that directors' Cybersecurity training and awareness is also one of the most important factor improve the internal cybersecurity governance of banks. Bank D1, H, I, and J – CISOs (4 out of 13 banks) mentioned that internationally banks are required to invest in appropriate cybersecurity solutions and by SBP as well as. Yet, 4 out of 13 banks explained that directors approve the investment strategy of their choice (Bank D1, H, I, and J - CISOs). Bank J, D, D1, H (CISOs – 3 out of 13 banks) further intensified that budget is allocated but not used, with hardly 5 to 10% implementation of documented strategies (Bank D1, F, I and M - CISOs), sticking to old solutions to save money (Bank D, D1, H, J - CISOs). Moreover, 5 out of 13 banks revealed that it is hard to convince directors to understand importance of cybersecurity and CISOs do not have right to vote for investment decision (Bank D, D1, I, K, L and M – CISOs). Bank H (CISO) revealed that such issues arise because the majority of board of directors do not have educational background in information security. Simultaneously, 5 out of 13 banks highlighted that along with educational lack there is also lack of training for directors (Bank D, D1, I, K, L and M – CISOs). Bank G (CISO) supported it as:

“Directors of the Board are the stakeholders of an organization. Training of the directors enables them to understand the Cybersecurity requirements, which in return helps investment in implementation of required controls and acquisition of tools (Bank G: CISO).”

Bank L (CISO) further explained it as internal education of cybersecurity is very important. 7 out of 13 banks commented that there is need of improved regulations in general (including directors' training) about internal governance of information security in banks (Bank C, D, D1, E, F, G, L, and M - CISOs). Specifically, 2 out of 13 (Bank B, D, and D1 – CISOs) banks mentioned that introducing regulations regarding directors' training and CISOs' rights as well as investment can help while, 7 out of 13 banks (Bank A, C, D, D1, G, H, J, and L – CISOs) shared that regulation should be introduced to require directors to increase in number of cybersecurity experts. However, Bank A (CISO) also commented that CISOs should be capable to convince the directors using easy language rather than technical language, yet training will help.

Table 14L: Directors' training and awareness

Directors' training and Awareness	CISOs	Other Respondents
One of the most critical factor (14)	All	
Background of board of directors is not information security related (1)	Bank H	
Internationally considered to allocate appropriate resources (4)	Bank D1, H, I, and J	
Budget is allocated but not used (4)	Bank J, D, D1, H	
Need for introducing improved regulations (5 -8)	Bank C, D, D1, E, F, G, L, and M	
It is essentially required by SBP to invest appropriately in cybersecurity (1)	Bank D1	
Approve the strategy on their choice (4)	Bank D1, H, I, and J	
CISOs have no right to vote for investment (5)	Bank D, D1, I, K, L and M	
Lack of training for directors (3)	Bank D, D1, I,	
Hard to make directors understand importance of cybersecurity (5)	Bank D, D1, I, K, L and M	
Training enables them to understand the Cybersecurity requirements	Bank G and L	
Introducing regulatory requirement regarding directors' training and CISOs' rights as well as investment (3)	Bank B, D, and D1	
Increase number of cybersecurity experts (8)	Bank A, C, D, D1, G, H, J, and L	
This is all about the capability of the CISO not just	Bank A	
Stick to old measures and save money (4)	Bank D, D1, H, J	
Hardly 5 to 10% implementation (4) refer to governance approach	Bank D1, F, I, and M	
Internal education is very important	Bank L	

Source: Interview Data

Summary of Directors' Training and Awareness Findings

The findings show that there is lack of technology, experts, and strategic implementation in cybersecurity internal governance of private commercial banks of Pakistan resulting from directors' lack of understanding and awareness of cybersecurity need. The CISOs can convince the directors but not the majority agreed therefore, a specific regulation requiring directors to have specific training and awareness, along with CISOs rights to support investment in cybersecurity; and specifying number of experts would help. However, Table 14M highlights the quotes for the above findings.

Table 14M: Directors’ Training and Awareness Quotes

Question 6.	Directors’ Training and Awareness Quotes	Supported by CISOs	Supported by Other Respondents
Q6. Should executives really be updated with knowledge of trending cybersecurity threats and their possible impacts on banks cybersecurity governance if yes, then why?	“Unfortunately, the background of board of directors is not information security related neither they are required. Rather most of them relate to finance, business management or accounts related fields. This creates the sense that the board of directors are not the people who will ultimately understand the essence and necessity of information security (Bank H: CISO).”		
	“Internationally (especially for developed countries), it is considered an important factor for banks to allocate appropriate resources for cybersecurity otherwise information control system will not be effective. Also, it is requirement by SBP. Then the question is if it is required then how the directors decide to invest just based on their decision? (Bank D1: CISO).”	Bank H, I, and J	
	“Directors of the Board are the stakeholders of an organization. Training of the directors enables them to understand the Cybersecurity requirements, which in return helps investment in implementation of required controls and acquisition of tools (Bank G: CISO).”	Bank L	
	“This neglect can be cured with the training. The directors only approve the cybersecurity strategy the one they think is good and how much they like to invest – following box centric approach. Also, in this case the CISOs do not have right to vote and defend their hard work and the interest of bank and customers. Either its technology, experts, or employee as well as customers’ training, the directors only invest when they understand the necessity. Hence, having different background of study and knowledge this indicates the lack of training for directors as they do not deal with cybersecurity directly (Bank I: CISO).”	Bank D, D1, K, L and M	
	“One aspect is if an effective proposal is presented from bottom (CISO) to board of directors, and because of lack of knowledge and training about cybersecurity that proposal is refused. This will not only result to demotivate the work of CISO but will also put the security of whole organisation at risk. The other aspect is that most of the delegations are appointed by board of directors so if they do not have appropriate knowledge of problem, they will not be able to hire the right person for the job. Subsequently, the whole information security system will be affected. Hence, their training is very important to enable them to make right decisions (Bank D1: CISO).”		
	“The directors are the only one who approve the amount of investment in cybersecurity. The problem is they are not happy to invest in latest solutions as they want to stick to old measures and save money. The SBP would notice that the amount is allocated in documents. Even having and allocating that amount the board is not willing to invest. This means the whole banking system is on risk (Bank J: CISO).”	Bank D, D1, and H	
	“The board of directors have been excessively focused on governance and documentation overkill -means most of cybersecurity is just shown in documents with hardly 5 to 10% implementation (Bank D1: CISO).”	Bank F, I and M	
	“The State Bank of Pakistan should introduce improved and clear regulations for banks specifying minimum requirements about controls, technology and experts which can held the executives responsible to understand the essence of cybersecurity internal governance (Bank C: CISO).”	Bank D, D1, E, F, G, L, and M	
	“Regulation should set certain number of experts to be hired based on the size of the bank (Bank D: CISO).”	A, C, D, D1, G, H, J, and L	
	“Regarding the directors and the board, the CISOs should explain to them the issues and the basic requirements of information security, in their language then they will definitely be able to get the support from them. Therefore, this is all about the capability of the CISO. Though, the training will be effective (Bank A: CISO).”		
	“The SBP should focus on introducing regulatory requirement regarding directors’ training and CISOs’ rights. And require banks to invest in cybersecurity (technology, experts, and training), (Bank B: CISO).”	Bank D and D1	

Source: Interview Data

Investment on cybersecurity

By commenting on Is your bank financially strong to invest in cybersecurity, if yes then why cybersecurity is an issue, the respondents acknowledged following points:

Following the regulatory requirements banks have to invest to provide adequate information security and banks in Pakistan are financially strong to invest in cybersecurity (all respondents 21, Table 14N). Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker further discussed that banking industry in Pakistan is at its boost, and Pakistan banking industry has never been defaulted (Bank B: Customer's relationship and marketing manager). Moreover, 11 out of 13 banks referred that the government do not provide financial support, otherwise the bank will be dissolved (Bank A, B, D1, E, F, G, H, I, J, L, and M – CISOs; Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker, and Bank F: Cash controller). Yet, the SBP has right to request financial help from government (Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker).

Likewise, SBP will support banks regulating but not financially (Bank F: Cash controller). Nonetheless, 6 out of 13 banks mentioned that our banks can afford high-tech experts (Bank A, B, D, J, L, and M – CISOs and Bank B: Customer's relationship and marketing manager). However, 11 of 13 banks (Bank C, D, D1, E, F, G, H, I, J, L, and M – CISOs; and Bank B: Customer's relationship and marketing manager) mentioned that our banking industry has never been defaulted but the amount of investment either it is for technology, employee training, hiring experts, or customer awareness will be decided by directors. Bank E and A (2 out of 13 banks) remarked that budgeting for cybersecurity is a challenge as it depends on banks' balance sheet.

Yet, Bank A, C and K (CISOs) highlighted that inadequate cybersecurity will result in cybercrimes, loss of customer trust and economy will suffer (3 banks out of 13). Bank K said that integrity is one of the core values of the bank therefore our management prefer to invest in cybersecurity. In addition, Bank A, B, H (CISOs) told that their information security software updates are up to date with no investment issue (3 banks out of 13).

Contrarily, Bank D (CISO) addressed that:

“We as the experts in the field of information security, work hard with full dedication towards the development of bank as well as nation as a whole and provide the best recommendation as per our knowledge and expertise. But our hard work and recommendations become worthless when they are presented in front of board (Bank D: CISO).”

Bank M (CISO) revealed that there are high level of vulnerabilities in the internet banking applications introduced by banks. Bank I (CISO) supported by similar statement that the vulnerability scanners (basics of information security) are required in our banking industry. However, he also heightened that vulnerability scanning is not an easy task it might take years following proper techniques, indicating that one bank can have one hundred thousand vulnerabilities in its information security system. At the same time, 7 out of 13 banks (Bank A, C, D, D1, E, G, H, and J – CISOs) it was disclosed that there is a need to invest in innovative technology and increase the number of cybersecurity experts. However, Bank G (CISO) mentioned that many banks developed their e-banking applications locally but no code analysis is done leaving is vulnerable. Further, the investment issue was explained using technology infrastructure as follows.

Use of outdated infrastructure

6 out of 13 banks highlighted that it costs a lot to update the information technology infrastructure (Bank C, E, F, I, J, K and M - CISOs). Likewise, Bank J, (CISO) mentioned that:

“Most of the ATM machines need to use the upgraded version of software in our country. Upgrading whole ATM system of a bank throughout the country is very expensive. I think that is why it has been neglected over years. And I strongly believe that this has been the reason of ATM scams. In short, either banks invest in upgrading infrastructure or bear financial loss and loss of customer trust (Bank J: CISO; supported by A, G and M - CISOs).”

Similarly, 9 out of 13 banks (Bank A, B, D, G, I, J, K and L - CISOs; Bank F: Cash controller) commented that there is a need of cyber resilience in our banks which is possible if technology is upgraded. Bank F1: Operations head disclosed that our bank recently upgraded its information system after the cyber incidents of 2018 and 2019. Alike, bank L (CISO) referred that it is crucial to assess your bank's information security capability which includes technology upgrade. Otherwise, 9 out of 13 banks supported that the sustainability of information security will be affected (Bank A, B, D, G, I, J, K and L - CISOs; Bank F: Cash controller).

Table 14N: Investment on cybersecurity

Investment on cybersecurity	CISOs	Other Respondents
Banks have to invest to provide cybersecurity (21)	All	All
Investment amount (for technology, employee training, hiring experts, or customer awareness) is dependent on directors (12)	Bank C, D, D1, E, F, G, H, I, J, L, and M	Bank B: Customer's relationship and marketing manager
Banks are financially strong to invest in cybersecurity (21)	All	All
The banking industry in Pakistan is at its boost (1)		Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker
Government will not help financially (13)	Bank A, B, D1, E, F, G, H, I, J, L, and M	Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker Bank F: Cash controller
The regulator can request financial support from government (1)		Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker
The Pakistan banking industry has never been defaulted (1)		Bank B: Customer's relationship and marketing manager
Banks can invest in high-tech experts (7).	Bank A, B, D, J, L, and M	Bank B: Customer's relationship and marketing manager
Inadequate cybersecurity will result in cybercrimes, loss of customer trust and economy will suffer (3)	Bank A, C and K	
Integrity is one of the core values of the bank (1)	Bank K	
Our hard work and recommendations become worthless (1)	Bank D	
Need of innovative technology and increase the number of cybersecurity experts (8)	Bank A, C, D, D1, E, G, H, and M	
SBP is there to help banks except financial (1)		Bank F: Cash controller
Software updates are up to date (3)	Bank A, B, H	
The vulnerability scanners (fundamentals) are required (1)	Bank J	
Vulnerability scanning is a tough job and long procedure (1)	Bank I	
One bank might have 1 lack vulnerabilities in its information security system	Bank I	
Budgeting is a challenge because it's all dependent on banks' balance sheet.	Bank E and A	
No code analysis for banking applications	Bank G	
high level of vulnerability in internet banking applications	Bank M	
Use of outdated infrastructure		
It costs a lot to update (6)	Bank C, E, F, I, J, K and M - CISOs	
ATM machines need to upgrade to the latest version of software (4)	Bank A, G, J, and M	
Need of cyber resilience in our banks by innovation in technology (9)	Bank A, B, D, G, I, J, K and L	Bank F: Cash controller
Our bank upgraded its system after cyber incidents of 2018 and 2019 (1)		Bank F1: Operations head
Sustainability of information security is affected (9)	Bank A, B, D, G, I, J, K and L	Bank F: Cash controller
Assessing your own organization is crucial	Bank L	

Source: Interview Data

Summary of Investment in Cybersecurity Findings

Summarising the results, it can be said that the private commercial banks of Pakistan need to invest in technology and experts to improve the cybersecurity of their information system. However, the main problem is directors as discussed in the following section in detail. Following (table 14O) are the key quotes to shed light on the above results.

Table 140: Investment in Cybersecurity Quotes

Question 4.	Investment in Cybersecurity Quotes	Supported by CISOs	Supported by Other Respondents
Q4. Is your bank financially strong to invest in cybersecurity, if yes then why cybersecurity is an issue?	“The banking industry in Pakistan is at its boost now. GDP is also high and current account is in surplus. Except Summit bank none of the bank is in deficit. Also, banks have to invest in cybersecurity as government will not help directly (Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker).”	All	Bank F: Cash controller
	“The Pakistan banking industry has never been defaulted and is profitable. The banks can invest in high tech experts. But the main problem comes when the directors do not approve our proposed contemporary cybersecurity solutions. The directors do not comprehend the essence of information security that is why they want to rely on old ways of information security and do not think out of the box (Bank B: Customer’s relationship and marketing manager).”	Bank C, D, D1, E, F, G, H, I, J, L, and M	
	“If there is not adequate cybersecurity it will result in cybercrimes, and this will damage the reputation of bank which any bank will not want. Customers will lose their trust and it will raise the issue of banks’ integrity. Integrity is one of the core values of the bank. Bank should never compromise on its integrity. Also, the economy will suffer (Bank K: CISO).”	Bank A and C	
	“We as the experts in the field of information security, work hard with full dedication towards the development of bank as well as nation as a whole and provide the best recommendation as per our knowledge and expertise. But our hard work and recommendations become worthless when they are presented in front of board (Bank D: CISO).”		
	“We need innovative technology and to increase the number of cybersecurity experts in the bank. The number of cybersecurity experts is very less in bank. Before in IT department there used to be only one person to manage the information security of all branches of a bank in this city. Thankfully, after the incidents of 2018 and 2019 now there is a separate department for cybersecurity but still there are only three or four experts to deal with the cybersecurity. The cost deters the investment in cybersecurity (Bank D1: CISO).”	Bank A, C, D, D1, E, G, H, and M	
	“As per my knowledge, until 2018 most of the banks in Pakistan even did not have the vulnerability scanners. At recommendations by consultants to install vulnerability scanners the management preferred to save money and just bought tools from IBM such as installed firewalls. Hence, lacking the fundamentals (vulnerability scanning) none of the software can help to fully secure the whole information system of banks (Bank J: CISO).”		
	“Vulnerability is a tough job. It cannot be done in once. It’s a long procedure. On bank might have 1 lack vulnerabilities in its information security system which requires investment of time, technology, and experts (Bank I: CISO).”		
	“The cities which have head offices such as Karachi, most of the technology partners and service station partners are there. Therefore, their significant presence is there. Hence, availability and accessibility challenges are not there. Comparatively, there is a high cost of technological experts in other cities as compared to Karachi which is another challenge for the bank (Bank E: CISO).”		
	“There is vulnerability in a logical flaw. If there is the logical flaw in the application who will take care of it, the vendor cannot change the code based on the security requirements they don’t do that. There are multiple banks in Pakistan they have very high level of vulnerability whenever releasing their internet banking applications. I have reported a few of them to State Bank as well as to the bank but they don’t care.(bank M)”		
	“There are many banks in Pakistan, they are using in house developed application for banking which is being developed by one of the local company which is registered in Lahore and they are providing it. The question is who did the code analysis of that application no one (Bank G: CISO).”		

Use of outdated infrastructure Quotes			
"Innovation in technology and expertise is need of cyber resilience in our banks (Bank F: Cash controller)."		Bank A, B, D, G, I, J, K and L	
"In our country highest possible information technology solutions are available. However, the cost is a problem. Following weak symbolic logics of savings instead of investing, executives do not decide to invest in dynamic technology (Bank E - CISO)."		Bank C, F, I, J, K and M	
"Most of the ATM machines need to use the upgraded version of software in our country. Upgrading whole ATM system of a bank throughout the country is very expensive. I think that is why it has been neglected over years. And I strongly believe that this has been the reason of ATM scams. In short, either banks invest in upgrading infrastructure or bear financial loss and loss of customer trust (Bank J: CISO; supported by A, G and M)."			
"Recently our bank upgraded its system after the recent cyber incidents of 2018 and 2019. We managed it successfully with the help of experts and right technology (Bank F1: Operations head)."			

Source: Interview Data

Employees' Training and Awareness

When inquired does employee behaviour play role in cybersecurity governance of your bank, the following findings were formulated:

As per Table 14P, 18 out of 21 respondents revealed that employees as a human factor are one of the most critical factor (14 CISOs; Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst, Bank E: Senior credit control manager, Bank F: Cash controller, and Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker). Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker further mentioned that cybersecurity is a concern in whole country hence, training is being provided to staff for cybersecurity. However, most of the respondents highlighted some important issues relating to employee's engagement and involvement in information security of banks. Such as 3 out of 13 banks spotted that (Bank A and G – CISOs; Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst) lower-level employees' motivation and engagement makes it hard to manage information security of banks. Bank F1: Operations head discussed that employees' good relationship with their banking customers result in risk of fraud. Nevertheless, as a solution double approval of transactions is suggested. Almost half of the banks (6 out of 13 - Bank A, B, C, D1 F, and J: CISOs) proposed that these solutions are not appropriate, there is need of cybersecurity resilience culture instead. Having similar perspective, Bank H (CISO) told that employees are at the front desks to tackle cyber incidents. Hence, their motivation is important. Bank E: Senior credit control manager recommended that:

“The management need to engage all employees of bank (regardless of their designation or age) in cybersecurity system and keep scanning for factors of employee motivation to keep them on track for their dedication towards banks' cybersecurity (also supported by Bank A, B, D, D1, G, and J - CISOs).”

In a similar context, 5 out of 13 banks highlighted that cybersecurity is a teamwork and cannot be effective with alone compliance of CISO or higher management (Bank A, D, D1 and G). Further discussing it, 4 out of 13 banks disclosed that old and lower-level employees' training need attention (Bank B, C, H - CISOs; Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst). Bank C (CISO) elaborated it as old age staff hinder to adopt new technology therefore relevant motivational factors are required for example, pay rise, self-esteem, or recognition. Moreover, some other perspectives include lack of reward

function (Bank A and G – CISOs; Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst); need of comprehensive training (Bank A, B, D, D1, J, and M - CISOs); required increased training sessions (Bank D1 and J); and presence of untrained staff as a hurdle in information security of banks (Bank A, D, D1, G, K, and L – CISOs). Bank M (CISO) told that he attempted to be victimised by a banker call. However, it was informed that in case of a potential cybercrime from an employee banks do avoid any legal proceedings as mentioned by Bank A (CISO):

“Employees are insider threat while hiring people banks perform their clearance for example in my organisation they seek feedback from all the previous organisations which I have worked for so that is one way. But there is a tendency if some employee has been found with the aspiration to file for certain illegal activities so organisations do avoid any legal proceedings. They just give him a safe passage by asking the employee to resign so that in in such cases the blacklist employees become regular employees within industry (Bank A: CISO).”

2 out of 13 banks (Bank D and M – CISOs) advised that it would be effective to inform and train employees about consequences of security breaches and then punish them in case of fraud. Bank M (CISO) further added that all personnel have the access to customer confidential data which should not be the case. Apart of it, another reason of lack of cybersecurity expert staff along with investment issue was given is lack of Universities to offer cybersecurity degrees and presence of traditional PhDs with no industry experience (Bank M - CISO). Finally, 4 out of 13 banks (Bank A, D, D1, G, and M - CISOs) referred that the skilled cybersecurity graduates move abroad where they will be paid better, creating shortage of staff in Pakistan (Bank G: CISO).

Table 14P: Employees' Training and Awareness

Employees Training and Awareness		
One of the most critical factor (18)	All (14)	Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst, Bank E: Senior credit control manager, Bank F: Cash controller, and Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker
Training is given about cybersecurity and GST (1)		Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker
It is concern all over the country (1)		Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker
Lower-level employees' motivation and engagement (3)	Bank A and G	Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst
Employees' good relationship with customers is a threat(1)		Bank F1: Operations head
Double approve any transaction (1)		Bank F1: Operations head
Lack of cybersecurity resilience culture (6)	Bank A, B, C, D1 F, and J	
Consequences of security breach (2)	Bank D and M	
In case of an incident employees will be at the front desks to tackle it (1)	Bank H	
Cybersecurity is a teamwork (5)	Bank A, D, D1 and G	Bank E: Senior credit control manager
Old and lower-level employees' training (4)	Bank B, C, H	Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst
Old age employees create resistance to learn new technology (1)	Bank C	
Need of comprehensive training (6)	Bank A, B, D, D1, J, and M	
Untrained staff and investment on trainings and equipment (6)	Bank A, D, D1, G, K, and L	
Lack of reward function (3)	Bank A and G	Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst
Less training sessions for employees of bank about cybersecurity (2)	Bank D1 and J	
Keep scanning for factors of employee motivation (7)	Bank A, B, D, D1, G, and J	Bank E: Senior credit control manager
Organisations do avoid any legal proceedings	Bank A	
Lack of Universities to offer cybersecurity degrees	Bank M	
Lecturers are traditional PhDs with no industry experience	Bank M	
Outflux of skilled Cybersecurity resources from the country (5)	Bank A, D, D1, G, and M	
all personnel have the access	Bank M	
Fraudulent call to CISO	Bank M	

Source: Interview Data

Summary of Employee Training and Awareness Findings

The results show that in private commercial banks of Pakistan employees-being a human factor, are found to be the most relevant factor for internal cybersecurity governance of banks. Yet, less cybersecurity training sessions are provided. Besides, there is a need of comprehensive training for all level of staff (including lower level, old age, and IT related employees) to create cybersecurity resilience culture. However, the relevant motivation can be effective to keep all employees on track. The results also indicated that there is an open and relaxed culture where all employees have access to customers' data and are not taken to court in case of a criminal activity. It is also found that there's a lack of educational institutions in Pakistan to graduate cybersecurity experts. Additionally, most of the graduates move abroad for better career opportunities which justifies lack of cybersecurity experts in Pakistan. Table 14Q illustrates the key quotes to support the results of this section.

Table 14Q: Employee Training and Awareness Quotes

Question 5.	Employee Training and Awareness Quotes	Supported by CISOs	Supported by Other Respondents
Q5. Does employee behaviour play role in cybersecurity governance of your bank?	<p><i>"An employee became close friend of a customer. Consequently, the customers started relying on that employee for example by having his blank signed cheque to the banks' employee asking him that if in later dates he can fill in the amount and submit their cheque in his account with reference to a specific person. Subsequently, the employee tended to find financial benefits and used those cheques or personal information of his customer to withdraw big amount of money, once he found that the customer has accumulated a huge amount of money in his account. He stole that money and moved abroad with preplanning (Bank F1: Operations head)."</i></p>		
	<p><i>"The staff is informed about cybercrime at branch level. In 2018 the bank Islami had a big cyber-attack in 4 branches. Its treasury account was hacked. And funds were transferred to other countries. Since that there is strict monitoring and, in all banks, we are given training about cybersecurity and GST (general service administration) for IT. All over the country there is so much working going on relating to cybersecurity (Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker)."</i></p>		
	<p><i>"Such measures are not enough to demotivate such employees. There is a need of culture within the banks which can not only help to create comprehensive strategy for cybersecurity protocols but also promote its implementation (Bank D1: CISO)."</i></p>	Bank A, B, C, D1 F, and J	
	<p><i>"There should be culture of employee training. No doubt the banks have started providing training to employees. But this training needs to be more comprehensive nature instead of introductory nature. Also, the management should maintain ongoing checks on employees' performance and motivation to keep them on track (Bank J: CISO)."</i></p>	A, B, C, D1, and F	
	<p><i>"The old age employees are a hurdle in information security. They do not like to learn new technologies however they are part of banking system. To urge them to learn new technologies there is a need of some kind of relevant motivation for them. For example, self-esteem, recognition, or reward function (Bank C: CISO)."</i></p>	Bank B, C, and H and Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst	
	<p><i>"The lower-level employees are not involved in information security control survey. However, they just receive dictated orders of management to complete a certain training with limited knowledge of cybersecurity. Therefore, with low salary, less self-esteem, and no reward function such employees do not bother to look after the information security of bank (Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst)."</i></p>	Bank A and G	
	<p><i>"The management need to engage all employees of bank (regardless of their designation or age) in cybersecurity system and keep scanning for factors of employee motivation to keep them on track for their dedication towards banks' cybersecurity (Bank E: Senior credit control manager)."</i></p>	Bank A, D, D1, G, and J	
	<p><i>"Employees are insider threat while hiring people banks perform their clearance for example in my organisation they seek feedback from all the previous organisations which I have worked for so that is one way. But there is a tendency if some employee has been found with the aspiration to file for certain illegal activities so organisations do avoid any legal proceedings. They just give him a safe passage by asking the employee to resign so that in in such cases the blacklist employees become regular employees within industry (Bank A: CISO)."</i></p>		
	<p><i>"I wonder I opened up my account and just after 45 minutes I got a call from the Allied bank UN number and the person was telling me this is your father's name, this is your mother's name, this is your address; can you please confirm me your CNIC number. (Bank M: CISO)."</i></p>		
	<p><i>"I believe that after implementing all security measures in case of an incident employees will be at the front desks to tackle any cybersecurity issue in bank which can be either social engineering, hacking or fraudulent cheques (Bank H: CISO)."</i></p>		

<p><i>"By my point of view cybersecurity of banks cannot be possible solely by the compliance of CISO or higher management. Rather it's a teamwork. Every single employee of the organisation matters to a certain level for the cybersecurity of bank (Bank B: CISO)."</i></p>	<p>Bank A, D, D1 and G</p>	
<p><i>"In certain cases, the relevant IT team do not have full knowledge of the capability of their system and there in some cases they are legacy systems I mean system folders they do not have the capability to integrate with the cybersecurity controls or implement basic controls, that is one of the biggest challenges (Bank A: CISO)."</i></p>		
<p><i>"I believe that the employees should be trained well and informed about the consequences of involvement in criminal behaviour. However, the strict actions Should be taken in case of criminal act (Bank D: CISO)."</i></p>	<p>Bank M</p>	
<p><i>"Outflux of skilled Cybersecurity resources from the country. Its reason is availability of better opportunities in other countries. (Bank G: CISO)."</i></p>		
<p><i>"They are traditional PhDs who have no industry experience. NUST has started engagement with the industry which I really appreciate. It starting engaging people from industry to the teaching but the damage is the coursework where they still have a traditional ways so they're not improving in that context (Bank M: CISO)."</i></p>		

Source: Interview Data

Research Question Two: How the cybersecurity governance is perceived in private commercial banks of Pakistan which can ensure its maturity level?

6.3.3. Theme 3: Strategic planning - Cybersecurity Governance Perception

21 out of 21 respondents mentioned that all banks are required by SBP to consider cybersecurity in strategic planning so we must do (Table 15a). 15 out of 21 interviewees stated that banks used to consider cybersecurity a technological issue but not now from couple of years (All CISOs and Bank F: Cash controller). Now, the management of bank considers information security of bank a serious issue and our executives allocate a specific budget to invest in information security (21 out of 21 respondents). Bank K (CISO) further insisted that we plan strategically to ensure that our businesses have compatible resources. Bank I (CISO) supported it as it is higher management responsibility to give priority to the strategic planning for cybersecurity allowing banks to highlight previous cyberthreats and provide innovative measures. Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker referred that our bank have developed a crisis management team to support information security system.

Confirming the appreciation of strategic planning in their banks most of the respondents highlighted some issues in that system.

Such as 8 out of 13 banks pointed that strategic planning in their banks is ineffective (Bank D1, E, F, H, I, J, K, and L - CISOs) explaining as:

“In strategic planning process, initially it goes well when experts plan a road map for banks to highlight the previous threats, their reasons, and chances of reoccurrence. But when suggestions are sent for approval the required budget is not approved by board. Rather, the cheaper and temporary solutions are preferred. Hence, such a strategic planning is useless and ineffective for banks (Bank J: CISO).”

Moreover, 13 out of 13 banks (CISOs) mentioned that as required by SBP we always hire experts of the field but number of experts are not enough. 21 out of 21 respondents stated that failure to cybersecurity cause reputational impact (customers trust) and financial loss which was already faced in 2018 after cyberattacks mentioned in this study. Yet, 6 out of 13 banks (Bank C, E, F, G, I, and L - CISOs) disclosed that

information security measures are advanced based on investment decision rather than customer interest. Nevertheless, 21 out of 21 informants agreed that all measures can improve the cybersecurity of banks altogether.

Table 15a: Strategic planning - Cybersecurity Governance Perception

Strategic planning - Cybersecurity Governance Perception		
It is required by SBP to consider cybersecurity in strategic planning (14)	All	Bank F: Cash controller
Strategic planning in their banks is ineffective (8)	Bank D1, E, F, H, I, J, K, and L	
Crisis management team (1)		Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker
Banks do strategic planning for cybersecurity (14)	All	
Management of bank consider cybersecurity a serious issue (14)	All	
Bank allocates a specific budget for this issue to be handled (14)	All	
Bank used to consider cybersecurity technical issue but not now from couple of years (15)	All	Bank F: Cash controller
To ensure that their businesses have compatible resources (1)	Bank K	
Responsibility on the higher management to pay high attention to the strategic planning for cybersecurity (1)	Bank I	
Highlight previous cyberthreats and find the innovative solutions (1)	Bank I	
Budget is not approved by board (8)	Bank D1, E, F, H, I, K, and L	
Less number of experts (14)	All	
It is required by SBP to hire experts	All	All
Saving is preferred over customers' interest (6)	Bank C, E, F, G, I, and L	
Slow development of cybersecurity department	All	
Cheaper and temporary solutions are used (8)	Bank D1, E, F, H, I, K, and L	
All measures can improve the cybersecurity of banks.	All	All
Reputational impact (customers trust) and financial	All	All

Source: Interview Data

Summary of Strategic planning- Cybersecurity Governance Perception Findings

The results illustrate that the management understands the importance of strategic planning to ensure the information security of banks. However, the executives remain reluctant restricting the implementation of strategic planning. It is also ensured that most of the strategic planning is documented and implementation is very low. This confirms that the internal cybersecurity governance of banks is weak because of executives' lack of awareness and understanding. Thus, strategic planning as internal factor helped to answer research question that the maturity level of cybersecurity governance of private commercial banks of Pakistan is at initial stage where the cybersecurity concept is new and there is a need of development in areas of executives training and awareness which can promote the investment in cybersecurity. Following Table 15b presents the key quotes to support these findings while, Table 16 highlights the results for research question 1 and 2 to summarise the key findings.

Table 15b: Strategic Planning - Cybersecurity Governance Perception Quotes

Questions	Strategic Planning - Cybersecurity Governance Perception Quotes	Supported by CISOs	Supported by Other Respondents
Q7. Does the higher management of bank/just bank consider Cybersecurity in strategic planning?	“Before cybersecurity, incidents of 2018 the banks used to treat cybersecurity as a technological issue. Later as per the requirement of SBP, banks started considering cybersecurity in strategic planning and allocated budget for it. Therefore, cybersecurity department is separated from the IT department now (Bank F: Cash controller).”	All	All
	“The state bank has introduced the regulations most recently that the crisis management team of bank (which include board of directors, CEOs, and higher management) will hold a meeting after 21 days from 1st of every month, to review its strategy to stop the cybercrimes and report it to the state bank - ‘banking consumer department’ (Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker).”		
Q8. Does the higher management of bank take pre-planned initiatives to avoid Cybersecurity issue?	“The management plan strategically for cybersecurity to ensure that their businesses have compatible resources (technology, experts, and implementation) to combat the innovative ways of cybercrimes, with purpose to secure their information system (Bank K: CISO).”		
	“Strategic planning includes assessing your own organisation in terms of the proposal against those organisations that have been compromised. That would help the organisation to uplift their security controls. However, its implementation requires investment in technology, experts, and employee development which remains dependent on directors (Bank L: CISO).”		
	“In strategic planning process, initially it goes well when experts plan a road map for banks to highlight the previous threats, their reasons, and chances of reoccurrence. But when suggestions are sent for approval the required budget is not approved by board. Rather, the cheaper and temporary solutions are preferred. Hence, such a strategic planning is useless and ineffective for banks (Bank J: CISO).”	Bank D1, E, F, H, I, K, and L	
	“For effective solution, all of the security measures discussed including customer training, investment in technology and experts and directors’ training can improve the cybersecurity of banks (Bank E: CISO).”	All	All
Q9. Which type of IT experts the management of bank consider to deal with Cybersecurity issue and why?	“We have responsible experts working in the industry however they cannot support the information security system fully with inadequate number of colleagues (Bank D: CISO).”	All	
Q10. Do you think being unable to provide sufficient security for banking services will cause loss of customers’ trust on bank and why?	“So, in terms of strategy everything we discussed like training of the employees and board; investment and the policies, all those things come in strategic planning of cybersecurity. Ultimately, the implementation of such strategies can improve the cybersecurity governance and build our customers’ confidence on e-banking services provided by us. Yet, investment decision is contingent to saving money not securing customers’ interest (Bank G: CISO).”	Bank C, E, F, I, and L	
	“Primarily cybersecurity affects banks reputation. Based on your bank’s reputation your customers’ and stakeholders trust is dependent. Subsequently the life of your institution is dependent on cybersecurity. Therefore, cybersecurity is considered an ongoing concern. Once banks’ reputation is damaged customers’ trust is broken of course there will be huge financial impact because of broken trusts. So, there are two things reputational impact (customers trust) and financial, the executives need to understand it (Bank E: CISO).”	All	

Source: Interview Data

Table 16: Research Question 1 and 2 Key Results

Research Question	Key Findings	Participants
<p>Q1. Which significant internal and external factors (challenges) are affecting the cybersecurity governance in the private commercial banks of Pakistan?</p>	<p>Customer Awareness: One of the most critical factor human factor (13 out of 13 banks) Majority of banks (7 out of 13) have 40% awareness at average Banks use limited channels of awareness (13 out of 13 banks) Moreover, regardless of degree (financial literacy) a person who is digitally literate is secure (13 out of 13 banks) Yet, the literate people (educated) can learn fast the awareness (3 out of 13 banks)</p> <p>Finally, public literacy and awareness is useful to secure cyberspace and banking customers' data as people use banking data of relatives when using e-services such as shopping etc. (13 out of 13 banks) However, having limited sources in banks, Government need to use multiple channels of awareness at national level (6 out of 13 banks)</p> <p>Those should be well-designed awareness programs based on the category of people (7 out of 13 banks)</p> <p>Thus, regardless of education (financial literacy and digital literacy) customers will have awareness through TV and Radio</p>	<p>21 out of 21 21 out of 21 21 out of 21 21 out of 21</p> <p>Bank J and M (CISOs) and Bank F: Cash controller</p> <p>21 out of 21</p> <p>Bank A, C, D and M (CISOs); Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst and Bank E: Senior credit control manager</p> <p>Bank A, B, G, H, I, J, and K (CISOs)</p> <p>Bank M (CISO)</p>
	<p>Regulatory Framework: One of the most critical factor (13 out of 13 banks) Lack of satisfactory regulatory framework of cybersecurity (13 out of 13 banks) Policymakers in SBP are working without having background of information security (8 out of 13)</p> <p>Need of a comprehensive regulatory framework with efficient protocols of security as introduced by NIST or ISO 27001 (4 out of 13 banks) SBP only focuses on governance approach but less implementation (5 out of 13 banks)</p> <p>Our banking industry even lacks fundamentals of cybersecurity (3 out of 13 banks)</p>	<p>21 out of 21 21 out of 21 Bank A, E, G, D, D1, K L, M (CISOs) Bank D, D1, H and M (CISOs)</p> <p>Bank D, D1, E, H, and M (CISOs) Bank D, D1, and I (CISOs)</p>

	<p>Law and its Enforcement: One of the most critical factor (13 out of 13 banks) Lack of Law and its enforcement (13 out of 13 banks) Government have to play its role by enforcing law (13 out of 13 banks)</p> <p>Harsh punishments can demotivate the cybercriminals (4 out of 13 banks)</p> <p>If no law enforcement then heavy investment is required (4 out of 13 banks) Even robust technology will not help (13 out of 13 banks) Law enforcement agencies need capacity building 13 out of 13 banks) Banking call centres they hired fresh graduates (4 out of 13 banks) It is very hard to manage as awareness is the major factor (13 out of 13 banks) We have to strategically mitigate risk (6 out of 13 banks)</p>	<p>21 out of 21 21 out of 21 14 CISOs and Bank E: Senior credit control manager Bank I, L and M (CISOs) and Bank E: Senior credit control manager Bank C, D, D1, and M (CISOs) 14 CISOs 14 CISOs Bank F, E, L, and M (CISOs) 14 CISOs Bank A, B, E, G, L and M (CISOs)</p>
<p>Q2. How the cybersecurity governance is perceived in private commercial banks of Pakistan which can ensure its maturity level?</p>	<p>Strategic Planning (integrating investment, employee, and executive training): Need of cyber resilience in our banks by innovation in technology (9 out of 13 banks)</p> <p>Need of innovative technology and increase the number of cybersecurity experts (8 out of 13 banks)</p> <p>Keep scanning for factors of employee motivation (5 out of 13 banks)</p> <p>Untrained staff and investment on trainings and equipment (5 out of 13 banks)</p> <p>Lack of cybersecurity resilience culture (6 out of 13 banks)</p> <p>Organisations do avoid any legal proceedings (1) Lack of Universities to offer cybersecurity degrees (1) Outflux of Cybersecurity experts (4 out of 13 banks)</p> <p>Budget is allocated but not used (3 out of 13 banks) Hardly 5 to 10% implementation (4 out of 13 banks) Introducing regulatory requirement regarding directors' training and CISOs' rights as well as investment (3 out of 13 banks) Strategic planning in their banks is ineffective (8 out of 13 banks) Budget is not approved by board (8 out of 13 banks)</p> <p>Saving is preferred over customers' interest (6 out of 13 banks)</p>	<p>Bank A, B, D, G, I, J, K and L (CISOs) Bank A, C, D, D1, E, G, H, and M (CISOs) and Bank F: Cash controller Bank A, B, D, D1, G, and J (CISOs) Bank A, D, D1, G, K, and L (CISOs) Bank A, B, C, D1 F, and J (CISOs) Bank A (CISO) Bank M (CISO) Bank A, D, D1, G, and M (CISOs) Bank J, D, D1, H (CISOs) Bank D1, F, I, and M (CISOs) Bank B, D, and D1 (CISOs)</p> <p>Bank D1, E, F, H, I, J, K, and L (CISOs) Bank D1, E, F, H, I, K, and L (CISOs) Bank C, E, F, G, I, and L (CISOs)</p>

Source: Interview Data

Summary of Key Findings for Research Question 1 and 2

Customer awareness, regulatory framework, law and law enforcement and strategic planning all are found to be important factors to improve the cybersecurity governance in private commercial banks of Pakistan, with following justification.

Customer awareness - in general with low customer cybersecurity awareness rate banks have limited resources to spread the awareness. A customer with digital literacy can be aware but educational (financial) literacy can boost that awareness. However, public digital literacy and cybersecurity awareness can secure the cyberspace by avoiding social engineers to obtain banking information used by relatives performing e-services such as shopping. Nonetheless, government need to take immediate initiatives to run effective campaigns relevant to peoples' level of understanding and capacity.

Regulatory framework - in absence of comprehensive regulatory framework the banks have adopted some policies in implementation which shows the governance approach however the implementation of those policies is not in practice. Moreover, SBP also focuses on governance approach rather than implementation. This could be confirmed as majority of banks even lack fundamentals of information security. Hence, in lack of effective regulatory framework and check and balance from SBP the cybersecurity governance of private commercial banks is ineffective. Most importantly, the regulatory framework could be improved but it is again the result of negligence of SBP by not employing the experts who could develop complementary regulatory framework.

Law and Law Enforcement - Poor cybersecurity law and its ineffective implementation hinders the effective cybersecurity governance by banks. Given that Harsh punishments and effective law and its enforcement can demotivate cyber criminals. Otherwise, the banks have to spend a lot on cybersecurity (technology and other solutions). Yet, with low customer awareness, customers may become victim of social engineering as a weak link. Thus, law and its enforcement must be at place. Furthermore, the ineffective law its enforcement is affected by low level of capability of law enforcement agents. Additionally, the law enforcement supporting agencies (call centre with fresh graduates stealing peoples' data) are corrupt. Henceforth, Government need to make immediate actions to facilitate law enforcement to stragically mitigate cybersecurity risk.

Strategic planning - the private commercial banks of Pakistan require investment in innovative technology, employees training and motivation, and hiring required number of experts. In documents the budget is allocated but hardly implemented with policies 5 to 10%. Besides, the criminal employee is not taken to court to avoid expenses. Most importantly, the directors are the main character in banks who do not approve the budget preferring to save instead of investing in cybersecurity, ignoring the interest of customers. Therefore, the banks lack cybersecurity resilience culture and their strategic planning is ineffective. Furthermore, low existence of institutions to graduate cybersecurity experts is accompanied by immigration of cybersecurity experts for their career development. This creates scarcity of cybersecurity experts in Pakistan.

The factor strategic planning supports the understanding and perception of banks (executives as they make decision) about cybersecurity governance. The results show that there is a lack of awareness and training among directors who could support the cybersecurity resilience culture providing effective cybersecurity governance by approving the budget and ensuring 100% implementation of policies.

Overall, the findings suggested that each of these four factors is important to improve cybersecurity governance in private commercial banks of Pakistan. This implies the concept of institutional logics which suggests that organisational success can be result of structural, normative, and symbolic logics collectively.

Research Question Three: Which cybersecurity threats are caused by identified factors (challenges) in private commercial banks of Pakistan?

6.3.4. Theme 4: Cybersecurity threats affecting cybersecurity governance in private commercial banks of Pakistan

Specifically described which cyberthreat is of more concern for their banks and why?:

6.3.4.1. Sub-theme: ATM Skimming

21 out of 21 participants informed that ATM skimming is one of the challenging threat the private commercial banks of Pakistan are confronting (table 17a). Bank A, B, D, E, F, and M (CISOs); and Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker highlighted that the use of card reader slots for ATM skimming is increasing at fast rate which made ATM machines insecure in Pakistan (7 out of 13 banks). 8 out of 13 banks (Bank A, B, C, D, G, I, J, and K - CISOs) emphasised that it is bank's responsibility to provide secure e-banking services to customers otherwise they will lose their trust on e-banking. This can result in lower profits and banks will bankrupt (Bank B: Customer's relationship and marketing manager).

Bank D, E, H, and M (CISOs) confirmed that most of the ATM machines in Pakistan are not upgraded as investment is not approved (4 out of 13 banks). This has allowed international hackers to steal money recently from ATM machines. However, as a solution Anti-ATM skimming and Biometric ATM machines have been introduced but their adopt is dependent on budget (3 out of 13 banks; Bank A and G – CISOs and Bank E: Senior credit control manager). Bank E: Senior credit control manager also told that our managers must inspect ATM machines every morning to remove card reader slots if inserted. Yet, Bank E (CISO) said that ATM skimming is a continuous threat to banks. Bank G (CISO) suggested that ATM skimming is avoidable if along with installing anti-skimming devices customers remain vigilant about card-reader slots. Bank M (CISO) disclosed important issues such as the code analysis are not performed for ATM machines and the administrative staff have access two ATM windows which can be used to install malware to steal the data. Bank A (CISO) further tallied that in market certain models of ATM machines' keys are available which can be used to insert card reader or other devices in ATM machine to steal the data.

Moreover, he mentioned that such activity will not be detected because the ATM machine can be rebooted.

Table 17a: ATM Skimming

ATM Skimming	CISO	Other Respondents
Most challenging threat (21)	All	All
Use of ATM machines is not secure (7)	Bank A, B, D, E, F, and M	Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker
Most increasing trend (7)	Bank A, B, D, E, F, and M	Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker
Inserting card reader slots (7)	Bank A, B, D, E, F, and M	Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker
It is bank's responsibility (8)	Bank A, B, C, D, G, I, J, and K	
Insecurity resulting loss of trust on bank (8)	Bank A, B, C, D, G, I, J, and K	
Banks will bankrupt (1)		Bank B: Customer's relationship and marketing manager
ATM machines are not upgraded, depending on executives (4)	D, E, H, and M	
Money withdrawn from ATM machines by international hackers (3)	Bank A and G	Bank E: Senior credit control manager
Check machines everyday (1)		Bank E: Senior credit control manager
Anti-ATM skimming machine (3)	Bank A and G	Bank E: Senior credit control manager
Biometric ATM machine (3)	Bank A and G	Bank E: Senior credit control manager
Budget restrict to adopt it (3)	Bank A and G	Bank E: Senior credit control manager
ATM skimming is constant threat	Bank E	
Along with anti-skimming devices customers need to be vigilant	Bank G	
No code analysis	Bank M	
Admin have access	Bank M	
Interior machine to open ATM machine	Bank A	
Reboot ATM	Bank A	

Source: Interview Data

6.3.4.2. Sub-theme: Social engineering

All of the respondents (21) revealed that social engineering is most increasing and major threat. Bank D, F, and L CISOs (3 out of 13 banks) shared that social engineering is easy for cyber criminals as it is borderless approach to impersonate and steal data (table 17b). 9 out of 13 banks (Bank A, B, C, E, G, H, I, J, and K – CISOs) claimed that our customers and employees are the main target of such criminals because of low literacy and awareness. Nevertheless, Bank B, F, H, I, J, K

L, and M (CISOs, 8 out of 13 banks) spotted that finding our customers and employees as a weak link cybercriminals are attempting to try different techniques of social engineering. They use such methods (E-mail and SMS more frequent) that even literate people become their victims resulting in financial loss to banks (Bank K). 4 out of 13 banks (Bank B, E, and H – CISOs and Bank F: Cash controller) mentioned that people trust on luck and innocently give their personal information thus the whole culture is responsible (Bank F: Cash controller). Bank B: Operations head pronounced that cybercriminals use social engineering as a shortcut to data breach, which is similar to responses of Bank D, F, and L (CISOs) about borderless approach. Therefore, launching malware, ransomware, or Trojans, the social engineering is the main source (Bank A and E – CISOs, 2 out of 13 banks). Bank A and E (CISOs) also added that it is hard to deal with social engineering because it has to do with people. Hence, social engineering cannot be fully avoided (Bank G – CISO) since, human are biggest risk (Bank M – CISO). Consequently, the fastest solution is customer and employee awareness (21 out of 21 respondents).

Table 17b: Social engineering

Social engineering	CISOs	Other Respondents
Increasing trend and major challenge (21)	All	All
Borderless approach to breach data confidentiality (3)	Bank D, F, and L	
Our customers and employees are being affected increasingly (9)	Bank A, B, C, E, G, H, I, J, and K	
People with less literacy and awareness our major target (9)	Bank A, B, C, E, G, H, I, J, and K	
Multiple methods of social engineering are easy (8)	Bank B, F, H, I, J, K, L, and M	
Literate people are also victim (1)	Bank K	
E-mail and SMS are more famous (1)	Bank K	
Banks have to bear financial loss (1)	Bank K	
People trust on luck and share information (4)	Bank B, E, and H	Bank F: Cash controller
Culture is to blame (1)		Bank F: Cash controller
Cybercriminals prefer social engineering (1)		Bank: Operations head
To deliver malware, ransomware, Trojans social engineering is the primary tool	Bank A and E	
Major concern because it has to do with people	Bank E	
avoid social engineering is not possible	Bank G	
Human are biggest risk	Bank M	
Quick remedy is awareness	All	All

Source: Interview Data

Fake web sites and online shopping

Table 17c shows that the use of fake websites is increasing hugely adopting social engineering (6 out of 13 banks, Bank B, D, C, I, and K - CISOs; Bank E: Senior credit control manager and Bank B: Operations head) especially, since COVID-19 (Bank H

- CISO). The main source to trap people is by impersonating (Bank C and H: CISO). Bank F (Cash controller) further underlined that this impersonating is applied publicly as people use bank cards of family members. Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst insisted that apart of fake websites the online shopping websites are insecure while, online shopping is dynamically increasing in Pakistan. If the strict actions to ban such websites will not be taken by government then it can result in huge financial loss (Bank: Operations head and Bank D: CISO). Unfortunately, there is poor implication of banning fake websites with ineffective law enforcement (Bank L and M – CISOs and Bank B: Customer’s relationship and marketing manager).

Table 17c: Fake web sites and online shopping

Fake web sites and online shopping	CISO	Other Respondents
Fake websites increasing in bulk (7)	Bank B, D, C, I, and K	Bank E: Senior credit control manager Bank B: Operations head
People are trapped by impersonating (1)	Bank C	
Use of someone else’s card (1)		Bank F: Cash controller
Online shopping trend is new and increasing (1)		Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst)
Our online shopping websites are not secure (1)		Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst)
Government needs to wake up (1)		Bank: Operations head
Realise the need of immediate action (1)	Bank D	Bank: Operations head
Banned creation of such websites (1)		Bank B: Customer’s relationship and marketing manager
Leniency can shake the stability of economy (1)		Bank: Operations head
Low implication of ban (3)	Bank L and M	Bank B: Customer’s relationship and marketing manager
Fake websites increased during COVID-19 (1)	Bank H	
Impersonated e-mail leads to fake website (1)	Bank H	

Source: Interview Data

6.3.4.3. Sub-theme: DDoS

Table 17d highlights that DDoS is most common attack because of vulnerabilities in our information systems (7 out of 13 banks, Bank A, B, D, D1, E, G, H, and - CISOs; Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst; Bank: Operations head; and Bank B: Customer’s relationship and marketing manager). Bank F: Cash controller mentioned that often our banking applications or website is slow because of DDoS traffic; resulting in delay in transaction (Bank B: CISO). Bank D (CISO) indicated it the recent DDoS attack on Roshan digital account. Banks lost thousands of customers because of this incident (Bank J: CISO). Bank M (CISO) and Bank B: Customer’s relationship and marketing manager pointed that considering out weak information security infrastructure soon cybercriminals may demand heavy ransomware (2 out of 13 banks), if the solutions not adopted by banks, SBP and government (21 out of 21).

Table 17d: DDoS

DDoS	CISO	Other Respondents
Most common attack (11)	Bank A, B, D, D1, E, G, H, and K	Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst; Bank: Operations head; and Bank B: Customer's relationship and marketing manager
Roshan digital account is most recent case (1)	Bank D	
Lost thousands of customers (1)	Bank J	
Slow banking applications or websites by artificial traffic (1)		Bank F: Cash controller
Delay in transaction (1)	Bank B	
May demand heavy ransomware (2)	Bank M	Bank B: Customer's relationship and marketing manager
Solution is investing in technology, regulating effectively and enforce effective law	All	All

Source: Interview Data

6.3.4.4. Sub-theme: Malware

All CISOs and Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst) (15 respondents) agreed that Malware is another most infectious and common type of threat (15). Bank A, C, F, and M – CISOs and Bank: Operations head (5 out of 13 banks) cybercriminals use malware world widely in all sectors (table 17e). However, 6 out of 13 banks implied that in private commercial banks of Pakistan Trojan horse, virus and worm attacks are common (Bank A, B, C, D, H and M – CISOs and Bank B: Operations head). Some respondents provided positive insights of their IT infrastructure mentioning that our IT team is active (Bank E: Senior credit control manager), employees are not allowed to use computers for private use having restricted access (Bank F: Cash controller), virus does not spread and is managed by experts (Bank: Operations head), employees highlight suspicious activity (Bank L – CISO and Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker). Moreover, Bank B (CISO mentioned that cybercriminals attack on central system of bank using malware so employees are not involved directly. However, Bank H (CISO) demonstrating the recent cyberattacks of 2018 in banks told that if Malware attack is launched and successful it results in financial loss, such as transferring or withdrawing money (Bank B: CISO). Bank D1 (CISO) disclosed that the weak infrastructure supports the malware. Though, Bank A and M (CISOs) demonstrated that cybercriminals use phishing for Malware. This suggests the increasing focus on social engineering. However, it was recommended by 5 out of 13 banks that

professionals, right technology, and awareness is the solution collectively. Likewise, in this regard SBP and government should introduce law and regulation urgently (Bank D, H, I, J, and K - CISOs).

Table 17e: Malware

Malware	CISO	Other Respondents
Another most common type of threat (15)	All (14)	Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst)
Virus will not spread; it is controlled by experts (1)		Bank: Operations head
Malware is used all over the world in all sectors (5)	Bank A, C, F, and M	Bank: Operations head
Trojan horse, virus and worm are more repetitive attacks (7)	Bank A, B, C, D, H and M	Bank B: Operations head
Employees highlight suspicious activity (2)	Bank L	Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker
Malware resulting financial loss (1)	Bank H	
Recent attacks are example (1)	Bank H	
These attacks resulted to withdraw money (1)	Bank B	
Basic infrastructure is weak (1)	Bank D1	
Professionals, right technology, and awareness can help (5)	Bank D1, H, I, J, and K	
Need immediate action by SBP and government to introduce law and regulation (5) statement	Bank D, H, I, J, and K	
IT department is active (1)		Bank E: Senior credit control manager
Staff cannot use computers for private use (1)		Bank F: Cash controller
We have restrictions (1)		Bank F: Cash controller
Hackers attack on central system of bank (1)	Bank B	
Phishing is used for Malware (2)	Bank A and M	

Source: Interview Data

6.3.4.5. Sub-theme: Deepfake

When asked, how new technology (Deepfake) can have impact on information security of your banks, the following responses were received:

Only CISOs (13 out of 13 banks but 14 respondents) were aware about this new cybersecurity threat to banks (table 17f). The respondents revealed that the use of phone calls, emails, or messages is a common method of impersonating our customers and employees. However, the use of video impersonating in case of low literacy and less awareness can make people victim easily (all CISO). 5 out of 13 banks (Bank A, D, J, K, and M - CISOs) mentioned that the possibility of instant technological solutions is impossible with information security infrastructure map

without security protocols. However, the adequate employee and customer training and awareness can be effective (Bank B, C, H, I, and K - CISOs).

Table 17f: Deepfake

<i>Deepfake</i>	CISO	Other Respondents
New form of attack (14)	All	
Audio, e-mail, or message impersonating is in trend (1)	Bank H	
Video impersonating is worst (14)	All	
Infrastructure mapped out without security protocols (5)	Bank A, D, J, K, and M	
Employee as well as customers and appropriate actions can help (5)	Bank B, C, H, I, and K	

Source: Interview Data

Following are some key quotes of respondents to sustain above findings.

Table 17g: Cybersecurity Threats' Quotes

Research Question 3.	Cybersecurity Threats' Quotes	Supported by CISOs	Supported by Other Respondents
Q11. Which cyberthreat is of more concerned for your bank and why?	<p>ATM Skimming “Use of bank cards in ATM machines is not secure in Pakistan. It is most increasing trend in Pakistan to steal card details from ATM machine mostly by inserting card reader slots in ATM machines (Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker).”</p>	Bank A, B, D, E, F, and M	
	<p>“It is banks’ responsibility to secure their ATM machines. Also, the awareness to public to check fraudulent card reader slots in ATM machines before using it, can play a major role to lessen such frauds (Bank C: CISO).”</p>	Bank A, B, D, G, I, J, and K	
	<p>“The bank cards are the most convenient and used by our customers in daily lives. This results in increasing transactions of banks and profitability. If the customer will feel unsecure, they will lose the trust on bank and will stop depositing their money in banks. Consequently, the commercial banks will bankrupt - as they are run merely with the deposits of their customers and will affect the economy (Bank B: Customer’s relationship and marketing manager).”</p>		
	<p>“Most of the ATM machines in our banking sector are not upgraded. Their upgrades are expensive. However, the banks are profitable and can afford it, but it is entirely board of directors’ decision (Bank H: CISO).”</p>	Bank D, E, and M	
	<p>“After the substantial cyberattacks of 2018 and 2019 our bank has introduced anti-ATM skimming machine. Also, biometric ATM machine is launched in Pakistan by bank Islami. But, because of budgeting issue and update every year banks are adopting it slowly. This system is effective except card pin but still there is continuous work to make it secure. However, as a precautionary measure our managers are responsible to check ATM machines every morning (Bank E: Senior credit control manager).”</p>	Bank A and G	
	<p>“To instal ATM machines the service provider brings private circuit from one of the vendor and they connect ATM to the banking application. Number two their admins have administrative access to the ATM windows. Number three who did the code analysis or who did the pin test of the ATM machine, no one. So, you do not even know and if there is a compromise on the security weakness of the windows system on the ATM or by corporate users (Bank M: CISO).”</p>		
	<p>“ATM skimming can be avoided by installing anti-skimming devices on card-readers. <u>I</u>t however, requires the customers to be vigilant (Bank G).”</p>		
	<p>Social Engineering “Social engineering is our basic concern because our customers and employees (human factors) are being increasingly affected by social engineering techniques (Bank H: CISO).”</p>	Bank A, B, C, E, G, I, J, and K	
	<p>“The cybercriminals are emphasising to use multiple innovative methods of social engineering because this is the easy way to access the customers’ data. Using social engineering methods cybercriminals impersonate themselves (to create the sense of urgency, curiosity, or fear) which result in information shared by our customers and employees. And considering the lack of knowledge, awareness and literacy the cybercriminals’ social engineering techniques become successful in our society. Ultimately, this results in money stolen from our customers’ accounts and risk our reputation (Bank J: CISO).”</p>	Bank B, F, H, I, J, K L, and M	
	<p>“The intellectual cybercriminals keep using innovative unfamiliar methods of social engineering so that even the literate people including bank employees become prey of social engineering. Subsequently, if a fraud is resulted from our employee’s mistake or lack of awareness the bank has to bear the financial loss. However, e-mail and SMS are more famous methods of social engineering nowadays (Bank K: CISO).”</p>		

<p>“Another factor is our country’s culture. People in our society are living the life of simplicity where they trust someone who tells them that they have won the lucky draw. Correspondingly, people will share their personal details for example date of birth, identity card number or even bank details to receive the money of lucky draw. While, cybercriminals use those details then to steal the money from bank. Again, our culture lacks awareness (Bank F: Cash controller).”</p>	Bank B, E, and H	
<p>“Consequently, awareness and training of customers and employees is quick solution where technology adoption is a problem (Bank A - CISO)”</p>	All	All
<p>Fake Websites and Online Shopping “Everyday thousands of fake websites are created with purpose to access the confidential information of users. Many of our customers provide their details on such websites, believing the information impersonated on those websites because people do not have awareness of such scams (Bank C: CISO).”</p>	Bank B, D, I, and K	Bank E: Senior credit control manager Bank B: Operations head
<p>“The implication of banning malicious websites is not effective in Pakistan. Its recent example is YouTube, when it was banned as declared by the government of Pakistan, but still people were able to have access to it using different applications (Bank B: Customer’s relationship and marketing manager).”</p>	Bank L and M	
<p>“Apart of fake websites even our online shopping websites are not secure. They are developed with the basic features of the websites and without security protocols, which is a main problem. The government should require the businesses to ensure the information security of their websites before they launch them (Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst).”</p>		
<p>“With increasing trend of online shopping during COVID-19, the use of fake websites increased to steal personal information of users. Moreover, the impersonated confirmatory e-mails have mostly led to fake websites, as reported by most of our customers. Hence, use of fake websites can be considered as a category of social engineering (Bank H: CISO).”</p>		
<p>“The government need to stop the development of such websites or ban them strictly because. It is the game of fake, wake or shake (Bank: Operations head).”</p>	Bank D	
<p>DDoS “Most of the times our online facilities are distracted (availability issue). Most recent case of this is, when plenty of our customers and foreign residents who wanted to become our customers by opening Roshan digital account with our bank, reported to our bank that on our website the users have to refill the same details again and again after refreshing the page and they cannot proceed further. Apparently, those people already lost their personal information applying for Roshan digital account (Bank D: CISO).”</p>		
<p>“As per the bank’s estimate we lost thousands of customers who were tired of keep applying through our websites and they quitted when they could not. Approximately, this has resulted for bank to lose foreign remittances of Rs. 100 million in last year (Bank J: CISO).”</p>		
<p>“Often our banking applications or website is found slow because of artificial traffic created by cyber criminals (DDoS). Using malicious malware cybercriminals obtain access to our system and launch in bulk DDoS attacks (Bank F: Cash controller).”</p>		
<p>“Having weak information security infrastructure and providing it bandages with temporary security methods, it is possible that in future our banks will have to pay heavy ransomware amounts to regain access to their online services. Because our banking industry has potential deposits (Bank B: Customer’s relationship and marketing manager).”</p>	Bank M	
<p>Malware</p>	Bank A, C, F, and M	

	"Malware is most malicious cybersecurity threat because it is used to edit, alter, or delete the data. Going back to the fact that these malicious attacks have been continually affecting our banking industry from 2018 to 2019 (causing heavy financial loss) shows that our banking information security infrastructure is vulnerable, and it needs immediate security (Bank H: CISO)."		
	"Malware is most malicious cybersecurity threat because it is used to edit, alter, or delete the data. Going back to the fact that these malicious attacks have been continually affecting our banking industry from 2018 to 2019 (causing heavy financial loss) shows that our banking information security infrastructure is vulnerable, and it needs immediate security (Bank H: CISO)."		
	"The recent cyberattacks have resulted to lose the customers and their trust. If this continues our banks will lose their competitive advantage as the customers deposit enable banks to run smoothly (Bank B: CISO)."		
	"Our banks are vulnerable to such attacks because the basic infrastructure our banks is weak. Moreover, still we can improve it through heavy investment in professionals, right technology, and employees training as well as awareness. The respondent emphasised that SBP and government of Pakistan need to take immediate actions to solve this problem before it gets worst (Bank D1: CISO)."	Bank H, I, J, and K	
	"As a precaution the IT department keep checking all the activities and highlights any attack. They check the nature of the attack and take action. The data cannot be transferred from one PC to other. Even we cannot check the PC properties or change the date or time. We cannot use USB device or charge the device or play audio or video neither use internet for Facebook or YouTube. Only limited government sites are opened. Even managers have limited access (Bank F: Cash controller)."		
Q12. Are you aware of Deepfake technology? If yes how it can affect your bank?	Deepfake "Right now, the audio, e-mail, or message impersonating is so common to access the personal information of our customers. But deepfake attacks are going to be worst (Bank H: CISO)."	All	
	"With information infrastructure mapped without security protocols, the best way to deal with such a devastating technology is to focus on factors affecting cybersecurity (Bank K: CISO)."	Bank A, B, C, D, H, I, J, and M	

Source: Interview Data

Table 17h: Research Question 3 Key Results

Research Question	Key Findings	Participants
<p>Q3. Which cybersecurity threats are caused by identified factors (challenges) in private commercial banks of Pakistan?</p>	<p>ATM Skimming Most challenging threat (13 out of 13 banks) Use of ATM machines is not secure (7 out of 13 banks)</p> <p>It is bank's responsibility otherwise insecure e-banking results losing customer trust (8 out of 13 banks) Consequently, the banks will bankrupt (1 out of 13 banks)</p> <p>Anti-ATM skimming and Biometric ATM machines have been introduced (3 out of 13 banks)</p> <p>Still, customers have to act as vigilant (1 out of 13 banks) But the problem is that ATM machines are not upgraded, depending on executives who restrict the budget (6 out of 13 banks)</p> <p>Therefore, no code analysis are done saving costs and allowing admin access to vendor (1 out of 13 banks) The worst thing is that ATM machine can be opened using specific keys and reboot ATM (1 out of 13 banks)</p>	<p>21 out of 21 Bank A, B, D, E, F, and M (CISOs) and Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker Bank A, B, C, D, G, I, J, and K (CISOs) Bank B: Customer's relationship and marketing manager Bank A and G (CISOs); and Bank E: Senior credit control manager Bank G (CISO) A, D, E, G, H, and M (CISOs); and Bank E: Senior credit control manager Bank M (CISO)</p> <p>Bank A (CISO)</p>
	<p>Social Engineering, Fake web sites and online shopping Increasing trend and major challenge (13 out of 13 banks) Fake and online shopping websites are increasing as a source of social engineering (6 out of 13 banks)</p> <p>Banking customers and employees are becoming victim increasingly lacking digital literacy and awareness (9 out of 13 banks) Moreover, cybercriminals are consistently innovating multiple ways of social engineering (8 out of 13 banks)</p> <p>Even, to deliver malware attacks social engineering is the main source Hence, preventing social engineering is not probable However, possible solution is awareness (13 out of 13 banks) Also, ban use of fake and insecure websites to prevent such methods of social engineering (1 out of 13 banks)</p>	<p>21 out of 21 Bank B, D, C, I, and K (CISOs); Bank E: Senior credit control manager and Bank B: Operations head Bank A, B, C, E, G, H, I, J, and K (CISOs) Bank B, F, H, I, J, K L, and M (CISOs)</p> <p>Bank A and E (CISOs) Bank G (CISO) 21 out of 21 Bank B: Customer's relationship and marketing manager</p>

	<p>DDoS DDoS is most common attack because of weak information security infrastructure (7 out of 13 banks)</p> <p>Already banks lost many customers in past (1 out of 13 banks) It is expected that in future cybercriminals may demand heavy ransomware which will result in financial loss and customer trust loss (2 out of 13 banks)</p> <p>Solution is investing in technology, regulating effectively and enforce effective law (13 out of 13 banks)</p>	<p>Bank A, B, D, D1, E, G, H, and K (CISOs); Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst; Bank B: Operations head; and Bank B: Customer's relationship and marketing manager Bank J (CISO) Bank M (CISO); and Bank B: Customer's relationship and marketing manager 21 out of 21</p>
	<p>Malware It is another common cyberattack having weak security infrastructure (13 out of 13 banks)</p> <p>It causes financial loss (1 out of 13 banks) Investing in experts, right technology and awareness can help (5 out of 13 banks) Furthermore, it require immediate response of SBP and government to introduce regulations and law (5 out of 13 banks)</p>	<p>14 CISOs and Bank A; Cybersecurity Risk Analyst Bank H (CISO) Bank D1, H, I, J, and K (CISOs) Bank D1, H, I, J, and K (CISOs)</p>
	<p>Deepfake It is new version of cyberattack – not known by many people and can be worst by video impersonating, lacking awareness among people (13 out of 13 banks) Therefore, in case of weak information infrastructure employee and customer awareness along with appropriate actions of law and regulation can help (5 out of 13 banks)</p>	<p>14 CISOs Bank B, C, H, I, and K (CISOs)</p>

Source: Interview Data

Summary of Key Findings for Research Question 3

According to the results, ATM skimming, Social engineering, Malware and DDoS are the major threats the PCBP confronting. However, social engineering is more concerned finding unawareness among customers and employees as a weak human link for cybercriminals. This also proposed Deepfake to be effective for cybercriminals, as explained below.

ATM skimming – it is a major issue because cheap solutions are adopted skipping code analysis of ATM machines to check their reliability and providing access to external vendors to customer data. Furthermore, solutions such as Anti-ATM skimming and biometric ATM machines devices are available but their adoption is a problem which is related to executives' approval of budget. Moreover, it is also highlighted that even with such technological adoption awareness among customers about card readers slots is a crucial factor to completely prevent ATM skimming threat.

Social engineering – is affecting even educated people thus, the fast and effective solution for social engineering is suggested the awareness and training of customers and employees considering their low digital literacy and awareness rate in the country. Additionally, the use of fake websites and insecure shopping websites is another source of social engineering. This shows the increasing trend of social engineering using different techniques. However, along with awareness the government need to ban such websites to immediately stop the use of such social engineering techniques.

DDoS and Malware – DDoS is critical as it can result in ransomware amount to be demanded. Relatively, malware is of devastating nature as it will directly cause financial loss. However, DDoS and malware are threats to private commercial banks of Pakistan because of weak information security infrastructure. The solution is to improve the information security infrastructure, by investing in technology, regulating effectively, spreading awareness and enforce effective law.

Finally, Deepfake attack is new in Pakistan banking industry and can be devastating with weak security, low literacy, and awareness. However, since comprehensive technological adoption might take years, employee and customer awareness is the quick solution.

In short, increasing trend of these threats may result in loss of customer confidence on e- banking and banks may bankrupt.

Research Question Four: What can be the effective cybersecurity governance measures for the private commercial banks of Pakistan?

6.3.5. Theme 5: Recommendations for effective cybersecurity governance in private commercial banks of Pakistan

To justify if there is any other challenge or factor which is also affecting the cybersecurity of your bank, following views were received:

6.3.5.1. Sub-theme: Other Factors Explored - Factors affecting Information security control system

5 out of 13 banks indicated a few other challenges they were confronting in cybersecurity governance (table 18a). These all challenges relate to Information security control system somehow. Bank B and D (CISOs) indicated that during preparation phase it is hard to collection data from industry and selection of security measures based on budget allocated. Bank J highlighted the prevention phase issue as ‘the access to internet is restricted and lack of investment in innovative solutions. Bank D shared that during detection phase customer late response, less cybersecurity experts and customer unawareness remain issue to effectively implement controls. Bank K and L told that in response process the data collection from peer banks is a hurdle to efficiently deal with cyberthreats. Moreover, the learning process is mainly ineffective because of lack of employee training, untrained employees, investment on equipment, and reward function. However, besides data collection issue the other factors fall in one of the customer awareness, staff training or motivation, and investment issue category. However, this sub-theme will be used in discussion chapter under the theme of factors affecting cybersecurity governance in banks since it justifies if any other factors need to be considered.

Table 18a: Information security control system

Information security control system	CISOs	Other Respondents
Preparation process: Collection of data from industry (2), Deciding How Much to Spend on Information Security (2)	Bank B and D	
Prevention process: Online access of internet (1), Need recommended solutions but management do not invest. (1),	Bank J	
Detection process: Customer response time (1), Less cybersecurity experts (1), Customer unawareness (1)	Bank D	
Response process: Data collection from peer banks (1)	Bank K	
Learning process: Employee training, Untrained staff and investment on trainings and equipment, lack of reward function (2)	Bank K and L	

Source: Interview Data

6.3.5.2. Sub-theme: Third-Party Solutions, System Upgrade and MFA

The following statements explain why third-party solutions are not effective for cybersecurity of banks and what is the alternative:

11 out of 13 banks (Bank B, C, D, D1, E, F, G, H, I, J, K, and M - CISOs) confirmed that their management prefer to upgrade their banking systems instead of using third party solutions because they are not trustable and cost a lot (table 18b). They also proposed that system upgrades can be expensive but in long run it benefit the business to secure its information assets. Bank F: Cash controller further added that the use of APIs or third-party solutions can even increase the costs to business by adding risk to its information security. Comparatively, Bank A (CISO) mentioned that banks can use both the cloud storage and MFA as cloud storage will only store non-financial information. Relatively, Bank L (CISO) recommended that all third-party services should be used as it will transfer the risk to them and reduce the cost. Needlessness, there is no regulatory restrictions to use these solutions (Bank G). Similarly, all interviewees (21 out of 21) suggested that multifactor authentication can be a best solution being used internationally, as it is easy to adopt by customer and secure. However, majority of the banks in Pakistan are not using MFA because of investment required to adopt it, ignoring their responsibility of the writing secure information system to customers (Bank J). Only Bank B claimed that being a top bank in Pakistan they are using 3D secure multi factor authentication and it has been proven effective. Bank L and M (CISOs) highlighted that face recognition feature can help to avoid social engineering in case of low literacy and awareness.

Table 18b: Third-Party Solutions, System Upgrade and MFA

Solutions	CISOs	Other Respondents
Our banks prefer to upgrade banking system, as third-party solution is not secure and costly (12)	Bank B, C, D, D1, E, F, G, H, I, J, K, and M	
System upgrade is better but expensive (12)	Bank B, C, D, D1, E, F, G, H, I, J, K, and M	
APIs or external solutions for cybersecurity is not cost effective (1)		Bank F: Cash controller
Regulatory restrictions	Bank G	
The Multi Factor Authentication (MFA) is best as it is more secure, and it is an international standard (21)	All	All
Most of the banks in Pakistan are not using MFA (21)	All	All
Top Bank - Using 3D secure multi factor authentication (1)	Bank B	
Cybersecurity is banks' initial responsibility (1)	Bank J	
Cloud storage and MFA can be used (1)	Bank A	
Use all third-party services to reduce cost (1)	Bank L	
Device can be registered and face recognition (1)	Bank L and M	

Source: Interview Data

6.3.5.3. Sub-theme: Recommendations

When inquired, considering overall discussion what recommendations do you have to improve the cybersecurity governance of your bank?, below (table 18c) are the responses:

Table 18c: Key Result for Research Question Four

For Banks	CISO	Other Respondents
Multi factor authentication – face recognition	All	All
Device recognition	Bank L and M	
Investment in technology, experts, and training	Bank A, C, D, D1, E, G, H, I, J, K, L, and M	
Human should be the first focus then technology (Bank M)	All	All
Anti-fraud department	Bank B	
Information Security Control Improvement	Bank B	
Limit the amount of transfer		Bank: Operations head
Anti-skimming devices and surveys		Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker
For SBP		
Rigorous and comprehensive cybersecurity framework	All	All
Guidelines about directors’ training and investment decision	Other 13 CISOs	
Improve the capabilities of audit team	Bank D and M	
Work in partnership with government to spread the awareness	Bank J	
For Government		
Spread cybersecurity awareness	All	All
Comprehensive laws for cybersecurity and law enforcement	All	All
Maintain check and balance on SBP	Bank D	
Start courses related to cybersecurity	Bank F	
Tight check on the import of electronic items	Bank F	
Agents should not be asking credentials	Bank M	

Source: Interview Data

6.3.5.4. Sub-theme: Institutional logics Underpinning

Explaining if discussed factors can be sufficient when used alone or must be coordinated collectively for effective cybersecurity governance? the following opinion was created:

All of the respondents emphasised that none of the factors can help alone to improve the cybersecurity governance in our banks (table 18d). Each factor has different perspective in its own nature which other factors cannot complement. Such as low literacy and lack of awareness cannot be ignored having robust technology, regulatory framework and law and law enforcement. However, dealing effectively with each factor can mitigate risk to some extent but their collective implication can result in effective cybersecurity governance in banks.

Table 18d: Institutional logics Underpinning

Institutional logic Underpinning	CISOs	Other Respondents
Only collectively sorting these factors is useful	All	All

Source: Interview Data

To critically interpret the descriptive data, the research question 4 was supported by the following quotes.

Table 18e: Other Factors, Third-Party Solutions and Recommendations Quotes

Research question 4	<i>What can be the effective cybersecurity governance measures for the private commercial banks of Pakistan?</i>		
Q13. Do you think there is any other challenge or factor which is also affecting the cybersecurity of your bank?	Other Factors Explored Quotes	Supported by CISOs	Supported by Other Respondents
	“During preparation process we as information security officers find it difficult to collect data from industry. Because banks do not have built up connections with agencies who can provide such data. Another important factor during preparation phase we face is deciding the amount of money to spend on information security. Because, there is no point to provide such security solutions in which the board is not willing to invest. Therefore, it becomes difficult for us to choose the best solution of cybersecurity (Bank B: CISO).”	Bank D	
	“During prevention phase we do not have access to internet. Only the higher management have this access. This prevents us to perform the tasks we are required. There is need of recommended solutions, but management do not invest (Bank J: CISO).”		
	“During detection phase if customer responds quickly, then only we can chase up and spot on the threat. While, in our case because of lack of awareness customer response time is high. On the other hand, lack of experts increases the burden of detection throughout whole network (Bank D: CISO).”		
	“During the response process data collection from peer banks is a hurdle. It takes time. The SBP should provide a system which can enable such data collection in case of a threat. Also, lack of employee training, untrained staff, lack of innovative equipment and reward function restricts the learning process (Bank K: CISO).”	Bank L	
Q14. Based on the above discussion, what recommendations do you have to improve the cybersecurity governance of your bank?	Recommendations Quotes	All	
	“We should also focus on training the senior management and the board of directors on the requirements and we should make them aware of the cybersecurity tools that are arising cross the globe so that they should develop a good understanding on why cybersecurity is required for the bank (Bank A: CISO).”		
	“The authorities must implement strong checks and balance on the import of electronic items. Moreover, it is recommended to invest on producing the local computer hardware in Pakistan (Bank F).”		
	“Cybersecurity campaigns should be run using different mediums for example by advertisements to raise awareness at large scale, and cyber day can also be celebrated. Moreover, seminars and radio announcements need to be conducted, people with low literacy, youth, and common citizens to aware about the secure use of internet (Bank E: CISO).”	All	All
	“Banks across the globe should implement ISO/NIST standards to secure their environments.(Bank G: CISO).”	All	All
	“They have to start from the human then the technology. Plus, they have to start with the human executives, employees, their contractors, their customers, their support team, and their customer support team (Bank M: CISO).”	All	All
	“The Government should require the Higher Education Commission to start courses related to cybersecurity, to produce human resource who can meet the needs of the country (Bank F).”		

	<p>“The bank can recognise customer’s device by registering it with them as a trusted device. They should have a voice recognition also. Voice recognition can be done only through a machine not from the human. A man cannot understand, cannot even look voice (Bank M).”</p>		
	<p>“Moreover, your agents should not be allowed to see anyone’s credentials that should be automated. Why the personnel is asking customer’s mother name why should tell them, that is the biggest risk (Bank M).”</p>		
	<p>“However, what is actually required in Pakistan especially is that the users, the security personnel and to education their board (Bank L).”</p>		
Q15. Can third party solutions be an alternative for technology upgrade and multi-factor authentication be a useful solution?	<p>Third-Party Solutions, System Upgrade and MFA Quotes</p> <p>“Some of the banks are using external sources for example cloud storage and open banking etc. it can be useful for a short period of time but at the end those sources are also vulnerable if they are not provided with appropriate security. Therefore, it is always recommended to upgrade banking system even though if it is expensive, but it provides long term security and peace of mind – confidence (Bank B: Customer’s relationship and marketing manager).”</p>	Bank B, C, D, D1, E, F, G, H, I, J, K, and M	
	<p>“Being a top bank, we are using 3D secure multi factor authentication scheme for our banks’ visa MasterCard and debit card services. This has reduced the chances of fraud and our customers are satisfied (Bank B: CISO).”</p>		
	<p>“Banks usually use external services considering that it will cost them less comparative to system upgrade. While in reality the cost of service plus the cost of financial loss, if any occurs using external services with weak cybersecurity, equals the double of the system upgrade (Bank F: Cash controller).”</p>		
	<p>“Banks as an artificial person are agents of customers who deposited their money in banks. Therefore, it is initial responsibility of banks to secure them at any cost (Bank J: CISO).”</p>		
	<p>“The combination is better depending on requirement because in some systems you need multi factor authentication and sometime external services. Private cloud within provides the banking cloud services by not exposing the data to the outside world (Bank A: CISO).”</p>		

Source: Interview Data

Summary of Recommendations and Key Findings for Research Question Four

In regard to other social factors which could impact the cybersecurity governance of private commercial banks only a few factors (customer response time and awareness; lack of technology and experts, motivation, and reward etc.) were identified in relation to information security system specifically. These all factors again can be referred back to the main factors of this study. Considering third party solutions ineffective and expensive majority of respondents suggested to not use them. However, only a few of respondents recommended to use them in order to reduce the costs, if they are secure. Although, multi factor authentication is recommended by all respondents specifically registering the device and using the face recognition feature. Finally, multiple recommendations have been provided suggesting that collective use of them will be effective in respective to banks, SBP and government.

Note:

Results have considered bank D and D1 as one response when counting total number of banks.

CHAPTER SEVEN: DISCUSSION

7.1. Introduction

This chapter will include the discussion of interview data in detail indicating the key quotes listed in chapter Six and supporting the findings with literature. The chapter will adopt the strategy of discussing results critically aligning them with each research objective of the study and using the themes – upheld by sub-themes, spawned in chapter six. Thus, this systematic approach will support the accomplishment of each research objective. The key findings of this study exhibit multiple institutions to be considered to improve the cybersecurity governance of PCBP, under research objective one. Customer awareness is one of the institutions and the results show that the government need to make effective strategies to spread the fast cybersecurity awareness at national level. This will play a major role to prevent cyberthreats even if other institutions (law and its enforcement, regulatory framework, and internal cybersecurity governance of banks) are weak.

Concurrently, law and its enforcement is another major institution (even with feeble institutions of customer awareness, regulatory framework, and internal cybersecurity governance) as it can discourage the cybercriminals to conduct a cybercrime acknowledging the harsh punishment and fines. Interestingly, the institutions of frail regulatory framework determine the incompetencies of employees in SBP to develop a comprehensive regulatory framework. However, unstable law with its enforcement and regulatory framework encourage cybercriminals and banks to promote cosmetic performance and avoid compliance. Thus, the decision makers (directors) are the main players in PCBP who influence the strategic planning and its compliance, encouraged by less check and balance of unexpert staff of SBP.

This scenario confirms the low level of cybersecurity governance importance in PCBP and initial level of cybersecurity governance maturity, meeting research objective two. Besides, the findings of third research objective suggest that lack of awareness promotes social engineering while outdated technology is possible reason of ATM skimming. Comparatively, malware and DDoS are also major concern since investment in

technology is less. Based on the research objectives one, two and three the recommendations are provided to accomplish research objective four as discussed below in detail.

Objective 1: To investigate the significant internal and external factors (challenges) that affect cybersecurity governance in the private commercial banks of Pakistan.

7.2.1. Theme 1: External factors affecting cybersecurity in private commercial banks of Pakistan

7.2.1.1. Sub theme: Customer Awareness and Cybersecurity Governance

Investigating research objective one customer awareness was one of the factors of this study - which was explored in context of PCBP, supported by 6 interview questions (Q1a to Q1f – Appendix G). These questions studied customer awareness in relation to customer literacy, literacy among general public and awareness, literacy measurement, literacy rate in banks, and awareness program run by government. Responding to Q1a. all (21 out of 21) of the participants agreed that as a human factor customer awareness is one of the most vital external institutions for banks while dealing with cybersecurity (Innab et al., 2018; and Alzubaidi, 2021). Case 11 (Bank K: CISO) clarified the myth of management that the one and only solution to cybersecurity is to focus on symbolic logic of innovative technologies, yet not convinced to invest in the latest technology. In contrast, to take maximum benefit of that technology if the end user (the humans – normative logics) is unaware of secure use of it then the effective cybersecurity governance is impossible (Siyal et al., 2019). The respondent also highlighted that the increasing trend of social engineering by email, SMS or phone calls indicates that since banks started investing in technologies the cybercriminals has dragged their focus on normative logics of societies – banking customers, as a weak point to steal information and money (supported by Bada et al., 2019; Limna, et al. 2022). Hence, in this case technology and customer awareness (application of normative and symbolic logics) altogether can resolve the issue of cybersecurity (Awan & Memon, 2016; Gomes, et al., 2022). Case 7 (Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker) supports this assertion mentioning that their

customer awareness rate is almost same as it was during COVID-19 pandemic (2019 and 2020). In contrast, the rate of cybercrimes has been increased resulted from innovative methods used by cybercriminals (also confirmed from a study by Hummel, 2021). Case 8 (Bank H) further elaborated it highlighting that having 40% customers' awareness of cybersecurity our bank struggles to prevent cyberattacks. Case 9 (Bank I: CISO) tried to confess that our bank has only 50% customers awareness rate. This means that 50% of our customers (who are unaware) are more vulnerable. Even though having good technological instruments if a customer becomes a victim (for example by social engineering shares his information) we will be helpless to secure the confidentiality of customer data. Ultimately this will result in financial losses as well. Hence, customer unawareness is a risk for banks, promoting social engineering (also mentioned by Alzubaidi, 2021).

This can be further supported by literature which shows that the customers of banks are their main stakeholders as customers are the investors in banks who deposit their money which the banks rotate throughout the economy of a country and generate revenues (Awan & Memon 2016; Alzubaidi, 2021). However, being the main stakeholders of banks, the customers are also one of the main threats to their banks due to lack of their awareness about information security issue raised by their engagement with services provided by banks (Innab et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2020).

Relatively, Case 2 (Bank B: Operations head; supported by Bank B CISO) told that in Pakistan technology is available to deal with cybersecurity, but it costs a lot. However, still the human factor (customer awareness) gets involve in to comprehend the cybersecurity of banks. The response indicated the recent example of cybersecurity threats (section 2.3.9.) highlighting that even having 70% of their customers literate and aware about cybersecurity issue still their more than 70% cyberthreats are resulted from the mistake (unawareness) of customers. It reconfirms that customer awareness of cybersecurity is a crucial factor for banks' cybersecurity (Siddiqui, 2022).

Case 10 (Bank J: CISO) emphasised that the customers are not only the weak point to lose their money being unaware, but their unawareness also can result in losing

customers' confidence on bank. The rationale is that the customers do not realise their weakness of being unaware. Instead following their normative logics of unawareness, they expect that after depositing their money with banks it is only banks' responsibility to secure their deposits. Nevertheless, they ignore the factor that a technology can only help if humans make its secure use. These findings confirm the results of a study conducted by Alghazo, Kazmi and Latif (2017) that the banks expect their customers to use banking services keeping their personal information secure while the customers will use banking services based on their awareness and understanding their responsibility towards cybersecurity of their confidential information.

3 of the respondents (Case1 - Bank A: CISO and Cybersecurity Risk Analyst; Case 12 - Bank L: CISO) indicated the point that this normative logic of unawareness needs to be changed as their customers should be aware about the type of information they can share with others and the one they should not share at all. Moreover, the findings from Case 11 (Bank K: CISO) further elaborated it as people are even unawareness if they can block their bank card in case of becoming victim of social engineering (Bank K: CISO). These findings direct that in Pakistan there is lack of understanding the need for and importance of cybersecurity in general. This refers back to the reality that cybersecurity concept is new in Pakistan (Shahbaz UI Haq, 2019).

Furthermore, the following table 19 shows that majority of banks (10 out of 13 cases) have customer awareness rate under 50%. And, as per the above discussion it's a high risk for banks in this era of increasing trend of cybercrimes (Hafiz Ali, et al., 2019; Deshmukh and Anute, 2022). Therefore, 21 out of 21 respondents stated that customer awareness is a critical issue for their banks.

Table 19: Customer Awareness Percentage

Customer awareness	Number of Banks/Cases
30%	2 (Bank A and C)
40%	5 (Bank D, E, F, H, and J)
50%	3 (Bank G, I, and K)
60%	1 (Bank M)
70%	2 (Bank B and L)
Total Banks	13

Source: Interviewees

Similarly, acknowledging the importance of customer awareness, Siyal et al. (2019) in their study found that the lack of customers awareness about cybersecurity can have huge negative affect on information security of banks and that cybersecurity awareness and training to customers can help (Malik & Islam, 2019). Likewise, responding for the Q1b initially, all of the respondents (21 out of 21) agreed that to aware the customers about cybersecurity no specific training is required by SBP. Therefore, limited channels are used by banks to aware their customers for example, banks' websites, brochures, posters, handouts, in person, email and SMS etc.

In this view, the statement of Case 6 (Bank F: Cash controller; also supported by all CISOs-except Bank B) firstly clarifies that there is no specific mechanism used by banks to update the customers with contemporary cybersecurity needs. Secondly, it refers back to the above-mentioned statement of case 10 that the consideration of responsibility to secure their deposits is ignored by customers (Alghazo, et al., 2017). The justification of this no specific training was given by another bank - Case 5 highlighting that since all the ATM cards and credit cards of their bank are backed by big three (third-party services), therefore they only have standard writings on the documents they provide with the credit cards. Those documents clearly state that do not share your personal information such as your password, your security pass, your date of birth, your CNIC and, your mother's maiden name - which is one of the greatest security link for usage of the credit card. At

the same time, the interviewees agreed that cybersecurity training to banking customers can be effective. However, the banks can take initiative to train small number of customers (top 200 or 300 customers of each branch) which slowly will have affect. Contrarily, the government of Pakistan need to play its role and arrange multiple channels of awareness at national level. Because banks do not have high level of resources and time to engage in such activities (Bank E: Senior credit control manager; supported by Bank A, D and M CISOs). Hence, lack of investment in customer awareness is found to be a basic hurdle to initiate the customer training (Bada et al., 2019) while this can also be aligned with the recent initiatives of U.S. and Saudi Arabia governments (Khader, et al., 2021), and UK Government to introduce cybersecurity awareness program to fulfil the need of sufficient cybersecurity skills and knowledge to all people of the country (Odebade and Benkhelifa, 2023). The purpose of government support in cybersecurity awareness is to provide the detailed awareness about how to use banking securely rather than making them aware generally (Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst; supported by Bank D, I, and J - CISOs).

Referring to the awareness initiatives mentioned by case 5 or in start of this section and case 13, the respondents represented a unique point as the normative logics in our country is that the people do not even know what is meant by cybersecurity. They access cyberspace using different portals and websites where they share their information (Chang and Coppel, 2020). Most importantly, they save their passwords on malicious websites. Likewise, no antivirus is used on their personal computers and mobiles which results in hacking their devices and steal financial information.

These findings show that as weak normative logics customers' awareness is a crucial factor to prevent cybercrime in private commercial banks of Pakistan as same was found by Naik Bukht et al. (2020) in other banks of Pakistan. The customers of banks in Pakistan have less awareness and training about cybersecurity and this rationalises that they get hacked (Hafiz Ali et al., 2019; Anwar, 2020). Similarly, customer training can play a vital role to reduce the increasing cybercrimes in banks (Malik & Islam, 2019; Haq & Atta, 2019; Shah, 2009; Siyal et al., 2019). Hence, the first major factor of this study is customer awareness. However, the following section will discuss how some other factors can support the customer awareness.

Customer literacy, literacy parameter and literacy rate

Rationalising the importance of customer awareness all of the respondents (21 out of 21) highlighted that customer digital literacy is a major issue in information security of banks as literacy and awareness are somehow dependent on each other (Q1c.). In this regard, Case 11 (Bank K: CISO) pronounced that there are three categories of customers our banks have. Well educated (20% to 30%), people with low level literacy (high class in school or intermediate level; around 40% of total of our customers), and people with no literacy at all (almost 30% of our customers).

This finding suggests that the second type of people are vulnerable because they try to use multiple facilities of banks (ATM, mobile banking, online payments etc.) more often based on their literacy. Such people have show-off attitude (that they are part of modern society using technology and banking system) or ignore security feature of banking, creating a weak normative logic in the society. On the other hand, counting them with other 30% illiterate people, because they are not information security literate therefore, altogether 70% people can more easily become victim of cybercriminals ((by sharing their information either with employees of bank, at social platforms, or through social engineering, (Orji, 2019)). In contrast, the third type of our customers is vulnerable when they ask other people to help them to fill the cheques. This leads to duplicate chequebook fraud as well as social engineering.

This scenario was further elaborated by findings of Case 8 (Bank H: CISO) discussing that when a customer is not literate good enough, he/she does not acknowledge the essence and necessity of cybersecurity because of lack of awareness. Furthermore, in case they become victim it makes the information security of bank suspicious. Balaraj and Shetty (2019) shared the same point of view that due to low literacy people unintentionally share their bank details which makes them victim of cybercrime such as hacking or ATM skimming etc. A few responses (Bank F: Cash controller; supported by Bank J and M CISO) clearly articulated that that the awareness issue of customers and even general public relates to their literacy level. If they are literate, they can understand

the essence of information security. Hence, a bank with higher rate of illiterate customers is more vulnerable to cyberattacks (Ismailova & Muhametjanova, 2016).

These findings accentuated to raise Q1d. which focused on the parameter the PCBP use to measure the literacy of their customers. In response, Case 7 (Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker, supported by Bank L) pointed out that graduation should be the minimum level of literacy for banking customers to understand the cybersecurity issue. Moreover, people with low or no literacy are still explained with basic knowledge of using banking securely while opening account, assessing them through 'Know Your Customer' (KYC) technique. Additionally, the customers are being aware about cybersecurity through text messages that do not share your personal information with anyone. Again, people with low literacy do not even read the messages and ignore it, as shown from fraud inquiries conducted by bank. At the same time, all interviewees (21 out of 21) agreed that if a customer can operate e-banking services securely then he/she is digitally literate for us (Balaraj and Shetty, 2019). Another explanation was that the banking users need some level of literacy rather than a good level of literacy. Customers with degree if are not aware, and do not know how to operate a system, how it goes, then they are unable to operate it effectively (Bank E: Senior credit control manager; supported by Bank A, L, and E CISOs). Similarly, explicitly shedding light on customer literacy parameter, for banks any customer who can look after his personal/banking data is literate, unrelatedly of his/her formal education level (Case 7 - Bank G:CISO).

These findings are aligned with the results of a study by Rodrigues et al. (2019) which reveals that to be information security literate one does not need to be highly qualified. This recommends that people with less literacy can securely use banking services having training and awareness (Orji, 2019; Rodrigues, et al., 2019). Relatively, the respondent said that unfortunately we have a fewer number of people in our society who are less literate and still have good knowledge and awareness of using information technology securely. The reason is that people do not want to learn as they are unaware of cybersecurity issue (Bank E: Senior credit control manager). However, it can be concluded that an information security literate (digital literacy) customer of a bank is less vulnerable to cyberattacks (Naik Bukht et al., 2020; Magomedov, et al., 2020).

Following Table 20 provides the percentages of literacy level of customers in private commercial banks of Pakistan (PCBP), provided by respondents standardizing these literacy levels based on minimum education of graduation level. The second part of this table provides the awareness rate of those banks' customers extracted from the annual survey conducted by banks.

Table 20: Customer Literacy and Awareness Percentages

Bank	Literacy Rate	Awareness rate	Comparison
A	70%	30%	High literacy; Low awareness
B	70%	70%	Same literacy and awareness
C	5%	30%	Low literacy; high awareness
D	70%	40%	High literacy; Low awareness
E	30%	40%	Low literacy; high awareness
F	40%	40%	Same literacy and awareness
G	50%	50%	Same literacy and awareness
H	50%	40%	High literacy; Low awareness
I	40%	50%	Low literacy; high awareness
J	30%	40%	Low literacy; high awareness
K	60%	50%	High literacy; Low awareness
L	70%	70%	Same literacy and awareness
M	40%	60%	Low literacy; high awareness

Source: Interviewees

The above Table 20 shows that there is 5% literacy (1 – Bank C), 30% literacy (2 – Bank J and E), 40% literacy (3 – Bank F and I, M), 50% literacy (2 – Bank G and H), 60% literacy (1 - Bank K), 70% literacy (4 – Bank A, B, D, and L) in participated banks respectively. Thus, the overall literacy rate of customers is low (Balaraj & Shetty, 2019) with majority of banks (8 out of 13) having under 50% literacy level. However, in contrast to customer awareness percentage (above Table 20), the customer literacy in Bank C is 5% while their customer awareness is 30%. This supports to the above finding (from case 5) that regardless of degree a person who is information security literate (having low literacy which is in this case 5%) will be a literate customer of bank (Rodrigues et al., 2019). Similarly, Bank A, D, H, and K show high customer literacy (70%, 70%, 50%, and 60%) but low customer awareness rate (30%, 40%, 40%, and 50%) of cybersecurity in their banks respectively. On the other hand, bank B, F, G, and L had same level of customer literacy and customer awareness (70%, 40%, 50%, and 70% respectively).

Comparatively, bank E, I, J, and M presented high customer awareness (40%, 50%, 40%, and 60%) compared to their customer literacy (30%, 40%, 30%, and 40%) respectively.

However, the finding that most of the customers are not aware about what is cybersecurity or not interested to learn implies that not most of the customers will be information security literate with low literacy (Hafiz Ali et al., 2019). However, the training can increase and improve the awareness of cybersecurity between people with low literacy (Anwar, 2020). Orji (2019) validates that low literacy results into responding to the criminal attempts of cybercriminals made with purpose to attain personal details of banking customers, however awareness can help. Although, the literate people will adopt the importance and consequences of the training and awareness faster than less literate people (Ismailova & Muhametjanova, 2016).

Nevertheless, the reason of having low literacy rate of customers can be justified from the recent literacy report of Pakistan. As per the recent report on literacy percentage in Pakistan (section 4.4.5.) only 58% of population of Pakistan is literate (Neil, 2019). However, according to Sheikh (2017) this percentage of literacy is based on the literacy definition provided by the Government of Pakistan as the 'ability to read and understand simple text in any language from a newspaper or magazine, write a simple letter and perform basic mathematical calculation (i.e., counting and addition/subtraction).' Such people fall in the category who have minimum level of secondary education (from year 5 to 8). Although, no technique is used to test their literacy. Yet, Bizenjo (2020) states that there were only 15% people of Pakistan by 2020 who had graduation. Thus, with only 15% of whole population having graduation, the percentages in Table 20 of graduated people in banks shows a good number of graduated people as a banking customer. But the problem is that even they are not information security literate. Finally, the findings of this study show that the private commercial banks are having low customer literacy (digital literacy) issue regarding cybersecurity of their banks and awareness can play a major role. This establishes a link with previous study which indicates that in case of low customer literacy, awareness can strengthen the information security of banks (Anwar, 2020). The following section will discuss the role of general public literacy and awareness in information security of banks.

Literacy level of general public and awareness

Determining the strong connection between digital literacy and awareness question Q1e. probed how cybersecurity literacy and awareness among general public can support the cybersecurity governance in PCBP, since literature emphasised this connection. All of the respondents (21 out of 21) notified that the literacy level of general public and their awareness about cybersecurity plays an effective role in information security of banks (Švábenský, et al., 2021; Yaziz Bin Mohd, et al., 2021).

According to Tulder et al. (2019) globally increasing use of mobile broadband and smart phones has resulted to generate new personal data of public which is accessible and analysed by third parties for example different websites or applications. Though, if the information system of third party is not secure then users' data can be compromised easily. Subsequently, the general public should be aware to securely use technology (Aloul, 2012; Limna, et al. 2022). In this context Case 1 (Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst) mentioned that taking influence of the normative logics of low literacy and awareness the non-banking customers such as general public, is part of cyberspace and they affect the cybersecurity of banks indirectly.

All the same, Case 10 (Bank J: CISO; supported by bank M CISO) championed that a culture of literate and aware people in a country is a protection cover. The rationale is that the cybercriminals most probably will skip them from the list of their victims. Otherwise, as a human factor having awareness the general public will detect and prevent any attempt of criminal activity straight away. In contrast, the literature shows that companies have been just considering technological innovations and experts to secure their information system while, the cybersecurity awareness among general public has been ignored (Aphane, 2023). That is why finding the unaware public as a weak point, the cybercriminals are continually trying to steal money and information through general public (Bada et al. 2019).

Relatively, all CISOs (14), Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst; and Bank E: Senior credit control manager informed that the general public literacy rate in our country is quite low

(roughly around 60%, (section 4.4.5., Neil, 2019). Moreover, there is need of awareness about cybersecurity at large platforms by government of Pakistan (Bank A, C, M – CISOs; Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst; Bank E: Senior credit control manager). The reason is that even some very educated and technology savvy people are falling prey to simple social engineering techniques (Case 7 - Bank G; CISO).

Similarly, Yaziz Bin Mohd et al. (2021) in their study found that public awareness of cybersecurity highly contributes to banks' information security because, being part of cyberspace general public shares high volume of data. Although, general public digital literacy and awareness of cybersecurity will keep the cyberspace secure as well as will contribute to spread this awareness to the banking customers (unaware) in the society (Anisa, 2021).

These findings refer that to combat the cybercrimes in banks, digital literacy and awareness of general public is helpful (Aloul, 2012; Bada et al., 2019), which requires to change the normative logics of cybersecurity low literacy and awareness. Although, the findings show that banks cannot spread awareness at national level especially with normative logics of low literacy. Therefore, referring to Q1f the following section will spot on how the government awareness programme can support cybersecurity governance of banks.

Lack of awareness program by government

All of the informants (21 out of 21) highlighted that there is an urgent need of awareness program by government of Pakistan, providing multiple reasons. First of all, the findings depicted the negative side of technology which results in data breach (Case 1 Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst). This fact is proved with variety of literature such as Hussain et al. 2017; Buch et al. 2017; van de Weijer & Leukfeldt, 2017).

Simultaneously, as discussed in the above sections that there is low literacy and awareness between customers and general public in Pakistan. Hence, according to Case 9 (Bank I: CISO) government should realize that along with providing the national cybersecurity regulations it is also governments' responsibility to provide awareness

programmes at national level to educate its nation about the increasing issue of cybersecurity, especially when there is low literacy rate (Topping, 2017). This will mainly help the banking customers and banks as in less time at national level majority of the banking customers will become aware about cybersecurity (Khader, et al., 2021; Shillair, et al., 2022). Moreover, as per the above discussion, the banks do not have appropriate infrastructure and finance to aware and train each and every customer while, the government can do it using national assets (Bruijn and Janssen, 2017; Bada, et al., 2019; Alotaibi, 2019). However, Shahbaz Ul Haq (2019) also have highlighted that the introductory explanation of cybersecurity by media in Pakistan is another challenge because of weak institutional structure of the country. The government in Pakistan only focuses on traditional security culture.

Supporting this view, Bank A, C, M – CISOs; Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst; and Bank E: Senior credit control manager highlighted that the government of Pakistan have conducted some conventions continually after every six months but that is not sufficient. The use of television or a broad channel would be helpful. An auxiliary finding from Bank M (CISO) explained that cybersecurity awareness is the matter of whole nation instead of only banking customers. Hence, the government need to focus on initiating effective awareness programmes to educate people regardless of their level of educational literacy to avoid cyberattacks such as social engineering (Kovačević, et al., 2020; and Zwilling, et al., 2022). This can also be justified by the findings of study conducted by Nagyfejeo and Von Solms (2020) which suggests that even educated people who are aware of cybersecurity, do not apply cybersecurity protective measures since they are unaware of consequences of cyberattacks.

Consequently, Case 8 (Bank H: CISO) suggested that there is need of well-designed awareness program by government based on the category of people (level of education), with this fast-growing rate of cybercrime. The example of such efforts can include awareness programs throughout the schools, universities, Islamic organisations, public sector, including street-based approach for quick results. Another example can be the use of ads on TV and radio relating to cybersecurity because most of the people are not literate though they use radio quite often while travelling. Thus, even if they are not

interested to listen about cybersecurity, they will. Hence, despite of educational level they can training and awareness of cybersecurity (Bank M: CISO). The reason is to make awareness simple and understandable by people so that they can find it interesting and useful. These findings suggest the use of strategies introduced by Bruijn and Janssen (2017) to improve the cybersecurity awareness. According to these strategies the government should design cybersecurity awareness programmes which sound to be efficient, productive and create the perceived usefulness, which will motivate people to adopt them.

The similar point of view was provided by Bank A, B, G, I, J, and K – CISOs. The respondents insisted that such awareness programs can spread the awareness rapidly and this will play a vital role to support the information security system of banks. Especially, in the present case where even well-educated people become the victim of cybercrimes resulted from lack of awareness. These findings refer back to the studies suggesting use of customised awareness programmes to make them effective (Alruwaili, 2019; Chowdhury and Gkioulos, 2021; and Chowdhury, et al., 2022). In this regard, Case 1 (Bank A: CISO) pointed that spreading awareness is a CSR and banks have played their role in it by using electronic media, print media, advertisements, email, and message to their customers for securing data but still a number of customers failed to secure the data or share the data. The reason is smaller investment on cybersecurity. Hence, government to play its role. It was also found that the government of Pakistan cannot afford to have all the awareness programmes. Instead, there could be a certain contemporary topic (Bank A: CISO; supported by Bank B, L, and M - CISOs).

These results can also be supported by a recent study conducted by Awan and Malik (2018) which suggests that the government policies such as conventions can help to spread cybersecurity awareness but not at large level. Instead, there is need of comprehensive awareness program to aware people effectively. Additionally, being a developed country, the Government of UK has introduced the new national cybersecurity regulations, understanding the need of necessary cybersecurity skills and knowledge throughout the country, based on their people literacy and awareness level (Marsden & Goslin, 2022). This effort of UK Government points out that in this era of increasing

cybercrimes there is a need of cybersecurity culture throughout the country which will enable its people to learn, question, and challenge which will help to improve learning. Consequently, the UK Government declared that to ensure the effectiveness of awareness it is crucial to plan effectively (Odebade and Benkhelifa, 2023). This can be revolutionary example for the Government of Pakistan suggesting to change the normative logics of cybersecurity unawareness. In short, customer awareness is an important factor for cybersecurity governance of PCBP but government need to support it.

7.2.1.2. Sub theme: Lack of satisfactory regulatory framework of cybersecurity

The interview question Q2. receded the reason behind lack of satisfactory regulatory framework of cybersecurity in Pakistan to fill the research gap. All of the respondents (21 out of 21) agreed that the regulatory framework of cybersecurity is poor in Pakistan and is a critical factor. It is found from Case 1 (Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst) that management acknowledges the importance of regulatory framework. In general, Case 2 and 4 (Bank B and D - CISOs) pointed out that as per the recent regulations issued by SBP (section 4.4.6.9.) the cyber incident response plan of banks is quick and thorough; meets SBP requirements and is effective (Bank C, D, E, H, I, and J - CISOs).

This indicates the requirements of SBP for banks' information security but no guideline (rigid protocols) is provided (Case 3). Also, the banks in Pakistan are following the information security control cycle same as introduced by McLaughlin (section 2.9.2.1.), to be prepared for information security attacks (Bank C: CISO). This statements were also confirmed with case 8, 9, and 10 (Bank H, I, and J – CISOs respectively). Most importantly all CISOs (14) supported that banks must secure their information system at any cost to operate. Findings from Case 6 (Bank F: Operations head) further explained it stating that their banks use information security systems (supported by Bank C, D, I and J - CISOs) and those are tested 24/7 (also mentioned by Bank A, B, D, E, and H – CISOs; Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker). Even in ATM machines if any suspicious activity is there the system will record it. Now many people are aware about the ATM scamming, and they check the machine if there is a scamming device before they use ATM machine

(Bank C, D, L and M – CISOs; Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker). Besides, every three month a detailed report on our information security systems is provided and SOP is introduced to meet the dynamic requirement of system (Bank B – CISO).

Finally, executives are immediately informed about any cyber incident using hierarchy (4.4.6.10.). All of the above findings give the expression that by meeting the regulatory requirements of SBP the banks are fully secure and there is no information security lack. While, the following problems of regulatory framework of banking sector of Pakistan were also highlighted by interviewees.

For example, Case 2 notified that the guidelines provided by SBP in regulatory framework of banks are very generic and are not thorough (Sadiq, 2019). This indicates weak structural logics in banking industry of Pakistan. However, the Figure 23 (section 2.11.1.) of this study shows that NIST regulations have 20 families of controls to be used by banks to make their information security system rigorous. The most relevant controls based on the factors of this study are “awareness and training; access control; media protection; and personnel security”. SBP can use these controls to introduce an effective regulatory framework as these regulations are applicable to all kind of businesses (Hughes, 2022). Emphasising this perspective case 6 adds that the financial positions and performance of their banks is quite good. Still the information security is compromised because the banks do not have specific guideline from their regulator which can specify the requirements to meet the specified standards for cybersecurity (Syed et al., 2019; Ogunwale, 2020). On the other hand, Case 4 (Bank D: CISO) mentioned that lack of efficient staff in SBP is the reason of ineffective regulatory framework for banks. This stresses that the significance of cybersecurity in banks has been neglected by SBP since there is poor check and balance from government of Pakistan and political influences.

Contrarily, Case 7 underscored the importance of cybersecurity regulations as it plays the role of blood in banking industry justifying that without cybersecurity regulations the banking system can collapse. More importantly, it is vital for cybersecurity regulations to meet the complementary needs of information security because a regulatory framework

which does not provide the detailed guideline to secure banks is unsatisfactory so must be improved (Kaffenberger & Wilson, 2017; Ezu, et al., 2020).

Simultaneously, the findings of Case 2 (Bank B: CISO) recommended that if the regulatory framework of cybersecurity is thorough and rigorous, its implementation can safeguard the information security of banks. This will result in building customer confidence on e-banking (Artemenko and Bychkova, 2020). Moreover, by rigorous regulations the respondent means that the regulations should be detailed and specific which leaves no ambiguity for banks about the pathways and requirements to prevent cyberattacks (Ward, 2016; Thach, et al., 2021). The respondents also mentioned that NIST and ISO 27001 are the best example which SBP can use to make its cybersecurity framework rigorous and effective (supported by all CISOs; Thach, et al., 2021).

Supporting it case 10 added that the cybersecurity regulatory framework issued by SBP does not include all aspects of cybersecurity such as directors' training, maintaining certain number of cybersecurity experts based on their size etc. This provides a road map to follow and focus on securing banks' information system rather than focusing on saving money. Such legislations can be easily manipulated and dodged (Sadiq, 2019; Syed et al., 2019; Khan & Anwar, 2020).

Moreover, some findings (Bank H: CISO; supported by Bank B and M - CISOs) show a different perspective for instance in Pakistan banking industry practical implementation of cybersecurity is missing while it has become basic need of businesses to effectively implement the cybersecurity controls to prevent innovative cyberattacks (Bainbridge, 2017; Ezu, et al., 2020). The similar stance was provided by Bank D, D1, E, and M - CISOs. Bank D, D1, and I (CISOs) added in it mentioning that vulnerability scanning is the basic cybersecurity control which our banks are not provided. the real situation of banking industry of Pakistan which only a practically experienced person knows otherwise, general public can be deceived with this statement of SBP that we are fully secured (Mahmood, 2021; Kazmi, 2021). Case 10 further explained it as, it is complicated now to intrinsically adopt the information security in IT infrastructure of our banks and it might take a decade (Bank J: CISO; supported by Bank D, and D1 CISOs). These

statements show that lacking the comprehensive regulatory framework the private commercial banks in Pakistan are struggling to adopt and implement strict security controls as they are not mandatory requirements (Kesharwani, et al., 2019).

The findings pointed out the scenario that the people who provide the regulatory framework in State Bank of Pakistan are not compatible to develop a comprehensive regulatory framework for banks of Pakistan. However, just not to be blamed they do not take the responsibility of any cyberattack and declare that they are doing their best. This statement can be related to the lack of universities qualifying people with cybersecurity degrees and lack of graduates in cybersecurity disciplines (section 7.2.21.). However, lack of comprehensive regulatory framework provide relaxation to banks enabling temporary decisions regarding information security (Bank K: CISO; supported by Bank A, E, G, D, D1, L, and M -CISOs).

Likewise, the findings of Case 4 (Bank D1: CISO) presents the miserable information system security in banking industry of Pakistan lacking investment as, a bank with 12,000 computers has 20 IT staff and only 4 information security experts (Bank A, K, E, F, and M - CISOs). Furthermore, Case 5 mentioned that banks can invest in best practises but they try to achieve regulatory compliance minimum (Bank E: CISO; supported by Bank M - CISO). Besides, there is limited number of audit team thus, every bank will be audited after minimum two to three years. During that time if the bank is not following the right protocols of information security there is no check and balance on it (Case 4 - Bank D: CISO). Moreover, the auditors are the fresh graduates lacking the industry or practical experience and enough knowledge of cybersecurity (Case 13 - Bank M: CISO). This shows the reason why board of directors remain to follow box centric approach (Anwar, 2020; Syed et al., 2019). However, Case 2 (Bank B – CISO; supported by Bank D, D1 - CISOs) declared that in order to show off to SBP, the banks have just increased a little budget for CISOs after cybersecurity incident happened in 2018 (section 4.4.7).

Another finding was that following the concept of CSR banks in many countries are motivated to adopt best cybersecurity solutions (Case 5 - Bank E: CISO; Teoh, et al., 2017) however, this is not the case in Pakistan. Case 7 presented a contradictory point

of view that cybersecurity regulations are just fine. We should not expect the regulations to be too much explicit. It is banks' responsibility and implementation of controls in compliance to the regulations varies with respect to every organization's environment (Bank G: CISO).

These findings can be referred to the literature which show that the regulatory framework should specify the information security requirements based on different parameters of businesses to enable them it's adoption effectively (Ezu, et al., 2020). Hence, discussing all of the above issues case 2 suggested that the regulatory framework requirements of our banking industry are generic and not competitive for ultimate information security of banks in the era of innovative cyberattacks. Thus, SBP need to strengthen the structural logics by introducing a comprehensive regulatory framework with efficient protocols of security as introduced by NIST or ISO 27001. The CISOs of Bank D, D1, H and M also agreed with this.

Accordingly, results show that the cybersecurity regulatory framework does not provide specified guidelines and protocols (to private commercial banks) as are provided in NIST or ISO 27001. Furthermore, the requirements are not specified which gives the banks choice that they can implement cybersecurity as per their own pace. However, the respondents recommended that the State Bank of Pakistan should exemplify the NIST and ISO 27001 regulatory framework to provide Pakistan banking industry with a rigorous cybersecurity framework otherwise banks are finding it difficult to manage the cybersecurity (Novák and Doucek (2017) Didenko, 2020).

Hence, having robust policies adopted by banks if regulatory framework does not address the rigorous way to deal with security threats, then it is useless (Ogunwale, 2020). Moreover, Ward (2016) the cybersecurity regulatory framework should provide the detailed guideline to deal with the contemporary cyberthreats and a framework which does not meet this condition must be revised (Kopp et al., 2017). Finally, this study supports the results of a study conducted by Hafiz-Ali et al. (2019) finding that the lack of cybersecurity regulatory framework negatively affects the information security of banks in

Pakistan. Thus, banks are finding it hard to improve the cybersecurity governance in absence of satisfactory regulatory framework.

7.2.1.3. Sub theme: Improving Cybersecurity Governance through Law and Law Enforcement

Answering the interview question Q3 all of the respondents (21 out of 21) mentioned that lack of effective law and law enforcement remains a challenge for information security of banks, and it is one of the major factors. Case 10 demonstrated that the reason of required law enforcement is to help financial institutions against cybercrimes globally. According to Wang et al. (2021) the increasing rate of cybercrimes has become a challenge for law enforcement agencies all over the world. These agencies have noticed the fact that using cyberspace the cybercriminals have got access to information all around the world using innovative technology, and this has increased the number of cybercrimes internationally. Therefore, the local law enforcement agencies have started significantly emphasizing on law enforcement against those cybercriminals because it is found that law enforcement can considerably deter the international cybercriminals to not miss use the cyberspace (Kao, Hsiao, & Tso, 2020; Wang et al., 2021). Similarly, the respondent highlighted that the banks of Pakistan are not at exception of cyberattacks and they need law enforcement as the other countries do.

Case 5 further added in it as if banks are responsible to implement information security strategically simultaneously, the government have to play its role to back up the information security control system of banks by enforcing law (Bank E: Senior credit control manager; supported by all CISOs). Practically, there is inefficient law enforcement and ineffective cybersecurity law in Pakistan. (Bank A, B, D, D1, H, I, J and K: CISO; Bank F: Cash controller).”

In this view, Case 13 highlighted that the investment in updated technology will not be effective to prevent cybercriminals the customers remain a weak link for social engineering. Nevertheless, the strict punishment and high fines can demotivate them (Bank M: CISO; supported by all CISOs). Hence, from the above statements it is expressed that the law and law enforcement is as crucial as information security

implementation and, cybersecurity of banks is not possible just by efforts made by banks (Hafiz-Ali, et al., 2019). Rather the Government of Pakistan need to provide back up support to banks through law and its enforcement. This is further discussed below with help of theoretical concepts. Bank M (CISO) ,brought into attention the issue of social engineering which is a result of unawareness. The lack of awareness motivates criminals to target those customers but if strict punishment and the law enforcement is in place it can deter the criminals (Kesharwani, et al., 2019). In addition to it, Case 6 provided another aspect of lack of capacity building by attaining training and technology in law enforcement agencies to combat cybercrimes (Bank F: CISO; supported by all CISOs).

These statements not only confirm the lack of law and its enforcement in Pakistan but also highlight that there is a lack of expertise in law enforcement agencies. Lacking the required capabilities even with comprehensive law the law implementation will be ineffective. This represents the weak structural logics. Therefore, law and its implementation both have to work concurrently (Kethineni, 2020; Al-Bardan, 2021; Muhammady, 2021).

Case 11 (Bank K: CISO) exemplified Pakistan as a backward country where there is no concept of legislation and its enforcement to secure the assets of people living there. This is vindicated as the current legislation in Pakistan about cybercrimes is ineffective because it does not discourage the intruders to steal money and information of people residing there (Syed et al., 2019). The recent continued attacks from 2018 to 2022 (section 4.4.7.) are example of it. However, such a regular threat impacts the banks and the economy to a large extent, imposing heavy costs. Therefore, law enforcement is one of the major factors to cybersecurity (Khan & Anwar, 2020). Similarly, Case 9 (Bank I: CISO; supported by Bank L and M – CISOs and Bank B2: Operations head) further claimed that the developing countries like Pakistan do not have proper legislation and law enforcement in act. This encourages the cybercriminals to target such countries which hold considerable deposits of people having no cover of protection if stolen (Sadiq, 2019). Comparatively, the developed countries have well designed laws against cybercrimes and their strict implementation as well. This proves that there is a purpose for such legislation and its implementation as even being developed countries which have rigorous

IT infrastructure and cybersecurity techniques implemented in their organisations still give priority to update cybercrime laws and their enforcement (van de Weijer, et al., 2019; Świątkowska, 2020; ISA, et al., 2021).

Yaziz Bin Mohd et al. (2021) well explained the need of law enforcement in this context as, dealing with borderless cybercrimes involves the limitations of internet such as hiddenness, ambiguity, and provided guardianship to cybercriminals as well as the challenge of arranging connections between jurisdictions and availing requires support from different impacted authorities (Al-Badran, 2021). The consequences of failure of proper law enforcement opens the doors for cybercriminals and makes the country vulnerable. However, the effective law enforcement actions having skilled team which need efficient IT skills and in depth understanding of cybercrimes activities can protect the country against those cybercriminals (James & Warren, 2010; Kao et al., 2020; Vitvitskiy, et al., 2021). In this regard, Case 7 stated that law enforcement agents can only work to the capacity of available law. However, the weak structural logics of cybersecurity law also hinders those agents to effectively bring those criminals in the court.

In addition, Case 13 pointed out that even law enforcement supporting agencies are not working effectively since they employ fresh graduates who conduct legitimate fraud by inquiring personal information of customers and selling it (Bank M; supported by Bank F, E, and L). However, considering law and law enforcement an important concern all CISOs (14) mentioned that it is very hard to manage cybersecurity of banks as customer unawareness facilitates the cybercriminals to access confidential information through customers as weak link using e-banking (Rakha, 2023). In this context, Bank A, B, E, G, L and M (6 out of 13 banks) suggested that we have to strategically mitigate risk working altogether (referring to government, Wang et al., 2021). Similarly, Bank C, D, D1, and M (4 out of 13 banks) highlighted that if no law enforcement then heavy investment is required to fully secure the information system. However, that is not feasible since our banking sector lacks basics of security (Haroon et al., 2021).

Case 2 further expounded it as, our banking infrastructure is mapped out with no security and no security backup means no banking (supported by Bank A) yet, the law

enforcement could effectively help by demotivating cybercriminals afraid of punishments. Means the cybercrimes will increase and ultimately will result in loss of customers' trust. Consequently, the banks will lose profits and bankrupt (Bank B2: Operations head; supported by Bank D - CISO). These findings can be considered more relevant to emphasise the need of law enforcement in Pakistan to secure the banks considering that the banking infrastructure in Pakistan lack the essential security features which makes it more vulnerable. Therefore, the Government of Pakistan should strengthen the structural logics by understanding its responsibility to establish and enforce law having motivation from developed countries which have full security features in their banking infrastructure but still emphasise on law enforcement (Zia UL Islam et al., 2019). Hence, law enforcement is the third major factor of this study.

Theoretical Logics:

i) Deterrence Theory

Referring back to the statement of case 9, the concept of deterrence can be applied. According to this theory the criminal punishment is justified because it results to reduce or deter crimes (Lee, 2017). Therefore, to secure the nation the use of harsh punishments and penalties for cybercriminals can significantly demotivate cybercriminals (Yaziz Bin Mohd et al., 2021).

ii) CSR (stakeholder theory), Government of Pakistan and Law Enforcement Agencies

Referring back to the need of awareness program by the Government of Pakistan (section 7.2.1.1.), it was concluded that the Government of Pakistan is responsible to aware public of Pakistan about cybersecurity, taking motivation from government of developed countries. Similarly, it can be justified that as law and its enforcement is found to be a major factor which can help to improve the cybersecurity of banks therefore, the Government of Pakistan has higher degree of responsibility towards law and its enforcement in Pakistan against cybersecurity (Bada, et al., 2019). Additionally, this concept of responsibility can be linked with CSR theory whereby the businesses are

responsible for their actions which can impact their stakeholders or society. Likewise, it is Government of Pakistan's CSR to conduct such acts which can ensure the overall security of their stakeholders (voters and citizens) which also includes law and its enforcement (Williams, 2014).

The results of this study support the study by Zia UL Islam et al. (2019) that there is need of diligent efforts in Pakistan by government to establish a proper policy and law enforcement system to deal with cybercrime in banks. Moreover, the focus should also be on law enforcement agents' capacity building and technology innovation as well as on the corrupt agents.

7.2.2. Theme 2: Internal Factors affecting cybersecurity governance in private commercial banks of Pakistan

7.2.2.1. Sub theme: Directors' training

This factor could be better discussed with CISOs only. Hence, 14 CISOs in this study supported the discussion. Directly relating to highest position in information security department of their banks all of the respondents highlighted that directors training is the most crucial part of information security of our banks (interview question Q6). Case 8 (Bank H: CISO) mentioned that the background of board of directors is not information security related neither they are required. This statement develops the general understanding that a person with background other than information security has less understanding of the technological aspects and their implications. However, this is not an issue in Pakistan only (Alghamdi, 2021). Lehuedé (2020) states that previously it has not been required for board of directors to have qualification relating to information security therefore, majority of board of directors still have their backgrounds either in finance, law, and business etc. Nevertheless, the lack of directors in board who have good knowledge of up dated need of cybersecurity has become a risk for businesses because lacking required cybersecurity expertise or skills, the board would make a mis leading decision (Al-Alawi and Al-Bassam, 2021).

Case 4 (Bank D1: CISO; supported by Bank H, I, and J - CISOs) further explained this phenomenon as, in our banks the board of directors neglect the need of investing in cybersecurity, yet it is required by SBP. Robert and Ackerman (2021) explain its reason that there is minority of directors in boardrooms with up-to-date training and experience of IT or information security. That minority of directors indicates that their information security understanding and skills have become necessity for businesses in recent years. Therefore, a boardroom consisted of directors with required expertise and experiences who are able to diligently make decision about information security of business will be more effective (Rothrock, Kaplan, & Van, 2018).

Relating the first two statements of case 8 and 4 implies that the directors in private commercial banks do not have information security background therefore they ignore the investment in cybersecurity of banks and prefer to follow the traditional security approach. While, the Case 9 (Bank I: CISO; supported by Bank D, D1, K, L and M - CISOs) suggests that training can improve their conception of cybersecurity otherwise it is hard to make them understand the necessity of investing in specific proposed strategies of information security (budget approving). In this context, Gale, et al. (2022) stated that the cybercrimes are uncertain however the board of directors should consider this uncertainty as an obstacle to respond to cyber incidents. Although, they cannot predict cyber-incidents or their impact nevertheless having training about cybersecurity can help them to make the right decisions which can secure their organisation. Case 1 (Bank A: CISO) further provided a different aspect of approving the budget emphasising that from his personal experience he learned to convince the directors. He shared that he has received excellent support from directors to invest in required information security. According to him the directors are very kind to oblige if understand the issue. While Case 7 (Bank G: CISO) had a contrary view that training and awareness is must to support investment.

Supporting it Case 12 highlighted that internal education is very important to inform the management and executives with updated cybersecurity issues faced and solutions (Bank L). Agreeing with the phenomena, Case 4 further explained it as looking at the highest position of board of directors in information security control system (section 4.4.6.10.) there are two ways to see the impact of board of directors' decisions and

necessity of their cybersecurity training which are as follows. Firstly, an effective proposal is refused because of lack of knowledge and training about cybersecurity. This demotivates the work of CISOs and puts the security of whole bank at risk. Secondly, the appointment of important delegations by board of directors which can be ineffective hiring the incompatible person for the job, since directors will lack appropriate knowledge of problem. Successively, the whole security system of bank will be compromised (Bank D1: CISO). These findings match with the studies which suggest that the executives should be able to approve appropriate proposal and make effective decisions. However, those executives will be consisted of individuals possessing required training and experience to address contemporary cybersecurity threats. (Bada, et al., 2018; Alghamdi, 2021). Otherwise, the board will make ineffective decisions for information security of business and whole business will be on stake (Barker, 2016; Al-Alawi and Al-Bassam, 2021).

Case 10 justified it saying that directors have authority to approve the amount of investment in cybersecurity and they prefer to stick to old measures and save money, by allocating budget but not using it for cybersecurity (Bank J: CISO; supported by Bank D, D1, H - CISOs). Some of the respondents provided following point of views to strengthen this weak symbolic logics of banks. Case 3 explained it as, the SBP need to regulate banak by required minimum requirements about controls, technology, and experts (Bank C: CISO, supported by Bank D, D1, E, F, G, L, and M – CISOs). While, Case 4 added that SBP should mention certain number of experts in each bank based on its size (Bank D: CISO, supported by Bank A, C, D1, G, H, J, and L – CISOs).

Considering this issue Al-Bassam and Al-Alawi (2020) declared that many banks and financial institutions are still conservative to implement and adopt latest concepts of cybersecurity because they are not aware of the advantages of investing in cybersecurity. Hence, as per the above discussion of interviewees when it comes to investing on cybersecurity (customer awareness; employees - training and motivation; outdated infrastructure; hiring experts) all depends on the investment decision of directors and directors have weak symbolic logics of investing in cybersecurity. Also, according to a survey on 507 companies of 16 different countries and 17 industries, a single cyberthreat costed almost \$3.92 million at average. Thus, it has been compulsory now to invest in

effective cybersecurity decision-making trainings to make the right decisions about cybersecurity of business (Ponemon, 2019).

Theoretical Logics:

i) *Three-line model of defence*

According to this model the board of directors should have high level of integrity, appropriate governance model and wide-range transparency in information security decision making to be considered by their stakeholders (customers) as the reliable partners persisting high level of accountability towards them (Cro Forum, 2021). Likewise, Clinton (2020) highlighted that the governance of a business is run by board of directors. Additionally, the board of directors can attain high level of integrity and transparency in information security only when they are fully engaged in cybersecurity of business holding updated and required knowledge (IIA, 2020; Holland & Floam, 2020). This model suggests that being the main stakeholders of the business the board of directors are accountable for its performance. Hence, it is compulsory for directors to gain certain training for cybersecurity to secure the business (Brasseur, 2020).

In addition, emphasising on directors' training Case 4 confirmed that their directors excessively focus on governance and documentation overkill with hardly 5 to 10% implementation (Bank D1: CISO; supported by Bank F, I and M - CISOs). This refers back to the finding that directors have not been and are not understanding the necessity of cybersecurity. This was also mentioned by case 13, 9 and 6 (Anwar, 2020). While, the above discussion and model clearly suggests that it is directors' responsibility to obtain necessary cybersecurity training as whole business is dependent on their decisions.

Furthermore, Case 2 (Bank B: CISO; supported by Bank D and D1 - CISOs) asserted that SBP should make directors' training mandatory requiring them to invest in cybersecurity (technology, experts, and training) and provide CISOs' rights to vote in investment decision.

These findings show that directors' training for cybersecurity awareness is crucial. Also, directors have weak symbolic logics of the information security of private banks of

Pakistan with understaffed (section 7.2.1.2.), cosmetic and ‘security box centric’ approach which results in to weaken the security infrastructure. This refers back to the results of the studies on other than private banks of Pakistan (Syed et al., 2019; Anwar, 2020). However, there is need to make immediate legislation on this issue by SBP. The following section will discuss that how investment, employee training and awareness and strategic planning is affected by directors’ knowledge and understanding of cybersecurity.

Investment on Cybersecurity and Use of Outdated Infrastructure

All of the respondents (21 out of 21) pointed out that their banks are financially strong so they can invest in cybersecurity still, investment is an issue in their banks considering different circumstances (interview question Q4). Case 7 (Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker; supported by all CISOs – 14 and, Bank F: Cash controller) underscored that the banks in Pakistan are financially strong (section 4.4.4.). Although, in worst case (a bank does not have money) according to ‘securities and exchange commission law number-7’, a bank can request financial support through the regulator of banks in the monthly meeting with state bank regarding cybersecurity. The regulator will bring this issue in consideration of government. However, to operate banks have to be able to invest in cybersecurity (all respondents).

Furthermore, case 6 (Bank F: Cash controller) underlined that SBP will not financially help any bank. Combining this statement with the above stance of case 7 it can be said that neither government nor SBP will support the banks financially in usual case. Though, banks are supposed to secure their information security themselves.

However, case 2 (Bank B: Customer’s relationship and marketing manager) pointed out that the banks have money to invest in cybersecurity. Although, the investment decision is dependent on directors. But directors think that it is not necessary to use innovative ways of cybersecurity as in past days. Therefore, they tend to stick to old technical methods of cybersecurity by just justifying policies (Kazmi, 2021; Mahmood, 2021). Bank C, D, D1, E, F, G, H, I, J, L, and M CISOs (10 banks) also had similar viewpoint of this issue. Case 11 (Bank K: CISO; supported by Bank A and C) further indicated that in this

ever-changing technological based world the information security of banks is the base of banking industry (Awan and Memon, 2016). Therefore, the banks must ensure that either it's confidentiality, availability, or integrity of their information system, it should be secured (Na-jibzadeh and Park, 2021). This will retain customer confidence and will result in cyber resilience and sustainability. Most importantly, the ultimate result of losing money will be on economy (Geyres & Orozco, 2016; Wang, et al., 2020). Also, Cvitić et al. (2017) suggest that it is compulsory for banks in this technology-based world that they have updated as well as responsive technology and information security experts while, Al-Alawi and Al-Bassam (2021) asserts that for such advancement in technology and security a lot of investment is required.

Case 4 (Bank D: CISO) further elaborated that CISOs work hard to propose best cybersecurity solutions but directors do not value them lacking cybersecurity awareness. This finding shows the frustration of CISOs - who are the head of information security of a bank and are held responsible for it. While, their own reputation in the market is at risk if they fail, no matter what the reason is. Therefore, it raises job satisfaction issue for those CISOs (Kazmi, 2021). Additionally, discussing it case 4 (Bank D1: CISO) emphasised that our bank need to invest in innovative technology and number of cybersecurity experts. Followed by the 2018 and 2019 cyberattacks now there is a separate department for cybersecurity but still there are only three or four experts to deal with the cybersecurity. The cost deters the investment in cybersecurity.

This statement was also confirmed from other CISOs (Bank A, C, D, E, G, H, and M). In addition, it was pointed out that in case of a big incident where multiple attacks can be launched, the bank cannot secure its information system with this number of experts (Anwar, 2020; Mahmood, 2021). Supporting these findings, the results of studies conducted by Meulen (2015); Gordon et al. (2015); Dupont (2019); Wang, (2019) and Wang, et al. (2020) show that increasing rate of technological advancement requires businesses to invest in innovative solutions of cybersecurity while the lack of investment in those solutions is a big hurdle for information security of businesses. On the other hand, many of the respondents confirmed that banks are profitable to invest in high tech experts (Bank A, B, D, J, L, and M – CISOs; Bank B: Customer's relationship and marketing

manager). Besides, case 8 (Bank H: CISO) described that our bank's expensive software updates are up to date and authenticated from the software companies (supported by Bank A). In contrast, the respondent of case 10 (Bank J: CISO) claimed that until 2018 majority of the banks in Pakistan lack the vulnerability scanners. Moreover, instead of installing vulnerability scanners the organizations chose to save money and used firewalls. While, lacking the fundamentals (vulnerability scanning) none of the software can support to fully secure the whole information system of banks. Supporting it case 9 (Bank I: CISO) stated that vulnerability is not an easy job. It is a long procedure. On bank may consists of 1 lack vulnerabilities in its information security system. To remove them it will require investment of time, technology, and experts.

Hence, use of vulnerability scanners is the basic need of banks and none of the software can complement it. But of course, it requires investment (Al-Alawi and Al-Bassam, 2021). This discussion was concluded by case 8 (Bank H: CISO) as, either its investment in customer awareness, staff training, technology, or experts, it all entirely depends on directors, and they do not recognize the need of such investment.

The findings from case 4, 10, 9 and 8 can be further justified from the studies conducted by Bernik (2014); BIS (2016); Kopp et al. (2017); and Eling and Lehmann (2018) which reveal that the financial institutions cannot completely mitigate the risk of cybercrimes even substantially increasing investments in their information security systems, because financially motivated cybercriminals keep introducing innovative types of cyber-attacks. Likewise, the banks have to continuously adopt the latest cybersecurity solutions (Wang et al., 2020; Dupont, 2019; Cvitić et al., 2017). Further, it is to be noticed that the symbolic logics of strategic planning need to extend beyond the investment in technology to strengthen the information security of financial institutions by including the proper set up of cybersecurity experts and relevant staff trainings (Caron, 2015; Ahmad & Schreyer, 2016; Geyres & Orozco, 2016). While, case 8 highlighted that either its investment in technology, experts or staff training, the directors follow box centric approach that is why our bank lacks new technology, experts, and detailed training.

On the other hand, Bank E (CISO) mentioned a new point of view that the cities where head offices locate have more technological facilities and experts while banks in other cities lack investment in these assets. This makes hard for us to prevent cyberattacks. However, in some cases budgeting is a challenge because it's all dependent on bank balance sheet as well (supported by Bank A - CISO). Contrarily, Bank L (CISO) stated that evaluating the banks financials is mainly dependent on the management and board decision. However, they should not ignore the type of risk their business can accept, whether it could be prevented, or is appropriate investment is made to avoid any risk and what could be the impact of the risk if it turns into a cyberattack (Shillair, et al ., 2022).

These findings show that most of the CISOs confirmed that investment is an issue in banks and directors are mainly related to it. However, the findings also confirm the strong financial position of banks in Pakistan (Lukosiunas, 2021). The results also indicate the fact that some organisations and people still underestimate the importance of cybersecurity however, training can be the solution (Świątkowska, 2020). Thus, SBP need to regulate it considerably.

Similarly, a few of the respondents highlighted that some of the private commercial banks are still in progress to upgrade to the latest version of software and technology, even we have highest possible information technology solutions available in country. (Bank E - CISO; supported by Bank C, F, I, J, K and M – CISOs). Case 10 (Bank J: CISO; supported by A, G and M) pointed out that having outdated infrastructure in banking is unaffordable at all. Although, it is banks' choice to either invest in technology or bear the loss. This finding can be validated from the results of the studies conducted by Farnfield (2020); Prakash (2020) and Shahi and Sinha (2020) which show that with the increasing rate of cybercrimes still some banks are using the outdated infrastructure of technology which does not support the updated security requirements to prevent latest cyberthreats. Manning (2020) and Haroon et al. (2021) mention that the recent example of this is the increased number of malware attacks on ATM machines, because these machines mainly have used Windows 7 while, Microsoft does not support windows 7 from January 2020 anymore (Microsoft, 2021). Hence, the banks which still use window 7 their ATM machines are vulnerable to attacks.

Case 6 (Bank F: Cash controller) stated that because of high cost, the bank is slowly investing in latest technologies. But still a lot of work is required to get sustainability of information security. The finding contended that upgrade of technology and expertise is urgent need banks. This statement was also emphasised by different CISOs (Bank A, B, D, G, I, J, K and L). The responded meant to say that even though the innovation and cyber resilience of information security in banks comes at high cost. But banks' survival is not possible without that. Hence, at any cost banks have to invest in latest technology. Also, confirmed from case 2. Uddin et al. (2020) discussed similar situation in their study that even with such updated technology (which is costly) sometime the cybersecurity risks are unavoidable in the digital world. Still, financial institutions have to investment in cybersecurity (Sadiq, 2019; Syed et al., 2019; Kazmi, 2021).

Case 6 further discussed this situation as their successfully bank upgraded its system after the cyberattack of 2018 and 2019, hiring experts. This statement emphasised that with the help of appropriate investment the cyber resilience in banks is possible, after learning from financial loss (Moşteanu, 2020). However, taking back to the example of TSB, the bank failed to upgrade its system (Monagham, 2018) while having three times less customers as this bank does (interviewee). This shows proficiency of experts and technology in banking sector of Pakistan. Although, case 4 (Bank D1- CISO) emphasised that the management (directors) over think to find short cuts instead of investing in upgrades. Thus, the results suggest to the findings of the studies that high cost of updating technology is a hurdle (Furr, et al., 2022) but regardless of cost and complicated procedure the banks have to upgrade their technology (Alghazo, et al., 2017; Cvitić, et al., 2017; Stone, 2019; Wang et al., 2020).

Employees' Training and Awareness

Most of the respondents (18 out of 21) agreed that being a human factor employees remain the main threat to information security of banks (interview question Q5). Case 7 (Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker) illustrated that after the cyberattack of 2018 (section 4.4.7.) at branch level employees are told to not share their password also, the employees are getting training at basic level. This expression leads to the findings of Al-

Bassam and Al-Alawi (2020) that considering employees as a major human factor, the staff behaviour is getting increased attention for companies' information security vulnerability and breaches. The findings of Case 6 (Bank F: Operations head) explained a recent incident of their bank whereby the employee stole the money from customer's account since customer shared his financial information with bank employee and moved abroad.

The respondent stated that such employees keep looking for weak points within bank and conduct a fraud when feasible for them. This suggests to consider the findings of Conway et al. (2017) which highlight that a business with highly visible security systems having less reflection on exposure to risk result in poor security practices whereby the proficiency of dodgy employees is neglected. However, this cause huge financial loss to financial services industry. Anwar (2020) says that if a customer has awareness, he/she will not become the victim of dodgy employees. Hence, this is another scenario that customer awareness is so important. Nevertheless, respondent clarified that to stop this happening again, the banks have required to approve any transaction from more than one person. For example, if a cheque is to be proved first it will be drawn by one person, the second person will recheck it, and the third person will approve it. It means this fraud cannot be happened by one person as there are more checks.

Furthermore, Case 4 (Bank D1: CISO; supported by Bank A, B, C, D1 F, and J - CISOs) added that these measures will not demotivate criminal employees. Rather a culture within the banks which will not only support to create rigorous strategy for cybersecurity protocols but also promote its implementation. The findings emphasised that sometimes the lack of culture to maintain the cybersecurity protocols of bank results in persuading employees to involve in cybercriminal activities (Al-Badran, 2021). However, adopting cybersecurity resilience culture in the bank can make the employees understand the essence of cybersecurity and the consequences of its breach. Thus, it can be related to the theoretical logic of culture in a way that the organisations should focus on promoting security culture to spread Information Security Awareness (Wileya et al., 2019).

Also, case 10 (Bank J: CISO – supported by Bank A, B, D, D1, and M - CISOs) revealed that the banks should adopt the culture of employee training. The banks have initiated some training programs for employees. However, those trainings must be detailed instead of basics. Moreover, the management need to sustain continuous checks on employees' performance and motivation to keep them on track. Similarly, Bank D1 and J (CISOs) also mentioned that less training sessions as compared to the need are provided to employees which are not sufficient. Hence, there is untrained staff which needs investment on their training and the equipment provided to them for banks information security (Bank A, D, D1, G, K, and L - CISOs). Case 1 (Bank A: CISO) justified this issue as, sometimes the IT team does not have knowledge and capability to operate and control their system or implement basic controls, that is one of the biggest challenges.

This indicates the issue of incompetent training of employees. While, to enable employees to deal effectively with increasing trend of cybercrimes a more detailed training will help (Dhillon, 2020). Servidio and Taylor (2015) agrees to this observation implying that there is need of steady investment in employees' training, who are the first line of defence against cybercrimes. Also, Wang et al. (2020) suggest that employees' training to effectively tackle innovative cybersecurity threats is the crucial measure in banks' information security. Moreover, Malik and Islam (2019) in their recent study found that employees' awareness and training can play a major role in preventing cybercrime. Further, the findings show that banks do not have the culture of performance reward which demotivates employees to work in the best interest of bank (Eling & Wirfs, 2019). Apart of this there are some factors such as promotion or self-esteem etc. which can motivate employees to avoid cybercriminal acts, and management should focus on those factors. However, this is discussed in detail in the following theoretical logic section.

Likewise, case 1 added in that the lower-level employees have low motivation to pursue the application of information security protocols, since they are not involved in information security control survey, limited training, with low salary, less self-esteem, and no reward function (Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst; supported by Bank A and G -CISOs). Additionally, Case 3 (Bank C: CISO) further pointed out that old age employees are a big threat to banks as they lack necessary skills to effectively use banking system and resist

innovation in technology. Although they try not to get involve in more technological activities still somehow, they have to engage with such activities (Woldemichael, 2019). Thus, Bank B, C, and H (CISOs) and Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst (4 out of 13 banks) suggested that there is need of specific training for old and lower-level employees. However, summarizing the comments of case 1 and 3 could lead to case 8 (Bank H: CISO) suggestion that in case of an incident employees are the first point of contact to tackle any cyberthreat in bank. This pronounced the importance of employees within the banks. Supporting it case 2 continued the stance implying that employees are integral part of banks for effective cybersecurity of banks by complying with strategy. Thus, CISOs or higher management alone cannot improve the cybersecurity. It is a teamwork which requires all employees of the banks have to participate in cybersecurity of bank (Bank B: CISO).

This statement was well explained by case 5 (Bank E: Senior credit control manager) as, all employees of bank should be engaged (regardless of their designation or age) in cybersecurity system. Moreover, the management must consistently scan for the factors which motivate employees to keep them on track for their dedication towards banks' cybersecurity (also supported by Bank A, D, D1, G, and J - CISOs). Contrasting it, Bank A provided a different aspect that screening is done while hiring employees to check their criminal record. Yet, in case an employee is found with illegal activities the banks avoid any legal proceedings. Thus, the blacklist employees remain regular employees within industry (Bank A: CISO). Thus, there is weak symbolic logics of employee management. Supporting this statement Case 13 illustrated that he opened account in a bank and bank employee tried to get his bank details by calling him (Bank M: CISO). This indicates the employee engagement in social engineering activities which could be motivated by not punishing them. Furthermore, the respondent highlighted that every branch managers and all personnel have the access to the customers' data, and there are multiple teams on the head office they have the access to the banking application and to the code, which can lead to legitimate crime. This scenario can be explained by the study conducted by Conway et al. (2017) suggesting that highly visible information system with open controls can result in internal crime.

In this regard Case 4 mentioned that employees must be trained well first and told the consequences of conducting any illegal activity. However, it is to be ensured to punish in case of crime (Bank D: CISO; supported by Bank M - CISO). In addition, Case 7 pointed out the reason of shortage of trained employees as the skilled cybersecurity employees move abroad for better career opportunities (Bank G: CISO). Case 13 added in that when it comes to cybersecurity student numbers, there are not big level of courses or universities which are providing the cybersecurity degrees. So, there are no such institutions in Pakistan, just Air University started information security four years ago (Bank M). Thus, a country where there is only one recent organisation which is training people towards getting their degrees of cybersecurity how can we even expect that there will be enough people who can deal with cybersecurity. In addition, about lecturers he the findings show that they have no industry experience. NUST initiated to hire people from industry to teach yet the coursework still follow the theoretical traditional way (Bank M - CISO)".

Consequently, the results show that employees are the insider threat to banks and their motivation, training and awareness is a critical concern being weak symbolic logics in banks (Alotaibi, et al., 2017; Al-Badran, 2021). Moreover, appropriate number of experts must be available to effectively secure the information system of banks.

Theoretical Logics

i) Performance motivation cycle

These findings from case 10, 1, 3, 8, 2, and 5 articulate that to improve the cybersecurity of banks it is essentially required to keep all the staff engaged in information security by realizing the factors of their motivation which can be their involvement (opinion on cybersecurity), management support, reward, or training. This suggests the use of motivation theories ascertaining that as a nature of human there is always a need to determine the factors of motivation for certain employees to make them perform to the required level (McLeod, 2016). Hence, the employees' performance motivation cycle introduced by the researcher can be effective in this regard (section 2.8.6.3.). This cycle is based on the three steps. The first step management need to consider is to provide the

hygiene factors. These are the factors which do not motivate employees instead their absence will demotivate employees. These factors consist of better working environment and culture etc. Once these factors are provided then it will be easy to point out that with all facilities still which employees are not motivated to work and why. This is called employee categorizing step. The third step is to apply the right motivator (promotion, higher level of job offers, advancement and growth) based on the need of the employee to effectively motivate. Thus, it will save the time of management by selection of right motivator following the steps in this cycle, instead of spontaneously selecting any motivating factor.

ii) TAM model

The banks' management can use TAM model along with awareness and training program to motivate their employees to improve the symbolic logics by complying with cybersecurity protocols established by banks and use the technology provided (Kang, Choi & Kim, 2021). This can be supported through a recent study by Afshan et al. (2018) which highlighted that people with high trust, structural assurance and training have high tendency to follow certain protocols. Similarly, using TAM model banks can highlight the usefulness of complying with information security protocols and using the technology (Josefsson, 2017). Also, the management of banks will have to ensure that they provide the ease of using that technology and protocols also provide support when required Lai (2017). This will especially motivate the old employees as they are afraid of learning new technologies. Furthermore, the researcher suggests that if along with this awareness the performance reward will be linked then the results will be higher than otherwise.

iii) Deterrence theory and Information Security Climate (ISC)

The alternative can be the use of deterrence theory (punishment mechanism only). Although it is not recommended by researchers to create an environment pressurised by harsh punishments as it sometimes can demotivate employees (Trang & Brendel, 2019). However, it can be best to share the consequences of security breaches during awareness and training program instead of just making employees uncomfortable feeling

that they are part of an environment excessively controlled by harsh punishments (Lee, 2017). Therefore, first it is useful to pay attention to awareness, training and motivation factors and then align it with the fact of punishment against data breach because, the employees who will be already motivated to work in the best interest of banks will not consider data breach chance, will not be afraid of harsh punishments. Thus, this will create the Information Security Climate (ISC) and give the employees confidence through trainings and motivation (Trang & Brendel, 2019). Consequently, the third major factor of this study is employees.

Strategic planning

Majority of the respondents (14 CISOs and Bank F: Cash controller) highlighted that strategic planning plays a vital role in cybersecurity of banks. While, a handsome number of interviewees (8 – CISOs, 8 out of 13 banks) informed that strategic planning in their banks is ineffective. Countering to interview question Q7, Case 6 shared that until the cybersecurity incidents of 2018 (section 4.4.7) the banks used to treat cybersecurity as a technological issue rather than considering cybersecurity in strategic planning. Later on, banks started development of separate cybersecurity department from the IT department (Bank F: Cash controller; supported by all other 20 respondents). This confirms that the cybersecurity concept in banks of Pakistan is just new (Anwar, 2020) and businesses had the tendency to treat cybersecurity a technological aspect only which is not acceptable anymore (Bainbridge, 2017; Hafiz-Ali, et al., 2019). The reason is that the management must have a strategic plan to address the complicated cyberthreats (Marotta and Pearlson, 2019).

According to Ruiz-Vanoye et al. (2014) information security strategic planning is a process to develop, implement and analyse the decisions of technological security which enables the financial organisations to attain their objectives relating to information security. Moreover, Stine et al. (2020) describes that useful and comprehensive policies and strategic planning to deal with cybercrime is compulsory because the increasing rate of technological innovation and damaging nature of cyberthreats require the businesses to scrutinise the risk to enterprise and select the best solution. However, considering

cybersecurity as a new phenomenon the banks in Pakistan need a lot of expertise and attention to develop the culture of cybersecurity (Wiley et al., 2019).

Likewise, for interview question Q8, case 7 included that cybersecurity is being considered seriously in banks of Pakistan since SBP has required the crisis management team of banks (consisted of directors, CEOs, and CISOs) to hold monthly meetings, to review cybersecurity strategy and report it to SBP (Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker). Sadly, again this is only in documentation rather implementation is low; Anwar, 2020). Besides, case 11 explained that we must plan strategically to ensure that banks have compatible resources (technology, experts, and implementation) to combat the cybercrimes (Bank K: CISO). Pursuing this further, case 9 commented that the increasing rate of cybercrimes is imposing high responsibility on the higher management to pay high attention to the strategic planning for cybersecurity. Strategic planning allows to highlight the cyberthreats the banks have faced and find the innovative solutions against the previous threats and secure the information system of banks in future (Cvitić et al., 2017; Sajko, et al., 2021; Utami and Damayanti, 2022). This confirms the active and effective understanding of CISOs about importance of cybersecurity strategic planning.

While, case 10 emphasised that the strategic planning process becomes ineffective when directors approve selective proposals based on their choice for budget rather than the required budget which can complement the cybersecurity needs. Thus, the cheaper and temporary solutions are favoured (Bank J: CISO). This point of view was also presented by Bank D1, E, F, H, I, K, and L (CISOs). These results show that the decision makers have to make decisions regarding threats of which they are not aware intrinsically. Thus, lacking compulsory awareness their decisions are ineffective (Rothrock, et al., 2018). Further, in response to interview question Q9, the findings show that it is required by State Bank of Pakistan to hire experts of the field (21 out of 21 respondents). However, because of the cost, the number of cybersecurity experts are very low (14 CISOs). 14 out of 14 CISOs confirmed that since cybersecurity is a new trend in banking industry of Pakistan the development of cybersecurity department is improving slowly. Although, investment remains a concern (Malik and Islam, 2019). Supporting the lack of experts, case 4 stated that we have reliable experts however, they are unable to support the information security

system in full, with inadequate number of colleagues (Bank D: CISO; supported by all CISOs). This suggests that there is an insufficient number of experts working in private commercial banks of Pakistan to deal with cybersecurity. Consequently, the strategic planning in PCBP is ineffective as, strategic planning is internal cybersecurity governance for banks which enables banks to provide direction and effective controls which can secure the information assets of bank (Utami and Damayanti, 2022).

Case 7 (Bank G: CISO; supported by Bank C, E, F, I, and L) discussed strategic planning from customer point of view that the management place attention to build the customers' trust to promote e-banking by adopting best cybersecurity solutions (interview question in response to interview question Q10). However, it is neglected from executives who prefer to invest less, according to their ability to understand the importance of cybersecurity and ignore customers' interest (Rothrock, et al., 2018). Case 5 gave another understanding of customers' confidence on banks to support e-banking as, customers' and stakeholders build their trust on banks based on banks' cybersecurity reputation. If banks' reputation is impaired then there will be huge financial impact because of broken trust. Hence, cybersecurity can affect the reputation (customers' trust) and financial position of banks (Jibril, et al., 2020; Akinbowale, et al., 2020). Therefore, the directors should understand it (Bank E: CISO; supported by 13 other CISOs). These findings confirm the weak symbolic logics of strategic planning followed by the directors affecting the cybersecurity governance of banks.

According to Haggman (2019) cybersecurity requires computer science degree, relevant qualification, training, or awareness to develop the effective understanding of cyberthreats and their solutions. Contrarily, as a precaution, as mentioned before SBP introduced some new regulations according to which banks have to secure their information security system but no effective guideline is provided specifically requiring banks (decision makers) to adopt certain solutions. Moreover, now banks conduct monthly meeting with executives to inform them about cybersecurity position of bank; there is a slight increase in CISOs budget, upgrade of a few systems, establishment of crisis management team etc. which is not sufficient as per the above discussion. Instead, SBP should use structural logics to make it necessary for directors to acquire minimum

qualification or training and awareness about cybersecurity as structural logics have positive impact on executives to comply with requirements (Ogbanufe, et al., 2021). For example, the recent regulation proposed in EU to involve the executives in cybersecurity effectively suggested that executives compromising with cybersecurity of organisation will be prisoned for 20 years and must pay fine equivalent to 4% of company annual income (Chatterjee, 2019). Finally, the comprehensive statement presented by case 5 providing the perception of banks on cybersecurity governance shows that for effective cybersecurity governance, all discussed institutions such as customer training, investment in technology and experts and directors' training is required (Bank E: CISO; support by other 20 respondents).

These findings confirm that if strategic planning does not provide required solutions for cybersecurity, it is ineffective (Cvitić et al., 2017) and in private commercial banks of Pakistan the strategic planning is affected by director's investment decisions. Therefore, there is need to shift the attention towards executives from information security experts because the traditional methods of dealing with cybersecurity governance for example firewalls suggested by experts is no more effective since the executives are involved in decision making (Shillair, et al., 2022). Instead, a holistic approach must be used consisting of top to bottom awareness and training of cybersecurity implied strategically so that directors are enabled to assess bank's cybersecurity maturity against best solutions available and threats (Bada, et al., 2018). Henceforth, directors' training and awareness is the fourth important factor of this study.

7.2.2.2. Other Factors Explored - Factors affecting Information security Governance and Control System

During the interviews, some of the respondents emphasised on another factor which is information security control system (section 2.11.2.1.). The respondents mentioned that in each step of information security control system their banks face some issues as discussed below (responses for Q13).

Case 2 described that during preparation process (which includes measuring risks and developing strategies; Mahn, 2018) the data collection from industry is a challenge since banks lack connections with agencies who can provide such data. Furthermore, dedicating the effective amount of money for information security is difficult because the board might not accept it. Subsequently, it becomes hard for CISOs to select the best solution of cybersecurity (Bank B: CISO; supported by Bank D - CISO). Case 10 further mentioned that during prevention phase CISOs have limited access to internet, preventing them to perform their job effectively (Bank J: CISO). This shows the technological improvement section of banks where banks need to focus and invest in order to make their system efficient for all employees to continue regular activities without any obstruction (ISO, 2016).

Proceeding, Case 4 also pointed out that in detection phase we can detect the cyberthreat if the reporting system is efficient (McLaughlin & Gogan, 2018). However, practically our customers lack awareness and their response time is high. Similarly, smaller number of experts increases the burden of detection throughout whole network (Bank D: CISO). This is another inefficiency in information security control system of banks which is the result of lack of investment issue. Likewise, Case 11 highlighted that in response process data collection from peer banks is a challenge. It requires time. SBP must facilitate banks with a system which can enable easy access to such data in case of a threat (Tøndel et al., 2014). Moreover, less employee training, untrained staff, lack of innovative equipment and reward function restrict the learning process (Bank K: CISO; supported by Bank L; (Mahn, 2018). The results showed that apart of data collection issue from industry and peer banks, again these all issues move around the customer awareness, staff training as well as motivation, and investment issue.

7.2.2.3. Critical Findings - Factors' Interdependency

From the above analysis and discussion, it is found that some factors affect other factors. For example, awareness depends on literacy level of people as literate people can learn quickly (Ismailova & Muhametjanova, 2016). Similarly, law enforcement will demotivate criminal employees and external criminals. Hence, the investment in technology (symbolic logics) will be effective as supported by law enforcement (structural logics). On the other hand, the availability of satisfactory regulatory framework of cybersecurity (structural logics) can impose the necessity of directors' training (which will support strategic planning - symbolic logics). Furthermore, the literacy level of general public and awareness can positively impact on illiterate customers' awareness being part of society. The awareness program by government can increase the customer (normative logics) and employees' awareness (symbolic logics). This will also ultimately demotivate criminal employees and cybercriminals as they will reconsider the factor, repeatedly before conducting cybercrime, that they can be caught as people are aware about these criminal activities, which will become the culture (Chang & Coppel, 2020). In contrast, the investment on training, employee's motivation, awareness, and technology will also positively affect the employees (symbolic logics influenced from requirement of directors' training and awareness – structural logics). Finally, employees' training and awareness, investment on cybersecurity (as mentioned above), and use of outdated infrastructure is an investment issue which strategically depends on the directors' training.

7.2.2.4. Research Objective 1 Assessment

The results show that customer awareness, law and law enforcement, regulatory framework of cybersecurity, and directors' training affect the cybersecurity of private commercial banks in Pakistan collectively. Within banks the directors' training is the most important factor (as investment, employee awareness and strategic planning depend on it) as they do not invest having profits. Thus, compliance requirement of strategic planning (to invest in appropriate technology, training, and number of experts) and its actual implementation is heavily contingent to directors. Therefore, directors' cybersecurity training and awareness is the main factor for internal cybersecurity governance in PCBP. However, as a human factor within banks employees are the major challenge. Employees use the technology and work within cybersecurity environment of banks hence, if they are not satisfied/motivated, they will not perform in the best interest of bank. Moreover, PCBP have untrained employees and lack of cybersecurity experts. Additionally, there is need to invest in innovative technology to support the weak information security infrastructure. On the other hand, it is found that the incompatible regulatory framework of cybersecurity is result of SBP negligence employing incompetent staff and less check and balance on banks. However, this weak structural logics adopted by SBP have facilitated the weak symbolic logics of compliance by directors. Comparatively, ineffective law and its enforcement makes it hard for banks to secure their information assets in absence of customer awareness, weak information security infrastructure, incompatible regulatory framework, and ineffective strategy planning. Likewise, law enforcement is also affected as their agents have to improve their capabilities and their subordinates are fresh graduates using social engineering to support cybercrime. Finally, as another human factor customer awareness is crucial as even employing expensive technology, enforcing rigorous law, and providing effective regulatory framework, customers remain a weak link for social engineers. However, the customers do not need to have high qualifications to be cybersecurity aware but some level of financial literacy will help to learn quickly and adopt awareness. The well-educated customers of banks became victim of social engineering lacking awareness. In addition, banks cannot spread the awareness at fast pace and national level lacking the resources. Instead, immediately government need to

run effective cybersecurity awareness campaigns based on peoples' category. Besides, the other social factors found are related to information security control system again include customer awareness, employee training as well as motivation, and investment issue, apart from data collection. This meets research objective 1 and answers research question 1 of this study.

Research Objective 2: To determine the maturity of cybersecurity governance in private commercial banks in Pakistan understanding the perception of banks about cybersecurity governance.

7.2.3. Theme 3: Strategic planning - Cybersecurity Governance Perception

Perception of Banks - Research Objective 2 Assessment

To meet this research objective the concepts such as considering cybersecurity in strategic planning, pre-planned initiatives to avoid cybersecurity issue, type of IT experts hired to deal with cybersecurity issue and, impact of ineffective cybersecurity on customers' trust on e-banking were explored. Despite of that the factors discussed under strategic planning for example, investment, employee and directors training and awareness etc. provide the comprehensive knowledge of understanding and perception of banks on cybersecurity governance. The results showed that the CISOs who are the head of information security in banks possess the necessary expertise to strategically plan effective cybersecurity solutions for banks. However, the directors of private commercial banks of Pakistan lack the necessary awareness and training about cybersecurity. Hence their understanding and perception of cyberthreats and risks to their banks is weak (symbolic logics). Directors approve the proposed cybersecurity strategies considering box centric approach to avoid investment as they consider it pointless to invest in cybersecurity. Ultimately, the whole bank's information system and customers' money is at risk as the highly advanced businesses are failing to secure their information system because of ineffective decisions of executives resulting from their unawareness (Alghamdi, 2021).

Therefore, it is concluded that in private commercial banks of Pakistan banks follow weak symbolic logics having poor understanding and perception of need of adopting effective cybersecurity solutions. Thus, their cybersecurity is at initial level which requires effective practices (investment in training, technology, and experts) to be mature, building the culture of cybersecurity. this meets the research objective two.

Research Objective 3: To understand the cybersecurity threats caused by identified factors in private commercial banks of Pakistan.

7.2.4. Theme 4: Cybersecurity threats affecting cybersecurity governance in private commercial banks of Pakistan

This theme represents the recent threats faced by private commercial banks of Pakistan. Justifying interview question Q11, the interviewees responded that both their customers and employees are confronting increasing and critical threats against information security of banks caused by above discussed factors (challenges) of this study.

7.2.4.1. Sub theme: Social engineering

21 out of 21 respondents mentioned that social engineering is one of the major and a raising trend in banking industry of Pakistan to conduct the data breach through phishing attacks, fraudulent impersonating, SMS, and scam emails. Ghauri (2021) state that the borderless approach of cyberspace has enabled cybercriminals to reach people around the world using different methods for example emails, SMS or phone calls pretending that they reside locally. Their basic purpose is to breach the confidentiality of personal data of people to steal money (similar view of Bank D, F, and L - CISOs).

Bank A, I, K and L (CISOs) justified it as cyber criminals prefer social engineering finding people weak link and easy target. Bank M (CISO) specifically highlighted that the biggest risks to our banks are human in the banking industry, including the employees, the customers, and call centre people. The respondents explained the rational that because of lack of awareness social engineering is the main concern for the banks in Pakistan (Sadiq, 2019). Also, Hafiz-Ali et al. (2019) highlighted that the cybercriminals keep searching for their victims. However, their main victims are people who are less literate

and have less awareness of cybersecurity yet somehow, they are part of cyberspace. Such people are more vulnerable and become victim of social engineering. Bank A, B, C, E, G, I, J, and K – CISOs agreed with this statement.

While case 10 (Bank J: CISO) exemplified it directly towards banks as, because of lack of literacy and awareness among our customers and employees the cybercriminals create the sense of urgency, curiosity, or fear using multiple innovative methods of social engineering and successfully inquire the required data. This results in financial loss and affects goodwill of bank. B, F, H, I, J, K L, and M – CISOs also confirmed it. Terlizzi et al. (2017) explains this concept emphasising that social engineering is an act of bad faith following which the cybercriminal attempts to misuse peoples' greed, vanity, and positive beliefs. Therefore, social engineering is used to manipulate the weakest link (employees and customers) in the information security chain of an organisation (Allen, 2007).

Case 11 supported it by saying that cybercriminals use innovative-unfamiliar methods of social engineering to tackle the literate people including bank employees. Thus , in case of a fraud caused by bank employee's unawareness, the bank has to bear the financial loss. However, the most common techniques of social engineering are e-mail and SMS (Bank K: CISO). This statement clearly explains that why human factor is a risk for banks which makes social engineering a major threat for them (IBM, 2018; Swaine, 2022). Similar, thoughts were shared by case 10. On the other hand, case 6 (Bank F: Cash controller) held culture responsible mentioning that people in Pakistan are innocent where they trust others easily and share their personal details for example date of birth, identity card number or even bank details to receive the money of lucky draw. While, cybercriminals use those details then to steal the money from bank (Munirul, et al., 2011; Ghauri, 2021).

Again, this indicates that there is a need of developing a culture of awareness about cybersecurity with effective campaigns. Bank B, E, and H – CISOs explain this as 'people are innocent lacking the awareness about cybersecurity threats. Iqbal (2021) highlighted that in Pakistan lack of literacy and awareness has caused the culture of trusting on information provided by others. Bank A (CISO; supported by all CISOs) suggested that

having weak information security infrastructure and slow investment in technology requires quick awareness as an effective solution to prevent cybercrimes (Wang et al., 2021). Contrarily, Bank G (CISO) brought into attention that unscrupulous elements are continuously engaging in exploring new techniques for social engineering, hence making employees fully prepared to avoid social engineering is not possible.

In addition, case 2 (Operations head) articulated that social engineering is a shortcut to data breach. The cybercriminals avoid to directly breach the strict security controls implied by banks and prefer to use social engineering techniques to gain customers' data and steal money (Chaimaa, et al., 2021). Likewise, having controls on the e-mail, security controls and implementing them in particular you can improve cybersecurity to some extent but again social engineering is the primary tool even to deliver malware, ransomware, Trojans or viruses and ransomware. Therefore, the cybercriminals will keep introducing new methods to it (Bank A: CISO; supported by Bank E: CISO). Hence, banks are required to continuously provide up to date training and awareness to its employees and customers where possible.

These findings show that social engineering is one of a main challenge in Pakistan to information security of banks, by having illegal access to confidential data (Ghauri, 2021). Hence, as a human factor employees and customers become the main threat to banks rather than hackers (Allen, 2007).

Fake websites and online shopping

Discussing the social engineering, total 6 out of 13 banks implied that the number of fake websites is increasing in bulk every day, to trap people. Additionally, case 6 (Bank F: Cash controller) referred back to the scenario that making online payment using their own cards or guardians' or relatives' cards (section 7.2.1.1.) eventually results in our customers' data loss. These respondents highlighted that sharing information because of lack of awareness on fake websites or through online shopping is another cause of data breach (Salahdine & Kaabouch, 2019). In this regard, case 2 (Bank: Operations head) underlined that the government need to wake up and realise the necessity of immediately

putting ban on creation as well as advertisement of such fake websites (supported by Bank D CISO). Otherwise, leniency can result in to shake the stability of economy resulted from financial loss because thousands of new websites are developed every day to steal information and this trend is increasing (Alkhalil et al., 2021). However, agreeing with this case 2 indicated the irresponsible behaviour of government of Pakistan towards ensuring the information security since implication of banning malicious websites is ineffective in Pakistan (Hafiz-Ali et al., 2019).

Also, case 8 (Bank H: CISO) stated that the use of fake websites has increased to steal personal information of users since online shopping trend promoted after COVID-19. The customer report to banks that impersonated confirmatory e-mails have mostly led them to fake websites. Hence, fake websites can be considered as a category of social engineering. Case 11 further underlined it stating that couple of years ago only a few people used to make online shopping. However, the increasing trend of internet made people feel convenient to shop from home, especially during COVID-19. However, cybercriminals have targeted them as a victim. This highlights the increasing motivation of cybercriminals to steal data of less literate and less aware people (using fake websites and online shopping methods; Parakash, 2020).

Case 1 (Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst) notified that following the weak infrastructure throughout the country even the local businesses are not providing information security system to their customers since they are using the basic features of the websites and without security protocols. This ultimately results in financial loss to banks and their customers (Haroon et al. 2021). The government need to require such businesses to ensure the information security of their websites before they launch them. Bank E (CISO) mentioned that social engineering, fake websites, and online shopping are consistent threats. Every bank is exposed with them. Use of fake websites for social engineering is one of the major concern because it has to do with people and every bank has customers so it is very common in all banks resulting in digital frauds.

These results show that fake websites and online shopping is increasing trend in Pakistan with increase of internet users. However, this increase in use of online websites is

resulting in data loss and Government of Pakistan need to take action against it by awareness and strict rules to help the information security of banks ((Abdul Qadeer, 2020).

7.2.4.2. Sub theme: ATM skimming

The respondents highlighted that ATM skimming, DDoS and malware are directly related to the system of banks while other discussed challenges are indirectly related to information security of our banks. Although, 21 out of 21 respondents mentioned that ATM skimming is another major and most challenging threat to our banks.

Case 7 accentuated that the trend of inserting card reader slots in ATM machines to steal card details from ATM machine is increasing (Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker; supported by Bank A, B, D, E, F, M - CISOs). This indicates the insecure ATM system in banks of Pakistan (Syed et al., 2019). Case 3 (Bank C: CISO) emphasised that higher the security risk can result in higher the loss of trust or no banking. Therefore, banks should accept their corporate social responsibility to provide secure information infrastructure to their customers (Zia UL Islam et al., 2019). Moreover, the awareness to customers can play a major role to lessen such frauds. The similar view was shared from Bank A, B, D, G, I, J, and K – CISOs. Supporting it, case 2 (Bank B: Customer's relationship and marketing manager) summed up that the ultimate result of ATM skimming can be bankruptcy. Consequently, the economy will be defaulted since customers will feel insecure, they will lose the trust on bank and will stop depositing their money in banks.

Furthermore, case 11 exemplified that the COVID-19 lockdown has been the period of huge increase in ATM skimming because people were bound to use banking as a payment method. That is why banks' profits increased during lockdown. However, finding banks' ATM machines as a weak point, cybercriminals stole data of thousands of banks' customers (Vasiliev, 2021). Bank E (CISO) incorporated that having an ATM machine every bank will face sooner or later these kind of threats as they are happening and are reported every now and then in the banks. This can be well defined as the hackers use

'Skimer malware' which allows them to obtain full access to an ATM without inserting any card skimmer slot. This have made the hackers' strength to steal money easily while, for banks with outdated ATM infrastructure it's a potential threat (Velocci, 2016). Relating to this case 8 (Bank H: CISO) referred back to the use of outdated infrastructure issue (section 7.2.2.1.) where it was proposed that the ATM machines still use Window 7 as a result of directors' investment decision. This statement was also rephrased by Bank D, E, and M-CISOs.

Case 5 (Bank E: Senior credit control manager; supported by Bank A and G - CISOs) highlighted the recent cybersecurity attacks when the international hackers have been withdrawing money from different locations in Europe and have been making international payment transactions in foreign currencies using the stolen data from our ATM machines (section 4.4.7.). It can be noticed that anti-ATM skimming and biometric ATM machines are introduced but again investment budget remains an issue, even though the banks are profitable. These machines are effective yet need improvement. Case 7 further denoted back to the customer awareness as a potential source to prevent cybercrime suggesting that the updated technology (anti-skimming devices) will be used by customer and if they are unaware of its efficient and effective use then investment in technology is not effective (Hafiz Ali, 2019).

Instantaneously, Case 13 (Bank M: CISO) added that there is a logical flaw in installing ATM machines in our banks. The service provider uses private circuit to connect ATM with the banking system. Moreover, the banks allow them administrative access to the ATM windows. Likewise, no code analysis or the pin testing on the ATM machine is done before making it available to customers. Hence, there might be case of compromise on the security weakness of the windows system on the ATM or by the installer. Additionally, case 1 (Bank A: CISO) shared that there are a few models for instance, persona 77 persona 78 and persona 81 which are called master keys to open the ATM machine. If someone have that they can open any ATM machine. Inside the lockers in the ATM machine one can insert devices. They cannot takeout the cash but still they can play with an ATM dispenser. Such as they can attach their devices with ATM and yet plug in their keyboard and mouse to access the data of people. It is a big risk in Pakistan. In ATM

spots, there is a switch plugged inside the room and that is power input to that ATM machine. If someone just reboot it, ATM machine shutdowns and no one can detect who stole the data.

Henceforth, this indicates the higher management decision (directors') to invest in temporary solutions and ignore the information security of banks. Besides it, the unawareness plays the role of cover to cybercriminals attempting to hack such ATM machines (Johri and Kumar, 2023). Ultimately the customers will lose trust on e-banking. These results amplify the study conducted by Malik (2019) that Pakistan has increased ATM skimming issue and the reason is found the use of outdated infrastructure. Hence, the banking industry of Pakistan has lost a significant amount of money due to cyberattacks (Haroon et al., 2021). Also, the cybercrime results in loss of trust of customers in digital infrastructure of banks and they withdraw their deposits from banks. Subsequently, the banking sector development will suffer (Akinbowale et al., 2020).

7.2.4.3. Sub theme: DDoS

7 out of 13 banks illustrated that DDoS attacks are most common in our industry and are of malicious nature to be considered. DDoS is a cyberattack towards information system of businesses which exhausts the resources to make them unavailable for the end users (availability issue). There is an increasing trend of such attacks especially in financial organisations and are heavily devastating (Namanya et al., 2018). Similarly, case 4 embodied the recent example when plenty of their customers and foreign residents could not open Roshan digital account (new type of account), since the website requested users to refill the same details persistently. Apparently, those people already lost their personal information (Bank D: CISO). The respondent highlighted that the purpose of such attacks is to deny access to our website and interfere the data to steal it, so that it will demotivate people to not use banking and lose the trust as well as confidence on banks. The consequence will be bankruptcy (Qarar, 2018).

Case 10 (Bank J: CISO) confronting similar issue indicated the huge loss of foreign remittances of Rs. 100 million to their bank and more to banking industry of Pakistan. On

the other hand, case 6 (Bank F: Cash controller) added to the scenario that using malicious malware, the cybercriminals create artificial traffic (DDoS attacks) which delays the banking transactions and payments and slowdowns the money rotation throughout the country, resulting in delaying the business matters (Bank B - CISO). Consequently, the customers prefer not to use banking apps or system. This demotivates the use of services the bank has invested in (Swaine, 2022).

In this regard, Case 2 (Bank B: Customer's relationship and marketing manager; supported by Bank M - CISO) highlighted that if the security features of banks will not be strengthened providing appropriate investment, regulations and law enforcement and awareness, the banks will have to bear heavy financial loss caused by cybercriminal's motivated by money (all respondents; Hummel, 2021). Moreover, Case 7 (Bank G: CISO) claimed that various types of attacks are identified and blocked by controls. Most common types include social engineering and DDoS. Likewise, Qarar (2018) state that the banks in Pakistan are more vulnerable to malware and DDoS attacks. Following the recent cyberattacks of 2018 to 2022 in Pakistan using malware and DDoS (section 4.4.7.) the affected banks lost \$25 million (Haq & Atta, 2019).

The findings and discussion showed that DDoS attacks are of malicious nature and affecting private commercial banks in Pakistan. However, information security against them is necessity to run their banking system smoothly (Hummel, 2021).

7.2.4.4. Sub theme: Malware

More than half respondents (15 out of 21) highlighted that malware is another malicious type of cyberthreat (which affects the banks' information system) in PCBP.

Namanya et al. (2018) state that malware is a code added, changed, or removed from within a software system with purpose to deliberately damage or weaken the specific function of a system. Furthermore, malware is devastating which can harm the information and money. However, because of their malicious nature the use of malware is increasing globally especially where the information security infrastructure is weak. Also, a new banking Trojans is being used which can steal messages containing one-

time passwords (Tapales, 2021). However, Case 2 mentioned that malware is the most famous cyberattack being used throughout the country in all sectors. Moreover, Trojan horse, virus, and worm are more recurring attacks in PCBP. Furthermore, their computers are supervised by experts. Therefore, if any virus is detected, the computer will shutdowns so that the virus cannot spread over to other computers. This makes their system secure (Bank: Operations head; supported by Bank A, C, F, and M - CISOs).

The noticeable thing is that this is the case of one of the top banks. On the other hand, Bank G: Senior retail and corporate banker and Bank L – CISO added that employees must aware their managers if they detect any suspicious activity within computer systems. And in case of any cyberattack in a bank, the targeted bank is required to inform SBP immediately so that SBP can also aware other banks to be alert and secure their system. However, Bank A, B, C, D, H and M (CISOs) also confirmed that Trojan horse, virus, and worm are more frequent in banks.

In contrast, emphasising on the weakness of security infrastructure in banks, case 8 (Bank H: CISO) declared that *malware is most critical for them since it is used to edit, alter, or delete the data which resulted in cyberattacks of 2018 to 2019 (causing heavy financial loss)*. Similarly, case 2 (Bank B: CISO) advised that these cyberattacks (section 4.4.7.) have resulted to lose the customers and their trust. If cybersecurity will not be strengthened then banks will lose their competitive advantage as the customers deposit enable banks to run smoothly. These findings highlight the necessity of rigid cybersecurity in PCBP. In this support, case 4 said that with weak basic infrastructure of banks there is still room to improve it through heavy investment in professionals, right technology, and employees training as well as awareness (Khatri, 2017; Malik and Islam, 2019; Ometov et al., 2018; Świątkowska, 2020; Syed, et al., 2019). The respondent emphasised that SBP and government of Pakistan need to take immediate actions to solve this problem before it gets worst (Bank D1: CISO). Besides, these findings rationalized that the cyberattacks has increased all over the world and especially in Pakistan during last few years (using innovative methods). Although this is the beginning as Pakistan banking sector owns healthy amount with weak cybersecurity and that attracts the cybercriminals (Syed et al., 2019). This point of view was also shared by bank H, I, J, and K).

In addition, the results of case 6 (Bank F: Cash controller) suggest that some good protocols are being used in PCBP such as continuous check of all the activities, highlighting any attack, analysing the nature of the attack, taking appropriate and possible action, limiting data transfer from one PC to other, limited access to banks' PC properties, restricted use of USB device or charge the device or play audio or video, and limited access to websites. Further, case 5 added that if there is an attack from hackers on your system, then branches are not involved. It is the central system of the bank where the servers are present that is involved. It will be immediately highlighted in the system and the security team, and the experts will take up the network. Additionally, Case 6 (Bank F: Cash controller) stated that they have restrictions. Every computer has antivirus. IT regions keep an eye on each computer separately. No one is allowed to download or add anything in the computer. Their computers are very secure. Even if a virus is downloaded in a computer, different hubs of IT will be dealing with it and experts are aware about the download or any action of that. Even if any spam email comes, the antivirus will alert. Hence, it can be concluded that malware attacks are launched on banks' information systems (Haroon et al., 2021). However, the CISOs (Bank D, H, I, J, and K), point of view is that with having basic security lapses and a smaller number of staff how the whole system can be secured effectively. Therefore, investment in cybersecurity is the basic need of PCBP and board of directors and SBP need to understand this (Bukht et al., 2020).

These results follow the perspective that if the information security of a bank is compromised it will lose the competitive advantage and trust of their customers (Afshan et al., 2018). Also, such attacks are of harmful nature and have caused heavy loss to banking industry of Pakistan (Sadiq, 2019). Likewise, the private commercial banks of Pakistan need to take immediate actions to secure their information security as they are the main target of increasing cyberthreats because of weak security system and infrastructure (Chang & Coppel 2020; Jamshed et al., 2022).

7.2.4.5. Sub theme: Deepfake Attacks

Only CISOs acknowledged that this is a new form of cyberattacks. The other respondents were not aware of it (interview question Q12). Even some of the respondents also accepted that before participating in this study they even did not know about this new technology. However, Case 8 (Bank H: CISO) espoused that the use of audio, e-mail, or messages for impersonating is so common to access the personal information of their customers. Yet, video deepfake attacks will be worst. Case 2 (Bank B: CISO) explained this phenomenon highlighting that the deepfake attacks include the use of video impersonating. Use of videos can easily make people believing that the person in the video is the same they are familiar with. Especially in case of Pakistan where lack of literacy and awareness can make it worst (supported by 13 other CISOs; Kumire, 2020).

Supporting it, case 11 (Bank K: CISO) claimed that since the information infrastructure of banking industry of Pakistan is developed over years with no security features. Hence, investing time in only applying technological security protocols throughout whole banking industry cannot be effective (supported by Bank A, D, J and M - CISOs). Because it will take almost a decade to fully secure the information infrastructure of banking of Pakistan using essential protocols. However, meanwhile focusing on awareness and training of employee as well as customers, law and its enforcement and regulatory requirements can help to reduce cyberthreats or at least their impact (supported by Bank B, C, I and H – CISOs; Okwero, 2020).

7.2.4.6. Research Objective 3 Assessment

This section finds that the social engineering is one of the major and more frequent threat the private commercial banks of Pakistan are facing. This threat is more relevant to human factors (employees' and customers' awareness as well as training). Even though the banks will be using improved cybersecurity solutions still if customers and employees of banks will become the victims of social engineering then the investment in improved technology even could not help. However, the fake websites are used as a technique for social engineering which should be banned to stop the adoption of this technique. While,

DDoS, and malware are also of malicious nature therefore are major threats but less frequent. However, DDoS, and malware are the threats to banks' information system and having weak information infrastructure with lack of investment in required technology, number of experts and employee training, such attacks result in financial loss and loss of data of thousands of customers of banks (section 4.4.7.). Hence, even they are less frequent but devastating in nature if occur. Furthermore, another major challenge to private commercial banks is ATM skimming which is resulted from mainly outdated and cheaper infrastructure which need proper investment. Yet, awareness is required for immediate perquisite. Further, deepfake is emerging as a new threat which can also result in huge financial loss. Therefore, private commercial banks in Pakistan need to take immediate actions of improving their information security infrastructure with recommended solutions from consultants such as investing in vulnerability scanning or other technology etc. and reduce the effect of other factors (customers and employees' awareness) as discussed above. Additionally, the SBP and government need to play their role by providing regulatory framework and law with its enforcement respectively to fully secure the information system of banking sector. In short, social engineering, ATM skimming, DDoS, and malware are the major threats the private commercial banks in Pakistan confront while, deepfake (having worst consequences) are expected to increase. This meets the research objective 3 of this study and answers research question 3.

Research Objective 4: To recommend effective cybersecurity governance measures for the private commercial banks of Pakistan

This section analyses and discusses the results of questions about the third-party solutions the banks prefer to use (interview question Q15) and the recommendations provided from PCBP for banks, SBP and Government (interview question Q14 and Q16).

7.2.5. Theme 5: Recommendations for effective cybersecurity governance in private commercial banks of Pakistan

7.2.5.1. Sub-theme: Solutions

12 interviewees (representing 11 out of 13 banks) acknowledged that use of banking external tools and third-party services is not secure and is costly, therefore it is recommended to upgrade or develop your own banking system.

BAAS, cloud storage, open APIs and open banking services are provided by the third parties as a solution for the information security of business (Anderson, 2019). Many businesses are using these services as they are quick solutions and became easy to adopt, based on the services of third parties (Voas et al., 2022). However, it is noticeable that these solutions are only useful if the third parties who are providing these services have secured their own information security systems otherwise their customers (banks) will be vulnerable (Pratt, 2021). Case 2 (Bank B: Customer's relationship and marketing manager) underlined this perspective as, some PCBP are using cloud storage and open banking. However, it can be effective for a short period of time yet these services might also be vulnerable lacking appropriate security. Consequently, it is highly recommended to upgrade banking system even though if it is expensive, but it provides long term security and peace of mind – confidence (supported by Bank B, C, D, D1, E, F, G, H, I, J, K, and M - CISOs).

Supporting it case 6 (Bank F: Cash controller) mentioned that banks consider third-party services cost effective compared to system upgrade. Instead, in reality the cost of third-party service adding the financial loss – resulted from external services' weak cybersecurity, counts as double of the system upgrade. Thus, the use of open APIs or

external solutions for cybersecurity is not cost effective. Also, it adds to the risk of information security (Kumire, 2020). However, if the cyber-risk of third-party service providers' is incorporated into the enterprise-wide risk management of banks then it can be useful to use third party services (Crisanto & Prenio, 2017). Finally, all of the respondents agreed that multi factor authentication is useful, better, secure, durable, and reliable (Ometov et al., 2018).

Correspondingly, Case 2 (Bank B: CISO) expressed that as a top bank, they are using 3D secure multi factor authentication scheme for their banks' visa MasterCard and debit card services. Ultimately the chances of cybercrime are lessened, and their customers are satisfied. However, all other respondents (20) agreed that multifactor authentication is best and secure as it is being used in developed countries. However, not many of the banks in Pakistan are using multi factor authentication because its costly. Case 12 (Bank L: CISO) specifically stated that the reason of not adoption of MFA could be cost, limitation to the application that we are running, resource constrained, dependencies on any other application or budget and its approval. Nevertheless, case 10 (Bank J: CISO) emphasised that it is responsibility of banks to secure the deposits of their customers utilising all the resources. If banks fail in it, this means they are not doing their job right. Therefore, it is important to invest in the effective cybersecurity solution, either it is in-built or third-party (Premchand & Choudhry, 2018). However, as suggested by Bank M (CISO) for call centre agents, case 12 (Bank L: CISO) also suggested that the device recognition factor should be used for MFA. Their bank uses a biometric system and personal question as well to access the account. Though, having the device registered would definitely be beneficial for customers (Banyal, Jain, & Jain, 2013). Conversely, Bank A (CISO) provided a different concept mentioning that a combination of multi factor authentication and sometime external services is better depending on the need. Their bank is using cloud storage which only stores non-financial data while the financial data is stored in secure systems. Thus, the third-party service can be useful to low the data storage issue (Anderson, 2019). Similarly, Case 12 (Bank L: CISO) mentioned that banks should use all of these services. Outsourcing is always good because at the end of the day you are reducing your cost and you are transferring this. Otherwise, you would need to hire the

people and develop your set up and systems. Hence, if the third-party is providing similar sort of security controls or can amend you can always use that service (Pratt, 2021).

The findings relate to the previous study suggesting that the businesses should only use the third-party services if the third-party service provider is fully secure itself, given the examples of apple internet services with proved ISO certification to Netflix for post-production and widespread publicity (Culot et al., 2021). Further, MFA is suggested to use adding device recognition factor. Also, the above statement can be referred back to the corporate social responsibility (CSR) perspective whereby the bank should be held responsible to provide cybersecurity for information security system of the banks (Jamshed et al., 2022).

7.2.5.2. Sub-Theme: Recommendations

This section will highlight the recommendations for PCBP, SBP and Government of Pakistan based on suggestions provided by interviewees during interviews and literature review. Additionally, some of these recommendations are being used by only top private commercial banks of Pakistan (the banks which are in progress can adopt them), as discussed above while, some of them are purely the suggestions provided by interviewees which the SBP and Government of Pakistan can adopt to improve the cybersecurity in private commercial banks of Pakistan.

7.2.5.2.1. For Banks

7.2.5.2.1.1. Increased controls adopted from NIST

It is recommended by one of the top private commercial banks of Pakistan (Bank B: CISO) to use increased controls (McLaughlin & Gogan, 2018) following the NIST controls family (Hughes, 2022). Moreover, the use of highest version of T24 software recommended by SBP should be used, instead of using the lowest version which is T24. Using T24 software enables employees to use the latest features which facilitates them to perform their tasks easily and focus on information security.

7.2.5.2.1.2. Multi factor authentication – face and device recognition

It is highly recommended (21 out of 21 respondents) to use critical verification system (being used by only one of the top private commercial banks of Pakistan) for any transaction. This will reduce the chances and number of cybercrime. Since, the malware has been introduced to steal OTP (one time password) therefore it is best for banks to adopt rigorous multi factor authentication which can lessen the frauds (Heartfield & Loukas, 2016). For example, either withdrawing money from ATM machine, or making online payment the customers usually are required to enter the pin and password. If the face and device recognition factor is also added as a final authentication factor, then the transaction will be more secure than before (Ometov et al., 2018).

7.2.5.2.1.3. Investment in technology, experts, and training

11 out of 13 banks recommended that enhanced capability programmes which can train the employees (of all designation and age) to the extent that their understanding of cybersecurity can play the role of a guard at gateways of banks, to stop any effort made by the cybercriminals - either it's relating to social engineering or malware (Wang, 2019). Also, it is recommended to use the best quality system and technology. No doubt it will cost initially but in long run it will make the bank stress free from beating the cost of repetitive cybercrimes (Monaghan, 2018). Likewise, banks should also make efforts to spread awareness in partnership with Government of Pakistan (Haq & Atta, 2019). On the other hand, the experts are the one who can play the role of a firewall in case of a cyber-attack detected and experts provide the best solution available in the market as per the contemporary cybersecurity needs of the bank. Therefore, the banks should invest in to hire the essential number of experts (Anwar, 2020).

7.2.5.2.1.4. Anti-fraud department

Focusing on the fact that the 'National Response Centre for Cybercrime' is one and only organisation in Pakistan working to support the prevention of increasing cybercrimes with the help of CERT, every bank should have AFD (anti-fraud department) for cybersecurity and cyber monitoring unit to deal with phishing attacks as one of the top private

commercial banks has (Bank B: CISO). This will reduce the burden of work on cybersecurity experts especially in case if they are less in numbers. In addition, it will increase the efficiency and awareness of employees as they will be in contact with anti-fraud department more often to take advice or correspond (Kolade, 2022).

7.2.5.2.1.5. Information Security Control Improvement

The banks should use real time system monitoring, web application firewalls along with other various firewalls and required standards during prevention function of information security, as the top bank in Pakistan is using (Top bank, Bank B: CISO). This will help to detect any suspicious activity within the cyberspace network of the bank (Khan & Anwar, 2020). Also, it is best to use own developed reliable system for banking services instead of taking third party services unless they are secure. Thus, no bridging or De-hubs will be involved (Sadiq, 2019). This will help to detect any unwanted activity. Finally, there should be a system for developing and enhancing the security controls and protocols after an attack. However, this process of information security control should be updated with time. Most importantly, the banks should hire the experts who can perform system analysis to make the improvements for future, after responding to an attack (Syed et al., 2019).

7.2.5.2.1.6. Limit the amount of transfer

Banks can also consider to reduce the amount of bank transfer allowed to each customer in one day, based on the account type and card type (current, Gold, Premium) because it will demotivate the criminals as they will be less persuaded to make efforts for lower amount of money. However, this suggestion has already been implemented in one of the top private commercial banks and proved successful (Bank B: Operations head).

7.2.5.2.1.7. Anti-skimming devices and surveys

It is useful for banks to invest in anti-skimming devices introduced by SBP because this will automatically put the ATM machine out of service if any 'Skimer malware' will be found and once the threat is removed then the ATM machine will be back to service (Bank G:

Senior retail and corporate banker). Hence, one of the major challenges to private commercial banks of Pakistan could be removed (Johnson, 2022). However, these devices are costly but using them will benefit the customers by increasing their confidence to use ATM machines. Ultimately it will increase the transactions which will result in profitability for banks. Thus, the cost of anti-ATM skimming machine will worth. Also, the use of surveys or questionnaires to take opinion regarding cybersecurity from lower-level employees should be made, to make them feel a part of information security of bank (Terlizzi et al., 2017).

7.2.5.2.1.8. Theoretical Logics

All respondents recommended that humans should be the main focus. If they are all good with the humans then later on the technology comes. Because, the humans are the ones who are going to use the technology. It does not matter how good the technology you bring if they cannot use it properly there is no point of investing in that technology. Therefore, it is recommended to use the employees' performance motivation cycle introduced in this study because to motivate employees to work in the best interest of business their behaviour need to be determined. However, implying the right motivation factor will provide effective results (McLeod, 2016). Also, while providing training and awareness to employees about cybersecurity the banks can use TAM model whereby, they can justify the need for and importance of this awareness and training which will motivate employees to learn and adopt quickly. In addition, the TAM model concept of ease of use will be beneficial specifically if used for old age employees who are not willing to learn technology (Kang et al., 2021).

Additionally, besides this awareness and training program the motivational factors are added such as reward or recognition etc. then the results of this program will be better. Finally, after mentally preparing employees to follow the information security protocols using above mentioned theoretical concepts then the consequences of deliberate information breach (harsh punishment – deterrence theory) should be announced (Trang & Brendel, 2019). Consequently, this will result in developing the Information Security Climate (ISC) by giving the employees confidence gained from trainings and motivation

(Lee, 2017). Also, following the perspective of 'Three-line model of defence' the directors are responsible to gain the required skills and knowledge through training which will enable them to make right decisions of cybersecurity of banks as whole bank depends on their decisions (Brasseur, 2020).

7.2.5.2.2. For SBP

7.2.5.2.2.1. Rigorous and comprehensive cybersecurity framework

Considering the cybersecurity situation of banking industry of Pakistan, the literature, and results of this study (21 out of 21 interviewee) recommend that SBP need to take immediate actions to improve the cybersecurity of banks. For this purpose, it is recommended that the first step the SBP need to take is to provide rigorous and comprehensive cybersecurity framework following the protocols provided in NIST or ISO 27001 cybersecurity frameworks (Ward, 2016). The most important thing is that this framework should clearly mention the requirements to be met by banks based on the size of banks, to secure their information security instead of leaving them on banks' options (Kopp et al., 2017). For example, the SBP should make an effort to determine the required number of experts depending on the size of the bank.

7.2.5.2.2.2. Guidelines about directors' training and investment decision

13 out of 14 CISOs recommended that SBP need to provide specific guidelines (in regulatory framework) about directors' training and investment decision (technology, hiring required number of experts, and employee as well as customer training). Otherwise, the delay in investment caused by directors' lack of understanding of necessity of investing in proposed solutions can result in huge financial loss (Robert & Ackerman, 2021). This results in failure of strategic planning.

7.2.5.2.2.3. Audit team

SBP should increase the capacity of its audit team so that a good check and balance can be kept on banks actual performance instead of cosmetic performance. Moreover, instead of hiring the fresh graduates the experienced internal employees should be hired so that

they can scrutinise the strategic planning implementation in banks and detect any discrepancies used by executives such as cosmetic performance (Bank D and M - CISOs).

7.2.5.2.2.4. Work in partnership with government to spread the awareness

SBP should work in partnership with government to spread the awareness of cybersecurity at national level (Sadiq, 2019). Finally, SBP should make an effort to introduce a system to build up connections with agencies so that the banks can collect the required data in case of an cyberattack (Bank J -CISO).

7.2.5.2.2.5. Theoretical Logics

As per the stakeholder theory it is SBP's corporate social responsibility to provide information security to its stakeholders (banks and their customers). Hence, SBP should understand its responsibility towards banks and society by providing rigorous regulatory framework for information security of banks (Jamshed et al., 2022).

7.2.5.2.3. For government of Pakistan

7.2.5.2.3.1. Spread cybersecurity awareness

It is recommended (21 out of 21 respondents) that first of all the government of Pakistan should spread cybersecurity awareness throughout the whole country. Because this is the easiest task to perform as compared to other necessities of cybersecurity (for example law making or law enforcement). Consequently, a significant decrease in cybercrime will result as the people will prevent their selves to be involved in activities (social engineering etc.) which can make them victim (Marsden & Goslin, 2022). This initiative can involve TV and radio commercials, newspaper publications, university seminars, and introductory cybersecurity courses from schools to universities as a compulsory subject (Bada, et al., 2019). This will help to address the issue of illiterate people and they can learn about cybersecurity from TV or radio commercials. Furthermore, with increasing awareness around the people will help to spread the voice through them to the illiterate people of society as well. Consequently, it will develop the culture of awareness about cybersecurity

in Pakistan (Li, et al., 2019; Nagyfejeo and Von Solms, 2020). Moreover, it is suggested to use effective awareness programmes based on peoples' understanding which will not exacerbate cybersecurity, clearly highlight the cybercriminals and importance of cybersecurity, recognise the efforts of experts, and show political involvement, to attract people, as suggested by Bruijn and Janssen (2017).

7.2.5.2.3.2. Comprehensive laws for cybersecurity and law enforcement

Law enforcement is found to be a major factor for banks' cybersecurity in Pakistan because lack of law and its enforcement in the countries motivates cybercriminals to conduct criminal activities in those countries using cyberspace (Kao et al., 2020). Therefore, the government of Pakistan should focus on introducing comprehensive laws for cybersecurity and law enforcement for cyber criminals so that the punishment can deter them (21 out of 21 interviewees).

7.2.5.2.3.3. Maintain check and balance on SBP

As it is found that the SBP does not have competent staff to develop rigorous cybersecurity framework and that SBP does not have proper check and balance on banks' performance due to lack of extended and compatible audit team, the Government of Pakistan can maintain check and balance on SBP so that SBP will be active to improve its system (Bank D – CISO).

7.2.5.2.3.4. Start courses related to cybersecurity

Bank F (CISO) highlighted that since there is only one University in Pakistan graduating people for cybersecurity degree facilitating with professors who do not have industry experience. It is highly recommended to arrange degree courses in Universities with qualified experts of industry educating their students.

7.2.5.2.3.5. Tight check on the import of electronic items

Bank F (CISO) also suggested that the government should impose tight checks on imported electronic items to be used in banks. Those imports may be infectious and

should not be used straightaway in the banks without critically inspecting them by government experts (Khan & Ayub, 2020).

7.2.5.2.3.6. Agents should not be asking credentials

Bank M (CISO) recommended that the government needs to impose restriction on cybercrime investigation call centre agents to stop asking for personal information such as date of birth, CNIC, mother's maiden name, father name, and birth location etc. as these are security controls to access the financial information of banking customers. This can prevent the legitimate social engineering.

7.2.5.2.3.7. Theoretical Logics

First of all, the Government of Pakistan can apply the concept of deterrence theory whereby harsh punishments and penalties should be set in cybercriminal law to secure the nation as it will significantly demotivate cybercriminals (Yaziz Bin Mohd et al., 2021). In addition, the voters and citizens of Pakistan are stakeholders of Government of Pakistan (Williams, 2014) and according to stakeholder theory it is primary responsibility of everyone to act in favour of their stakeholders (Kim & Kim, 2020). Similarly, the Government of Pakistan should realize its responsibility of taking appropriate actions in this increasing trend of cybercrimes globally. Most importantly, having weak information security infrastructure throughout the whole country only Government of Pakistan must introduce new cybersecurity laws, spread cybersecurity awareness at national level, focus on law enforcement, and keep checks on SBP (Zia UL Islam et al., 2019).

7.2.5.3. Sub-Theme: Institutional logics implications

All of the respondents (21 out of 21) agreed that to ensure effective cybersecurity governance in banks it is vital to implement all discussed factors altogether (*Normative Logics: customer awareness, Regulatory Logics: regulations and law with its enforcement, and Symbolic Logics: director's training informing compliance of strategic planning*). For example, providing satisfactory regulatory framework, law and its implementation and investing in technology, employees training and experts still leaves

a room for cyberthreats if customers are not aware of how to securely use e-banking services (Forslund, 2020). Similarly, adopting regulatory and normative logics if strategic planning is ineffective then it provides the opportunity to cybercriminals to use social engineering to exploit employees or malware to steal money attacking the insecure information system (Christou, 2014). However, in case of absence of customer awareness, regulatory framework or effective strategic planning still harsh law and its enforcement can deter the cybercriminals. Thus, the structural logics stand strongest in this case. Yet, only application of law (structural logics) will not fully demotivate cybercriminals as they might find legitimate ways of social engineering by using human as a weak link. Therefore, it is important for banks, SBP and government to support each other by improving their relevant logics of the society (normative, regulatory, and symbolic) collectively to get effective outcome (Friedland, 2018; Farid and Waldorff, 2022).

7.2.6. Research Objective 4 Assessment

The findings show that almost all banks (11 out of 13) confirmed that system upgrade is better than private solutions (BAAS and cloud storage, open APIs, open banking etc.) yet some banks are using third-party services, because only the board can decide to invest in upgrade. Banks acknowledged that third-party services are only used when it incorporates secure system. It is also found that use of third-party services can reduce cost if it is secure. Moreover, all of the banks agreed that multi factor authentication is internationally used reliable and best method to secure transactions. While, most of the banks are not using multi factor authentication and some others are trying to adopt it gradually because it costs a lot. However, the banks can use combination of MFA and third-party services such as cloud storage where appropriate.

Additionally, based on the discussion on research questions one, two, and three, the respondents have provided useful recommendations which are also verified from the literature. However, these recommendations consist of the normative, structural, and symbolic institutions of logics for effective cybersecurity governance. This meets the research objective 4 and answers research question 4 of this study. Based on the data

collected and analysed evaluating with literature the following revised conceptual framework is developed in Chapter Eight.

CHAPTER EIGHT: CONCLUSION, CONTRIBUTION OF STUDY, LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

8.1. CONCLUSION

The aim of this study was to investigate key factors influencing effective cybersecurity governance in Private Commercial Banks of Pakistan. Although, the continuous recent cybersecurity breaches from 2018 to 2022 (which mainly targeted private commercial banks of Pakistan) attracted the researcher to conduct this study with purpose to identify that which cybersecurity threats the private commercial banks in Pakistan are facing and which factors (challenges) are assisting those threats to occur. The literature reveals that the developing countries are witnessing increasing number of cyberthreats in their financial institutions because of weak information security infrastructure in those countries. Moreover, the cybersecurity landscape of Pakistan shows that the information security infrastructure throughout the whole country is weak hence all sectors and industries in Pakistan have weak information security infrastructure. Consequently, the weak information security infrastructure in one industry will impact the information security of other industry which has link with on the prior industry.

This suggests that it is important to have proper information security infrastructure throughout the country. Sadly, 20 years back, when the technology infrastructure was developing in banking industry of Pakistan it was mapped out without integrating the security features in it. Therefore, the banking industry of Pakistan even did not have fundamentals of information security such as vulnerability scanners (Mahmood, 2021). Additionally, according to Kazim (2021) vulnerability scanning of whole information system of a bank throughout the country is a difficult task which requires a lot of time and investment. Also, it is four times difficult now instead if it would have been done 20 years back with technology configuration. In addition, the concept of cybersecurity is merely new in Pakistan which was given focused just after the topical cyberattack in 2018 in banks of Pakistan. Subsequently, it can be said that still many banks would not have used vulnerability scanners throughout their whole information security systems and integrated all the required security features in just couple of years.

However, as illustrated in literature, having such a weak information security infrastructure the banking sector of Pakistan is also confronting some other challenges (factors) for example, lack of law and law enforcement, lack of satisfactory cybersecurity regulatory framework, customer awareness, understaffed cybersecurity programs (lack of experts), cosmetic performance and 'security box centric' approach (investment issue). Although, the previous literature on these factors lack the empirical results, up-to-date literature on the topic, theoretical concepts, implication of third-party solution, multifactor authentication, NIST or ISO 27001 regulations, and application of institutional logic lens, as discussed in this study. Similarly, some other factors such as employees as a threat; use of outdated infrastructure; literacy level and awareness of general public; customer literacy; strategic planning; lack of awareness program by government; and directors' training either have limited number of studies or no studies conducted on banking sector of Pakistan (specifically private commercial banks).

Therefore, the ultimate objective of investigating key factors influencing effective cybersecurity governance Private Commercial Banks of Pakistan with the help of conceptual framework of this study which suggests that the cybersecurity of banks can be improved if the factors under investigation are dealt properly applying institutional logics. To conduct this study 21 interviews were conducted from 13 out of 15 private commercial banks of Pakistan. 14 of the interviewees were CISOs of their banks while 7 of the interviewees were mix of other employees having minimum five years working experience in their field. Moreover, the secondary data such as books, records, government reports, newspapers, published statistical data, published articles, journals, and databases were also used for this study. Thus, the combination of interviewees' data and secondary data helped to analyse the components of the conceptual framework of this study providing following results to meet the research objectives of this study.

Research Objective 1: To investigate the significant internal and external factors (challenges) that affect cybersecurity governance in the private commercial banks of Pakistan.

Accomplishment of Research Objective 1:

The results of this study show that there are 4 major factors which are affecting the cybersecurity governance of private commercial banks in Pakistan. Customer awareness is one of those major factors as literature shows that globally lack of customer awareness is a big issue which results in confidentiality issue because people share their personal information being unaware and become victim of cybercriminals such as social engineering. Comparatively, the findings show that the majority of the selected banks (10 out of 13) have hardly 50% of their customers aware about cybersecurity. This lack of awareness is interpreted as the people even are unaware of the facility that they can call and block their card in case if a fraud happens. In contrast, the literacy level of customers plays a major role in gaining cybersecurity awareness and majority of banks (8 out of 13) have low customer literacy (graduate people) rate which is under 50%. However, those literate people become victim of social engineering because they are unaware of cyberthreats and their impacts. Thus, banking customers can have cybersecurity awareness regardless of degree and will be categorised as digitally literate. Nevertheless, financial literacy will support fast awareness and understanding of digital threats. Similarly, the public cybersecurity literacy and awareness can prevent cybercrime targeted on them as weak human link in cyberspace using banking information of relatives. Further, it will foster the cybersecurity culture in Pakistan and fast awareness to banking customers being part of cybersecurity educated society. Nonetheless, this is government's corporate social responsibility to spread the cybersecurity awareness at national level - benchmarking the developed countries, as banks have limited resources (time, infrastructure, and finance etc.). Additionally, it is suggested to use TV, radio, and customised awareness campaigns for quick and effective results as it will be useful even for illiterate people who can become cybersecurity aware.

Furthermore, the lack of satisfactory regulatory framework of cybersecurity is another major factor because with ambiguous guidelines the banks are unable to adopt the appropriate cybersecurity measures, having choice to adopt temporary solutions and compromising with cybersecurity governance. The ultimate result is risking whole bank and possibility of losing customer trust and confidence on e-banking. The main reason of lacking satisfactory regulatory framework is incompatible staff. Besides, the auditors are

fresh graduates lacking industry experience who are unable to detect cosmetic performance regulated by directors' negligence. In addition, with no rigorous law for cybersecurity is encouraging cybercriminals to target banks in Pakistan. Therefore, there is urgent need of law and satisfactory regulatory framework of cybersecurity in Pakistan. Moreover, having law but no law enforcement is another reason which motivate cybercriminals to steal money from banks of Pakistan. Given that, the law enforcement agents need to enhance their capabilities and government needs to eradicate or control the corrupt agents through regulations. Hence, Government of Pakistan need to focus on law and its enforcement as the developed countries having innovative technology and regulation still emphasise on law and its enforcement to deter cybercriminals.

Finally, directors' training is a major factor because in Pakistan due to lack of understanding the necessity of investing in cybersecurity, the directors of banks prefer to use the box centric approach (using old measures of cybersecurity) and performance is document based rather than practical. Even though the regulatory framework requires banks to ensure their cybersecurity, but directors are not willing to invest. Therefore, the outdated infrastructure, ineffective strategic planning, employees' awareness, training, motivation, and number of experts (understaffed) is an issue which are affecting the cybersecurity of private commercial banks in Pakistan. The reason is that lacking suitable number and experience of audit team and compatible staff to introduce satisfactory regulatory framework, SBP is unable to keep proper check and balance on banks' performance and failed to provide satisfactory cybersecurity regulatory framework. However, if directors will continue to use temporary solutions which is a bandage on information security vulnerabilities instead of investing in proposed solutions from their CISOs, then the increase in cybersecurity threats is sure. Besides, the data collection from peer banks and industry is an issue in banks which requires SBP to facilitate collaboration in banks.

Research Objective 2: *To determine the maturity of cybersecurity governance in private commercial banks in Pakistan understanding the perception of banks about cybersecurity governance.*

Accomplishment of Research Objective 2:

The second research objective of this study was achieved by analysing the strategic planning factor which comprehends the internal policies and practices of banks for cybersecurity governance. However, as discussed in research objective 1 the results showed that the CISOs who are the head and experts of cybersecurity in banks are performing as per their best capacity to provide contemporary strategic planning to prevent the dynamic cyberthreats. Thus, they entail the required knowledge and understanding of importance of cybersecurity in banks. On the other hand, the directors of banks who do not have background of study in cybersecurity and lack the necessary knowledge and awareness about importance and implementation of cybersecurity, intend to focus on box centric approach and cosmetic performance. The reluctant behaviour of directors to invest in appropriate technology, number of experts, and cybersecurity training of employees has created the weak institutions of strategic planning and its implementation. This has resulted in increasing cybercrime in those banks exemplifying the recent cyberattacks of 2018.

Research Objective 3: *To understand the cybersecurity threats caused by identified factors in private commercial banks of Pakistan.*

Accomplishment of Research Objective 3:

It is found that with weak security infrastructure the cybercriminals are able to use malware and DDoS attacks in banking sector of Pakistan which are of devastating nature. The lack of investment (in technology, experts, training, awareness, and motivation of employees) is the main reason the private commercial banks are unable to prevent those attacks. However, the continuous cyberattacks from 2018 to 2022 indicate that the private commercial banks of Pakistan have become a target for cybercriminals because of weak security infrastructure and if the banks will not secure their information system by

investing in required technology, experts, and training then those attacks will continue and will affect the economy. Therefore, there is an extreme need of directors to train themselves with effective knowledge of cybersecurity to sit in the board.

Further, social engineering (including fake websites and online shopping) in Pakistan is at the boost because of lack of awareness. Both the banking customers and even well-educated employees as a weak human link become victims of social engineers. The social engineers are finding innovative techniques to prey even well-qualified people, considering it indirect and easy method of cybercrime. Thus, social engineering cannot be avoided fully but up to date training and awareness can be preventative. ATM skimming has been an issue in private commercial banks of Pakistan possibly because of outdated ATM Windows, neglection of code analysis, access to admin controls of ATM Windows to vendor, availability of keys to open ATM machines and reboot facility at ATM after inserting card reader. The directors ignore to invest in the updated ATM technology such as anti-skimming machines introduced by SBP or biometric ATM machines available in Pakistan. Slow adoption of anti-skimming and biometric ATM machine along with dynamic techniques established by cybercriminals it is suggested for customers to be vigilant through awareness to avoid ATM skimming. Also, the deepfake attacks of video impersonating people are not common yet but are the major concern because of lake of awareness.

Research Objective 4: To recommend effective cybersecurity governance measures for the private commercial banks of Pakistan.

Accomplishment of Research Objective 4:

The results recommend to not use third-party services as a temporary solutions (unless it is secure as it will reduce the cost). The use of multifactor authentication is not appreciated in private commercial banks of Pakistan due to lack of investment which means the necessity of security is being ignored there while, the use of multifactor authentication can be useful with face and device recognition features to prevent unauthorized use of bank cards through social engineering. Moreover, based on the

above findings the following recommendations are made for private commercial banks of Pakistan, SBP and government:

- **Banks** should use increased controls adopted from NIST; multi factor authentication with face and device recognition; investment in technology, experts, and training; introduce anti-fraud department with increased experts; improve information security control system, limit the amount of transfer, and use anti-skimming devices and surveys. Furthermore, emphasising on human factor, it is recommended to use deterrence theory perspective along with performance motivation cycle and TAM model to enhance the acceptance of cybersecurity and develop the culture of information security. Finally, using three-line model of defence the directors should understand their role and get trained.
- **It is recommended that SBP** should introduce a rigorous and comprehensive cybersecurity framework exemplifying NIST or ISO 27001; regulate on directors' training and investment decision; increase number of audit team members and their capabilities; and work in partnership with government to spread the awareness because its SBP's corporate social responsibility based on stakeholders' theory.
- **For the Government of Pakistan**, it is recommended to run effective cybersecurity awareness campaign at national level; provide comprehensive laws for cybersecurity, and emphasise on law enforcement; uphold check and balance on SBP; initiate cybersecurity courses; constricted check on the import of electronic hardware; restrict agents to not inquire credentials by regulations; and apply the concept of deterrence theory through enforcing harsh punishments against cybercriminals understanding its role towards its stakeholders (voters and citizens of Pakistan).
- **Institutional Logics Application**
Lastly, it is recommended to banks, SBP and government to play their roles as social actors in improving and implementing normative, structural, and symbolic institutions altogether for effective cybersecurity governance.

8.2. CONTRIBUTION OF STUDY

The present study attempts to address multiple research gaps and doing so make important theoretical and practical contributions.

8.2.1. Theoretical Contributions (Contribution to knowledge)

Conceptual Model – concluding from the above facts and evidences, it is imperious to revise the conceptual framework of this study. The initial conceptual framework of this study demonstrated in chapter 4 has modified, since my knowledge of the field enhanced meaningfully after collecting and analysing primary data. Hence, it requires to provide a revised framework depicting the reality and extended meaningful as well as reconstrued relationships (Miles and Huberman, 1994; Miles, Huberman, and Saldana, 2014). Likewise, theoretically the conceptual framework of this study (Figure 35) adds in the literature of cybersecurity governance in developing countries as Pakistan. The revised conceptual framework of this study confirms that the combined improvement and application of normative (customer awareness), structural (law with its enforcement, and satisfactory regulatory framework), and symbolic (directors' training) institutions can prevent cyberthreats the PCBP are confronting. Ultimately, it will enhance the customers' confidence and trust on e-banking and banking sector will grow as it has potential with fast growth rate since 1960 (Qamruzzaman & Jianguo, 2018).

However, in revised conceptual framework the emphasis on strategic planning concept is modified to bring the attention of SBP (following the logics of stakeholder theory and CSR) to provide a comprehensive regulatory framework including regulations relating to directors' training and awareness, since the required compliance and implementation of strategic planning (investing in technology, experts and staff training and motivation) in PCBP mostly depends on directors' understanding of cybersecurity (Alghamdi, 2021). It is possible by hiring skilled and professional employees which will ultimately assist in continuous check and balance on banks' performance. Therefore, directors' training and awareness is a main internal institution which SBP need to change through regulations (structural logics) in order to improve internal cybersecurity governance (strategic

planning) of banks. Thus, revised conceptual framework also highlights the dependency of symbolic institutions (directors' decisions) on structural institutions (regulations) in context of banking sector of Pakistan.

On the other hand, as per the experts (CISOs - participants) since the banking industry lacks the basic security in its information infrastructure hence it is understood that the embeddedness of security features in technology might take years (decade). However, the awareness throughout the country (which will include, banking customers and employees, and public) by effective government schemes (applying the logics of stakeholder theory and CSR) can be a quick measure to prevent cyberthreats (Wang et al. 2020; Gomes, et al., 2022), in absence of regulatory framework, law with its enforcement, and internal institutions. It will build the culture of digital awareness in the society (Shillair, et al., 2022).

Likewise, it indicates that the structural institutions (law and its enforcement) can be of more significant nature by deterring cybercriminals even in absence of customer awareness, regulatory framework, and effective decisions by executives. This highly empowers the structural institutions to influence the cybersecurity governance in PCBP and requires the attention to modify and strengthen them, along with normative and symbolic institutions for effective cybersecurity governance. Consequently, Government is the main actor facilitating the cybersecurity awareness along with law and its enforcement and, extending the prevention of encroachment by SBP; where the adoption of technology is time consuming and challenging task even having enhanced regulatory framework and internal governance.

Furthermore, the primary data highly supported the implications of TAM model, deterrence theory, motivation cycle, and three lines of defence model by PCBP to comply with the regulatory requirements of strategic planning for effective internal cybersecurity governance considering. Finally, constructing theoretical logics the government, SBP, and PCBP can manage the customers and employees (human factor) since they are the ultimate users of banking system. Regardless of effective technology human factors are easy trap if they cannot use the technology adopting secure behaviour (Anwar, 2020).

Literature – The revised conceptual framework of this study will help the future researchers to understand the cybersecurity issue in developing countries, mainly in Pakistan, in relation to how the factors (challenges) of this study assist cybercriminals to successfully become a threat for banks. Theoretically, this study confirms that as a human factor customer awareness is of major concern. Additionally, law and its enforcement, regulatory framework, directors training, and customer awareness affect the cybersecurity governance of private commercial banks of Pakistan from various perspectives. However, the joint improvement in these factors will be effective to resolve the cybersecurity governance issue in banks. This study highlights that how customer awareness can be influenced by digital literacy, public literacy and awareness and how effective awareness campaigns run by government can be useful. Moreover, the results of this study provide the deeper understanding of how lack of law, its enforcement and lack of satisfactory regulatory framework is further weakening the cybersecurity governance of banks. Although, it is also found that lack of law enforcement is impacted by low capabilities of law enforcement agents and corrupt agents. Further, it is noted that having NIST guidelines the banking industry in Pakistan is lacking comprehensive regulatory framework because of incompatible people working in SBP. The fact that there is lack of appropriate number and experienced audit team facilitates the executives to manipulate the actual performance. Hence, government's check and balance on SBP is neglected. Following the concept of weak regulatory (structural) institutions the directors lacking the cybersecurity awareness prefer not to invest in innovative technology, number of experts, employee awareness and training, justifying the reason of box centric approach and cosmetic performance. Therefore, in documents banks are performing well in cybersecurity but in reality there is minimum standards are adopted applying cheaper solutions. This shows how structural institutions of society can influence symbolic institutions in practice. Furthermore, in developing countries like Pakistan with weak information security infrastructure the law and its enforcement (structural institutions) are found to be the strongest institutions to deter cybercriminals, lacking awareness, regulation, and compliance. The theories used in this study applying them to the concepts of cybersecurity governance in developing country have shown their high applicability and implications to improve the cybersecurity governance of banks. Besides, the conceptual

framework of this study can be tested in banks of Pakistan other than private commercial banks. Further, this study empirical added to the previous studies conducted in Pakistan without empirical results. Also, with the technology infrastructure of banking industry of Pakistan decade back in security implementation (technology, experts and awareness etc.) with no effective law and regulations, based on the findings of this study it can be clearly said that the declaration by banks and government of Pakistan that the banking industry is now secure just by conducting a few formal seminars or introducing a national cybersecurity policy is a false statement because, providing secure infrastructure to banking industry of Pakistan is more of constituent progressive work which can only be done over time with continuous efforts.

Methodology - this study has implied interpretivism approach to deeply analyse the context of cybersecurity governance in private commercial banks of Pakistan. The main respondents of this study were CISOs (chief information security officers) who hold the highest position in banks, controlling the cybersecurity governance. Moreover, the adoption of advanced institutional logics approach has provided a critical conception of how different institutions in society collectively can impact the social behaviour of actors (banks, SBP, and government) and how a single institution can influence the other institution in society.

8.2.2. Practical contribution

The literature shows that the banks, SBP and government lack the understanding of the importance of cybersecurity governance in banks (Shahbaz UI Haq, 2019; Hafiz Ali et al., 2019; and Syed et al., 2019) which is supported by the results of this study. Practically, in general the conceptual framework of this study will help the practitioners (banks), SBP and government of Pakistan to understand how the information confidentiality, integrity, and availability in private commercial banks is affected by various factors and, how different measures can play their role in improvement of information security of those banks.

Further, one of the major reasons of cybersecurity breaches is found the disconnection between the cybersecurity experts and board of directors because of directors' lack of ability to understand the importance of cybersecurity (Robert & Ackerman, 2021). Hence, the board of directors (main player of cybersecurity as they make decisions) can learn the importance of their training proved from the literature and findings of this study. In addition, considering the weak information security infrastructure of banks (Syed et al., 2019; Sadiq, 2019) the private commercial banks of Pakistan can use recommendations (as a solution to their cybersecurity governance issue) of this study such as increased controls; multi factor authentication; investment in technology, experts and training; introduce anti-fraud department with increased experts; enhanced information security control system; limit the amount of transfer; and use anti-skimming devices.

Additionally, the results showed that there is lack of lower-level employees' involvement, old age staff tendency to not learn new technology, reward function and customer and employee training. Thus, the banks can apply the deterrence theory concept along with performance motivation cycle of this study and TAM model to effectively increase the acceptance of cybersecurity in banks and create the culture of information security (Trang & Brendel, 2019; Ofori et al., 2020).

The stakeholder theory of this study (Phillips et al., 2019) will take the attention of SBP to understand its CSR towards its stakeholders (banks and society) and notice the necessity of urgently providing a rigorous regulatory cybersecurity framework by improving its staff efficiency and using NIST or ISO 27001 as an example. Specifically, understanding directors' training, lack of and experts as an issue based on the results of this study, the SBP can provide certain regulations about them to make it compulsory for banks to provide training to their directors and have certain number of experts based on the size of the business. Moreover, following the findings that limited number and inexperience audit team delays in check and balance on banks which gives the management chance to manipulate actual application of cybersecurity, the SBP can make an effort to either increase the number of audit teams and improve their capability or find another way to maintain check and balance on banks. Also, SBP can get the idea of engaging in awareness program in collaboration with government as per the suggestion of this study.

Finally, acknowledging the findings and theoretical implications of this study the Government of Pakistan will be able to understand its responsibility towards its stakeholders (voters and citizens of Pakistan). Henceforth, considering the strength of structural institutions, government can initiate to immediately develop a comprehensive law for cybersecurity (applying the concept of deterrence theory) and emphasise on law enforcement, maintain check and balance on SBP, and spread cybersecurity awareness.

Figure 35: Revised Conceptual Model on Cybersecurity Governance of PCBP

8.3. LIMITATIONS

According to Price and Murnan (2004) all research studies have limitations. However, it is important to highlight them to understand the facts that can affect the findings and the quality of the study. This study has following limitations:

Sample representativeness - Considering the time and cost constraints, only the banks from Lahore have been selected, while the responses of people from other cities could be different based on facilities they might have. Also, the participation of directors in interviews could have broadened the results of study and add in literature.

Choice of Research method - This study is based on interviews following the research objectives of this study and to focus on in-depth knowledge of the cybersecurity governance issue which has rarely been explored before. However, using mixed methods or multiple methods would have been allowed to generate vast variety of knowledge if time and cost was not the reluctant.

Analysing the NIST and ISO 27001 Regulations in Context of Pakistan Banking – Maintaining the focus on just exploring why regulatory framework is not improved the cybersecurity regulatory framework of NIST and ISO 27001 is not scrutinized in detail to highlight which cybersecurity protocols are useful for selected banks.

8.4. FUTURE RESEARCH

Since this study is first in nature of its conceptual framework hence there are many opportunities for future research on cybersecurity governance in banking sector of Pakistan such as:

Use Large Sample Size – The future research on banking industry cybersecurity governance can be conducted using extended sample size for example conducting double or larger number of interviews. Also, the sample population could also have directors, banking customers and public to explore their understanding of cybersecurity in banks. Likewise, the research can include the mix of all types of banks to explore the differences between responses, instead of focusing on private commercial banks.

Mixed Method Approach and Testing Theories - Understanding the basic phenomenon of the cybersecurity governance in context of conceptual framework of this study, the future research can be conducted using more than one method. It will allow the triangulation of results. Also, the theories used in this thesis can be tested on other banks.

Comparison of NIST and ISO 27001 – It would be of great help for SBP if the future studies could highlight the major differences in NIST or ISO 27001 to improve the cybersecurity regulatory framework for banking industry of Pakistan as none of the previous studies has worked on it.

ATM Machines Outdated – The findings showed that the possible reason of recent cyberattacks in banks of Pakistan (2018 to 2022) are expired window 7 of ATM machines. The future studies can work on case studies to find if the ATM machines have updated software and then compare the performance of banks' information security.

Cultural Dimensions – The results showed that in Pakistan the culture is to blame for lack of cybersecurity awareness and becoming victim of social engineering. The future researchers can deeply scrutinise the impact of culture on customers' awareness and use of e-banking services, proposing how the government can provide effective awareness campaigns based on the cultural dimensions.

Performance Motivation Cycle - the performance motivation cycle introduced in this study was supported by the results which suggest continuously identifying factors of motivation. However, to convert it into a theory it requires detailed analysis by collecting large amount of data by future researchers.

9. References

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10. Appendices

Appendix – A: Ethics Form

20/04/2021

Dear Miss Faryal,

Your application 10796: An Empirical study: To formulate best guidelines of cybersecurity measures to be used by Pakistani private banks, submission 13563, has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr D Turner

Appendix – B: Case Profiles

Case 1

Bank A

Bank – Introduction:

This bank is a Pakistani commercial bank. It has around 10,000 employees with almost 1,000 branches and 400 sub-branches all over the country with a presence overseas. Its total assets are worth nearly RS. 1.5 trillion. This bank was one of the top 200 “Best Under a Billion companies” by Forbes Asia in 2005. In 2012, it also held the Asian Banker’s “Strongest Bank Balance Sheet in Pakistan (Angelus, 2012). Furthermore, this bank’s profit for the half year ended June 30, 2020, was around Rs 7.5 billion and by last year, its deposits exceeded Rs. 1 trillion (Profit, 2020).

Interviewee:

The interviewee is a graduate in finance, an experienced Credit Risk Analyst with more than five-years’ experience in the banking industry. He is expert in Financial Risk, Credit Risk, Market Risk, Banking and Compliance. The interview lasted a one hour. There were some connection problems, but the interviewee cooperated and was supportive.

Case 2

Bank B

Bank - Introduction

This is one of the leading banks in the banking and financial services sector in Pakistan. It has about 4.2 million customers. It consists of more than 1,400 branches and has around 40,000 Omni Agents (known for branchless banking as a pioneer) and over 1,300 ATMs (Zafar Khan, 2021). It is spread over different continents. Its customers all around

the world have 24/7 access to the bank using its world class Internet Banking. This bank was awarded the 'Best Bank for Corporate Finance & Capital Market Development' in 2017. The bank's total assets in 2020 were over Rs. 3 trillion with deposits and profit of over Rs. 1.5 trillion and Rs. 34 billion respectively (Desk, 2021).

Interviewee:

The interviewee is a customer relationship and marketing manager. He has an MBA degree. He has over 10- years' experience in the banking industry. The interview lasted one hour and 15 minutes. The interviewee was cooperative. He tried to reveal as much information about issues as he could share so that my research could help to solve them.

Bank B1

Bank – Introduction:

This is the same bank as for interview number 2. Taking multiple interviews from the same bank will help to validate the results.

Interviewee:

The interviewee is part of bank's cybersecurity department and works as a senior information security member. He has been working in the banking sector for more than 10 years and has a Master's degree in Information Security Management from a renowned organisation of Pakistan. The interview was given in written form by email and some parts of the interview was completed by phone because of confidential information. It was hard to get his response because of his busy schedule and his concerns for confidentiality but after continuous struggle the interviewer managed to gain the required data for this study.

Bank B2

Bank Introduction:

This is the same bank as for interviews 2 and 3.

Interviewee:

The interviewee is the Head of operations. He has been working in the banking field for more than 10 years. The interview was taken for an hour. He holds an MBA. His qualification and experience in the field has enabled him to attain diversified knowledge of the field.

Case 3

Bank - C

Bank – Introduction:

This bank is a leading full-service commercial bank of Pakistan. Now it has more than 300 branches and ATMs all over the country, over its history of three decades.

Interviewee:

The interview was taken from the Banking and Compliance officer who has been working in the banking field for the last eight years and has been working in this bank for the last 1.5 years. This interview took one hour and the respondent gave all answers in a friendly mood.

Case 4

Bank D

Bank – Introduction:

This bank is one of the listed private commercial banks for this study. It is also one of the largest multinational banks of Pakistan for internet banking, remittances, retail banking and other banking functions. It has more than 1,500 branches all over Pakistan.

Interviewee:

The interview was taken from the CISO of this bank. He has been in this position for the last three years in this bank. He also holds vast experience of eight years in the banking industry along with holding a Bachelor degree in computer science (BCS) and degree from USA for specialising in cybersecurity in this field. Also, he holds various up to date licenses and certificates. He has also worked as an external auditor for different banks in Pakistan. Due to his busy schedule the interviewer only could take a half an hour interview. However, during this time, he brought some very important points to my attention.

Bank D1

Bank – Introduction:

This bank is the same as of interview number 6.

Interviewee:

The interviewee has 12 years-experience in networks, Information Technology, and Information Security. He has held senior positions at IBM Pakistan, World Call Telecom Group, and Wateen Telecom. He is a key figure in the Information Security space in Pakistan. He is working as a CISO in the relevant bank for 5 years.

In 2012 he became a director of one of Pakistan's leading Information Security consulting firms. Today that company is known as a premier IT and Information Security consulting organisations providing distinctly exceptional & world-class ISO27001:2013 (ISMS) programs and a variety of security implementation projects for banks, telecoms, and enterprises. The interview ended after half an hour. It was hard to get in contact with him because of his busy lifestyle but he managed to arrange it and gave me time for collecting important information.

Case 5

Bank E

Bank – Introduction:

This is one of the largest private banks in Pakistan. It has more than 800 ATMs and branches all over Pakistan and some international branches in Bangladesh, Afghanistan, Bahrain, and UAE. The bank made profits of around 11 billion rupees in 2021 which was 26% more than the previous year. Its total assets are worth roughly Rs. 14 billion. Also, it has 11,000 employees with Rs. 9 billion deposits approximately (WSJ, 2021).

Interviewee:

The interviewee has been working in the banking industry for the last 20 years. His qualifications are B.Com, ACCA, and certificates in financial accounting. He is a senior credit control manager. The interview lasted for an hour. The interview was interrupted because of signals and the busy work routine of the interviewee. But the interviewee tried to give me maximum time.

Case 6

Bank F

Bank – Introduction:

This bank was developed three decades ago. Now, it is an international bank and is one of the prominent financial institutions of Pakistan with AA ratings from Pakistan Credit Rating Agency. Its profit for 2020 was around Rs. 12 billion with more than 6,000 employees (The nation, 2021). It held assets of more than one trillion rupees by 2020 (Profit, 2020).

Interviewee:

The interview lasted for about an hour. It was hard to manage time for interviewee as she had to be engaged with young children after work. The interview was interrupted by the children for a while, but the interviewee managed to answer all relevant questions. She has more than 5 years' experience working in the bank. She is a cash controller who also authorises payments. Her qualification is MBA.

Bank F1

Bank Introduction:

This is the same bank as for interview 9.

Interviewee:

The interviewee is Head of the Operations Department in one of the branches of the bank. He holds a Master's degree in Banking and has almost five years' experience in the field of banking. The interview ended after one and a half hours.

Case 7

Bank G

Bank Introduction:

This bank is a leading trade finance bank. It has more than 400 branches. Its total assets are Rs. 1 trillion and deposits are Rs. 68 billion with profit of Rs. 9 billion.

Interviewee:

The interviewee has been working in banks for more than 10 years. He holds retail and corporate banking experience. He does not have direct contact with cybersecurity however, he provided important insights about banks. He holds a B.Com (Hons). The interview was for one hour and was troubled with internet issues, but the interviewee cooperated.

Case 8

Bank H

Bank Introduction:

This is almost 3 decades old private commercial bank of Pakistan. Its recent revenue was Rs. 34.75 billion (2021) having net income of Rs. 8.35 billion (2021) and total assets are worth Rs. 869.968 billion (Khan, 2021).

Interviewee:

The interviewee is CISO of the bank. He has obtained Master's degree in information security and has more than 7 years' experience in the field of information security. The interview went smooth and responded gave satisfactory responses.

Case 9

Bank I

Bank Introduction:

It is the fifth largest commercial bank of Pakistan. It is one of the largest banks within the country having more than 1,400 branches and ATMs. For last year it had revenue of Rs. 28.39 billion, net income of Rs. 17.30 billion and total assets are worth Rs. 2.01 trillion (Mehdi, 2014).

Interviewee:

The interviewee is head of security department (CISO) of the bank. He holds a Master's degree in IT and relevant diplomas from U.S. in security management. Also, he has 10 years' experience in the field of cybersecurity. The interviewee provided up to date knowledge of the field which helped to complete this study.

Case 10

Bank J

Bank Introduction:

This is one of the largest banks in Pakistan. It has more than 1,700 branches with presence in over 20 countries. During last year it had revenue of Rs. 167.73 billion, net income of Rs. 35.50 billion and total assets of worth Rs. 431.7 billion (Profit, 2021).

Interviewee:

The interviewee is senior information security officer (CISO) of the bank. He holds a Master's degree in Information Security (MIS) and various trainings in cybersecurity. Also,

he has 15 years' experience in the field of cybersecurity. However, it was difficult for him to manage the time for interview because of workload but he managed.

Case 11

Bank K

Bank Introduction:

It has around 1000 branches in more than 400 cities across Pakistan having some branches in other countries. For 2021, it had revenue of Rs. 34.56 billion, net income of Rs. 18.70 billion and total assets worth Rs. 2.29 trillion (Habib, 2021).

Interviewee:

The interviewee is CISO of the bank. He holds a Master's degree in IT and multiple diplomas in cybersecurity. Also, he has 6 years' experience in the field of cybersecurity. However, because of internet problem the interview was interrupted but the interviewee showed patience.

Case 12

Bank L

Bank Introduction:

It is largest and oldest international bank in Pakistan with 2800 employees within 40 branches across 10 cities. It had Rs. 37.393 billion worth sales ended with Rs. 24.762 billion profit and total assets of Rs. 8.3 trillion for 2021 (Standard Chartered, 2021).

Interviewee:

The interview was conducted with a CISO of this bank. He holds MSc IT degree and some certificates in cybersecurity field of study. He has 8-years' experience in the field. The interview ended in an hour, considering the tight schedule of interviewee.

Case 13

Bank M

Bank Introduction:

This bank has been awarded for Best Innovation in 'Retail Banking Pakistan 2020. It has 123 branches in Pakistan. However, its financial statements are not updated to highlight its' financial position (SBP, 2021).

Interviewee:

The interviewee was an expert (CISO) in cybersecurity of banks. He had 8-years' experience and BS (Masters) degree in IT along with certification. The respondent was very cooperative and repeated the responses to ensure the validity of data.

Appendix – C: Participant Information Sheet for Interviews

Participant Information Sheet

1. Research Project Title

An Empirical study: To provide the set of recommendations for cybersecurity measures to be used by private commercial banks of Pakistan.

2. Invitation

You are being invited to take part in this research project. Before you decide to do so, it is important you understand why the research is being conducted and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish.

Ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part. Thank you for reading this.

3. What is the project's purpose?

The basic purpose of this study is to provide the set of recommendations for cybersecurity measures to be used by private commercial banks of Pakistan. This project builds on studies previously carried out by different authors in different countries and has been designed to allow comparisons with previous in other countries.

4. Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen because as a bank manager/employee you will have knowledge about cybersecurity related issues in bank.

5. Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part, you will be able to keep a copy of this information sheet and you should indicate your agreement to the consent form sent by email. You can still withdraw at any time. You do not have to give a reason.

6. What will happen to me if I take part?

You will be asked to participate in an hour based semi-structured interview to give the research a chance to explore the topic of research.

7. What do I have to do?

Please just answer the questions during the interview as per your best knowledge. There are no other commitments or lifestyle restrictions associated with participation.

8. What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

Participating in the research is not anticipated to cause you any disadvantages or discomfort. The potential physical and/or psychological harm or distress will be the same as any experienced in everyday life.

9. What are the possible benefits of taking part?

Whilst there are no immediate benefits for those people participating in this research, it is hoped that this work will have a beneficial impact on improvement of cybersecurity measures in private commercial banks of Pakistan. Results will be shared with participants in order to improve banks' cybersecurity.

10. What happens if the research study stops earlier than expected?

Should the research stop earlier than planned and you are affected in any way the author will tell you and explain why.

11. What if something goes wrong?

If you have any complaints about the research in the first instance you can contact the author any time. If you feel your complaint has not been handled to your satisfaction you can contact the University of West of Scotland to take your complaint further (see below, contact no 3).

12. Will my taking part in this research be kept confidential?

All the information that the researcher will collect about you during the course of the research will be kept strictly confidential. You will not be able to be identified or identifiable in any reports or publications. Your institution will also not be identified or identifiable. Any data collected about you during interview will be stored in a form protected by passwords

2. Steve Smithson,

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Thank you for taking part in this research.

Appendix – D: Consent Letter for Interview

Interview Consent Letter

Dear participant:

My name is Faryal and I am a research student at University of West of Scotland (School of Business and Creative Industry, UK). For my thesis, I am conducting a study to provide the set of recommendations for cybersecurity measures to be used by private commercial banks of Pakistan. As your title in your company qualifies you to understand the impact of cybercrime on your bank, other banks, and the economy, I request you to please take participation in my research through answering the questions in semi structured interview.

No compensation will be made to participate in this study and it is ensured that there is no risk. Also, the standard time for interview will be one hour but you can quit when you like. The thesis will be submitted at University of West of Scotland (UK). If you agree to participate, kindly sign the form and send it to the following email.

Thanks a lot for helping me in completing an important part of my research. If you sign and return this form, it will be considered your consent to participate in this study.

If you require any additional information or inquiry, or have complaints about the research manners, please freely contact me by email address: [REDACTED].

[REDACTED] [REDACTED]
[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]
[REDACTED] _____

Appendix - E: Codebook

Codebook

Theme - Factors

Investment on cybersecurity

Example: invest in cybersecurity either in technology or employee,

Customer awareness and training

Example: customer awareness or unawareness, customer training

Lack of law and satisfactory regulatory framework of cybersecurity

Example: absence of law or regulation, law or regulation is satisfactory or unsatisfactory

Law enforcement

Example: law enforcement

Employees as a threat

Example: Employee - motivation, confidence, interest, knowledge, training, reward, performance, support, and involvement

Use of outdated infrastructure

Example: lack of up-date in technology, old technology, outdated technology

Literacy level of general public and awareness

Example: illiteracy of public, lack of awareness to public, public unawareness or literacy and lack of literacy of public

Customer literacy

Example: illiteracy of customer, lack of literacy of customer, customer literacy, literacy level

Strategic planning

Example: long term planning, strategic thinking, strategic planning

Lack of awareness program by government

Example: awareness program, awareness initiatives or efforts by government

Directors' training

Example: directors' efficiency, role, decision-making

Theme – Challenges

Social engineering

Example: E-mail, call, or SMS fraud, phishing, impersonating, vishing, smishing, social engineering

Fake websites

Example: online shopping or browsing, link to website, fake website

ATM skimming

Example: rain cover, the card reader slot of ATM machine, use of debit or credit card to withdraw money, install fake keypad, capture the pin codes entered

DDoS

Example: exhaust the resources, make data unavailable, violating security components' availability

Malware

Example: code added, changed, or removed from a software system, intentionally harm or subvert the intended function of the system, steal messages containing one-time passwords, capture keystrokes, overlying bank login screen changed, taking screen snapshots, and getting Google Authenticator codes, virus, worm, trojan horse, spyware, ransomware, crypto ransomware, doxware.

Deepfake attacks

Example: upcoming crucial cyberthreat, Deepfake, deep learning, machine learning, artificial intelligence to manipulate voice or video content with the purpose to deceive people.

Theme – Solutions

Example: System upgrade, third part solution, private solutions, external solutions, BAAS and cloud storage, open APIs, open banking, and multi factor authentication

Theme - Regulations

Example: Regulatory framework, specific guidelines, information security control protocols, thorough and rigorous regulations, NIST or ISO 27001.

Appendix - F: Darknet Dump Data

First Dump from Darknet

No.	Bank Name	Type of Card in the Darknet Dump	No. of Cards
1	Bank Alfalah	VISA (Prepaid, Classic, Platinum)	28
2	Bank Islami	VISA (Classic, Gold)	508
3	Faysal Bank	VISA (Classic, Gold, Platinum)	120
4	Habib Bank	VISA (Classic) Mastercard (Standard, Titanium, World)	6170
5	JS Bank	VISA (Classic, Gold)	355
6	Samba Bank	Mastercard (Standard)	16
7	Soneri Bank	Mastercard (Standard, Gold)	333
8	Standard Chartered Bank	VISA (Classic)	586
9	The Bank of Punjab	Mastercard (Prepaid, Standard, Gold, Platinum)	748
	Total		8864

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Mohammad and Ahmed (2018)

Second Dump from Darknet

No.	Bank Name	Type of Card in the Darknet Dump	No. of Cards
1	Al Barak bank	Mastercard (Standard, Gold)	25
2	Allied Bank	VISA (Classic) Master	741
3	Askari Bank	VISA (Classic, Gold) Master (Gold)	493
4	Bank Alfalah	VISA (Prepaid, Classic, Gold, Platinum, Signature)	795
5	Bank Al Habib	VISA (Classic, Gold)	489
6	Dubai Islamic Bank	VISA (Classic, Platinum)	199
7	Faysal Bank	VISA (Prepaid, Classic, Gold, Platinum, Signature)	458
8	Habib Bank	VISA (Classic) Mastercard (Standard, Titanium, World)	2043
9	Habib Metropolitan Bank	VISA (Classic, Gold, Platinum)	344
10	Js Bank	VISA (Classic, Gold)	163
11	Kasb Bank	VISA (Prepaid)	2
12	MCB Bank	VISA (Prepaid, Classic, Gold, Platinum)	1125
13	Meezan Bank	VISA (Classic, Gold, Platinum) Mastercard (Standard, Platinum, Titanium)	1375
14	Nib Bank	Mastercard (Standard)	8

15	Samba Bank	Mastercard (Standard)	14
16	Silkbank	VISA (Classic)	146
17	Standard Chartered Bank	VISA (Classic, Platinum) Mastercard (Standard)	733
18	Soneri Bank	VISA (Classic, Gold) Mastercard (Standard, Gold)	162
19	Summit Bank	VISA (Classic, Gold)	184
20	The Bank of Punjab	Mastercard (Prepaid, Standard, Gold, Platinum)	120
21	UBL	VISA (Prepaid, Classic, Gold) Mastercard (Standard, Platinum)	1381
	Total		11000

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Appendix - G: Interview Schedule

Research Question One: Which significant internal and external factors (challenges) are affecting the cybersecurity governance in the private commercial banks of Pakistan?

Q1a. Does awareness of your customers have any impact on cybersecurity governance of your bank, if yes then how and what percentage of your customers are aware?

Answer: Our customers need detailed awareness about how to use banking securely rather than making them aware generally. We need to think above than traditional concepts of training our customers (Bank A: Cybersecurity Risk Analyst).

Q1b. If customer awareness is important then what role does your bank play to create that awareness?

Q1c. Can the level of literacy of your customers be useful for their cybersecurity awareness?

Answer: One of the major impacts of low financial and cyber literacy is poor understanding of cybersecurity and its importance. Consequently, they share their confidential data and become victim which result in financial loss to them and reputational loss to bank (Bank H: CISO).

Q1d. If literacy is important then is a degree holder customer considered literate to support cybersecurity governance of your bank and what is literacy rate of your banking customers?

Q1e. How would you explain the relation of public literacy and awareness to cybersecurity governance of your bank?

Q1f. How the awareness is possible where literacy rate is also low?

Q2. Having NIST or ISO 27001 guidelines why regulatory framework issue is not resolved and how your bank provides effective cybersecurity governance then?

Q3. In the absence of law and its implementation how your bank manages with cyberthreats?

Q4. Is your bank financially strong to invest in cybersecurity, if yes then why cybersecurity is an issue?

Q5. Does employee behaviour play a role in cybersecurity governance of your bank?

Q6. Should executives really be updated with knowledge of trending cybersecurity threats and their possible impacts on banks' cybersecurity governance if yes, then why?

Research Question Two: How the cybersecurity governance is perceived in private commercial banks of Pakistan which can ensure its maturity level?

Q7. Does the higher management of bank/just bank consider Cybersecurity in strategic planning?

Q8. Does the higher management of bank take pre-planned initiatives to avoid Cybersecurity issue?

Q9. Which type of IT experts the management of bank consider to deal with Cybersecurity issue and why?

Q10. Do you think being unable to provide sufficient security for banking services will cause loss of customers' trust on bank and why?

Research Question Three: Which cybersecurity threats are caused by identified factors in private commercial banks of Pakistan and why?

Q11. Which cyberthreat is of more concern for your bank and why?

Q12. Are you aware of Deepfake technology? If yes how it can affect your bank?

Research Question Four: What can be the effective cybersecurity governance measures for the private commercial banks of Pakistan?

Q13. Do you think there is any other challenge or factor which is also affecting the cybersecurity of your bank?

Q14. Based on the above discussion, what recommendations do you have to improve the cybersecurity governance of your bank?

Q15. Can third party solutions be an alternative for technology upgrade and multi-factor authentication be a useful solution?

Q16. Can these factors be sufficient if used alone or must be coordinated collectively for effective cybersecurity governance?

Designation:	Experience:	Qualification:	Gender:	Age:
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• CISO• Other	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Less than 2 years• Between 2 and 5 years• Between 5 and 10 years• Between 10 and 15 years• Between 15 and 20 years• More than 20 years	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Bachelors• Masters• PhD• Other	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Male• Female	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• 26-35• 36-45• 46-55• 56-65• Above 65